

Exploring career barriers to successful women entrepreneurship in the
food industry of Nepal and how to overcome these barriers

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DECLARATION

I declare that this thesis entitled “Exploring career barriers to successful women entrepreneurship in the food industry of Nepal and how to overcome these barriers” is in line with the requirements of University of the West of Scotland and the result of my own research except as cited in the references. This thesis has not been accepted for any degree and is not concurrently submitted in candidature of any other degree.

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Personal details withheld.

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ABSTRACT

Women entrepreneurship has gained popularity globally over the past few decades because it increases productivity, innovation, economic prosperity, reduces poverty, and creates jobs. Women have shown an increased interest in the Nepalese food industry, and several have begun their careers to improve their living standards and social status. However, past studies show that women entrepreneurs still face significant barriers despite an increasing number of starting businesses in the food industry. In Nepal, few researchers have discussed the barriers women entrepreneurs face, and none have examined the barriers women entrepreneurs face in the food industry, leaving a research gap. Therefore, the main research objective was to shed light on barriers that women entrepreneurs face that limits their business involvement in the Nepalese food industry and provide solutions to overcome the identified barriers to enhance the status of women entrepreneurship in Nepal.

This study followed mixed method approach for data collection. The survey was distributed to 150 women entrepreneurs for quantitative study, and 8 women entrepreneurs and four business development officers were interviewed for the qualitative study. The quantitative survey data was analysed with the help of SPSS and descriptive analysis, whereas thematic analysis was used to analyse the qualitative data.

This research made significant theoretical and practical contributions by identifying women entrepreneurs' barriers limiting their involvement in Nepal's food industry. Quantitative analysis revealed significant barriers facing Nepalese women in the food industry, including a lack of training, inadequate education, legal constraints, cultural obstacles, financial barriers, and balancing work and family responsibilities. In contrast, qualitative analysis revealed barriers such as a lack of mentoring, entrepreneurial mindset, networking, and skills constraints that were not explored in depth in previous studies. This research also provides recommendations for enhancing and boosting the status of women entrepreneurs in Nepal.

Keywords: Women entrepreneurship, Barriers, Nepal, Culture, Economy

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

B.S.: Bikram Sambat

BCG: Boston Consulting Group

CBS: Central Bureau of Statistics

CBN: Central Bank of Nigeria

DCIS: Department of Consumer and Industry Service

e.g., Example

FNCCI: Federation of Nepalese Chambers of Commerce and Industry

FWEAN: Federation of Woman Entrepreneurs' Associations of Nepal

HNDs: Higher National Diplomas

ILO: International Labor organization

LBDQ: Leader Behaviour Description Questionnaire

MAC: Middle and Affluent Consumer

MFI: Micro Finance Institution

MoAD: Ministry of Agricultural Development

MSE: Micro and Small Enterprises

NFWBO: National Foundation for Women Business Owners

NTFS: Nepalese traditional and indigenous foods

OECD: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

SBPP: State Board of Pardon and Parole

SD: Standard Deviation

SPSS: Statistical Package for the Social Sciences

SSS: Senior Secondary School

U.N.: United Nation

UNIDO: United Nations Industrial Development Organization

USA: United States of America

VDC: Village Development Committee

WDP: Women for Peace and Democracy Nepal

WE: Women entrepreneurship

WEAN: Women Entrepreneurs Association of Nepal

WED: Women Entrepreneurship Development

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CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the study

Women entrepreneurship is increasing globally, contributing to innovation, income, and job creation in all economies. Many public and private, national, and international organisations are increasingly paying attention to women entrepreneurs and contributing significant resources to their economic empowerment (Khajuria, 2020). As a result, women are starting businesses in more significant numbers, and according to the World Bank's Enterprise Survey (2021), the percentage of enterprises with female participation in ownership has increased more than 80% in developing countries. According to the GEM Global Women's Report (2021), the highest rates of established business owners are in Sub-Saharan Africa (11.3%) and Asia (9.1%), with the lowest rates, MENA (4.5%), Europe (5.3%), North America (5.7%), and Latin America (6.5%).

Despite the large number of women who start enterprises, research shows that gender-specific barriers to the development and sustainability of women entrepreneurship persist (Bardasi & Sabarwal, 2019). On the other hand, women entrepreneurship promotes social integration and empowerment (Scott et al., 2020), contributes to regional economic development (Shiralashetti, 2018), and improves nation entrepreneurship and economic performance (Scott et al., 2020; Welter, 2014). The significance of women entrepreneurship and its impact on the nation's economic growth and sustainability presents a rationale to encourage and motivate women entrepreneurs (Kantor, 2017).

The role and significance of women entrepreneurs in Nepal are also similar. Since Nepal is a patriarchal country, most sectors are male dominated. Women entrepreneurs are limited to sectors like aviation, construction, engineering, etc. The typical stereotype and gender-based role have limited the participation of women entrepreneurs in the type of industry they want to pursue. Nepal is culture embedded country, where even the laws are bend in favor of men than women, but despite this hostile business environment, women are entering in the entrepreneurship field to gain financial freedom, pursue their careers, and predominantly for survival.

In 2015, Nepal was hit by a massive earthquake killing almost 6 million people. Due to this devastation, many male guardians lost their lives who were sole earners of a family and women had to join the entrepreneurship field to feed and bring food to their table. It was a positive indication in the food business, making women aware of food availability and its importance for survival. Then tight after this, in 2016, the Nepal government had a dispute with India that caused a blockage in the border between Nepal and India. As India was the sole provider of every essential requirement needed for living, and many people struggle to keep up with their everyday lives, from medical supplies to basic food. This havoc also raised another alarm amongst women to participate in entrepreneurship. It has brought approximately \$ 1.5 million in revenue to the nation's GDP and reduced poverty by up to 12% (CBS, 2021). Also, the Covid-19 pandemic resulted in many closer businesses owned by both men and women. During a lockdown, thousands of businesses were down, raising Nepalese unemployment, suicidal rate, and mental illness. However, women entrepreneurship again raised in food business showing their skills in cooking and delivery via digital marketing and working from the home trend. These events have alarmed both government and women about the significance and positive impact of women entrepreneurship. Therefore, according to DCIS (2021), there are now 3848 companies that women have officially registered. Mainly women entrepreneurs are 88.6% active in the food industry of Nepal (CBS, 2020).

Although, despite this positive indication, there are still significant barriers that hinder women entrepreneurs' career progression, limiting them in male-dominated sectors, still underutilized. These barriers are mainly social, cultural, financial, legal, and skills. In addition, women face more complex barriers than men, and female entrepreneurs have different perspectives on the world. Therefore, women entrepreneurs need support from all relevant institutions, including collaborative government and business support initiatives (Rabbani & Chowdhuri, 2020). As a result, the idea of solely supporting female entrepreneurs is gaining popularity (Byrne & Fayolle, 2019). Hence, it is crucial to address these barriers in-depth, aware policymakers to implement practical action plans, achievable policies, and recommendations to remove the identified barriers. Since this is DBA, the researcher has looked at perceptions from different stakeholders related to the topic to provide practical recommendations to boost women entrepreneurship in Nepal.

Hence, this study aims to explore the barriers that women entrepreneurs face in the Nepalese food industry that limit their involvement and overcome these identified barriers. To study the topic in-depth, the researcher has exhausted all the relevant literature from a different perspective like gender, social, finance, legal, human rights, and business. Also, scholars like Bushell (2008), Siegel (2021) have looked at the general understanding of women entrepreneurship of Nepal and investigated the issues women entrepreneurs face in general. Likewise, Tripathi (2012) and Gautam (2020) have also talked about the food industry and its impact in general. There are few studies conducted on women entrepreneurship and food industries independently, but this research attempts to look at and explore the barriers women entrepreneurs face in the food industry of Nepal in depth. This research tries to explore all the significant barriers from different perceptives and provide solutions to reduce these barriers.

1.2 Women Entrepreneurship in Nepal

Women entrepreneurship has become an essential topic in academia because it is a driving force for increased productivity, job creation, and profits (Berglund, 2007). It facilitates micro, small, medium, and large businesses, resulting in poverty reduction and economic growth. The importance of expanding its production base for developing countries is well known (Knox, Agnew & McCarthy, 2014). The role of the entrepreneurs in developing countries, especially for small-scale industries (Valliere & Peterson 2009), is exceptionally crucial even though there are numerous and complicated mechanisms and effects, and specific studies have revealed a negatory association in developing economy entrepreneurship and economic growth due to a shortage of human capital (Stel et al., 2005).

However, female business owners in Nepal often find it extremely difficult to conduct business, make required relations with other entrepreneurs, and even engage with customers. They face various challenges due to insufficient funding and government support, a shortage of business education opportunities, and specific religious and cultural barriers. Due to their inability to obtain credit, they have turned to the informal economy, and their lack of capital has led them to seek loans from Micro Finance Institutions (MFI) (Klein, 1993). On the other hand, women-owned companies are considered minor, with lower growth and profit margins than male-owned businesses (Greene, Han & Marlow, 2013). Moreover, even though the number of women who engage in entrepreneurship increases in developed countries, women still manage fewer businesses than men. The start-up stage, women's entrepreneurship success, and

recognition of their business objectives are constant factors (Cole, 2015). The condition is no different when it comes to Nepal, but the difference is more significant compared to international countries. Women in Nepal face greater cultural and social barriers, limiting their participation in industry, the types of businesses they can start, and the amount of funding they can get (Tlaiss, 2013). Due to factors primarily related to their society, tradition, and norms, women in Nepal have been reluctant to participate in many fields of employment and lack the resources to operate businesses. Other considerations can also influence their participation (Jamali, 2009). Despite depicting formalising informal firms as rational and ethical, many women entrepreneurs in Nepal continue to operate informally regardless of their perceived illicit status (Karki et al., 2021). According to Hillman & Radel (2021), there is a significant increase in women attempting to disrupt poverty in Nepal through entrepreneurship, but they face much more significant obstacles than their male counterparts. In Nepal, women entrepreneurs face marginalization in business. Furthermore, caste, class, and patriarchal inequality play an essential role in their regulation (Gautam, 2020). Similarly, Ranabhat, Baburam & Kiruna (2021), suggested that through microenterprise development, Nepali women can overcome patriarchal embeddedness in social and business environments. Women engage in female domains such as homestay and infiltrate male domains such as trekking and tour-guiding. Nepali women's political strategies are subtle and understated. Nevertheless, the capacity of Nepali women to encroach on patriarchy through tourism shows that women have adapted to redress socially constructed imbalances. Still, women's skills and roles infiltrate ingrained patriarchy (Siegel, 2021).

Hence, this study aims to identify the significant challenges facing Nepalese entrepreneurial women and the resulting consequences. Governments promote entrepreneurship among women through several programmes and organisations. For instance, in Nepal, the headquarters of Kathmandu, Nepal is Federation of Woman Entrepreneurs' Associations of Nepal (FWEAN), Women Entrepreneurs Association of Nepal (WEAN), Federation of Nepalese Chambers of Commerce and Industry (FNCCI), Women for Peace and Democracy Nepal (WDP) and many more. Although these organizations exist, women are often unprepared to set up in business due to fear, lack of support, and family responsibilities (Mazzarino, 2013). Therefore, women entrepreneurship is a method for rectifying and helping women become empowered and positively contribute to all economic development sectors (Shmailan, 2014).

1.3 Nepalese Food Industry

The food industry encompasses all activities and resources that produce, distribute, and consume food and all the relationships and feedback loops between the system components (Finlay, 2016). The food industry comprises complex food products and services supply, consumption, and catering activities employing a massive number of both skilled and unskilled workers. It is one of the world's most dynamic economic sectors. Nevertheless, the food industry excludes the farmers who consume or produce food for self-consumption. This paper briefly introduces the food industry (Sadiku, Musa & Ashaolu, 2019).

Thus, food entrepreneurs are crucial to developing regional food systems (Miller, 2001). The values they hold are likely to influence their business mission and may be integral to their motivations for starting and maintaining a food business (Knudson et al., 2004). According to research studies on entrepreneurs in general, food entrepreneurs take risks, push boundaries, and enjoy the challenge of venturing into the unknown (Zein et al., 2009). However, food entrepreneurs retain unique insights based on their core values and possess the ability to communicate their vision to others (Knudson et al., 2004). Despite many opportunities in the food industry, women entrepreneurs still face many barriers that hinder their progression. Based on their unique role in the food system and contribution, this thesis explores the barriers that women food entrepreneurs face in Nepal.

Nepal has always been a popular destination for avid food lovers, and it is best known for its use of spices in food items. However, changes in demography and lifestyle have brought a massive influx of money into the food business. According to Boston Consulting Group [BCG] Perspectives (2015), around 7 per cent of the population has the power to purchase goods and services. That translates to roughly 11 million middle and affluent consumers (MACs).

Recently, most graduates have sought employment in the food processing industries in Nepal. A recent report on the status of food sector graduates (Guragain, 2021) shows that most Nepalese graduates (33%) are absorbed by the food industries, followed by academic institutions (11%) and government sectors (10%). According to Gartuala & Adhikari (2020), about 21% of the graduates are abroad, pursuing their higher studies or working in food-related sectors. Only about three per cent work for development organizations, about two per cent in marketing sectors, and about two per cent own their businesses. This convenience pattern and

on-the-go likely snacking will continue, driven by time pressure and busy schedules (Saad, 2020). With the advancement of technology and increasing time crunch, the introduction of food delivery companies, eco-friendly restaurants, and authentic food has seen a splurge of customer requests pouring into the food industry. Since the women in Nepal are housewives there is enormous scope for women to start business in food industry.

1.4 Problem Statement and scope of research

Many academics studied women entrepreneurship, who have described many problems that have a detrimental impact on the growth of their businesses. Also, this research is about Nepal, where 25% of the population is still lacking. Nepal is heavily dependent on remittances, which account for 29% of GDPs. Agriculture is the region's economic foundation, accounting for one-third of GDP and employing nearly 70% of the population. The 7.8-magnitude earthquake that struck Nepal in 2015 took a significant toll on the economy. More than six years have passed since the earthquake that killed over 9000 people in Nepal, but the country is still struggling to recover, but then Covid-19 hit the economy very hard. Also, the decreasing involvement in business, growing suicidal rate, and rising domestic violence due to lockdown have worsened the situation. Hence this alarming situation points out the importance of women entrepreneurship in Nepal (Knight et al., 2015). Nepal is among South Asian countries with the most significant female participation in the informal economy (International Labour Organization [ILO] Nepal, 2014). The overall literacy among women in Nepal is just over 40%, with age, caste, and spatial changes in the region. For example, 70% of women aged 40 to 44 have no education, while over 40% of women aged 20 to 24 marry before 18 years of age (UFPA, 2017). The root causes of the increasingly slow recovery process are political rhetoric, the lack of local level government, failed global funding, and cultural disputes (Pokharel, 2015). Women in Nepalese society are also predominantly responsible for household tasks such as cooking and childcare (Erogul & McCrohan, 2008), even though their extended families play an essential role in mitigating this. As a result of these societal perceptions, women find it more difficult to truly participate in entrepreneurship because they fear violating social and cultural norms. Women's ability to engage in training or receive formal education and access knowledge, markets, and institutions is affected in settings where socio-cultural norms hinder their mobility (Tlaiss, 2014). According to Bashyal & Panthi (2019), there is a lack of understanding of the importance of entrepreneurship. Therefore, promotion strategies are required to meet the specific needs of entrepreneurs, especially women.

Although many laws have improved the law on the heritage of Nepal, women are rarely permitted to inherit land or other property. Inheritance rules are often bent to give land ownership to a male relative, placing widows and daughters at an unfairness (Pandey, 2009). Finally, in situations where men are breadwinners, political affairs that embrace this successfully prioritise men's investments while restricting women's right to use the family property as collateral (Vinothalakshmi & Ganesan, 2013). Women are marginalised when finance fails to fund the kinds of activities that women choose to perform, refuse to consider other women as guarantors, have vague conditions, or grant smaller loans than men for related activities (Okafor & Amalu, 2010). Many studies have found that women trying to start a business face many barriers (Wanjohi & Mugure, 2008). However, only a few studies attempted to explain why women entrepreneurs, particularly in Nepal, face these barriers (Zeidan & Bahrami, 2011). This motivates the researcher to examine the barriers to successful women entrepreneurs, which limit their participation in any business activities, primarily in the food industry of Nepal.

1.6 Research Aim

Considering the preceding discussion, Nepal's women entrepreneurs face significant barriers when conducting a business. Also, the lack of adequate and in-depth study of the food industry's barriers and practical recommendations leads to more research into the topic. Hence, this research aims to identify a significant barrier that limits women entrepreneurs' business involvement in the food industry of Nepal. Furthermore, this study also aims to provide recommendations to eliminate these identified barriers to boost status of women entrepreneurs in Nepal.

1.7 Research Objectives

To achieve the aim of this study, the following objectives identified as follows:

- a) To discuss the current situation of women entrepreneurship in the food industry of Nepal.
- b) To identify the main barriers limiting women entrepreneurs' business involvement in Nepal.
- c) To recommend grassroots solutions on overcoming the identified barriers and uplift the status of women entrepreneurship in the Nepalese food industry.

1.8 Research questions

To meet the research aims and objectives, the main research questions formulated for this study are:

1. What is the current situation of women entrepreneurship in the food industry of Nepal?
2. What are the main barriers that women entrepreneurs face that limit their business activities in the Nepalese food industry?
3. What measures are needed to eliminate the identified barriers to strengthen women entrepreneurship and increase business activities in the Nepalese food industry?

1.9 Rationale of the study

Women entrepreneurship development plays a significant role in a country's development, and women entrepreneurs have made a considerable impact in almost all segments of a country's economy (Verheul et al., 2006). Women are critical human resources which constitute more than half (51.41%) of the total population in Nepal. Hence the government should utilise them as mediators of economic growth and development. Due to various barriers, including legal barriers, gender biases, human rights, socio-cultural, environmental, and individual, women's brainpower is not adequately harnessed and underutilized (Bhuvaneshwari & Annapoorani, 2022). Like wisely, the food industry ranks second largest industry of Nepal. This industry provides job opportunities to a diverse workforce irrespective of skills. Especially for women, this industry has been the easiest route for entrepreneurship (Karki et al., 2021).

Moreover, women in the food business are widely accepted and recognised by Nepalese culture than beauty parlour, tailoring, handicrafts. According to the World Bank (2021), this industry provides 33.3% of job opportunities, making this industry the fourth largest industry in terms of job opportunities. Therefore, the women entrepreneur's representation in this industry is very high, accounting for 88.16% of active women entrepreneurs. As a result, the food industry has brought a massive influx of money into the business and contributed to revenue growth and aided economic stability.

Likewise, an encouraging fact on women entrepreneurs who are gradually growing in numbers, and some policy instruments have found helpful to encourage its growth. "Industrial promotion of statistic Report of Department of Consumer and Industry Services (DCIS)" shows that the total number of registered women entrepreneurs in DCIS is 3894 as of 2069 Bikram Sambat (B.S.). This report shows that enthusiasm among women to earn a living seems to increase in Nepal despite socio-cultural constraints (Thakral, 2010). Thus, it can be a positive indication of the recent development phenomenon. However, the rate of entry into entrepreneurship is still low, and those already in the forum face various constraints, including legal ones. In such a scenario, it is necessary to remove obstacles faced by women in building entrepreneurship. However, several studies conducted on women entrepreneurship of Nepal, such as Bista & Shrestha (2020); Bajracharya, Parajuli & Maharjan (2013); Ranabhat, Baburam & Kiruna (2021)); Bushell (2008) but only a few of them have focused on the food industry of Nepal from challenges and opportunities encountered by women entrepreneur's perspective. The previous research conducted in the field of the food industry of Nepal has focused only on describing the facts and figures of the industry and explaining whether the sector is at the growing stage or the declining stage. Moreover, previous research in the literature lacks reviews on career barriers faced by women entrepreneurs in this industry. The previous studies have been conducted only in the food industry or women entrepreneurship independently.

Therefore, it indicates that the pace of development depends on the action-oriented and practical policy. Significant incentives and motivational factors are needed to upgrade entrepreneurship and productivity. Especially equal opportunity for the overall economic activities without any gender bias is essential to accelerate economic growth and attain consistent growth for sustainable development (Tripathi, 2012). Policies need remodelling and retouch to remove various hurdles faced by women entrepreneurs.

Consequently, this in-depth study is thus essential to identify the significant barriers and eliminate them to sustain the women entrepreneurship programs (Subedi, 2020). This research provides recommendations that will create a background for smooth economic development and uplifts the women entrepreneurship. In this research, the study's findings are compared with those from similar previous research to gain insights into the barriers faced by women entrepreneurship in the food industry of Nepal. This research focuses on providing a solution to the barriers found in the study. This study set out to answer the following research questions. This study can help fellow Nepalese women entrepreneurs voice their perception of the barriers

and how to overcome these identified barriers to empower other women and create awareness of the importance of women entrepreneurship.

Additionally, from the researcher's motivation, there has always been an interest in the topic because even the researcher's mother is women entrepreneurs in Nepal. Hence, from personal reflection and expertise, the researcher knows the barriers that women entrepreneurs face, and there has never been a smooth progression in women entrepreneurs' life. The life of the researcher's mother as women entrepreneur has always inspired and, at the same time, questioned many events on why specifically women entrepreneurs face barriers than their counterparts. Thus, a researcher has always found culture as the significant barrier and many other barriers like training, entrepreneurial mindset, education, finance. Then an interest was developed to conduct this in-depth study to bring awareness and insight into the barriers. It is crucial to remove these barriers for economic prosperity. It was proved from home science because if the mother is successful, well off, she can nurture, raise her children, shape their future in the path to success. It will bring sustainability to society and create more job creators than job searchers. Thus, this study can present the prospects and challenges of women entrepreneurs in the context of Nepal.

1.10 Contribution to the knowledge

Women entrepreneurship in any country focuses on economic growth, competitiveness, job creation, and social welfare enhancement (Neumann, 2020). It is a critical tool to create employment opportunities for women and use them as a critical source of livelihood and business revenue. Though women entrepreneurship is not as common in Nepal as in other countries, it is gradually gaining popularity (Sigdel, 2020). Therefore, from this study, various significant barriers were found. The data was collected employing a mixed-methods approach via survey questionnaires and interviews tools. The data collected was from diverse stakeholders like women entrepreneurs, a business organisation that solely focuses on developing women entrepreneurship in Nepal because women entrepreneurs alone cannot provide a clear picture of the barriers. Therefore, the researcher has interviewed these policymakers to understand and evaluate what mechanisms are already available for women entrepreneurs. Hence, from this diverse perception, this report has found a lack of adequate training and development programmes required for women entrepreneurs, lack of primary

education, legal barriers, financial barriers, culture barriers, and balancing work and family life.

Also, previous studies have not yet mentioned women entrepreneurs involved in the food industry. Hence, due to the high representation of women entrepreneurs in this business, this study contributes both theoretically and practically that the findings and recommendations provided to relevant stakeholders can be generalised to other industries. Thus, for scholars such as researchers, policymakers, donors, entrepreneurship mentors, and women development consultants who are passionate about developing women entrepreneurship in Nepal, the findings of this study will shed light on the career barriers and prospects of women entrepreneurship in Nepal.

1.11 The Structure of the Thesis

This study has three major sections, including this first introductory chapter (see Figure 1) and seven chapters. The brief details on each chapter are as follows:

Chapter two: This chapter has progressed from presenting an evolution of entrepreneurship and the concept of women entrepreneurs to past studies from different continents globally. This chapter presents the overviews of the topic from a global perspective and summarises barriers identified by academic scholars related to women entrepreneurs.

Chapter three: In this chapter, the researcher has presented the past studies on barriers related to women entrepreneurs in Nepal. This chapter includes a brief overview of the food industry, and all relevant evidence found relevant with the topic in the context of Nepal. Then a comparison from a global perspective to Nepal regarding the barriers identified was presented in the table form. Also, this chapter ends with the conceptual framework of the study and a summary of the chapter.

Chapter four: This provides a systematic discussion of approaches to a thesis, justifying the research philosophy, the methodological context, the methodology adopted and the effects on the research questions and hypotheses. The chapter then provides an in-depth overview of research questions and ideas, including target population selection, sampling approach,

research tools and analytical methods and evaluating the findings' reliability and validity. It also describes the pilot study used to improve research design.

Chapter five: This chapter provides the data collected from the surveys and interviews. This chapter has the data from surveys, women entrepreneurs, and the data from the sample involved in organisations supporting women entrepreneurship in Nepal.

Chapter six: This chapter aims to analyse the data and then discuss the data found to support the research hypotheses and meet the aims and objectives of this research. This chapter has the data analysed and debated accordingly of the topics from chapter 5.

Chapter seven: This chapter summarises the thesis and gives practical input and recommendations for how prospective researchers should use the findings of this study. This chapter offers specific advice on how women's entrepreneurship should be encouraged so that Nepal, as a developing country, can become more competitive in the future. It also addresses the research journey and the shortcomings of the present thesis and how prospective studies in this field will overcome those limitations.

Further to an introduction of the problem, objective, and aim of the study, the following chapter will dig into the literature to figure out whether women entrepreneurs face the essential barriers in the context of Nepal. Hence, the pictorial representation of the structure of the thesis is as follows:

Figure 1: Structure of the study

Source: Researcher's own work

As a result, the purpose of this thesis is to explore the significant career barriers that Nepalese women entrepreneurs face limiting their business involvement in the food industry and how to overcome these barriers. Henceforth, this chapter provides a detailed overview of the current situation and develops a problem statement. The chapter also describes the study's objectives

and the research questions before explaining the thesis structures and the researchers' aim to explore women's entrepreneurship in Nepalese contexts.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW OF WOMEN ENTRENEURHSIP (PART I: GLOBAL PERSPECTIVE)

2.1 Introduction

This chapter provides an overview of the study conducted on women entrepreneurship globally. The chapter starts from an evolution of conceptual view about entrepreneurship and successfully understands the women entrepreneurs' terms and their role in economic development. Next, this chapter aims to draw attention to areas where there are still gaps, problems, and opportunities for women entrepreneurs. Finally, this chapter illustrates the summary on barriers identified to women entrepreneurship from different continents to aid the researcher in comparing the findings from past studies with the Nepalese context.

2.1.1 Evolution of the concept of Entrepreneurship

Here the researcher has separated the concept of entrepreneurship periodically. Through this section, the researcher will be able to grasp better the concept as it currently stands, which will further assist the researcher in identifying the barriers that limit women entrepreneurs' participation in business activities.

a) From the 1950s till the 1970s

An entrepreneur word is derived from 17th-century French *entreprendre*, meaning "undertaker" - meaning someone who assumes the risks of enterprises. They were "contractors" who bore the risk of profit or loss, and in the early days, entrepreneurs were soldiers of fortune, adventurers, builders, merchants and, incidentally, funeral directors. In the 16th century in France, the term entrepreneur was used for army leaders engaged in military expeditions (Holt, 1998, p 53). In the 17th century, it then covered civil engineering activities such as construction and fortification (Cochran, 1965). About the 1700s in France, "entrepreneur" was frequently applied to refer to government road, bridge, harbour, fortification contractor and somewhat later, to architects. After the 1750s, it covered other types of adventures, mainly civil engineering like wood bridge construction, harbours, and building. In the Middle Ages, an entrepreneur was a person who merely managed large projects such as architectural works. It

did not involve taking risks but involved using the resources available. Risk became connected with Entrepreneurship in the 17th century when an entrepreneur bears the chance at a fixed price and contracts with the government (Hoselitz, 1951, p.121).

According to Say (1845), an entrepreneur unites the cost of production and finds the product's value. It results from their unemployment reconstitution of the real money that utilises and the value of the wages, interest, and rent and profits belonging to entrepreneurs. An entrepreneur may or may not supply capital but must have judgment, perseverance, and knowledge of the business world and must possess the art of superintendence and administration. The author claims that entrepreneurs influence society by creating new enterprises and at the same time get influenced by culture to recognise the need and fulfil them through astute management of resources. Then defines an entrepreneur as the most important agent of production who provides continuing management and brings together the factors of production. His definition associates the entrepreneur with coordination, organisation, and supervision. Say's emphasis is that entrepreneurs must have judgment, perseverance and knowledge of the world and business. Say was the first economist to differentiate the function and remuneration of the entrepreneur from those of the capitalist. There are three more implicit factors to provide continuing management. Firstly, moral qualities for the work include judgment within when the business is operating. Secondly, the prospective entrepreneur should have a hold over sufficient capital resource. The third factor refers to the uncertainty of profits. To overcome the uncertainty element in business, Say prescribes superintendence and administration as essential for entrepreneurship. Say defined entrepreneurship in the most general term. It was a classic definition that survived almost till the twentieth century.

However, Drucker (1985) disagrees with this view of Say (1845) and Cantillon's (Henry Higgs, ed. & trans. 1959) view. According to Drucker, successful innovators are not risk-takers but successful in defining risks and confining risks. Entrepreneurs are conservative and not risk-focused, but opportunity focused. Like wisely, Schumpeter (1934) revived the concept of entrepreneurship that specifically addressed entrepreneurship. Schumpeter described entrepreneurship as a force of creative destruction of old things by creating a new and better way to get things done. Entrepreneurship is often a subtle force, challenging the order of society through a marginal and small change. Still, Schumpeter described entrepreneurship as a process and entrepreneurs as innovators who use the technique to shatter the status through new combinations of resources and new methods of commerce.

In the *Trailed Economic Politique (Translated into English in 1845 as A Treatise on Political Economy)*, Say (1845, p.79) described an entrepreneur as one who possessed specific art and skills of creating new economic enterprises yet a person who had exceptional insight into society's needs and was able to fulfil them. Say (1845) combined the "economic risk-taker" of Cantillon and the "industrial manager" of Smith into an unusual character. According to Knight (1921), entrepreneurship is a specialised process where a person bears risks and deal with uncertainty. An entrepreneur is an economic functionary who undertakes such responsibility, which cannot be insured or salaried. He also guarantees specified sums to others in return for their assignments. The supply of entrepreneurship involves three factors: ability, willingness, and power to extend guarantees about returns to others. Knight also identified the economic, social, and psychological factors, which govern the supply of entrepreneurship.

However, there is still difficulty identifying entrepreneurs, finding them, or determining what they do with a definition in mind. For example, Schumpeter's (1934) viewpoint is that entrepreneurs bring resources to gather in unusual combinations to generate profits. Vesper (1980) found that psychologists tend to view entrepreneurs in behavioural terms as achievement-oriented individuals driven to seek challenges and new accomplishments. Hence entrepreneurial concept itself is evolutionary. The following section presents all the studies from the 1990s to 2010s.

b) From the 1970s till the 1900s

At the beginning of the 18th century, entrepreneurship was referred to as an economic activity to designate a dealer who buys and sells goods at specific prices (Parrek & Ventreswore, 1978). From this usage, it was easy to apply entrepreneurs as a person who bought a commodity or other economic goods at a fixed price that could not be determined. Entrepreneurship is one of the four mainstream economic factors: Land, Labour, capital, and Entrepreneurship (Herbert & Link, 1982). However, researchers have been inconsistent in their definition of entrepreneurship (Gartner, 1989). Reports have emphasised a broad range of activities, including the creation of organisation (Gartner, 1989), the carrying out of few combinations (Schumpeter, 1934), the exploration of opportunities (Kirzner, 1973), the bearing of uncertainty (Knight, 1921), the bringing together of factors of production (Say, 1845). At the same time, Smith (1976) described the entrepreneur as an industrialist with unusual foresight and could recognise potential demand for goods and services. In Smith's view, entrepreneurship

is related to economic change, thereby becoming the economic agents who transform the market into supply. Entrepreneurship will generate more income, reduce the acute problem of unemployment, minimise the incidence of poverty, reduce the regional imbalance, increase the export trade, and reduce the balance of payments to the possible extent (Kirzner, 1973).

In contrast, Kilby (1971) emphasises the role of an imitator entrepreneur who does not innovate but imitates technologies innovated by others and is very important in developing economies. Timmons & Spinelli (2004) explains that entrepreneurship is a method of taking the initiative, accepting failure risk, and having an internal locus of control. Similarly, Stevenson (1975) states that entrepreneurship is the pursuit of opportunity without regard to resources currently controlled. Hornaday & Abond (1971) analysed many characteristics that they felt were significantly associated with entrepreneurs. Out of nine factors (achievement, autonomy, aggression, support, conformity, recognition, independence, benevolence, and leadership), they needed achievement, help, independence, and leadership as the most significant characteristics.

c) From the 1990s till 2010s

The concept of entrepreneurship is still very complex and disputed (Bull & Willard, 1993). It is an attitude and a reality to develop something new that adds value to the entire social ecosystem. One definition of entrepreneurship sees the entrepreneur as the self-employed, based on the notion that a person can either be unemployed, self-employed or wage employment. It is measured either statistically through the number of self-employed or dynamically through the rate of start-ups (Wennekers & Thukik, 1999).

Entrepreneurship was first identified by the French economist Cantillon in the early 18th century as self-employment, regardless of risk (Landstrom, 2010). To settle an individual's life, they have two ways of earning a living: searching for employment in existing concern or becoming independent people who manage their venture and take full responsibilities and risk. In other words, this person is called an entrepreneur (Das, 2000). The functional analysis of entrepreneurship focuses upon the economic role rather than the individual who performs such a role. It came out because of industrialisation, which occurred throughout the world in the 18th century. The report from Shrestha (2001) comments that business entrepreneurs were those with (i) high need for achievement and (ii) who take high risks. Since then, the concept of entrepreneurship has been associated simply with owning one's own business with

innovations and risk to the king (Parker, 2009). Collins & Moore (1970) concluded that entrepreneurs as restless, independent, and creative after interviewing 150 small business entrepreneurs. Several social scientists have prescribed that entrepreneurship is the critical variable, linking the socio-cultural milieu with economic development (Williamson, 1966). Entrepreneurial action is essential not only for economic growth but also for regional development and capital formation. Moreover, it solves the problem of unemployment. For this reason, government and private agencies have embarked upon undertaking the task of entrepreneurial promotion. A significant movement in Austria subsequently influenced 20th Century concept of entrepreneurship (Menger, 1871). Menger (1971) established the subjectivist economics perspective in his book Principles of economics. He says economic change does not arise from circumstances but an individual's awareness and understanding of those circumstances. Therefore, an entrepreneur becomes the change agent who transforms resources into valuable goods and services, often creating events that lead to industrial growth.

However, a critical point in Cantillon's argument was that entrepreneurs consciously decide on resources allocation. Consequently, astute entrepreneurs would always seek the best opportunities for using resources for their highest commercial yields. Cantillon played out his theory in real life, becoming a wealthy arbitrageur investing in European ventures, dealing in monetary exchange, and controlling commodities in high demand markets. Thus, an entrepreneur is an individual who bears uncertainty and takes risks. So, they engaged in economic activity as entrepreneurs, from landowners to salaried workers. An entrepreneur is a bearer of non-insurable risk and can carry on production and exchange of goods at some risk, facing the possibility of bankruptcy when the demand for their product is expressed (Venkataraman, 2010). Schumpeter did not equate entrepreneurs with investors, suggesting that an inventor might only create a new product. In contrast, the entrepreneurship will gather resources or gain talent and provide leadership to make it a commercial success. Drucker (1985) described the entrepreneur's role as gathering and using resources. Still, he allied those resources to produce results must be allocated to opportunities rather than problems (Drucker,1985). In Drucker's view, entrepreneurship occurs when resources are redirected to advanced options and not used to ensure administrative efficiency. This redirection of resources distinguished the entrepreneurial role from traditional management (Parker, 2009).

Schumpeter provided a framework for understanding both in terms of a process. The entrepreneur seeks to revolutionise the production pattern by exploiting an invention or, more

generally, an untried technological possibility for producing a new commodity or producing an old one in a new way by opening a fresh supply of materials new outlet for the product. Entrepreneurship essentially consists of doing things not generally done in the ordinary business routine (Shane & Venkataraman, 2000). On the other hand, Marxist philosophers may see entrepreneurs as exploitative adventures, representing all negative in capitalism (Holt, 2000). Therefore, the concept of entrepreneurship developed and redefined periodically according to entrepreneurs' situations and changing characteristics.

d) From the 2010s- till date

Researchers have sought to define traits common to most individuals who start and operate new ventures to understand entrepreneurs better. Research studies exploring the character and personality traits of and influences the entrepreneurs have come to differing conclusions. However, most of them agree on specific, consistent entrepreneurial characteristics and environmental effects. Still, certain entrepreneurial behaviours are also dynamic and influenced by environmental factors. For example, Shane & Venkataraman (2000) argue that entrepreneurs are solely concerned with opportunity recognition and exploitation in their entrepreneurship research paper. Though, the recognised opportunity depends on the type of entrepreneur, while Thakral (2010) argued that many different styles are contingent upon environmental and personal circumstances.

According to Hisrich, Peters & Shepherd (2013), entrepreneurs view changes as the norms. They constantly search for change, respond to them, and exploit them as opportunities. In that sense, entrepreneurship is a behaviour rather than a personality trait. Economic development of a country essentially means a process by which the country's per capita income changes upwards over some time. Entrepreneurship plays a vital role in economic development by creating utilities and generating employment quickly. The impetus of entrepreneurial ventures had come from industrialisation in developed nations by selling up large technological and sophisticated industries investing colossal capital.

Entrepreneurship refers to starting a new firm or revitalising an existing one to capitalise on new prospects. These entrepreneurs change the economy by innovating new goods and services and producing new money and employment (Bhardwaj et al., 2011). In developing countries, many formally registered unemployed or low wage employees in large enterprises or

government departments (Formal Sector) seek to survive to increase their income through entrepreneurship (Ikupolati et al., 2017). Hence, Sahasranamam & Sud (2016) define an entrepreneur as one who undertakes an enterprise, especially a contractor- acting as an intermediary between capital and labour. The undertaking of an enterprise involves combining wealth and work for production. Therefore, anyone who undertakes this task is an entrepreneur.

Similarly, Minniti (2010) states that among the Asian countries, the concept of the enormous capital-intensive industry has failed to solve their economic problems and triggered a spate of human and social issues. Stagnation of economy, widening inequality staggering unemployment and under-employment, and a valley of the socio-cultural issues associated with urbanisation played the Asian countries when they attempted to transplant Euro-American concept of entrepreneurship in their countries. This experience has led these countries to follow the policy of encouraging individual small-scale ventures.

In this way evolution of concepts has generated many definitions of entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurships are the dynamic process of creating incremental wealth. Individuals assume significant risks in terms of equity, time, and career commitment of providing value for some product or service. This product or service may or may not need unique, but the entrepreneur must somehow infuse the value by securing and allocating the necessary skills and resources (Nieuwenhuizen, 2014).

Additionally, according to Kumar (2014), entrepreneurship has assumed super importance for accelerating economic growth both in developed and developing countries. It promotes capital formation and creates wealth in the country. It reduces unemployment and poverty and is a pathway to economic development. Entrepreneurship is the process of exploring the opportunities in the marketplace and arranging resources required to exploit these opportunities for long term gain. Entrepreneurship is an economic venture by which many people can be changed upward quickly, especially from employment generation. Many nations have an abundant natural, biological, and human resources like other developing countries. However, technical progress alone cannot lead to economic development unless the entrepreneurs use the technologies. Entrepreneur organises and uses capital labour and technology. An entrepreneur is indeed an agent of the economic development of a country. Therefore, entrepreneurial awareness among the people in general and educated is perhaps an urgent need.

To support this, Thornton, Ribeiro-Soriano & Urbano (2011) has argued that some of the most significant influences on an individual's decision to become an entrepreneur are workplace peers and the social composition of the workplace. Researching the likelihood of becoming an entrepreneur is based upon working with former entrepreneurs. So, it is evident that entrepreneurs have some characteristic behaviours which distinguish them from the rest of the population. Since the main objective of entrepreneurship is to contribute to the development of society by developing persons who perform entrepreneurial roles, efforts were to promote self-employment among women in many developing countries, including Nepal, during the last two decades. It indicates new awareness of the government and policymaker's role to recognise the role of women in economic growth and their capacity to alleviate poverty at the household level (Zein et al., 2008). According to Munoz & Cohen (2020), entrepreneurship is a solution rather than a probable source of social inequality and environmental damage in the last decade. All actions that revolve in and around the creation of organisations, such as creating, operating, and terminating an organisation, are considered entrepreneurial activities (Eijdenberg et al., 2021). Entrepreneurship is on a pedestal. As a result, young people are encouraged to become entrepreneurs when they get older. This idea took deep roots in many of America's young people's minds. As a result, 12% of all SMEs have millennial owners (Guidant Financial, 2020).

Consequently, Ireland et al. (2020, p.51) defined entrepreneurship as a "context-dependent social process through which people and teams generate wealth by putting together unique resources to exploit marketplace opportunities". Entrepreneurship is one of the four resources economists identify as integral to production, land/natural resources, labour, and capital (Hayes et al., 2021). Entrepreneurship is a critical component of economic growth and development (Meyer & Synodinos, 2020). Entrepreneurship is defined as the inventive integration of scarce available production resources, resulting in maximum satisfaction for both customers and the producer, i.e., the entrepreneur (Deo, 2021). According to Bryne et al. (2019), entrepreneurship is a critical tool for reducing unemployment and improving the economy. If entrepreneurship has long-term technical, social, and cultural advancements, then societal and economic benefits are achieved. Entrepreneurship is the process of putting people together in specific ways and combining them with physical capital and ideas to generate an invention or to produce a new product in an effective way (Yaqoob, 2021).

According to Rao (2021), many people worldwide call for an entrepreneurial revolution to fix social and economic problems. Therefore, entrepreneurship needs to address the issues. The revolution should transform contemporary entrepreneurial culture to make it more socially minded. Entrepreneurship is known for creating new ventures that creatively solve problems. It is a powerful tool of cultural change capable of transforming societies. It means consciously incorporating social goals into entrepreneurs' strategic thinking to maximize personal and collective benefits. It demands getting rid of the paradigm that only governments and established companies can address social needs. Hence, entrepreneurship is the way to identify and tackle critical problems, such as poverty and lack of access to health and education.

Hence, from the above works of literature, it is evidence that entrepreneurship do not have fixed definitions. The definition depends on perception, situation, the current environment of the nations. In the next section, the perspective on entrepreneurs is to understand and reflect a diverse view on the role of entrepreneurs.

2.1.2 Who is an entrepreneur?

After reviewing and understanding the concept of entrepreneurship, it is clear who entrepreneurs are. According to Illie (2008), entrepreneurs are the one who plays a fundamental part in the economic progress of the nation by generating employment opportunities for others. According to Kirzner (1973), entrepreneurs have a deep understanding of a business, are proactive, and take advantage of opportunities to benefit from the exchange of services or goods they make. On the other hand, Madichie (2008) describes entrepreneurs as capable of using finite resources, making choices and judgments, and taking risks. The psychological approach identifies successful entrepreneurs' personality patterns or traits. According to McClelland (2004), successful entrepreneurs have initiative and assertiveness, the desire to see and respond to opportunities, and loyalty to others. According to Madichie (2008), entrepreneurs' success is determined by a society's culture because entrepreneurship is a social, behavioural process, as they have a desire for success, are rational risk-takers, possess a strong sense of self-control, creativity, imagination, a need for autonomy, uncertainty, tolerance, and vision.

Entrepreneurs are those who can take high risks despite uncertainty and the one who identifies business opportunities and turn the scarce resources into opportunities instead of being employed or unemployed (Lehner & Kansikas, 2012). Also, Lorz, Mueller & Volery (2013) define entrepreneurs as individuals who organize, manage, and take the enterprise's risk. Finally, according to Hebert (1988), entrepreneurs can be defined as taking responsibility and making judgment decisions that affect the location, form, and use of goods and resources and firms.

In a simple world, entrepreneurs perform a business activity and run firms. Hence, entrepreneurial activities originate from individuals. However, the lack or absence of entrepreneurship skills often makes an entrepreneur incapable of performing tasks. Therefore, entrepreneurship involves all those characteristics and qualities found within the entrepreneurs to make him/her run the business successfully, thus helping him/her make profits. First, many scholars believe that the human element is crucial to entrepreneurship's success. This human aspect could include, for instance, an entrepreneur's history and demographic characteristics. Second, it involves ideals, principles, orientation, and manipulative abilities. Finally, an entrepreneur's leadership style and assertiveness are qualities that define him or her (Bruton, Ahlstrom & Li, 2010).

These entrepreneurial attributes and characteristics, according to researchers, are most seen within the person. These characteristics allow an individual to succeed as a potential entrepreneur. It has become the school's predominant viewpoint, which holds that entrepreneurs are born, not created. The other school of thought, on the other hand, believes that many entrepreneurs master the art of entrepreneurship through experience and through time (Hisrich, 1986). First-generation entrepreneurs, especially those who have never worked in a company, start businesses after completing entrepreneurship training. These first-generation entrepreneurs start a company and learn the game's rules by trial and error. This group of first-generation entrepreneurs includes many of today's successful entrepreneurs, whereas entrepreneurs are not only born but may also be made, according to the other school of thought (Shepherd et al., 2018).

As previously mentioned, developing countries continue to shift toward an entrepreneurial economy via entrepreneurial behaviour, which is the driving force behind a market-based capitalist economy. As a result, characterizing a country's entrepreneurial activity dynamics is

critical for understanding its economic processes and culture. An entrepreneur is someone who starts a new business, company, or project and takes responsibility for the risk and results, or someone who gathers resources (such as innovations, capital, and knowledge) and converts them into financial goods (Reynolds, 2009). Hence, the emergence of entrepreneurs in a society depends significantly on economic, social, religious, cultural, and psychological factors prevailing in the community. In many of the world's advanced countries, there was a phenomenal increase in the number of self-employed after the world war (Deshpande et al., 2009).

According to Sharma & Sahoo (2021), an entrepreneur is a person who takes on new challenges, sees an opportunity for business growth, arranges the necessary resources for the start-up of the business, and bears the risks associated with it. He/she is an innovator, an organizer, and a risk-taker, introduces new products, finds new markets for existing products, introduces new production techniques, and launches new marketing strategies. An entrepreneur also bears the risks and uncertainty of business. All the factors of production, like land, labour, and capital, are arranged so the business can take advantage of the opportunity. Therefore, an entrepreneur is a person who sees a business opportunity, takes steps to promote the business, gathers resources in the form of personnel, materials, and capital to make the business a success, and bears the risks and uncertainties associated with the venture.

In other words, entrepreneurs are the brains behind the scenes who find opportunities and solutions to what the average person views as inconveniences and issues (Deo, 2019). According to Yaqoob (2020), entrepreneurs are those who put people together in specific ways and combine them with physical capital and ideas to generate an invention or produce a new product.

Therefore, entrepreneurs play a vital role in society, both in innovation and disruption, resulting in economic development and the rise of a new era in terms of digital industrialization. Furthermore, this process can encourage self-employment and job generation (Mehta, 2020). According to Abuhussein & Koburtay (2021), emphasize that entrepreneurs have special strengths (e.g., innovation, resources) to achieve sustainable development.

Similarly, according to Sharma & Sahoo (2021), an entrepreneur is an individual who runs a small business and assumes all the risk and rewards of a given business venture, an idea, rather

than working as an employee or service offered for sale. The entrepreneur is a business leader who innovates new ideas and business processes. Today's entrepreneur has the initiative in investment and making decisions about the enterprise; seeking all resources of management, behaviour, culture, economics, and politics for establishing, innovation, and starting up the enterprise and assumes risk, profit, and growth going forward.

2.1.3 Concept of women entrepreneurship

Women entrepreneurs have been making a considerable impact in almost all economic segments. Women entrepreneur refers to a woman or a group of women who start, organise, and run a business. Hence, the concept women entrepreneurship refers to the act of owning and starting a business that financially empowers women and improves their economic strength and status in society (Bharadwaj et al., 2011). According to the Indian government, women entrepreneurs are businesses owned and operated by women that have a minimum financial stake of 51 per cent of the capital and employ at least 51 per cent of the workforce (Hagargi & Rajnalkar, 2011).

A woman entrepreneur takes on a challenging task to fulfil her requirements and become economically self-sufficient. Entrepreneurial women who can contribute to family and social life values have an inbuilt drive to accomplish something positive. Because of the media, women are more aware of their characteristics, rights, and job position (Rao, 2011). In the words of Knight (1921, p.142), entrepreneurs are a specialised group of people who bear risks and deal with uncertainty. Suppose a woman takes the same uncertain risk of initiating a business, sustaining it, and successfully running it by contributing to the nation's economic development in capital formation, improvement in per capita income, and balanced regional development. In that case, she is the real "undertaker of the business" and a successful women entrepreneur.

The term woman entrepreneurship refers to the act of owning a company or starting a business that empowers women economically and improves their social status. As a result, women entrepreneurs have significantly influenced almost every economic sector (Natrajan, 2019). The author also pointed out the motivational factors for women entrepreneurship research. According to the author, there has been much debate in the print and electronic media, parliament, and other forums about entrepreneurship development amongst women in recent

years. Due to various cultural and social reasons, women in different parts have different motives, aspirations, social status, needs and urges. Therefore, varied motivation needs and interest plunges in women entrepreneurs for establishing an enterprise. Factors like economic need, fulfilment of personality needs like power, achievement and novel experience, knowledge gained by educated women, taking their family business, and women's leisure time typically make women entrepreneurs.

In the last few decades, there has been a substantial increase in female entrepreneurs who have become more prominent and thriving in the professional and public spheres. According to evidence, women entrepreneurs are progressively gaining the confidence, leadership, and management abilities needed to thrive in business (Rao, 2011). The number of women entrepreneurs has grown over time, especially in the 1990s. Women entrepreneurs appraisal is a must for their increased utilisation of modern technology, increased investment in finding a niche in the export market, creating suitable employment for others, and setting the trend for other women entrepreneurs in the organised sector (Sathiabama, 2010) because woman entrepreneurs in the United States start businesses at twice the pace of men, but men's enterprises last longer (Hisrich, 1996). Women empowerment fuels thriving economies all over the world. Diversity facilitates a better understanding of problems. However, the maritime industry, the backbone of the global economy, is missing out on a large talent pool that could help it meet the next set of challenges. If every woman entrepreneur inspires and supports two other women to join the start-up ecosystem and become entrepreneurs, the increase in women entrepreneurship can be exponential in base 2. In Europe, women account for 51% of the overall population. The female employment rate is now 67.3%, and women account for 34.4% of those working as independent contractors and 31.2% of those working as start-up entrepreneurs. Nevertheless, female founders account for just 14.8% of all start-up founders. Women in Europe still have the most untapped entrepreneurial and leadership potential (Munoz, 2020). Women control 25% of businesses in the United States, despite their revenues being less than a fifth of other small company groupings. Women own 1/3 of small businesses in Canada and 1/5 of small businesses in France. Since 1980, the number of self-employed women in the United Kingdom has risen three times faster than self-employed males (Deshpande & Sethi, 2009). Currently, only around 6% of working-age women are involved in early-stage entrepreneurial activities, compared to over 10% males. By 2025, increasing female involvement in the industry to 10% would result in a total economic contribution of more than £180 billion from women-led SMEs (Deloitte, 2021).

According to Kumbhar (2013), women are critical human resources of the nation, and every state should try to utilise them as a mediator of economic growth and development. Also, women comprise half of the human resources, they are crucial agents of sustainable development. Therefore, women's equality is central to a more holistic approach toward stabilising new patterns and processes of sustainable development. In today's business world, where there is a severe shortage of entrepreneurial talent, if women do not play a significant role in business, half of the country's potential talent pool will go untapped (Bhargava, 2007).

The role of women entrepreneurs in economic development has been evident since the 1990s in various parts of the world. Women entrepreneurship has become an essential movement today and in all working areas. The United Nations (U.N.) report has also concluded that economic development is closely related to the development of women. In a nation where women have advanced, economic growth has usually been steady. In contrast, many countries restrict women, which results in a stagnant economy (Bharadwaj et al., 2011).

As women entrepreneurs have demonstrated their potential, the fact is that they can contribute much more than what they already are. Therefore, it is necessary to formulate appropriate strategies for stimulating, supporting, and sustaining their efforts in this direction to harness the potential and continued growth and development (Rao, 2011). Furthermore, a distinguishing feature of a woman entrepreneur is the willingness to work hard. Therefore, she must follow the principle that hard work is the key to success (Kumar & Jayachitra, 2013).

Likewise, Ganesan et al. (2021) study that self-motivated women entrepreneurs confront significant problems, and the author tries to establish the role of entrepreneurial training and sustainable, successful women entrepreneurs. It recommends suitable training and boosting women entrepreneurs by building networks and alliances.

Nowadays, women get involved in selected professions like trade, industry, and engineering. Women are also willing to take up business and contribute to the nation's growth. Their roles are valued, and policies are updated to promote women entrepreneurship. Women entrepreneurship must be moulded properly with entrepreneurial traits and skills to meet the changes in trends, challenges, and global market and be competent enough to sustain and strive for excellence in the entrepreneurial arena (Das, 2000). Women have provided work for themselves and others (Stevenson, 2004). However, entrepreneurship offered a partial answer.

Entrepreneurship has triggered women to take a positive step they have been contemplating for some time. Yet, on the other hand, the negative realities of the company posed severe challenges to these women. For most of them, obtaining and maintaining an adequate balance between the domestic and working spheres of their lives has remained a constant challenge, a source of stress.

Additionally, women and men do not have access to the same kinds of capital, which prevents them from participating in the same entrepreneurial activities. According to Johansen (2013), there is a lack of support (institutional, financial, and family), fear of failure, and unfavourable social perceptions. Noguera et al. (2013) identify fear of failure and self-efficacy as significant barriers that prevent women from pursuing a business career. The conclusions reached by Wieland et al. (2019) are like those reached by other authors. The situation is similar in start-ups around the world. The Start-ups Outlook 2018 survey published by Silicon Valley Bank (SVB) (2019) shows that 71% of new American companies lack women on their board and 57% lack women in C-Suite roles. Similarly, companies registered in CrunchBase in 2017 had only 17% female co-founders, confirming the findings of the SVB Survey.

A comparison of the percentage of men and women engaged in entrepreneurship activities focused on innovative products in developed and developing countries is shown in Figure 2. In mid-Asia, South Asia, and the United States of America (USA), women contribute to GDP that contributes more than men entrepreneurs. In contrast, both men and women contribute equally in the developed and developing economies of Europe. However, in developing economies of Asia, women entrepreneurs contribute less to the GDP than men.

Figure 2: Percentage of male and female engaged in entrepreneurship activities

Source: Adapted from GEM, 2021

Many women entrepreneurs are also motivated by a desire for self-determination, self-esteem, appreciation, and increased self-satisfaction (Buttne & Moore, 1997). Over the past decade, women's entrepreneurship has emerged to address unemployment and income generation. They play an increasingly important role in promoting a country's communal and economic growth (Dhakal, 2006). According to Bruin, Brush & Welter (2007), many companies are now owned by women, as seen in the USA, Australia, and India. Women entrepreneurship is critical for the growth and development of the economy (Jamali, 2009). Due to this, governments have realized the importance of female entrepreneurship and implemented several programs to foster it (Vossenber, 2013). As part of this development, education is likely to become one of the biggest wealth generators in the future (Bajracharya, 2007). However, female entrepreneurs have 63 per cent fewer opportunities to access external risk capital than their male counterparts (Guzman & Kacperczyk, 2019).

Likewise, a stereotyped picture of a woman in business has persisted in developing countries due to a lack of evidence, data, and advertising about women entrepreneurs (Kumar & Jayachitra, 2013). Nonetheless, some women have managed to break free from the constraints that confine them to the domestic sphere and have pursued careers and services in various

fields. In addition, women entrepreneurs are highly driven and successful entrepreneurs, capable of challenging their male peers in all aspects of market knowledge and ability (Carter et al., 2001). In a predominantly male society, there are various reasons for women to engage in entrepreneurial activity. Women's entrepreneurship is a vital chance to transcend any feeling of inferiority they may have in their communities and culture (Kargwell, 2012). Women entrepreneurs are not a homogeneous group, according to researchers in women entrepreneurship. Women who seek entrepreneurship have quite different motives, backgrounds, and attitudes depending on the country, culture, or sector (Syedda, 2018). Also, women in developing countries are aware of their rights, and they can achieve a respectable position in society by starting their businesses. It allows them to serve their families better while also benefiting society by reducing poverty, creating job opportunities, and serving as role models for other women (Yaqoob, 2021). According to UN Women and NRNA (2019), if women can participate, contribute, and lead in all areas. Indeed, women at work can be proven to bring about observable improvements in families and society and to significantly reduce poverty with economic growth in developing countries (OECD, 2021).

In the next section, the researcher presents all the findings from past studies and literature reviews on exploring barriers women entrepreneurs face.

(Please see appendix 8 & 9 for the previous studies on women entrepreneurship and motivational factors for women to become entrepreneurs, respectively).

2.2 Past studies on women entrepreneurship based on continents

The previous section clarifies the meaning of entrepreneurship, women entrepreneurship, the impact, and role women entrepreneurs play in today's business world. Since the topic of this study is to explore the career barriers to successful women entrepreneurs in the food industry of Nepal, the researcher's initial step is to exhaust all the findings from the previous study. Thus, this section presents all the results on the barriers women entrepreneurs face whilst doing business in their respective countries. The themes are created based on the continent and presented accordingly.

2.2.1 Women Entrepreneurship in Europe

According to Hostak (2019), on "Fostering women's entrepreneurship in the European Commission's Executive in Europe: 15 concrete solutions" using in-depth interviews and a focus group of a total of 33 women entrepreneurs from Moldova concluded that women entrepreneurs in Eastern Europe face significant barriers like finance as one of the most significant barriers. Female entrepreneurs revolve around financial schemes and instruments, lack of awareness about them or their insufficient diversity. Other relevant issues found are a lack of financial literacy, capacities suited to the needs of female entrepreneurs in a financial institution, stereotype, developing entrepreneurial competencies for women and adequate entrepreneurial education, lack of tailored mentorship and mature support networks for the female entrepreneur, insufficient support for and during parental leave, a lack of female role models.

Similarly, the study on "Women Entrepreneurs in Europe" by Geambasu (2019) used qualitative methods using interviews and focus tools on collecting data for 70 participants, ten each from Hungary, Germany, Austria, Romania, Iceland, Spain, and Portugal. The participants were selected using the convenience sampling method. The study revealed that women entrepreneurship in these countries faces barriers like switching employment to entrepreneurship dilemma, time famine, lack of security in finance, networking with friends, family, and acquaintances. However, the barriers identified were more finance and personal confidence related barriers, limiting women entrepreneurs' activities in these countries.

Iakovleva, Solesvik & Trifilova (2013) conducted a study on the topic "Financial availability and government support for women entrepreneurs in transitional economies: Cases of Russia and Ukraine" of 60 Russian and Ukrainian entrepreneurs 60 interviews data collection achieved. Of the 60 interviews conducted, 42 were in Russia and 18 in Ukraine. The study concluded that female interviewers in Russia do not use the programmes or support activities. It happens because they do not know about such programmes or perceive that obtaining such support is too complex and demanding. However, in Ukraine, women entrepreneurs do not receive substantial support from the government. They have not heard about government educational and other support programmes related to female entrepreneurship.

2.2.2 Women Entrepreneurship in Asia

The study conducted by Jamali (2009) examines the relationship between constraints and opportunities affecting female entrepreneurship in developing countries. It integrates salient micro-and macro-level perspectives and provides a rounded account of options and conditions as part of a holistic interdependent system. He adopts an integrative multi-level research design and an interpretive research methodology, capitalising on in-depth interviews with ten women entrepreneurs to explore their perceptions and interpretations of constraints and opportunities facing female entrepreneurship in the Indian context. The findings illustrate the relevance of micro, meso and macro-level factors in entrepreneurship research and the usefulness of integrating multiple lens and units of analysis to capture the complexity of the women entrepreneurship experience in any context. Das (2000) found a study on women entrepreneurs of SMEs in two states of India, viz, Tamilnadu and Kerala. The initial problems faced by women entrepreneurs are pretty like those faced by women in western countries. However, Indian women entrepreneurs faced a lower level of work-family conflict. They differed from their counterparts in western countries based on reasons for starting and succeeding in business—similar trends found in other Asian countries such as Indonesia and Singapore. Again, the statistics showed that women's proportion of business and operations is much lower than the figures found in western countries. Das (2000) shows that more than 50 per cent of the women used their funds or funds borrowed from their spouse or family to set up their business. Another such study done among women entrepreneurs in Coimbatore District, Tamil Nadu, points out financing the enterprise as a significant problem women entrepreneurs face. Most entrepreneurs rely on family finance or, at the maximum, on partners and friends. Lack of access to capital has been a primary obstacle for women entrepreneurs. Research suggests that women's primary funding source has been family loans, personal savings, credit cards, and home equity loans.

Also, the study conducted by Chiplinkar & Goldberg (2021) identifies and quantifies barriers to entry and operation faced by female entrepreneurs in developing countries and applies them to the Indian economy. The study found that female entrepreneurs still face substantial entry and business registration costs (almost twice their male counterparts) despite considerable progress over time. The costs of expanding a business, conditional on entry, are also substantially higher for women and revealed that the sectoral composition of female

employment does not drive the pattern. Counterfactual simulations indicate that removing all excess barriers faced by women entrepreneurs would

1. increase the fraction of female-owned firms significantly (nine times).
2. increase the real wages of females relative to male workers, and
3. generate substantial aggregate productivity and welfare gains (ca. 7% and 18% respectively).

Reallocation of resources is the reason for these significant gains: low-productivity male-owned firms sheltered from the female competition are replaced by higher-productivity female-owned firms previously excluded from the economy.

Nevertheless, Nawaz (2009) aims to analyse the critical factors of women entrepreneurship development in rural Bangladesh. The analysis was on recent theoretical ideas that empirical research findings have supported. Nawaz depicted an analytical framework based on institutional theory, which focuses on three kinds of factors: regulative, normative, and cognitive. Despite having access to various micro credits, rural women receive almost no training from development organisations, adversely affecting their efficiency and performance. Widespread illiteracy, lack of primary education, training and experience remain serious obstacles in rural women's entrepreneurship development. Besides the lack of awareness, social superstitions, and the absence of the rule of law also affect the rural women's participation in economic activities outside the family.

Research undertaken on women entrepreneurs in Pakistan states that increased participation of women in the labour force creates challenges for them balancing work and family obligations. The situation becomes more complicated in patriarchal societies such as Pakistan due to women's stereotypical domestic roles, religious prescriptions, and cultural norms and values. Their study aimed to explore different factors influencing women's work and family roles in the unique Pakistani socio-economic and cultural environment. Their results showed that achieving work-life balance was one of the most significant among other motivational drivers to start their businesses. Their businesses gave them flexibility, control, and freedom to juggle their family and social responsibilities. Lack of sufficient time, gender bias, social and cultural norms, and family responsibilities were the most significant challenges women face to achieve balance in a patriarchal Islamic society. Strategic planning, organising, and delegating are the most effective strategies women use to cope with work and family competing roles (Rehman & Roomi, 2012).

The study by Rao & Venakatachalam (2012), "Challenges Faced by Women Entrepreneurs Running Micro, Small and Medium Scale Fashion and Apparel Business: A Study on Fashion and Apparel Enterprises in Coastal Karnataka." is focused on listing the challenges faced by women entrepreneurs with a high value associated with the MSMEs and the potential fashion and apparel sector. A primary test questionnaire and means were employed to find the most critical challenges women entrepreneurs face. They emphasise the following critical problems women entrepreneurs face: access to finance, labour shortage, lack of relevant education and experience, conflicts between work and domestic commitments, and access to training. The findings from this study revealed that the success of women enterprises depends on the formal education and the training related to the business they received on their entrepreneurial journey. The critical challenges faced by women entrepreneurs in establishing and growing the business were finance, finding skilled labour and increased competition.

The research conducted by Manila (2019) on "Breaking Barriers: Women Entrepreneurs in Asia" research intended to find out the key challenges are lack of access to finance and markets, as well as limited education and training in starting, managing, and growing a business. Legal and regulatory barriers across the region; lack of an enabling environment, including networks; and unpaid care work impede women's ability to start a business. In addition, social and cultural norms and practices constraining women's mobility and interactions affect women's opportunities for entrepreneurship. Despite these difficulties, women-led micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) are growing, and some are successfully thriving, including those in the technology sector (e-commerce, online marketing) and other emerging innovative areas. The seminar highlighted initiatives such as enacting laws and strategies on financial inclusion and setting numerical targets for women leaders, entrepreneurs, and women led MSMEs. Comprehensive support for start-ups and entrepreneurs for women is a must, including access to finance, financial literacy, business skills, networking, and mentoring. The panellists also cited that support from peers, partners, and family members are critical in changing deeply entrenched social norms and helping women engage and succeed in business.

2.2.3 Women Entrepreneurship in South America

The study by Nassif et al. (2012) on "Women entrepreneurs: Discussion about their competencies" was to analyse the entrepreneurial competencies that characterise women in the

Southeast region of Brazil, with some financial limitations, when responding to quotidian challenges in their businesses, these being the result of their trajectories built throughout their social interactions. It also sought to understand the meaning of the challenges, obstacles, and competencies upon which they rely on unexpected circumstances, without concern for enumeration and measurement of the events studied or generalisation results. The research is classified as exploratory, intending to explain the phenomenon studied based on the point of view of the research subjects. Seven female participants were involved in an entrepreneurship program in Sao Paulo city and financed by an American bank. Data were collected using in-depth interviews, followed by a flexible questionnaire. The data analysis was based on the content analysis and classified into three blocks: Category 1 – decisive factors in beginning the business; Category 2 – challenges and obstacles in the entrepreneurial career; Category 3 - competencies developed and under development during the trajectory.

The results reveal that female entrepreneurs perceive their potentialities, limitations, desires, and concerns within the scope of cognitive and affective competencies. They recognise the importance of developing a perception of opportunity, business and applying leadership competencies. Interpersonal skills, commitment, and social perception are sets of entrepreneurial competencies that contribute to their companies. It is evident that although fragmented in theory, cognitive and affective aspects are, in practice, inseparable. Following a similar study Kirkwood (2009), in his research, found that men tend to have higher self-confidence than women and affect their entrepreneurial intentions. However, how self-confidence affects entrepreneurs in their start-up decision is not known. Even less is understood about how it affects entrepreneurs' decisions and actions in their ongoing business. Her study aimed to meet these two objectives by using a gender comparative approach. Her research findings concluded that women lack self-confidence in their abilities as entrepreneurs compared to men. This finding parallels the results of prior research. Once in an established business, women relate to entrepreneurship less than men and do not feel comfortable calling themselves entrepreneurs. For some women, entrepreneurial self-confidence grew over their time in the industry. However, it appears to continue to constrain other women, affecting their ability to access finance and curtailing their growth aspirations.

Conversely, Edwards (2012) examines the current literature on Women Entrepreneurs and their access to financial resources in Colombia. It goes on to review what are the challenges faced in acquiring these resources and the current gaps that exist in the research, particularly in the

developing world. The key themes that emerge from the literature are that women entrepreneurs face challenges accessing finance, particularly debt and equity, due to business and industry. The challenges include the age, size, risk, potential, financial savvy, and networks that women businesses possess. Additionally, angel financing, bootstrapping, and funds from family and friends have not been studied in detail, even though many women use these types of funds to start and grow their firms. Women continue to face challenges in accessing debt finance. It is a challenge for women who withdraw or are involved in low growth businesses within industries, either small or stagnant. The size and growth potential of the firm also plays a significant part in determining whether the entrepreneur can easily access debt finance. Equity financing for women entrepreneurs appears to be even more challenging to obtain. Bruin, Brush & Welter (2009) have argued that women are willing to access and obtain equity financing through equity and angel funding. They also suggest that the difficulties exist due to the myths, which include women's unwillingness to own high growth businesses and do not have the financial savvy or network to start these high growth businesses that attract equity funding. Further research is recommended on the supply side of the equity industry to determine, like with banks, whether there are factors that affect the supply of venture capital to women entrepreneurs.

Another study by Carter et al. (2003) surveyed "Women entrepreneurs who break through to equity financing: the influence of human, social and financial capital" of 235 Chile women business owners to systematically study attributes of women business owners and their equity financing strategies. The study explored the factors associated with the use of equity capital in a women-led firm. Carter et al. (2003) used a survey method to administer a questionnaire with a "closed" response to women business owners via a telephone interview. Potential respondents for this study came from a survey of US women business owners conducted by the National Foundation for Women Business Owners (NFWBO) in 2000. Since women who seek and acquire equity capital appear to be few, a sampling procedure was adopted to maximise the probability of finding representatives of this elusive population. Respondents were women who owned firms identified by Dun and Bradstreet and who met one or more of the following criteria: business operated within an industry associated with venture capital; located in one of the top states for venture capital activity or showed 15% or more revenue growth over each of the past three years. The main characteristics of respondents were as follows. Almost 40% of the women were between 45 and 54 years of age, and few were non-white; approximately two-thirds (64%) of the businesses operated in the service sector. Most companies reported annual revenues of less than \$250000 (62%), and less than 18% reported sales totalling \$1 million or

higher. Nearly 45% indicated they had ten or fewer full-time employees, and 41% reported less than \$50000 capital available in their businesses. Data analysis showed only graduate education significantly influenced the odds of using outside equity financing. Social capital had no direct effect on increasing the likelihood of using equity but influenced bootstrapping techniques. Network diversity was positively related to private funding sources, while professional advisor relationships were negatively related to private funding sources. This research suggests that women obtaining higher levels of education may increase their likelihood of securing funding. Further, during the bootstrap phase, utilising social capital is an asset.

2.2.4 Women Entrepreneurship in Africa

Few researchers like, Bosma & Harding (2007), Parker (2009) and Verheul & Thurik (2001) showed that women represent massively in the consumer-oriented, retail, service, and personal services sector, where men mostly have their businesses in the manufacturing, the financial and the construction sector. These differences are factors like education, job experience and start-up capital. So naturally, these factors impact the type of industry women want to engage in, but it also influences becoming an entrepreneur.

However, Brixiova & Kangoye (2019) also conducted a study on "Networks, Start-Up Capital and Women's Entrepreneurial Performance in Africa: Evidence from Eswatini ". The paper analyzes the role of networks in women entrepreneurs' access to start-up capital and firm performance in Eswatini, a country with one of the highest female unemployment rates in Africa. According to the paper, both male and female entrepreneurs with higher initial capital have better sales performance. Women entrepreneurs start their businesses with less capital and are more likely to fund them from private sources, which reduces their company's size and sales level. However, women with higher education tend to start their firms with more capital. In addition, women who receive support from professional networks tend to have more outstanding initial capital, whereas women trained in financial literacy are more likely to access external funding sources, including their professional networks.

A study titled "Microfinancing and Micro-Enterprise Growth in Nigeria" by Taiwo, Alege, and Olokoyo (2016) found that enterprises owned by male microentrepreneurs generate more employment than those owned by female microentrepreneurs, while jobs in enterprises owned

by those with no formal education decline. The study in Accra and Ghana to find out the challenges female entrepreneurs face identified as individuals who encounter more obstacles in starting and growing their businesses than their male counterparts, especially within informal SMEs where they are predominantly employed. Thus, female entrepreneurs in Danquah Circle were participants of the study. Women who owned and managed businesses in the saloon industry answered the interview questions to further their constraints in starting and growing their businesses—data collection for this research via secondary and primary data. Most saloon owners completed high school and furthered their education by tertiary education in universities and polytechnics, while others completed diploma courses such as the Higher National Diplomas (HNDs). However, few women were at Senior Secondary School (SSS) but attended vocational schools where they learned about hair and other beauty-related courses. The researcher found two significant reasons for being an entrepreneur: personal and financial motivation. Women, especially those in Ghana, are driven by self-fulfilment and achievement because, in Ghanaian society, there is respect for women for their accomplishments and abilities. However, they found that financial motivation was not the primary reason to start their business. However, it is a motivating factor because of the rewards in that it generates income. The most common challenge faced by Ghanaian women while starting up their business was access to credit and human capital problems, mainly management and technical skills and the hiring and training of competent staff during the growth phase (Cham, 2011).

Researchers Morris & Sexton (1996) suggest that female business owners are subject to gender-related discrimination. In addition, Abor & Biekpe (2006) emphasise that this discrimination against women seems to be even worse in sub-Saharan African countries, such as Ghana, where the financial sector is male-oriented. Support from Marlow (1997) commented that discrimination remains a problem for women in self-employment; for example, they experience difficulties gaining bank finance for their ventures. Challenges to women entrepreneurs cover a broad spectrum, including the level of education, inter-role conflicts emanating from greater parenting responsibilities, a dearth of financial assistance and socio-cultural constraints (Danish, 2012). Women reported more difficulties than males, even though both men and women have personal concerns. It is particularly true for lack of trust and not being taken seriously by fund providers when asking for funds (Davis, 2012). In addition, African women have fewer resources than their male counterparts. For example, compared to males, they have less access to property, financing, education, and training opportunities (Drine & Grach, 2012).

Furthermore, in many African countries, women have fewer inheritance rights by law or obstacles preventing women from realising their economic potential and constraining economic development (Unruh et al., 2014). However, Budlender & Moussie (2013) argue that growth-oriented donors have promoted investment strategies in Africa that typically exclude women due to the commonly held view that women enterprises are in undynamic sub-sectors with little potential the growth.

The study conducted by Halkias et al. (2011) performed a study on "Challenges facing women entrepreneurs in Nigeria". The study examines the business and social profiles of 67 women entrepreneurs in three regions of Nigeria to identify patterns of entrepreneurship and social and economic challenges facing women business owners in Nigeria. The study aims to support and encourage sustainable small-scale economic development activities by Nigerian women and determine ways to integrate these small businesses into existing urban economic development projects and strategies for poverty alleviation, expand understanding of the business and social profiles of women entrepreneurs in Nigeria, examine the contextual influences on their work, raise the level of awareness of women entrepreneurs amongst all economically active agents and researchers, influence social and economic policy addressing issues of women entrepreneurs. A survey of 62 practising Nigerian female entrepreneurs. The survey divides into sections that record personal demographics, the entrepreneur's perceptions of the business environment and their venture and the motivations and drives that led to the birth of their business. The study found that with no or few significant differences between male and female business owners or managers once they have already started an enterprise, there is a strong indication that Africa has sizeable hidden growth potential in its women. Furthermore, the results show that micro-financing and family dynamics drive female entrepreneurship that shape and influence Nigeria's birth.

2.2.5 Women Entrepreneurship in MENA region

Directing on the geographical context, Chamlou (2008) wrote a report on "The Environment for Women's Entrepreneurship in the Middle East and North Africa Region" about how women entrepreneurs could contribute more to the quality and direction of economic and social development in the Middle East and North Africa region. The objective of the report was to provide a better understanding of barriers to investment and doing business that might be

common to all investors and those that affected women entrepreneurs disproportionately. This report offers policymakers and stakeholders contemplating reforms to the investment climate. The report examined newly available data from over 5100 surveyed firms in the formal sector in eight Middle Eastern countries (Egypt, Jordan, Lebanon, Morocco, Saudi Arabia, Syria, Gaza, the West Bank, and Yemen). The report intended to provide an overview of the characteristics of female-owned firms in the region; analyse gender-specific barriers that exist across the region or within countries and identify other factors outside the business environment that might affect women's entrepreneurship. The report concluded that all entrepreneurs face highly critical barriers in the investment climate, with few differences between male and female entrepreneurs. However, some elements of the investment climate are gender-differentiated, and women seem to face hurdles outside the investment climate that hold them back from participating in the formal economy. The report finishes with policy recommendations to reduce the identified barriers and create a level playing field for women entrepreneurs. The report acknowledges limitations from the availability and depth of data. Indeed, it may raise more questions than it answers. The hope is to spur greater interest in researchers and policymakers.

According to Laffineur et al. (2021), women entrepreneurs in the MENA region face discrimination, difficulties in accessing financial, stereotyping and preconception about the roles and abilities of women are the main barriers in six different countries, namely Egypt, Jordan, Lebanon, Morocco, Palestine, and Tunisia on the topic, "Insights from Female Entrepreneurs in MENA Countries: Barriers and Success Factors." The author provided a recommendation to focus more on educating women on managing and maximising entrepreneur skills. Also, the author suggested the need for networking and experience in business as the significant drivers for growth, whereas government, structure and marital status are other influencing factors to enter the entrepreneurship field.

Also, a critical view by Bahramitash & Esfahani (2018) was put across whilst conducting a study on "Women's Economic Role in the MENA Region: Growth and Equality through Female-Owned SMEs." The data from 11 countries in the MENA region found a considerable number of informal SMEs and micro-enterprises, and the challenge they faced was even more significant than those involved in formal sections. It is due to failure by mainstream policymakers to bring inclusive growth or to reduce inequality. In terms of women's economic roles, neoliberalism has resulted in two outcomes: First, gender-related economic policy has

shifted to increasing women's employment, based on the idea that higher employment leads to greater economic empowerment for women. Second, there has been a greater focus on strengthening the role of women as entrepreneurs, particularly those who run small and medium businesses (SME). Also, some beliefs regarding Islam's role as a significant impediment to women's participation in public life in the literature and media. Sexual harassment at work is another major sociocultural issue that impacts women's economic involvement and empowerment. Working women's sexual harassment is a common and well-known problem worldwide. Most nations have legislation and legal sanctions against criminals. Based on statistical analysis across nations, we discovered that the presence of criminal punishments for sexual harassment in the workplace tended to increase the representation of women in male-owned SMEs.

Likewise, from the study conducted by Salama (2021), concluded that more than other regions, the MENA region faces specific barriers for women to interact in the public sphere and to access vital resources. In addition, it poses constraints that need attention on specific access to technology, financing, and access to information, which is necessary in a globalized world. Some of the main barriers and constraints identified in hampering women entrepreneurs from entering the economic mainstream are gender-specific barriers that have made considerable efforts to narrow the gender gap, cultural norms, civil law to enforce certain customs and social norms, access to financial services and resources, barriers in the business environment, lack of research and data to inform an effective advocacy strategy.

The study by Modaressi et al. (2021) reveals that despite the expansion of women's entrepreneurial activities and its positive effects on the economic development of societies, women still face numerous difficulties in starting and running a business compared to men, especially in developing countries, because of gender discrimination in the field. Therefore, the cultural context in societies is a significant factor affecting the status of entrepreneurship among Iranian women. The present study aims to identify the challenges faced by Iranian women entrepreneurs. Results from 30 semi-structured interviews with women entrepreneurs and women in entrepreneurial roles showed that socio-cultural challenges faced by women entrepreneurs are in three categories: "the society's perception of entrepreneurship among women," "women's social security," and "common family norms governing society."

Likewise, a study conducted by (Elsayed, Namoro and Roushdy, 2021), "Empowering women in conservative settings: evidence from an intervention in rural Egypt," found that Women in several developing nations confront significant problems because of their lack of economic and social empowerment. The situation in the Middle East is one of the worst in terms of women's empowerment since they face both human capital and societal limitations. Despite the growing number of initiatives aimed at women and designed to address their human capital restrictions, they are not always practical. One explanation for this might be failing to appreciate the conservative social milieu—the data from 30 women entrepreneurs via in-depth interviews in Cairo. The study suggested the need for training and education to uplift and overcome the barriers that women entrepreneurs face. The subsequent section summarises the barriers from past studies, which further enables the researcher to construct a conceptual framework.

Also, Abuhussein & Koburtay (2021) enlighten that drawing on the "5Ms" gender cognizant framework, this study seeks to investigate how money, motherhood, management, the market and the macro/meso environment dimensions of the 5Ms may influence women's entrepreneurship in Jordan. A related aim is to offer in-depth insights and a fresh understanding of potential factors not included in the original 5Ms model. The study takes a qualitative-inductive approach, using semi-structured interviews with 14 women entrepreneurs from various industries in Jordan. The paper highlights the positive (or adverse) impact of the 5Ms factors (motherhood, macro/meso environment, the market, management, and money) on women entrepreneurs in Jordan and introduces new emerging factors. The paper concludes with a comprehensive view of the 5Ms model. Developing sensitivity and understanding about some of the adverse gender practices women entrepreneurs face might be possible through this study.

For this reason, policymakers in Jordan and other Arab countries may consider providing more monetary funds and facilities, social support, and managerial empowerment to women entrepreneurs. The study creates more sensitivity and awareness about the current dynamics, opportunities and impediments that affect women entrepreneurs; thus, it contributes to the extant literature by suggesting new propositions and a novel framework. This study adds three essential factors (Mental health, maturity, and maintainability) to Brush et al. (2009)'s gendered 5Ms framework. The empirical update and contextual extension of Brush *et al.*'s (2009) 5Ms model highlight a theoretical contribution.

2.3 Summary on the barriers identified to women entrepreneurs in the context of global perspective

Studies on women entrepreneurs have typically focused on examining entrepreneurial women's and men's qualities and unique properties based on personality traits, promotion, or experience. Other aspects investigated include the size, goals, access to capital, performance, and business management processes. Furthermore, scholars have recently focused their efforts on determining macro-level influences on women entrepreneurs (Verheul et al., 2006). Whereas the studies on women entrepreneurship, its challenges and prospects, scope in developing countries, mainly at India, Bangladesh, Arab countries, Pakistan, and even Africa, unfortunately, there is very little research on this topic in Nepal. It is evident from the above literature review and ongoing literature.

However, the data to gather this information is significantly less available. Hence more investigation should be carried out to explore various barriers faced by women entrepreneurship. Also, previous literature has identified many barriers to women entrepreneurship. However, it is still unknown how significant these barriers are at any time or situation. Therefore, emerging contextual barriers in the existing research need in-depth exploration of how these barriers occur and affect women entrepreneurship in that context. In Table 3, the barriers women entrepreneurs face is summarised from past studies from different international countries.

Table 1: Barriers identified faced by women entrepreneurs in context of global

Continents	Barriers identified (Global Perspective)
Europe	Lack of financial scheme, lack of tailored mentorship, double responsibilities, fear of failure
South America	Access to financial credit, self-confidence, equity capital, entrepreneurial information
Asia	Social norms, access to finance, legal constraints, stereotyping, gender discrimination
Africa	Gender discrimination, lack of finance,
Mena	Social norms, gender roles, legal barriers, child responsibilities

Source: Researcher's own work

From table 3, it is evidence that women entrepreneurs in international countries like face significant barriers. The most common barriers are finance and skills related barriers. Nevertheless, other barriers like socio, gender, and culture are also evident in most countries. Therefore, the summary aids the researcher to contrast the barriers identified in the context of Nepal.

CHAPTER THREE: LITERATURE REVIEW ON WOMEN ENTREPRENEURSHIP (PART II: NATION'S PERSPECTIVE)

3.1 Introduction

Nepal is "a heterogeneous nation, where geographical isolation works to reinforce linguistic, caste and religious divisions" (Zivetz, 1992, p. 50). It is a multicultural country and relies heavily on its neighbours' infrastructure, peace, prosperity, politics, and administrative practices. Nepal may have economic constraints because its landlocked country relied on surrounding nations to move commodities and connect them to international markets (Paudel & Burke, 2021). For example, Nepal depends on India for trade access to the Indian Ocean (Lahiri & Masjidi, 2011). Therefore, this chapter begins with the status of Nepalese women entrepreneurs. This chapter also provides an overview of the impact of social norms on women entrepreneurs and gradually describes the food industry of Nepal.

This chapter presents a comparative analysis from past studies conducted on women entrepreneurs in Nepal with the global context. Furthermore, the researcher has then constructed a conceptual framework as a roadmap to conduct the research in-depth.

3.1.1 Status of women entrepreneurs in Nepal

Women in many developing countries face different types of discrimination (Mishra & Sam, 2016). Women are considered "second-class people" in patriarchal Nepalese society (Acharya & Gurung, 2016, p. 102). Nepalese men possess power over women, making women solely responsible for household chores, childbirth, and family matters (Acharya & Halpenny, 2013). According to Dhakal et al. (2007), "Nepalese women generally have a low social status." "The role of women in advancing a society is rarely discussed as a growth option" in Nepal (Acharya & Halpenny, 2013, p. 374). According to the findings, they are "treated as commodities or as child-producing machines" according to the results (Acharya & Gurung, 2016, p. 102). Similarly, Nepalese women have only a "housekeeper and child-bearer" job at their husband's house like other Asian women (Pradhan et al., 2011, p. 59). "The social condition of Nepalese women is complicated and not clear within a single paradigm," writes Luitel (2001, p.101). "Nepal's first task of the twenty-first century would be to effectively modify existing patriarchal

practices that obstruct the objective of gender equality for women," writes Rai (1981, p.37). Women have made a comparatively late entry into business scenarios in Nepal, mainly due to Nepal's orthodox and traditional socio-cultural environment. However, specific communities in the country, especially the Newars, Sherpas, Gurungs, Thakalis, women are traditionally involved in the small business enterprise (Tuladhar, 1996) and have a unique talent for economic activities.

According to Bhardwaj et al. (2011), women's hidden entrepreneurship potential has gradually changed with a growing awareness of their role and economic status in Nepalese society. As a result, women become more aware of their roles, responsibilities, and working conditions. Today, women entrepreneurs represent a community of women who have ventured off the beaten track and sought new economic opportunities. Women run organised enterprises for various reasons, including their expertise and experience, skills, ability, creativity in the industry, and a compelling desire to do things independently (Tripathi, 2012).

Therefore, the emergence of women entrepreneurs and their contribution to the national economy is visible in Nepal. Earning quick money is the main reason for Nepalese women to start entrepreneurship. The status of women of Nepal has been changing due to growing industrialisation, globalisation, and social legislation. With the spread of education and awareness, women have shifted from the kitchen to a higher level of professional activity (Kumbhar, 2013).

They have a deep-seated need for a sense of independence along with a desire to do something meaningful with their time and to have their own identity instead of remaining closeted behind their husbands' nameplates. Agreeing to Kumbhar (2013), entrepreneurship has been a male-dominated phenomenon very early. Still, the time has changed the situation and brought women as today's most memorable and inspirational entrepreneurs. In almost all the developed countries globally, women are taking their steps on a par with businesspeople. Therefore, the role of women entrepreneurs in economic development is inevitable. It is also evident that in developed countries, women are actively participative in business and trade activities, including agriculture, without any social or other restrictions (Rao, 2011).

In this 21st century, even women's status has changed, especially in developing countries like India, Nepal, and Pakistan, due to growing industrialisation and urbanisation, spasmodic

mobility, and social legislation. With the advent of media, women are aware of their traits, rights, and work situation. Women are indulged in every type of business from "papad" to power cables. The challenge and opportunities provided to the women of the digital era are proliferating. Consequently, the job seekers are turning into job creators (Goyal et al., 2011). They are flourishing as designers, interior decorators, exporters, publishers, garment manufacturers and still exploring new avenues of economic participation. Women-owned businesses are highly increasing in the economies of almost all countries. More and more women are going in for higher education, technical and professional education, and their proportion in the workforce has also increased. With the spread of education and awareness, women have shifted from the kitchen, handicraft, and traditional cottage industries to non-traditional higher-level activities. Even the government has provided special entrepreneurial training programmes to women to start their ventures (Nachimuthu & Gunatharan, 2012). Field et al. (2016) reported that women who participate in a business training programme with a friend are more likely to take out business loans, are less likely to be housewives, and report improved business activity and household income. The advantages of training with a friend are much more evident amongst women from religious or caste groups where social norms constraint female flexibility. According to this study, empowering female entrepreneurs to build more ties with other female entrepreneurs may help them succeed.

However, conservative societal mindsets and the state's and respective authorities' incompetence remain significant barriers to women's entrepreneurship growth (Karki, 2017). Women also face many social and cultural barriers in Nepal, and as a result, their participation in entrepreneurial practices is lower than it should be. Even though Nepal and South Asian countries have recently but rightly recognised the importance of women entrepreneurship, entrepreneurship is a realm associated with men in every culture due to numerous social factors and bigotry against the phenomena of female entrepreneurship. Despite their significant entrepreneurial presence in developed countries, scholars and governments in these parts of the world have failed to bring women entrepreneurs into the spotlight. Gender inequality is rooted in the entrepreneurial community and in developed nations that are economically and culturally backwards and marked by social imbalances. As a result, the country is not utilising women's talent in every aspect of life (Kote & Honnakeri, 2012).

Nepal's sociological setup has been traditionally a male-dominated one. Women are considered the weaker sex and always depend on menfolk in their family and outside throughout their lives. They are left with lesser commitments and kept as a dormant force for quite a long time. Nepalese culture made them only subordinates and executors of the decision made by other male members in the basic family structure (Hada & Shrestha, 1992). Women are also called "DEVI", which means God in Sanskrit. She can multitask regarding entrepreneurial activities.

Nevertheless, society is still confining women to their home's four walls in traditional society, children, and family rituals. Though the woman is a dynamic and dependable worker who works without pay for 12 to 14 hours a day around the year, she suffers the subordinate's humiliating status. Moreover, granting equal status to women in Nepal has remained imbalanced due to social prejudices and other self-factors like lack of education and adequate employment opportunities. As a result, Nepali women have remained the nation's most excellent untapped resources (Tuladhar, 1996).

Nevertheless, the traditional setup is changing in the modern era. The transformation of the social fabric of Nepalese society, in terms of the increased educational status of women and varied aspirations for better living, necessitated a change in the lifestyle of Nepalese women. Women are trying to become no longer the fairer or the weaker gender. She has competed with men and successfully stood up with them in every walk of life, and women-owned businesses are highly increasing in the economics of almost all countries (Shrestha, 2007). Women experience managing one of the household's most complex organisations, with its many human interfaces and interplay between the sexes, different age groups, and stakeholders. Women have learned the art of negotiation and reconciliation over the centuries, qualities of patience and understanding, and the inherent quality of emotional intelligence. These transferable skills can be brought to bear in the workplace, making it richer from these valuable experiences (Parikh & Mahruk, 1999). Despite all the hurdles the modern Nepali women have realised, their neglected power is at the core of their backwardness. Hence, the women have taken the significant step of empowering themselves with available resources to make their own decisions. Within the last two decades, the concept of women entrepreneurship has gained some acceptance in Nepalese society. Also, women have recognised their importance and role in the nation's economic development, which leads to their economic self-reliance. Women today are under historical stress to rethink and redefine their beliefs and roles at home and outside the home. A new economy, social order, and way of thought have arisen, primarily

shaped by science and technology. Only those who will confidently shake hands with the emerging global economy and adapt to faster technological change have a future (Dhakal, 2006).

In Nepal, from the very beginning, women have been the kitchen manager and have solely dominated household activities. So, in general, the people's attitude about women entrepreneurs is that they are makers of pickles, pappads, masalas and other household goods (Malla & Chhetri, 2009). The economic status of women is an indicator of a society's stage of development. Therefore, it becomes imperative for the government to frame policies for entrepreneurship development among women (Bhuvneshwari & Annapoorani, 2013). The concept of developing women entrepreneurship emphasises women's productive utilisation to generate income and alleviate poverty. In today's context, both in developed and developing countries, the emergence of women entrepreneurs and their contribution to the national economy is quite visible. The number of women entrepreneurs has grown over time, especially in the 1990s. UN's report has also concluded that economic development is closely related to the advancement of women. A nation where women have advanced, they are applauded for their business due to their utilisation of modern technology, which results in an upsurge of business investment, finding a niche in the global market, creating employment for others (Reddy, 2012).

Figure 3: Time taken by women to start their business in Nepal

Source: Adapted from The World Bank, 2020

The above two figure 3 is the comparison of days taken by Nepal to start a business concerning the countries of South Asia. The graph shows females' time taken (in days) to start a business in the South Asian region. It also compares this to the world average. According to the graph, Nepal takes almost 23 days to start a business, which is less than the number of days shown as the average of low-income countries and the world average. Still, it is a more significant number of days than the average of South Asia (15 days).

Women's participation in the industry is now mainly affected by various factors categorized as personal and contextual driving forces for women entrepreneurs. First, with the evolving family dynamics, the individual elements are that women consider themselves significant participants in caring for their families. Second, with increased education and competence, emerging women business leaders have shown to contribute equally to management and strategy as their male counterparts. First, business is gradually becoming gender neutral. Second, technical innovation has created tremendous versatility, allowing women to operate from wherever and at any time as it is convenient to them (Tripathi, 2012). Hence, the subsequent section an overview of how social, cultural norms impacts women entrepreneurship in Nepal.

(See Appendix 14 for the status of women in Nepal in brief).

3.1.2 Impact of Socio-cultural Norms on Women Entrepreneurship in Nepal

More women are playing a role in the entrepreneurial world in recent years, which is traditionally viewed as a male preserve. Across the world, the number of enterprises being run by women is growing exponentially. Nepal is not an exception to this emerging trend. However, embedded structural and socio-cultural constraints pose a challenge to the growth of women entrepreneurs and the stability of the entrepreneurial ecosystem in Nepal (Acharya & Pandey, 2021). Hence, the researcher points some significant impact of socio-cultural norms on women entrepreneurship in Nepal.

3.1.2.1 Low value attached to women's work

Nepalese societal and cultural practices have given low value to women's work. They are frequently not even considered work or worthwhile work - it is only supplementary part-time, ad hoc, and frivolous work. Thus, these prevailing social values, cultures, and perceptions

restrain the growth of women entrepreneurs in Nepalese society (Ranabhat, 1995). Nevertheless, his study shows that most Nepalese Women Entrepreneurs whose family values their work succeeds.

3.1.2.2 Low level of confidence

A low confidence level is one of the most-cited problems among women entrepreneurs as women accept subordinate status. As a result, they lack confidence in their capabilities. Even at home, family members do not have much faith in women's decision-making. Women's lack of self-confidence, willpower, a positive emotional attitude, and an optimistic outlook generates a dread of making errors at work. As a result, family members and society are hesitant to support their business endeavours (Gautam & Singh, 1994).

The study conducted by Ranabhat (1995) concluded that Nepalese women entrepreneurs are more concerned about high work and efficiency. Still, they were weak in self-confidence, persuasion and assertiveness compared to male entrepreneurs. The family also doubt and lose confidence in woman's capability, whether it is related to their mobility outside the home or mortgage as collateral to obtain loans from a bank. Such lack of confidence in women's capabilities is evident in the family circle and the supporting agencies. About 29% of the organisation (involved in the WED Program) mentioned that women entrepreneurs lacked the confidence to carry out entrepreneurial decisions (Hada & Shrestha, 1992).

3.1.2.3 Double Roles and Responsibilities

One of the primary duties of women in Nepal is to look after the children and their family members. There is little time and energy left for business activities. A married woman entrepreneur must strike a perfect balance between domestic and business activities. The women entrepreneur cannot succeed without the support and approval from husband (Pradhan & Shrestha, 2010). Thus, families' occupational backgrounds and education levels significantly influence the growth of women entrepreneurship. Their inability to attend to domestic work, time for children's education, and personal hobbies and entertainment add to their conflicts (Rai, 2010).

3.1.2.4 Lack of access to primary education and necessary training programmes

There is more importance to a male child than a female child in Nepalese society. This entrepreneurial mindset results in a lack of access to primary education and necessary training for women. One of the main objectives of training and education for women is to increase their role and participation in the national economy. It helps them to become an entrepreneur through self-employment. It also leads to creating employment opportunities for others. Some organizations are involved and are working in women entrepreneurship development for the economic upliftment of the country by providing opportunities and promoting women to engage in economic activities. In Nepal, only 57.4 per cent of women are literate; females who have ever attended school are 42.9% (Bajracharya, Maharjan & Parajuli, 2003). Women-owned enterprises are frequently small, and women do not always have easy access to knowledge about technology, training, creative ideas, discounts, alternative markets. Only a tiny percentage of women entrepreneurs use technology, and they are also limited to word processing software on their computers (Singh, 2018).

Training how to run a business independently, e.g., understanding accounts, sales, marketing, requires some educational background as essential for being an entrepreneur. Training, in simple words, is arousing an interest, instilling knowledge, creating awareness, and stimulating her to move forward by implementing awareness development, achievement motivation, management skill development. Entrepreneurship training effectively changes the individual's knowledge, attitude, and skills relevant to the entrepreneurship function (K.C., 2019).

3.1.2.5 Financial Constraints

There is a need to motivate and maximize women's participation in economic activities to improve the country's economy in today's context. Therefore, finance plays as "lifeblood" of every business undertaking, whether large, medium, or small-scale enterprises. Usually, women entrepreneurs face a shortage of finance, like women do not generally have properties in their name to use as collateral securities for obtaining from banks and other financial institutions (Rakhal, 2020). Lack of access to credit has been an important limitation on women's opportunities to establish an enterprise and engage in economic activities. Due to a lack of funds, many women entrepreneurs have been unable to expand their businesses. Also,

married women have no right to ancestral property, and they cannot claim any property from their husbands. This women's property rights system leaves them with no own capital (Sarfaraz, 2016). Therefore, it is crucial to look at the overall status of the food industry of Nepal to meet the research aims and objectives. Therefore, the researcher attempted to cover all aspects of the Nepalese food industry in the following section.

3.2 Overview of the food industry in Nepal

One of life's essential and fundamental parts is food, and one cannot survive without food. Therefore, the food industry is crucial to every nation worldwide. It is one of the 17th national critical sectors of the US economy, public health, food safety, social development, and nutrition. It covers diverse food supply, production, harvesting, processing, packaging, transportation, distribution, consumption, and disposal. The development food industry began in the early 1900s, and the most lucrative areas of the food industry are meat, vegetable and fruit processing, confectionery, dairy, sausages, wine, and bakery (Sadiku et al., 2019).

Today's food industry has become highly diversified, with manufacturing ranging from small, traditional, family-oriented businesses high labour intensive to significant capital intensive and highly mechanized industrial processes. Most food industries depend on agriculture and fishing (Arcari, 2019). According to the UK food standards agency (2015), the food industry is the whole food industry from farming and food production, packaging and distribution to retail and catering. Also, it is the complex network chain between farmers and industries that link to them. The links can be makers of farm equipment and chemicals. These firms provide services to agro businesses like transportation, finance, food marketing, food and fibre processor, wholesalers, retailers, and foodservice establishments (Nesheim, 2015).

Generally, according to Nakat & Bou-Mitri (2020), the food industry includes agriculture, manufacturing, food processing, marketing, wholesale and food distribution, food service, grocer, farmers market, public markets and other retailing, regulation, education, research and development and financial services. Only subsistence farmers and hunter-gatherers are outside of the modern scope of the food industry.

3.2.1 Recent status of the food industry in Nepal

Nepal is a landlocked country known for its natural resources and biodiversity. Hence, Nepal has a vast diversity in its food value plant species (n=790) and forage species (n=577) grown in major three agro-ecological zones: high hill, mid-hill, and Terai. Agriculture contributes a third of the country's GDP and employs about 2/3 of the population, primarily dominated by women. However, Nepal still faces food insecurity by more than half of the people; 52% and 10% of them are severely food insecure (Basnett et al., 2019).

Figure 4: Entrepreneurs engaged in Nepalese food industry

Source: Adapted from CBS, 2021b

Figure 4 demonstrates the recent trend in the Nepalese food industry. The proportion is higher in manufacturing grain mills products, starches, and starch products than in beverages. There are 25,263 entities involved in the food business, with 54.7% contributing to Nepal's GDP (CBS, 2021). However, the recent trend during the Covid-19 on the food industry has a different scenario from author Nakat & Bou-Mitri (2020). According to them, the food industry is on the verge, meaning that this industry was supposed to run on total capacity but due to lack of facilities and relief offered to the sectors of other sectors that are reeling under an unprecedented challenge to manage cash flow and find the market of its products. This industry will fall if there are no innovative measures within a few days. This industry runs only at 30% of its

capacity maximum, but only 20% of these industries are running. Also, due to lockdown, customers' preference has changed like consumers are enjoying delicacies which this industry is not meeting their expectations (Modnath, 2020).

3.2.1.1 Characteristics of Nepalese traditional and indigenous foods (NITFS).

Nepal is rich in culture with thousands of different ethnicities. The cuisine is a manifestation of culture, and in Nepal, a great variety of food is available with varying preparation methods, regional availability, flavour, shelf life and use. Nepalese food is worth praising for its uniqueness, preparation techniques and delicacy. The characteristics of NITFS are non-junk dietary with high fibre foods, nutritional composition, functionality, and unique sensory traits.

Table 2: NITFS prepared in different geographical regions

Source: Adapted from Nepal Food and Beverage, 2020

Table 1 from above depicts various types of food of Nepal according to geographical regions. All the foods have their unique taste and preparing process traditionally. However, adopting new technology shortens the time to prepare food to serve the customers. Therefore, all the food in Nepal has its own story behind it, and food in Nepal is available according to climate change.

3.3 Importance of Women Entrepreneurship in Nepal

According to the World Bank, women's entrepreneurship is a "vital source of economic development for developed countries" according to the World Bank (De Vita, Mari & Poggesi, 2014, p. 451). Women are seen as "central players" in the economic growth of these nations (Kadakol & Appasaba, 2012). Women are motivated to become entrepreneurs in emerging Asian countries to help reduce poverty and overall economic growth (Ikupolati et al., 2017). As a result, extensive research to learn more about entrepreneurial women in developed countries were available in the works of literature (Maden, 2015). In addition, interest in and research into women's entrepreneurship appears to be growing faster in developing countries than in developed countries (Minniti & Naude, 2010). "Gender parity, which is traditionally lower in developing countries than in developed countries, is closely linked to the degree of women's entrepreneurship development" (Ikupolati et al., 2017, p. 31). By comparing data on women in developing countries to data on women in developed countries, they fall behind in areas such as education, market form, employer benefits, employment climate, financial resources, relevant networks, and family responsibilities (Radovic-Markovic & Alechhi, 2018). Adequate resources for women's entrepreneurship aids in women's development and societal change (Maden, 2021).

According to Vinothalakshmi & Ganesan (2013), women's participation in entrepreneurship is considerably lower in developing Asian countries due to the lack of formal education, inadequate training in skills development, intense household responsibilities, and socio-cultural constraints. Furthermore, women's issues and participation in business can vary depending on their land and culture (Kelley et al., 2013). Due to gender issues, women entrepreneurs in both emerging and industrialised economies have difficulty accessing resources (Radovic-Markovic & Alechhi, 2013). According to Sahasranamam & Sud (2016), entrepreneurship is a critical tool for boosting global economic growth and resolving unemployment and a method for dealing with an unstable setting. As a result, it is an essential tool for addressing society's unemployment problem. Promoting entrepreneurship ventures and training people about launching them will help improve human resources and contribute to socio-economic growth. Women entrepreneurs play a critical role in manufacturing and economic development by creating jobs for others, increasing their wealth, and breaking the poverty cycle (Shah & Saurabh, 2015). Women's unemployment is a massive loss of human

capital used for economic and social advancement. According to the literature, entrepreneurs are risk-takers, implementers, and innovators who bring about change in society by developing, exploiting, and exploring business operations (Sharma & Sharma, 2013).

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Women entrepreneurship programmes encourage women development with new skills relating to solutions to other problems in life, as well as non-cognitive skills such as opportunity perception, creativity, strategic thinking, flexibility, decision making, collaboration, and leadership, all of which would help Nepalese women entrepreneurs, whether they wish to or are already entrepreneurs (Sijapati, Bhattarai & Pathak, 2015). Similarly, Singh & Chauhan (2016) cites the importance of women entrepreneurship for the following reasons: creating employment opportunities for self-employed women as well as the other young people they employ; reintegrating alienated and marginalised women into the economic mainstream and giving them a sense of meaning and belonging and assisting in the resolution of specific socio-psychological issues.

Hence, it is very clear from the literature review about women entrepreneurship, the current context of Nepal, its prospect and challenges, and the importance of women entrepreneurship in Nepal. Nepal has many SMEs owned mainly by women, as stated by CBS. These SMEs tend to raise the degree of competition in the market, resulting in more customers in each market (Verheul et al., 2010). As a result of globalisation, women entrepreneurship can promote innovation as it boosts women to find solutions, new ideas and ways of doing things through experience-based learning. Women Entrepreneurship can provide alternative ways of working that generate wealth, transfer technology, and new perspectives in the market (Sadi & Al-Ghazali, 2012). Entrepreneurship can be a basis for new employments, develop women's livelihood, and encourage economic freedom in developing countries like Nepal.

3.4 Role of women entrepreneurship in the food industry in the context of Nepal

Rural women play a significant role in agriculture in developing countries, accounting for 60-80% of food production and selling food products at markets. In Nepal, up to 98% of women are active in the food sector, which is higher than that for men (91%). Therefore, contribution by women is critical in this industry to achieve global food security. However, they generally do not have the same access to land, water, seeds, training, and credit as men. Consequently, in Nepal, women's involvement is more significant in minor and subsistence food production for millet, maize, and soybean crops. At the same time, men are more involved in cash crops and commercial production of crops such as rice.

Moreover, whilst men generally perform heavy physical labour, women are more involved in tedious and time-consuming work such as weeding, harvesting, threshing, and milling. Many studies have shown that improving the status of women by giving them access to resources increases productivity and, therefore, income in the food industry. According to USAID, in 2020, an estimated 10% of Nepali men were employed abroad, leaving more women in charge of the household and farms. This phenomenon, called the "feminization of agriculture," has created challenges and new opportunities for women in rural areas (CABI, 2021). As a result, they further boost the food industry by empowering women in agriculture.

The food industry continues to be a booming sector in Nepal that faces a contradiction between the leaders of the industry and those who make the purchasing decisions. Women account for

most of Nepal's food-purchasing choices and make up almost half the entry-level workforce in the food industry. However, women are not given value across the board above this level. Despite this current state and the unknowns around the barriers to addressing gender inequity, the picture is not all bleaks. There are sections within the food industry that are making great strides in increasing the representation of women. This study needs to continue highlighting the success stories and spreading those practices across the food industry. This study aims to uncover the barriers familiar to many in the industry, if not outside of it. The food industry has an opportunity to lead the next phase of creating gender and racial equity. In taking the lead, the food industry will also benefit economically. A more equitable workplace continues to show itself to meet the triple bottom line of a socially responsible business: good for business, suitable for individuals, and good for the world at large.

3.4.1. Current state of gender diversity in the food industry in Nepal

From Figure 5 below, compared to other significant fields of study, women entrepreneurs' enrolment in the food industry is 10.8%. According to CBS (2021), women entrepreneurs are more involved in manufacturing than other food services with 25.9%. However, inadequate gender-sensitive extension services hamper Nepal's effective delivery of food services compared to men (MoAD, 2020).

Figure 5: Representation of number of food businesses by sex (in percentage)

Source: Adapted from CBS, 2020

Figure 6: Male and female entrepreneurs in different field of the food industry (in percentage)

Source: Adapted from Department of Cooperatives, 2020

From a local perspective, most women entrepreneurs are active in Gandaki than Bagmati. The lowest proportion share from province two falls under rural areas. Most women entrepreneurs in the food industry come from urban areas with access to facilities that enable them to become entrepreneurs (Heard, 2021).

Figure 7: Share of men and women in food development programs at the district level (in percentage)

Source: Adapted from MoAd, 2020

As shown in figure 7, the MoAd (2021), has made efforts in implementing various programmes related to food industries for women entrepreneurs, including indigenous and smallholders, such as contract farming, cultivation in leased land, group farming, off-season (vegetables and crops) production, value-chain management, export marketing through agricultural cooperatives, and improved seed production. Various agriculture development programmes in districts with women's participation. Women's participation is more than 40% in all district-level agriculture development programmes, except in youth-targeted programmes (34.6%) compared to male entrepreneurs. It is also evident from the figure that women in urban areas are more active in these programs.

Many researchers have projected that 90% of 6.8 billion people living in developing countries will reside in towns and cities, which means providing food for this growing population will be more demanding and exacting. It means the demand for food in cities will increase tremendously, replacing food production in rural areas. The rapid rate of urbanisation in developing is due to poverty, food security and malnutrition (Gupta, 2019). Many researchers argue that the advancement of technological and production techniques will neutralise this displaced labour, but this is partly true as technology is not gender neutral. Historically, women in developing societies were principally concerned with food crop production. According to

Kim & Ncube (2019), 70% to 80% of women accounted for food crop production in sub-Saharan Africa.

In contrast, McGuire & Popkins (1990) affirms that women's triple roles as food producers, income earners and home managers make them indispensable in the drive towards food security. Unfortunately, most of these women lack a working environment to operate this function. Multiple conflicts frequently challenge them to carry out these triple roles. These women conflict with time, energy, and resources (McGuire & Popkins, 1990) furthered by institutional and cultural barriers.

Furthermore, lack of infrastructures in various localities and lack of resources like helpful technology forced them to devise means to sustain production and survival, which have implications on their health, output, and national food security (K.C., 2020). According to the Food and Agriculture organisation (2021), women are the vital human resources to this sector. Literature has pointed out the importance of women entrepreneurship in food crop production. According to National Planning Commission (2021), provision of access to subsidised loans and credit for entrepreneurship development or starting a business through self-employment; expansion of labour and time-saving technology for women and ensuring the quality promotion and market access for products produced by women's groups implementing it for fourteenth plan approach (2019-2021). About 88.6% of women are active labour in the food crop sector, producing 90% of total production (Subba et al., 2019). Quisumbing, Haddad & Pena (2001) affirms that women entrepreneurs in food crop production form an essential distribution link in ensuring food security in big cities and towns. This data demonstrates that women entrepreneurship in the food industry is vital for economic growth and food security. Thus, it is essential to examine the status of these women and the circumstance they operate to increase the result they have achieved so far.

According to Dwibedi (2017), women are not staying inside the four walls and doing household chores; they are now taking various entrepreneurial challenges and are taking multiple careers to earn income. Since women have been engaged in food processing for probably a century now, almost all women have their skills and knowledge about food, executing it in productive ways to generate more income. Though the food industry is very vague, women can succeed in this industry whether attached with home or not (Raynolds, 2012).

Also, recognition to all women entrepreneurs in the food industry by mass even in developing countries. Therefore, this study can be of great significance to home science. Home science today aims to the overall development of women. Since time immemorial, the homemaker's tag for women was evident, highlighting why entrepreneurs get into the food business. Whether educated or not, the food industry can be easy for women entrepreneurs. They can be independent and implement their decision-making skills in this business (Acharya, 2007). Therefore, women entrepreneurs in the food industry play a significant role in employing many other women. From the literature, the food industry can provide a massive opportunity for all women entrepreneurs to explore, exploit and bring new innovative ideas to generate income and gain success in terms of career.

3.5 Empirical studies on Women Entrepreneurship in Nepal

Women entrepreneurs are critical for a country's development, especially for developing countries like Nepal, which has extensive poverty, inadequate resources, a local and dispersed sector, and a complex topography (Bajracharya, 2007). To start a new business and be competitive in Nepal, an entrepreneur must play multiple roles, including innovator, investor, manager, leader, and promoter (KC, 2004). Entrepreneurs in Nepal are also honoured for their contributions to creating jobs and human capital growth (KC, 2004). Nevertheless, Nepalese entrepreneurs faced a variety of challenges in 1992 due to inconsistencies in government rules and regulations over international trade with India and due to the lack of cooperation between government ministries and offices for licenses, taxes, and loans, as well as bribery and corruption among government officials (Zivetz, 1992).

Nepalese entrepreneurs faced challenges like political unrest, a lack of stable government policy, pervasive corruption, and a lack of financial support, and so on (Karki, 2010). In addition, they have faced challenges due to a lack of training, education, a low rate of return on industrial investment, a lack of sufficient investor protection, a lack of confidence, and banks' and financial institutions' restrictive lending policies, political and labour instability, as well as an unreliable workforce and a shortage of skilled labour, trigger frequent job interruptions in Nepalese businesses (Aparicio & Muzzini, 2012). Furthermore, according to Khare & Gautam (2014), a lack of resources, regulation, a shortage of competent human resources, and a lack of awareness limits entrepreneurship in Nepal (Dana, 2014).

The study by IEDI (2013) on "Women entrepreneurship development programmes (WED) and services in Nepal" in Kathmandu was to prepare an inventory of the organisation involved in women entrepreneurship development program and find out the women-specific consideration in WED programmes and services and assess WED programmes provided by those organisations. This study was on training business (awareness, start-up management and skill) and also covered areas like credit linkage to market, link to credit counselling business, education, policy intervention, technical support information seminar/workshop/trade fair, exhibition, interaction program microfinance program, social mobilisation secretarial training programmes and resource management are the program and services provided by the organisation involved on WED. Regarding the content/subject of the training program, most of the respondents expressed that the content of the training programmes was on the demand and nature of the training they conduct. Training for 261360 women in different training programmes to uplift the poor women and make them independent to minimise poverty and gender equality and make them capable of managing a business are the main reasons behind continuing the WED program.

From the study by Ranabhat et al. (2010) on microfinance. How do we enhance the entrepreneurial skills of MFI clients? This presentation is about the relationship between entrepreneurship developments and microfinance or, more precisely, how Nepal can improve the entrepreneurial skills of prospective clients of MFIs. The training intervention was on two distinct methodologies for entrepreneurship development. Are micro-entrepreneurs maximising profits with the finance available to them, or can basic entrepreneurship training improve managerial decisions and gain? The study showed that credit alone does not help the individual overcome poverty. An increasing number of financial institutions cannot meet the demand for credit among small businesses because many small entrepreneurs find it challenging to apply for a loan successfully. The difficulty of identifying business ideas, market niches, and investments with perspectives in the small-scale business sector makes many borrowers find it challenging to utilise credit profitably, repay it timely, and become a steady and reliable client. He concludes that there is evidence that the enhancement of entrepreneurship increases the benefit of borrowers and provides advantages to financial institutions. Therefore, a financial institution should openly acknowledge investments entrepreneurship training as an asset of their client. In this case, many small-scale businesspeople will be interested in contributing to the costs and making such a programme sustainable.

However, MEDEP (2010) has prepared a report "On Economic Empowerment of Women". This study attempts to analyse economic and social empowerment in the family and society after micro-enterprises. In Nepal, women are generally poor regarding income, asset holding and access to essential social services. Gender disparities in human development, especially literacy, school enrolment and life expectancy, are significant problems. Gender discrimination and social exclusion remain serious in Nepal. However, since the last two decades, social development indicators in both women and men have been observed. The main objectives of this study were (i) to examine the effectiveness of micro-enterprises in creating employment among women, (ii) to assess the magnitude of involvement of women in micro-enterprises and (iii) to explore the level of economic empowerment of women before and after the involvement in micro-enterprises. It is an impact study of micro-enterprises in the Nuwakot District. Based on the results obtained from 100 sample women entrepreneurs in Nuwakot District, women's socio-economic condition has changed, and women's access to and control over the resources has increased. As a result, the empowerment level in decision making and expenses on their own needs, their children's needs and family improved—however, efforts to empower women through self-reliance, entrepreneurship skills and management awareness training are essential. In Nuwakot, there were 1,143 micro-entrepreneurs, consisting of 667 women in the district. Out of this, 100 women micro-entrepreneurs had a group discussion, and semi-structured questions were asked to the sampled women entrepreneurs on their socio-economic condition, education, access to and control over resources, income sources, decision making power, social network. This study attempted to analyse the level of economic and social empowerment of women in the family and society after undertaking micro-enterprises. Micro-enterprises have been a significant agent in changing women's roles from traditional work to non-traditional work. As a result, the socio-economic condition of women has changed, and women's access to and control over resources has increased.

Similarly, Shrestha (2007), in his thesis "Entrepreneurship development in Nepal", has stated that there was more significant growth of business run by women entrepreneurs than men. The study also found that most entrepreneurs (56%) had received some training. In his case study, he presented that willingness to do something, demonstration effect, availability of free time, and business background were factors leading to entrepreneurship. He further concluded that successful entrepreneurs did not have a stereotypical profile. People of every age, sex and race had created a successful business. They also were originated from different backgrounds.

According to the finding, the entrepreneurs hailed from a business family with education, some work experience and inborn talent, new ideas, and unexploited (but existing) ideas. Khanka (1998) also has broadly classified barriers into economic and non-economic factors. Economic factors include financial capital, labour, raw materials, and the market, whereas non-economic factors may include the legitimacy of entrepreneurship, mobility, socio-cultural values. However, the economic factors are prerequisites for the start-up of any enterprising activities, for their continuation and expansion. Easy access to the institutional source for credit is a primary hurdle for ambitious activities, particularly in rural areas of Nepal. In the absence of an institutional credit facility, the recognition from informal sources is often not competitive due to a higher interest rate, which results in a low saving pattern. It is applicable more in females than males in rural Nepal (Dhakal, 2006).

If an enterprising activity is contingent upon far-fetched raw materials and the market is at a distance for hauling the finished product, it poses significant challenges. Other marketing problems of the products in MEDEP districts are damaged goods due to insufficient packaging, credit sales, lower price (Subedi, 2006). Transportation linkages reduce risks, production costs and improve easy access to markets, business ideas, knowledge, and capital (McGowan et al., 2012). However, the prevailing social values, culture, and perception have become a restraint to the growth of women entrepreneurs in society (Ranabhat, 1995). Restriction in decision making and mobility in Nepal has adversely affected entrepreneurial ability. Shrestha (2001) pointed out the need for entrepreneurs to mobilise resources in the country and develop skills, knowledge, and vision through the country's formal and semi-formal education system. He suggested that the development of a nation depends on developing the capacity of promotional institutions, which implement the policy and programmes. In his opinion, the entrepreneurs should help themselves devise and run the mechanism for resource mobilisation for their mutual benefit rather than expecting support from the usually inefficient and distorted resource supply system.

In contrast, Bista & Shrestha (2000) found the opportunities and challenges for entrepreneurs and the development of small and medium enterprises in Nepal. The options are for the private sector to play a leading role in economic growth in Nepal. The challenges are dealing with the present stage of Nepalese market opportunities, availability and quality of human and natural resources, and a set of institutional reforms. Apart from suitable macroeconomic measures and facilitation in creating a conducive industrial and business environment by the government, the

paper stressed, it must take the lead in human resource development and updating, leading to overall competence enhancement with the active participation by the private sector.

Nonetheless, Adhikari (2011), cited in Shrestha (2007), observed women entrepreneurship in Nepal's small-scale industries. The objectives were to evaluate women's entrepreneur's programmes conducted by WEAN and other Chambers, examine the family support received by women entrepreneurs and social obstacles facing them entering business and industries, and identify need-based programmes for developing women entrepreneurship such as training and marketing. Her findings of women entrepreneurs were that the Newar (ethnic group) is a dominant majority in the community of women entrepreneurs. Most of them hold certificates in vocational courses such as hairdressing, serving, and painting. They also had some job experience before establishing their own business. There were only a few percentages of non-traditional businesswomen, and they jumped into the company because of job dissatisfaction (partiality, inadequate salary, and intellectual frustration). These findings support the view that people from some communities are more entrepreneurial than others. For example, people from the Newar community are more entrepreneurial in Nepal because of their socio-cultural background. The study also indicates that women from this community are in entrepreneurial activities. As noted in the study, training those women received helped them enter entrepreneurship. Before starting their businesses, they also had some job experience, which supports the notion that replacing existing jobs forces people to enter entrepreneurship. The women of Terai were not aware of SBPP training and credit programmes. So, she had strongly suggested women need-based programmes and a separate bank to support women in the Terai. According to Tuladhar (1996), accesses the status - barriers and constraints and opportunities and support mechanism of women entrepreneurship in Nepal. It also highlights the socio-cultural, legal, and educational barriers to women's entrepreneurship in Nepal. In addition, there is a valuable overview of personality traits viz. self-confidence, task-oriented result, risk-taker, and leadership essential for successful entrepreneurship with consideration given to the distinction between female and male entrepreneurs. Her study has also found that lack of access to credit has been an important limitation on women's opportunities to start businesses and engage in economic activities. She also identifies that social barriers, inadequate education, family responsibilities, dependent on guardians, and absence of government protection on women-run enterprises.

Pant (2013) cited the need for massive reform in the policy and the structure to support women entrepreneurship development and other women development-related activities. He has emphasised that SBPP should assist WED programmes by directly supporting them and providing the support to create the intermediary institution or existing institution at the local and national level. He also concludes that SBPP (State Board of Pardon and Parole) should play the leading role in its field. This study focuses on the policy aspect of entrepreneurship development of Nepal.

Similarly, Shah (1991) researched "Need Assessment Report for Women Entrepreneurship in Nepal". She observed no such institutional skills and competence to develop women entrepreneurship in Nepal. The activities undertaken by some agencies were of traditional types like embroidery, dressmaking, and food products. The efforts for developing non-traditional activities to women entrepreneurs' skills or competencies were lagging. She has concluded that no special financial incentives were available to women except for some in the specified rural area. Specific environment and personal constraints prevented the women from flourishing in industry and business. Most of the women are shy and shaky initially because of socio-economic and cultural conditions. She has identified several problems like marketing of products because of low quality, higher cost of production than imported items, lack of experience. So, she felt that the proper identification strategy for selecting women participants for training is necessary. Shakti (1995) later discussed the biographical and psychological profile of Nepali entrepreneurs. Their findings concluded that a typical Nepali entrepreneur was a male from the poor or lower middle class and well educated. Their significant problems were related to finance and government regulation. They had an internal locus of control. They believed in hard work rather than fate or luck. These findings were more related to a personal variable and the problems faced by Nepalese entrepreneurs.

Furthermore, Gaudel (2006) has described those Nepalese entrepreneurs are reluctant about investing their capital in the industrial sector. So, the government should come forward with appropriate policies to attract entrepreneurs and develop the industrial sector to produce essential goods. He made a strong plea to the government to formulate a practical approach to change people's attitudes to be successful entrepreneurs.

Due to industrialisation, globalisation and social legislation, the status of women in Nepal has changed tremendously. With the mounting spread of women empowerment programmes and

awareness, women have shifted from the kitchen to a higher level of professional activity (Kumbhar, 2013). Entrepreneurship has always been a male-dominated phenomenon, but women today have become the most inspirational and memorable entrepreneurs in Nepal due to change in time. Nowadays, women involve themselves in selected professions and engage in engineering, trade, and industry. Women are stepping out to contribute to economic development and promote women entrepreneurship (Das, 2000).

Though women entry has been late in the business scenario due to the orthodox and traditional socio-culture environment, Nepalese society has accepted women entrepreneurship in the last two decades. People in Nepal generally view women as the sole manager of the kitchen, making pickles, papad and masala. They are now the leading indicator of society's stage of development which made the government consider and put the framework to develop the women entrepreneurship of Nepal (Dhakal, 2006). Therefore, many factors such as contextual and personal motivational factors for women entrepreneurs of Nepal. The individual factors can be family structures, whereas the contextual factors are education, training and development programmes, gender equity, and technological advancement (Tripathi, 2012). According to Shakti (1995), women in Nepal are vital and productive contributors to the national economy, but their access to knowledge, skills, resources, opportunities, and power remains low. Also, according to Singh (2021), the study on "Understanding socio-economic challenges faced by Nepalese women" presented that access to finance, poor economic condition and family responsibilities, lack of exposure and conventional orientation, limited mobility push women entrepreneurs to more vulnerable situations. These should be understood well by all relevant parties to ensure fair economic participation of Nepalese women entrepreneurs. To support these findings, "A study on Motivational factors influencing women entrepreneurs in Nepal" by Sharma (2021) revealed that Nepalese women entrepreneurs are highly dominated by male entrepreneurs a case study analysis on Dharan, a city of Nepal with qualitative methods using interviews of 67 women entrepreneurs in the textile industry. The majority of women entrepreneurs face constraints like lack of confidence, knowledge and management skills, lack of risk-taking abilities, legal formalities, and society's attitude toward women. Hence, this study was limited with the data available and studied the pull and push factors affecting women entrepreneurs in Nepal.

Another critical study on women entrepreneurs and opportunities in Nepal by Gaudel (2020) found that despite a lot of entrepreneurship promotional activities, entrepreneurship

development in Nepal is slow due to load shedding, lack of irrigation facilities, shortage and high cost of raw material, lack of transportation facilities, political instability, and industrial unrest and the like. This finding was an excellent tripartite statistical relationship among the number of employments, industries, and total capital investment through the Poisson Regression Model using statistical software XI-stat.

According to CBS (2021b), women own 29.8% of the enterprises in Nepal. Entire enterprises are 247880, and 30 % of the enterprise are now run by women, depicting that Nepal women are coming out from the everyday household chores. The following tables rank the industry according to the engagement of women entrepreneurs.

Table 3: Status of the sector owed by women in Nepal

Industry	Rank
Wholesale & retails	1st
Accommodation and food service	2nd
Agriculture	3rd
Trading	4th

Source: Adapted from CBS, 2021b

From table 2 above, women's participation in these sectors adds economic value to the nation, which can boost the development of Nepal. Moreover, as the sectors increase Nepal's GDP, these sectors are Nepal's most wealth generating indicator.

3.6 Barriers to women entrepreneurs identified from the past studies in the context of Nepal

From the literature review, we can grasp common barriers to all women entrepreneurship in every sector. However, Nepal shares similar culture with India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, and other South Asian countries or even with Africa; it is essential to narrow down the focus to Nepalese women entrepreneurs. Nepal is small and under developing country; there are so many areas where women entrepreneurship can play a vital role. The food industry is one of the primary revenue-generating industries where Nepalese women find it easy to sustain and showcase their skills in production, distribution, catering, logistics, food regulations. This section will review

the literature on all aspects of women entrepreneurship where the most barriers exist. From this available information, hypotheses statements and the research design process to find barriers to successful women entrepreneurship that limits involvement Nepalese women entrepreneurs in the food business are mentioned below:

3.6.1 Lack of easy access to financial resources

Adequate finance or capital is the most vital for all entrepreneurs, and it has been one of the most significant barriers, especially to women entrepreneurs (Coleman, 2002). All entrepreneurs face this barrier, but generally, women tend to find difficulty accessing the fund to start their ventures due to conflict between family and work issues (McClelland, 2004). Women had a more significant restriction in private funding due to interrupted and punctuated work history and low wages (Carter & Kolvareid, 2018). Difficulties in capital access will result in women starting their ventures from their savings and securing fewer individual investments (Chu, Kara & Benzing, 2018). Therefore, women entrepreneurs face these barriers regarding banking lending and private investment of personal savings (Jamali, 2009).

3.6.2 Legal barrier

This barrier is due to the impacted business start-up process for women entrepreneurs, which discourages women entrepreneurship in Nepal for the big time. Due to the unstable legal environment, policy, and institutional support, women entrepreneurs of Nepal must tackle this or overcome this to set up their business (Reeves, 2010). For example, for any business to start, it takes 17 months to finish all the legal procedures, one of the barriers women entrepreneurs faces in Nepal (United Nations Industrial Development Organization [UNIDO], 2011). Furthermore, as world bank reports (2006), though laws may appear gender-neutral, many other legal obstacles resulting from social and religious dogma hinder women entrepreneurs from starting their ventures. For example, a woman needs a male guardian to approve work or travel in terms of the paperwork that inhibits a women entrepreneur or improves their business (Poon et al., 2016). Recently in Nepal, a new law has been passed that states that women up to 40 years of age cannot travel alone for any purpose without the consent of family members, husbands, or government (Sarker & Palit, 2014).

3.6.3 Lack of adequate training & development and access to basic education programmes

It is another barrier women entrepreneurs face, which is necessary to develop their business plans and set up a venture (Sila, 2018). It may be challenging for women entrepreneurs to become successful if they are under skilled and has less knowledge regarding the business they are about to start (Schmidt & Parker, 2003). In the context of Nepal, education is not the choices of women instead constructed significantly by the culture and society of Nepal. Even though women have education and training programmes, they get influenced by others in Nepalese culture. In addition, marriage, family responsibilities, childcare restrict women in the economic sector (Fernandes & Cabral, 2019).

Even though Nepal has achieved gender parity in enrolment rates, girls are more likely to drop out, particularly in upper grades. Rural living, coming from a low-income family, early marriage, gender-based violence, and insufficient learning environments are all issues (Wier & Price, 2019). High school graduates have more opportunities to continue their education or obtain entry-level employment in the formal sector. However, those who do not graduate high school are limited in their choices and opportunities. Alternative learning methods, such as TVET programmes that educate young people for jobs, are few or non-existent. The informal sector, which comes with a higher risk of abuse and exploitation, appears to be the only way to get work. The informal sector employs two-thirds of the 2.64 million females now employed, most between the ages of 15 and 24. Furthermore, more than one-third of the girls in this age range are unemployed or have no education or training, implying a higher risk of exploitation (Paudel. 2021).

3.6.4 Lack of socio-cultural support

Culture is the combination of norms, values, beliefs and the behavioural manner in a specific society or communities (Sharma et al., 2018). In many countries, especially developing countries like Nepal, it is believed that a woman's primary job is to look after her family and do household chores. For instance, a woman must balance her professional life and personal life in the presence of her husband and other family members (Jayawarna, Ruse & Kitching, 2020).

According to Klyver, Nieslsen & Evald (2019), females are the most humble and modest beings on the planet. Hence, her primary concerns are the responsibilities as wives and mother rather

than a woman entrepreneur. About Nepal, most women in rural areas are still confined to four walls, as mentioned in an earlier section. Her sole responsibilities are childbearing, cooking for family members and doing household chores. The world bank studies reveal that several challenges are associated with culture and lack of support like social limits, gender, discrimination, lack of support from social circles, negative attitudes, and perception from society (Koellinger, Minniti & Schade, 2013). Women must deal with smaller salaries, discrimination, difficulty to advance. It is mainly due to the patriarchal societies and conservative attitudes towards women, the lack of legal mechanisms and institutions to monitor and penalize discrimination. As found in the research, other reasons are related to the family's constitution and the role of each member in it, to school, mass media, civil society, and the political sphere (Rao, 2021).

3.6.5 Work-family interface

As Noor (2019) stated, one of the most significant barriers women entrepreneurs' faces is balancing their professional and personal lives. Women can stabilise their work and personal lives, which results in self-employment to obtain more flexibility and control (Ward, 2017). There is typical stereotyping in terms of gender roles in Nepal. For instance, men are breadwinners, and women are homemakers, meaning gender as a social construct leads to the mother being more responsible towards the family than the father (Vossenber, 2013). Women entrepreneurs of Nepal would accept the international venture, but if their children are underage significantly must drop the globalisation idea and stick with traditional small (Tripathi, 2012). Thus, this barrier holds women entrepreneurs from operating in international and national business markets due to the absence of a strategy to manage family and business lives, lack of family support, and patriarchal society existing in Nepal (K.C. et al., 2011).

3.6.6 Personal constraints

This barrier depends on individual women entrepreneurs —the barrier within women themselves. According to Lakshmi & Vidya (2019), it relates to individuals' locus of control. This somehow is general in the context of Nepal. Some women entertainers who successfully believe in controlling their destiny, known as internal locus of control, whereas some women entrepreneurs are operating but not making news think on other external factors that affect their business, are the external locus of control. According to literature, entrepreneurship defines

entrepreneurs are those who take the risk, creative, innovative, self-confident with what they do. Therefore, entrepreneurs who are afraid to risk are not successful (Mahat, 2018). There are two barriers which are self-confidence and insufficient knowledge about the market. Successful women entrepreneurs have personality traits of being proactive, positivity and enthusiastic. Therefore, most urban women who qualify for these traits and entrepreneurial activities are more exposed to media, extroverts, come out of the shell and become successful.

In contrast, rural Nepalese women are least exposed to globalisation, media, and training, making them small business entrepreneurs. Hence, these factors affect woman entrepreneurship to gain success or not (Manandhar Bajracharya, 2021). Also, studies have pointed to shortages of soft skills, including self-confidence, among female entrepreneurs (Brixiova & Kangoye, 2021).

3.6.7 Other issues

Since the early start of women entrepreneurship, this barrier has been seen to date; mainly, it's a concern for those from the informal sector. There are many murders, rape, harassment, abuses of women entrepreneurs (Malla & Chhetri, 2021). These barriers are not covered by most researchers and is a bit unexplored when it comes to the obstacles of women entrepreneurs. Violence or threats hinder women from setting up their business in high profile areas with loss of security; it brings stress and continuous fear, which also inhibit the working hours of female entrepreneurs. Typically, in the context of Nepal, when a woman is progressing, then men or women start to threaten, harassment and other sorts of extortion are faced by women entrepreneurs. Women entrepreneurs need extra security and support from government laws that discourage women from going big and becoming successful in Nepal (Yadav, Sarangdevot & Sharma, 2019).

To sum up, these are the most common barriers faced by women entrepreneurs in Nepal. Data will be collected based on these identified barriers and test the hypotheses outlined. These barriers can or not apply to the sample of women entrepreneurs the research tends to collect data from. But will conclude at the very end of the chapter, whether these barriers exist in the context of Nepal.

3.7 Summary on the identified barriers to women entrepreneurs in the context of Nepal

From the chapter 2 literature review, it is evident that barriers to successful women entrepreneurs they face in Nepal and comparison to global perspective has a distinct difference. Though many generally barriers are like the context of Nepalese society, but some barriers are much significant and have impacted the way women do business in the Nepalese business industry. Some barriers have a significant impact on women entrepreneurs in other countries but not in the context of Nepal, but some barriers which are foremost in global perspective does not affect successful women entrepreneurs of Nepal. Therefore, the table below represents some barriers in context of Nepal, which will aid the researcher in designing a conceptual framework in Nepal.

Table 4: Barriers identified faced by women entrepreneurs in context of Nepal

Barriers Found in Nepal
Lack of social cultural support
Lack of education
Lack of business development training
Stereotyping on gender roles
Lack of finance
Lack of legal structure to support women business
Family interest conflict
Lack of security
Abuse and harassment to women entrepreneurs

Source: Researcher's own work

3.8 Conceptual framework

In the literature reviews, chapters two and three and ongoing research, the author has set out the most significant barriers to women's entrepreneurship in the food industry in Nepal. The aim is to provide these barriers and produce recommendations that may assist in overcoming these barriers. It gives other researchers insight, especially in the context of Nepal and other

developing countries. The author has drawn a conceptual framework which is a roadmap to the researcher to analyse the data gained from interviews and questionnaires.

Figure 8: Conceptual Framework of the thesis

Source: Researcher’s own work

The figure 12, the independent variable here is lack of adequate training and development and access to primary education, legal constraints, lack of easy access to financial resources, lack of socio-cultural support and the work-family interface. This conceptual framework provides and illustrates the obstacles/barriers Nepalese women entrepreneurs face in the food industry.

3.9 Summary of the chapter

Women's entrepreneurship is critical for a country's economic growth in developed countries (De Vita et al., 2014). However, due to a shortage of funds, education, training, and social, cultural, and religious constraints, female entrepreneurs face more obstacles than men (Kandalkar, 2020). Most of the studies found that lack of easy access to financial resources, adequate training and development programme to women entrepreneurship, gender inequality, cultural barriers, and access to the primary education system is the most significant barriers to women entrepreneurship. According to Bushell (2008), women have been given little attention as entrepreneurs in Nepal and need further study. Poverty, gender inequality, patriarchal norms,

social taboos, deeply rooted stereotypes, and cultural restrictions have impeded Nepalese women from becoming successful entrepreneurs. As a result, this study is to learn more about the barriers faced by Nepalese female entrepreneurs.

Secondly, the author feels that the other sphere of barriers like mentoring, skilling, mental and physical health, and childcare issues are not discussed or researched. Also, due to globalisation and the advancement of technology, developing countries and developed countries still face problems related to women entrepreneurship. The literature has talked a lot about gender roles. However, men, also known as breadwinners from the literature above, have more burdens than women. Hence, this concept still exists in the modern world, indirectly affecting women's entrepreneurship. For instance, most women in the world are earning or involved in some economic activities. Still, this breadwinner concept has somehow relaxed women's inability to take responsibilities and prevented them from creating something independently. Women being privileged these days should also be covered, which is somehow the barrier of women entrepreneurship. Also, literature has demonstrated how cultural barriers affect women entrepreneurship but somehow ignored the ill-practise or astrological part, which is also a barrier to women entrepreneurship, especially in Nepal. The literature review has shown the characteristics of women entrepreneurs, motivation factors for women entrepreneurs, the intricacies of women entrepreneurs, and the study made so far available in the context of Nepal.

Thus, in this chapter, the author has reviewed the literature review on barriers to successful women entrepreneurship of Nepal in the food industry. An overview of all concepts related to this topic and the researchers have attempted to explore institutional theory to understand the barriers of women entrepreneurship in the context of Nepal. Therefore, the following chapter will discuss how data will be collected and analysed.

What emerges from these extensive studies on women entrepreneurship, the constraints, challenges, or barriers they face in any industry they choose to operate, which are of different dimensions and magnitude, prevent them from realising their full potentials (Ikupolati et al., 2017). This chapter describes the research methodology and introduces the research design used to identify barriers to women's entrepreneurship in Nepal. Therefore, with the thorough study on research methodology for business management, the researcher will answer the research questions constructed in section 1.6 to validate these findings from the literature

review on women entrepreneurship. Furthermore, to validate and test the theories from the literature review, the researcher has constructed some research hypotheses, which is explained in section 4.14.2 and developed a conceptual framework (Figure 9) in the following chapter.

CHAPTER FOUR: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1 Introduction

The chapter provides the research methodology used to answer the research question and to meet research objectives. This thesis adopts both positivist and interpretive philosophies with a deductive and inductive approach employing mixed methods techniques, i.e., quantitative, and qualitative data, to provide a rich framework for empirical data. This chapter also discusses the research design tools, including survey questionnaires and semi-structured interviews. In addition, this study adopted convenience sampling techniques to study Nepalese women entrepreneurs in the food industry—also explained the used pilot study and its importance.

This chapter also discusses how the data was collected, interpreted, and analysed and summarises the ethical, validity, and generalisation issues this study had to address at each research stage. Finally, this chapter explains why the researcher decided to use specific models and techniques to conclude the study.

4.2 Overview of research methods in business and management

According to Bernard (2011), research methods in business and management helps researchers to be more specific about the research and make sure that the study comes from a good source and collects and analysed appropriately. When conducting business research, the research question and objective must be valid and fair, directly related to the need for information. Hence the research onion in Figure 9 offers a clear and structured approach to identify each choice in selecting the research design for the project. Developing a research design begins with the location of the proposed work within a particular research paradigm (Sreejesh, Mohapatra & Anusree, 2014).

Figure 9: Research Onion Ring

Source: Adapted from Saunders, 2009

4.3 Research Context

Part 1: Theoretical overview of research methods and approach

A significant body of research has emerged over the last twenty years on the growth and development of women entrepreneurs, their contribution to the economy and why supporting them is of any significance and perhaps the argument to determine that as a group, they are an untapped economic resource (Edwards, 2020). Public perception and history would propose that entrepreneurship is naturally the field of businessmen. As in most countries, many businesses mainly are owned by men (Dzisi, 2018). Entrepreneurship has been a critical indicator of global economic growth around the world. As a result, any action that promotes entrepreneurship by encouraging individuals, including women, to start and expand new

companies that can grow into Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) is equally essential for a country's economic growth (Abor & Biekpe, 2020).

In Nepal, women have always accepted society's roles assigned to them. Household roles, caring for the home and relatives, and raising children are where they make the most substantial contributions (Jha & Upadhaya, 2021). Recently, women's entrepreneurship has surged in Nepal, prompting academics and development professionals to pay more attention to the topic. As a result, many international institutions, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), sponsors, national and local governments, and educational institutes have formalised policies, plans, and programmes to grow, promote, and empower women entrepreneurs in Nepal (Minniti, 2010).

Even though the number of resources and programs available in developing countries to promote and encourage female entrepreneurship has increased significantly, women still run fewer companies and big ventures than men. They start a business, expand slowly, and earn lower financial returns (Naser, Mohammed & Nuseibeh, 2019). Furthermore, new companies owned by women have a higher failure rate, and women are less likely to become entrepreneurs (Goby & Erogul, 2017).

As a result, this study will focus on the significant barriers that women entrepreneurs face in Nepal, specifically in the food industry. Furthermore, it aims to include appropriate recommendations for addressing the obstacles to the participation of women in business in Nepal. Therefore, the following sections are the methods and techniques briefly described and discussed adopted by the researcher to achieve the research aims and answer the research questions.

4.4 Research philosophy

It may cover extensive subjects more than a basic methodology, approaches, or design research used to conduct the study. Two contrary thoughts, epistemological and ontological, correlate with research philosophy. Epistemology summarised "what is known to be true" whereas ontology sums up "what is believed to be true". These two theories of research converge into a positivist and interpretative approach (Schadewitz & Jachna, 2007, p.41). Then research philosophy is broadly classified into four groups: Positivism, Interpretivism, Realism and Pragmatism.

4.4.1 Positivism

The positivist theory believes that experience gained by factual observations, measurement, and testing is trustworthy and reliable. It refers to testing hypotheses based on current literature and ideas. In positivism, the researcher uses an objective approach to restrict data collection and interpretation, and the conclusions collected using positivism theory are quantifiable. The positivist theory believes measurable observations and the evidence obtained in this philosophy are for the statistical process of analysis (Ormston et al., 2014).

4.4.2 Interpretivism

On the other hand, Interpretivism is a method of study in which the researcher uses and integrates human interests and values to analyse or test the data gathered to conduct research. The main goal of interpretive philosophy is to combine human interests, values, attitudes, and behaviours in conjunction with the research questions to produce viable results at the end of the analysis (Bryman & Bell, 2015).

4.4.3 Realism

According to Galloway (2013), realism emerged because of previous discourse in the last decade about positivist philosophy, which believes that there was little space for choice about the fundamental laws of the universe that constructivism and was considered contradictory positivist philosophy. The realism philosophy considers that knowledge arising from human reality is an outcome of social situations within the framework of existing systems that coexist outside human consciousness.

4.4.4 Pragmatism

According to Fetters, Curry & Creswell (2013), the pragmatic approach incorporates both interpretivism and positivist philosophies into a single piece of study to derive more detailed conclusions about the characteristics and aspects of both methods. The research questions

consider both the subjective and objective aspects of the study. According to Robson and McCartan (2016), the researcher has the liberty to use any of the methods, procedures, or techniques to conduct research and gather data; however, the researcher may still use all approaches depending on the complexity and quality of the research questions.

4.5 Research approach

According to Smith (2015), two approaches to conduct the research are inductive and deductive. Since it is clear from the previous section that the researcher is going for mixed methods for data collection, the researcher used both inductive and deductive approaches.

4.5.1 Inductive Approach

According to Bryman (2015), inductive research, also known as inductive reasoning, is a collection of theories and observations developed and introduced through careful study and critical description of evidence relevant to a specific piece of research. The primary goal of inductive research is to understand the data collected by the researcher by various interpretations that adopt a consistent pattern to construct a theory. In this regard, the inductive approach is the bottom-up method, in which the researcher uses a process of developing concepts to explain the study's subject (Gray, 2013).

Furthermore, it is critical to emphasise that the inductive approach allows the researcher to establish the purposes and objectives of the research that will be analysed and examined using existing literature, information, and ideas. The inductive approach is on acquiring new ideas and concepts by research experience. Conclusions are reached by analysing every aspect of the event to build a new theory based on the hypotheses proposed (DePoy & Gitlin, 2015).

4.5.2 Deductive Approach

On the other hand, in the deductive approach, hypothesis statements are formulated at the start of the research study, based on current literature and theories. Then, the research technique is built to test the hypotheses. According to Sekaran (2004), hypothesis statements are made in response to contemporary literature and question previous theories in a generalised pattern in the deductive method. For example, the reasoned approach is used to evaluate the relationship

or impact of two independent variables on one another in a generalised sequence (Cooper & Schindler, 2007).

The deductive approach investigates facts and theories related to the research subject to testing the idea. The reasoned approach follows a distinct trend, beginning with adequate reasoning and clarification of why a given view has been incorporated and concluding with the generation of new hypothesis statements based on a new or specific theory (Gill, 2014). The formulated hypothesis statements are subject to evaluation using various statistical tools and techniques to determine if the hypotheses produced are proven or not.

4.6 Research strategy

According to Bryman & Bell (2007, p698), research strategy is "a general orientation to the conduct of research". Collis & Hussey (2009) define research strategy as the overall course of the research. According to Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill (2009), an optimal research strategy should be chosen depending on the research questions and objectives, the scope of existing knowledge on the subject area to be studied, the amount of time and money available, and the researcher's philosophical underpinnings.

4.6.1 Case study

An in-depth, systematic analysis of an individual or a small group of individuals is case study research. It focuses on the exploration and explanation of a phenomenon. Case study research has limited scope, a high level of detail, and the ability to combine objective and subjective data to obtain a comprehensive understanding (Sage, 2015).

A case study aims to shape a hypothesis for future studies. In social science research and education, case studies investigate psychological issues such as an infant raised by a single deaf parent or the impact on a child isolated, abused, and neglected before twelve. In an educational setting, case studies investigate the progress of writing skills in a select group of high school freshmen taking a creative writing class (Samani, 2004).

4.6.2 Action Research

The concept of action research goes back to the German psychologist Kurt Lewin (1890-1947). Action research is a family of research methodologies that simultaneously pursue action (or

change) and research (or understanding). Thus, an emergent process takes shape as understanding increases; it is an iterative process that converges towards a better understanding of what happens.

Its characteristics is the importance of critical theory, in which transition is the primary topic of research and the researcher is a participant in the process (Koch, 1995). Action research is a forward-looking method with ramifications beyond the primary mission, thus the value of analytic generalisation (McManners, 2015). As a result, the approach is more suited to methodology development or theory building than hypothesis testing (Baskerville & Wood-Harper, 2016).

4.6.3 Grounded theory

Barney Glaser and Anselm Strauss founded the qualitative research approach known as "grounded theory" (Glaser, 1978, 1992; Glaser & Strauss, 1967, 2009; Strauss, 1987). They described the grounded theory as the theory derived from systematically gathered data and analysed during the research process (Clarke, 2014). This approach aims to build a theory on an evidence basis.

4.6.4 Experiment

Experimental Research is a set of methods in which the researcher creates various treatments or conditions and then tests their effects on the participants. Experimental studies are the most definitive of all laboratory designs because of their ability to modify treatment outcomes and control specific extraneous causes (Bider, 2005).

4.7 Research design

Essentially, the research design is the strategy used by researchers to address research questions and accomplish the goals and objectives of their studies. Therefore, any research design should be descriptive, rational, and attainable to solve research problems while eliminating data confusion and complexity. Several research designs are available to perform research in detail, including correlational, descriptive, experimental, and meta-analytical designs (Harrison, 2013).

4.7.1 Explanatory Research

When the study focuses on specific questions aimed at determining "why" questions in the first place, then adopting an explanatory research design is essential. This design is to remember that the data for the study is collected impacts this research design, resulting in differences in generating the best empirical results for the research. Different causal explanations to deduce the answers relating to why doing the research is essential. They often disagree with how various factors are affected by each other (Brigandt, 2016, p.251).

4.7.2 Exploratory Research

Exploratory research is a methodological approach that focuses on developing or discovering new theories. The exploratory research design proposes investigating the research question rather than providing a definitive answer to the current research problem (Saunders et al., 2012). This research design does not offer a solution to a research problem, but it does detail the issue (Brown, 2006).

4.7.3 Descriptive Research

According to Omair (2015), descriptive research design incorporates massive volumes of information about the structure and character of human culture. Mackey & Gass (2015) claim that descriptive design will reduce the need for time-consuming figurative data collection, also known as abstracted empiricism. As a result, not every reasoning question must have valid and absolute evidence, and there are various examples of unfinished surveys and cases that provide little knowledge about trivial descriptions.

4.8 Research methods

It is the procedure that the researchers intend to follow to meet their research goals and address their research questions. It serves as the basis for a series of well-thought-out decisions researchers make to complete the thesis. As a result, it can identify a range of critical aspects that researchers must recognise to move forward with their Study or Research, such as the

overall research approach, data collection methods, and data analysis techniques (Collis & Hussey, 2009).

All researchers do not use data collection and interpretation methods in the same way. As a result, this chapter will explain why the researcher has chosen specific approaches or processes for data collection and interpretation. This chapter's strategies and techniques apply to Nepalese female food entrepreneurs.

4.8.1 Qualitative Research Methods

The qualitative research method identifies and perceives, ideas, opinions, and feelings of the participants selected for the Research (Smith, 2015). In other words, this specific research method deals with the rationale of the perception depicted by the real world.

This research method is an inductive approach since it centralises that a new theory or the researcher formulates a concept upon which the entire basis of the research is laid (Myers, 2020).

According to Taylor, Bogdan & Devault (2015), there are five types of qualitative research. These five domains comprise narration, phenomenon-based analysis, using research theories to base the central theme of the research topic on, discussions of case studies, and ethnographic research (Smith, 2015).

4.8.2 Quantitative Research Methods

According to Stokes (2011), the quantitative research method is an attempt to utilise imitation, generalisation of the outcomes of the research study that exclusively attracts the researcher's attention to the prediction of the final verdict of the research study in a sophisticated tabular and statistical format.

According to Cassell, Cunliffe & Grandy (2018), the quantitative research method is a research study that makes use of the deductive style of research to put into action the application of statistical tests with regards to the development of the hypothesis for determining the specific features, factors and characteristics of the research studies by analysing concerning a large group of people.

4.8.3 Mixed Methods

The mixed-method approach is a bridge that fills the research gap in the contrasting theories based on quantitative or qualitative Research (Molina-Azorin, 2016). This research approach also disregards any forms of restrictions and limitations typically associated with a single research method (Hesse-Biber, 2010). Bamberger (2013) proposes a formal definition of the mixed research method, which incorporates both quantitative and qualitative research techniques, depending on the different approaches taken for each methodology.

4.9 Pilot study

According to Pretorius (2008), a pilot study is a small-scale inquiry of the techniques or rehearsal that the research uses before conducting data to a larger population. Here, the researchers have stressed the questionnaire survey and interview with a small sample of the people within the conduct of women entrepreneurs in the food business to test the proposed method's feasibility to study a larger scale. Hence, it plays a crucial role in evaluating the viability of recruitment of refinement of new interventions, evaluations, and other study methods (Bernard, 2011).

It is a tool for gaining a better understanding of the research. The purpose of the pilot study is not to collect research data but to test and verify whether any necessary changes need to be made before the actual data collection. It is also to see if the statistical analysis that was planned works or not. It is possible to fix any issues or mistakes found during the pilot study by altering the data collection method or the statistical computations (Gardner, 2003).

However, the practice of pilot study is not an actual method for investigating any study because it is not broad enough to offer conclusive results (Mulepati, 2012). Nevertheless, the pilot study aimed to test and improve the survey questionnaire and interview guide & questions before completing the primary research. Piloting the surveys and interviews was extremely useful in determining the time needed for interviews. The findings from the pilot study were consistent with the preliminary analysis. The pilot study ascertained that the survey questionnaires and interview schedule was well articulated and would enable the participants to provide

information pertinent to the research questions. However, some minor changes on the questionnaire were not enough to grasp the carriers' barriers of Nepalese women entrepreneurs in the food industry. Also, the researcher later added more questions on the demographic info of the participants to get rich data. Generally, most women do not have any prior training to launch their own business. From age 26-35, women seemed more involved in some business activities. Most of them are married and has children. From the questionnaire, these barriers do affect their career development.

4.10 Data Collection Methods

According to Zikmund (2010), there are two major data collection methods: primary and secondary data collection. Primary data is considered first-hand collection, where the researcher utilises various resources to collect data directly from the participants. In contrast, secondary data collection is where the researcher collects data from previous research.

Primary sources of data collection can be sub-divided into several categories as follows.

4.10.1 Primary Data Collection

The primary data collection methods include focus groups, interviews with participants, and direct observation.

4.10.1.1 Direct Observation

Adams, Khan & Raeside (2014) define direct observation as a systematic approach that involves recording, demonstrating, probing, and interpreting the attitudes and activities personally of the respondents.

4.10.1.2 Conducting Interviews.

According to Yilmaz (2013), conducting interviews collects data from respondents and can be divided into several forms, including structured, semi-structured and non-structured interviews. For example, the researcher conducts semi-structured interviews in qualitative research, not structured interviews. Semi-structured interviews aim to provide an in-depth understanding of the research topic. Structured interviews, however, are typically understood as non-directive interviews (Phellas, Bloch & Seale, 2011).

4.10.1.3 Focus Groups

According to Doody & Noonan (2013), focus groups usually consist of a small number of individuals that range from five to fifteen in number, with a specific theme to communicate with and discuss the research's particular elements.

4.10.2 Secondary Data Collection

According to Nassaji (2015), the secondary data collection method is considered a second-hand data collection method. It includes the collection of data from previously conducted research. By reviewing these previous studies, the researcher can better understand the study topic and check the theories and concepts related to the study variables to carry out the study more appropriately. Secondary data collection sources from journals, articles, magazines, and newspapers should be authentic and reliable. Secondary data collection is collecting facts and figures as secondary content analysis.

4.11 Data analysis

Data analysis is an essential part of the research. According to the research onion model developed by Saunders (2007), research data should be analysed based on the specific research strategy to proceed with accurate and reliable results. The data collected for the current study was on both qualitative and quantitative research design. The researcher employed thematic analysis to analyse data obtained from the qualitative study design, while SPSS analysed quantitative data.

4.12 Sample

According to Gibbs (2007), sampling collects a sample from the entire population. It is difficult to collect data from the whole population due to limited time and budget resources. The sample size influences the reliable and accurate findings from the people. The sample size is determined mainly by time and funding. If the researcher has more time and money, then the scope of the study increases. The sample size depends on the statistical tests intended for the Study (Hair et al., 2005).

4.12.1 Sampling Methods and Techniques

According to Gorny & Napierala (2016), there are two sampling methods: probability and non-probability sampling. In probability sampling, the respondents have an equal chance of selection for the study. However, for the non-probability sampling technique, the respondent does not get a chance of being equally selected.

4.12.1.1 Probability Sampling Techniques

Random sampling, cluster sampling and stratified sampling techniques are varieties of probability sampling techniques described below.

Table 5: Types of probability sampling

Types of Probability sampling techniques	Descriptions
Random Sampling	Random sampling is a type of probability sampling technique in which, according to Acharya et al., (2013), the respondent has an equal chance of being selected.
Systemic Sampling	The systematic sampling technique involves the collection of data from every third and fourth individual within the frame of sampling (Emmel, 2013). The systematic sampling technique is considered more structured and enables the researcher to collect the data within a short time span. This technique also enables the researcher to minimize the error rate.
Stratified Random Sampling	The stratified sampling technique involves the gathering of data by dividing the population into different strata and then collecting the samples from each stratum. When the researcher wants to rank the data then this sampling technique is used (Gorny & Napierala, 2016).
Cluster Sampling	According to Levy & Lemeshow (2013), in this method of sampling, the population is divided into different clusters and each cluster is named as a single unit. For example, students in one class may be considered as part of a single cluster. This approach can be used when time and money resources are limited. In this technique the chance of errors is considered to be high.

4.12.1.2 Non-probability Sampling Techniques

Non-probability sampling can be further sub-divided into quota sampling, convenience sampling and snowball sampling techniques. These techniques are described in more detail below:

Table 6: Types of non-probability sampling

Types of Non- Probability sampling techniques	Descriptions
Convenience Sampling Technique	The convenience sampling technique is one of the easiest approaches used by the researcher. This where the collection of data is based on the feasibility and the accessibility of the researcher. The disadvantage of such a technique is that it is associated with the probability of bias Acharya et al., 2013.
Quota Sampling Technique	According to Gorny & Napierata (2016, p.645), the quota sampling technique is similar to the cluster sampling approach. The only difference between the two types is that the cluster of the population is demonstrated in the same proportion in relation to the entire population.
Snowball Sampling Technique	This particular sampling method is relatively popular among recent research studies in relation to observational research within specific communities (Gornall, 2011). It involves a minimal number of respondents chosen when conducting interviews. The participants then indicate other people with similar characteristics, and they are then interviewed based upon the original interviewees' reference.

4.13 Research problems and hypotheses for this Study

4.13.1 Research problems

A research problem is a specific issue, difficulty, contradiction, or knowledge gap addressed in the research. Practical problems contribute to change or theoretical problems to expand knowledge (Ritchie et al., 2013).

The researcher has found the central research problem from the literature review by different journal articles, books, and media in Nepal. First, there is no research or little research conducted on women entrepreneurship in Nepal. Moreover, since Nepal, a food industry, dominates the market, the statistics available are not up to date. There are many aspects the researcher could conduct. Still, due to lack of time and Covid-19, the researcher could not

research different industries, enabling researchers to understand and compare with those industries.

4.13.2 Research hypotheses

A research hypothesis is a specific, clear, and testable proposition or predictive statement about the possible outcome of a scientific research study based on a particular property of a population, such as presumed differences between groups in a specific variable or relationships between variables. Specifying the research hypotheses is one of the most critical steps in planning a scientific quantitative research study (Ritchie et al., 2013).

Here, **H₀** represents, researcher cannot reject null hypotheses because the pi-value is more than 0.05 whereas,

H₁ represents, researcher can reject null hypotheses accept alternative hypotheses because the pi- value less than 0.05

Hypothesis A:

H₀: *A lack of adequate training & development and access to basic education does not affect the business involvement of women entrepreneurs in Nepal.*

H₁: *Adequate training & development and access to basic education strengthen business involvement by women entrepreneurs in Nepal.*

Hypothesis B:

H₀: *Legal constraints are not the main barrier for Nepalese women entrepreneurs to involve in business.*

H₁: *Legal constraints is the main barrier for Nepalese women entrepreneurs to involve in business.*

Hypothesis C:

H₀: *Lack of socio-cultural support does not hinder women entrepreneurs in business activities in Nepal*

H₁: *Lack of socio-cultural support does affect women entrepreneurs in business activities in Nepal*

Hypothesis D:

H0: Lack of easy access to financial resources obstructs business activities amongst women entrepreneurs in Nepal.

H1: Easy access to financial resources boosts business activities amongst women entrepreneurs in Nepal.

Hypothesis E:

H0: The work-family interface does not affect business activities for women entrepreneurs in Nepal.

H1: The work-family interface affects women entrepreneurs' business activities in Nepal.

4.14 Variables

In research, variables are characteristics that can take on different values, such as height, age, species, or exam score. For example, the variables in a study of a cause-and-effect relationship are called the independent and dependent variables (Thomas, 2021).

4.13.3 Dependent variable

Those variables that independent factor influences are dependent variables. These variables depend on and are the outcome or results of the influence from independent variables. Therefore, these variables receive the intervention (Wilson, 2021).

Women entrepreneurship has increased drastically due to rapid globalisation, affecting the world. However, men still dominate the business market. It was discussed in the literature review that even though women participation in the business world is increasing, there are still gaps that need lights on in many aspects (Robson & McCartan, 2016).

In the context of Nepal, there is a gap where women still face many barriers in the respective industries they choose to operate. Even though government schemes on empowering women have increased significantly in Nepal, they still face repayment of loan barriers. Still, women have equal family responsibilities and many more. Thus, how women entrepreneurs operate in the business environment will be addressed, used as a dependent variable affected by many barriers (Shinnar, Giacomini & Janssen, 2012).

4.13.4 Independent variables

Independent variables are those variables that manipulate or the variables that vary. These variables are also called predictor or treatment variables. These variables are the cause and do not depend on other variables (Thomas, 2021).

From the previous studies from chapter 2 and 3, it is evident that women entrepreneurs face many challenges, barriers, obstacles whilst doing a business. Though there are variations in these factors, they all affect women entrepreneurs in the same way that hinders women career progressions in business, ability, and motivation. Most of the barriers are the same for all women entrepreneurship irrespective of their chosen industry (Karki, 2013). The study conducted by FNCCI (2019) on women entrepreneurship and their challenges revealed that 2631 of the women are engaged in a small industry, and about 54.7% faced financial barriers to setting up their business. Nepalese women entrepreneurs are more exposed to cultural constraints. Many women find it challenging to start their venture due to the culture followed by the family member (Bajracharya, Maharjan & Parajuli, 2003). Another barrier the women entrepreneurs of Nepal in the food industry face are access to financial resources. Though the government has made it easier to access bank loans, micro-financing companies still charge a 2% interest rate. Still, it appears, work is getting more hassle. It means they still suffer from a lack of capital (K.C. et al., 2011). A legal constraint is another barrier found in the literature review. Since Nepal's political system is unstable and frequently changing, especially in the food business, women find it difficult to sustain their business due to legal constraints. The lengthy process of acquiring or setting up their own business has demotivated or stopped women entrepreneurs from progressing (MEDEP, 2010).

Likewise, lack of adequate training and access to the basic education system, the work-family interface, lack of family support, and many more, as discussed above, are emerging and still prevalent in Nepal regarding barriers faced by Nepalese women entrepreneurship in the food industry. Therefore, the researcher has decided to study the five most significant obstacles women entrepreneurs face in Nepal's food industry in this study. Moreover, the researcher has tried to add value by focusing on some barriers ignored in previous studies, focusing solely on using barriers that women entrepreneurs face in the Nepalese food industry as the independent variables.

Part 2: Mixed Method Designing Process

This study adopted mixed methods for data collection. Hence, the advantages of each method, i.e., quantitative data and qualitative data, were equally applied to get reliable data. The research findings from this study address the issues that women entrepreneurs face whilst doing business in Nepal. Hence, the researcher has adopted various approaches and techniques for collection and data analysis to conduct this research. This section describes the data collection and analysis process, and Table 7 presents a presentation below to illustrate the research methodology and strategies used to achieve this research and meet the aims and objectives.

Table 7: Research methodology and strategies used for the study.

Research Philosophy	Pragmatism
Research Approach	Deductive and Inductive
Research strategy	Case study and Action Research
Research design	Exploratory research
Research methods	Mixed methods i.e., Quantitative and Qualitative
Data sources	Primary and secondary data
Sampling Techniques	Non-Probability, Convenience sampling
Data collection tools for primary data	Questionnaire survey and interview
Data collection tools for secondary data	Online, journal, books, organization (WEAN, FWEAN, FNCCI, etc)
Data analysis for questionnaire and interview	SPSS and thematic analysis respectively

Source: Researcher's own work

4.14 Data collection and analysis process

4.1.4.1 Stage 1: Getting started

The initial stage in conducting this study was to determine the research's aim and focus. This stage entails a thorough review of the literature, previous studies, discussions with academics and practitioners, and determining the researcher's motivation. Then, to offer a clear picture for this research, the researcher designed research questions with broad perspective inferences based on the research aim and objectives.

As a result, all relevant data on women entrepreneurship, barriers to women entrepreneurship, the food industry of Nepal, and women entrepreneurship in the global and Nepal's context was exhausted in terms of gender, human rights, social, and financial perspectives to identify essential themes to help shape the initial research design. The conceptual framework on barriers to women's entrepreneurship in Nepal was then constructed based on the literature study and previous studies. The conceptual framework comprised dependent and independent variables that served as a road map for conducting the study, and the researchers' developed hypotheses based on the research's issues and problems. The researcher then developed null hypotheses based on the problem and alternate hypotheses based on the tentative answer.

4.14.2 Stage 2: Selection and recruitment process of participants and interviews

This study used convenience sampling method which is a type of non-probability sampling techniques because convenience sampling enabled rapid recruitment of readily available participants online to the researcher. Also, due to the Covid-19 pandemic and travel ban, the access to reach participants was challenging. Hence, the selection was based on the availability of the population. It aided the researcher to collect data within the time constraint and allowed to generate more sample with no investments. Furthermore, the researcher used these techniques to meet the target responses and collect crucial data on women entrepreneurs.

Hence, the researcher initiated by approaching organisations from a population of business support organisations in Nepal. Then the researcher selected the organisations as these organisations provided specialist support to women entrepreneurs. FNCCI website provided a list of 56 organisations that support women entrepreneurs in Nepal. This study focuses on

barriers of women entrepreneurs and validates it with the business organisation that support women entrepreneurs as this would allow for comparison with existing literature on mainstream institutional support. The researcher received an overall population of 245 from FWEAN. Using a scientific calculator with a 5% margin of error, the researcher came up with 150 participants for the survey and achieved a total of 140 responses out of 150. These responses were collected based on the researcher's continuous reminder message, and it approximately took three months to receive this response. Moreover, the researcher selected further 12 participants for interviews and then contacted them as they were renowned women entrepreneurs and business organisations supporting women entrepreneurship in Nepal.

4.14.3 Stage 3: Analysis for relevant stakeholders

During the literature review, most research only presented a single stakeholder group (for instance, Mole et al., 2008; 2011; Kim, 2014). Therefore, a stakeholder analysis aids the researcher to understand the people and processes to be surveyed and interviewed. A stakeholder is a person or organisation who stands to benefit or lose because of a project, programme, or process's outcomes (Hovland, 2005). Hence, identifying the stakeholders early in the research process is critical. In stakeholder analysis, the researcher identifies each stakeholder, explains their wishes and requirements following the research, and determines their level of interest in and influence over research results; in this case, the primary stakeholder was women entrepreneurs, selected for in-depth surveys and interviews. Also, to determine what mechanisms exist in Nepal to promote women's education, business organisations, both NGOs and government-funded organisations, were interviewed to confirm the findings. Following the stakeholder analysis, prospective participants were selected based on their knowledge of the topics and attempts to gain access. The researcher contacted all participants via social media and emails for this study. In parallel, the researcher applied to the University of the West of Scotland's ethical committee for ethics permission for the research. After prompt approval, the researcher verified and negotiated access to business support organisations and women entrepreneurs and a research plan with the gatekeepers.

4.14.4 Stage 3: Ethical consideration

Many significant ethical problems arise while collecting data in a natural setting (Lambert et al., 2011). Two such issues (Oliver, 2010) are the cementing of connections and establishing trust. Research on women entrepreneurs in various contexts was complex in this study since non-consenting research was not allowed. The researcher presented her findings and briefed the participants as needed to address this issue. The study fully adhered to the Ethical Guidelines of the University of the West of Scotland (UWS). Before starting the data collection, the researcher sought UWS ethical permission. Then the researcher gave confidentiality notification, information on the study and the researcher's contact to all the participants. The researcher also informed participants to ask questions about the study or discuss the research process.

Furthermore, the researcher briefed the participants about voluntary entry and exit from the survey or during an interview without consequence. Likewise, the researcher assured their identity protection during the research. Any references, information, or replies provided by participants will be treated with confidentiality and encrypted in the university's one drive. Then the researcher assured that statements in the oral or written section of the study would be anonymised and secure any personal information. During the data collection stage, the emphasis on ethics was essential since it allowed participants to express their thoughts without fear of being judged openly. As a result of these factors, the researcher gathered high-quality data following the research procedure.

4.14.5 Stage 4: Gaining access to participants

Obtaining access to the participants is critical for all types of study. The type and quality of data gathered is determined by the researcher's ability to gain access to participants (Shenton & Hayter, 2004). FWEAN granted access for the researcher were identified based on the stakeholder analysis of the participating organisations. To get access to participants, the researcher used several methods. The researcher likewise followed a progressive approach to the groups. The researcher did this through attending networking events, public seminars, and conferences hosted by the women entrepreneur's business development organisation of Nepal which was conducted virtually via zoom. There were both mixed and women-only based events. It ensured that women entrepreneurs were immediately approached and asked to discuss the proposed research. The researcher also gave possible informants information about the

research at the events. The researcher also accepted an offer to attend meetings related to the topic. Participants were emailed a Participant Information Sheet and a Consent Form after contacting these virtual meetings. Participants signed the consent form to confirm their participation. After receiving their consent, the author approached FWEAN and women entrepreneurs to find more possible participants who might contribute information to the study. After this, the researcher selected 150 participants on a convenience basis for a survey and 8 participants for the interview who were prominent women entrepreneurs in their field and four experts from a business development organisation who knows best about the women entrepreneurship status of Nepal.

4.14.6 Stage 4: Data collection tools

The researcher has adopted both open and close-ended questionnaires for this study to collect data. For quantitative data, the researcher used a survey questionnaire, and then interviews were conducted online with the help of zoom. The following sections provide a detailed description of how data was collected.

4.14.6.1 Questionnaires

This research adopted a self-administered questionnaire regarding research questions and objectives in context to the literature reviews and careful consideration of the barriers faced by women entrepreneurship in the food industry of Nepal. The questionnaire was developed in the Nepali language as most women entrepreneurs do not understand English. This method has two sections, the first is general demographic information, whilst the second section aims at collecting data regarding the variables used in the research. The questions used were closed questions used to validate the variables identified and hypotheses formulated.

There are typically three types of response formats open-ended, closed-ended or a combination of both (McClelland, 1994). The questionnaire response used in this research is the closed-ended Likert scale format. The questionnaire level of measurement used for this research was an ordinal scale. Therefore, the participants had to choose from strongly disagree to agree strongly based on their agreement. Since this research has two way forced choice, researchers can grasp how variables affect the independent variable presented in the conceptual framework. The questions were framed based on the theoretical reviews and previous studies available so far and strictly keeping in mind the objectives of the research study. The questionnaire consists

of various information about barriers faced by women entrepreneurs of Nepal. Google Forms aided the researcher to conduct the survey questionnaire. The link was distributed to all participants using this link.

4.14.6.2 Interviews

Some questions require further examination, but some answers were crested other questions for the researcher. That is why the researcher decided to do an interview. As mentioned above, qualitative research methods in this study help researchers focus and understand the women entrepreneurs' experiences, perspectives, and thoughts. Hence, this method helps to explore the meaning, purpose, and reality (Phellas, Bloch & Seale, 2011).

Therefore, interviews are to offer further understandings and triangulation of the findings. Quality is essential for the effectiveness of interviews, and flawed interview process and analysis of the consultation results in preliminary data findings. Nonetheless, according to Doody & Noonan (2013), qualitative researchers tend to use intuition for making inferences, empathy, perceptiveness, and creativity. Englander (2012) stated that this is the technique to find information from a study sample from participants' expertise. There is no perfect way of documenting an interview or ensuring a set for an ideal interview. Still, the only thing in the study that the researcher can do is elicit a description given by the participant's experience as clear and complete as possible. The researcher can conduct and get good information for data collection and analysis by doing this. All interviews provide richer results because of nuance, depth, and accuracy from the participant's mouth.

Especially during the Covid-19 pandemic, the researcher benefited greatly from online interviews. Before running the meeting, the researcher did a pre-meeting virtually to discuss the trust issues regarding confidentiality and other ethics forms. By doing this, the researcher collected additional data without excess further questions (Marshall et al., 2013). In addition, it allowed the interviewee time for further reflection, which may prove a boon as self-interpretation and some recommended needs for the researcher to conduct other interviews with other women entrepreneurs ((Dayan & Yuksel-Kaptanoglu, 2021)). Any discussion aims to uncover the psychological reasoning provided by the interviewee's self-interpretations.

Thus, the researcher took the interviews via Zoom, an online platform, to gather the data from the Nepalese women entrepreneurship to understand the women entrepreneurship of Nepal in the food industry and identify the barriers faced by these successful women entrepreneurs. In this case, quantitative data alone was inadequate to understand the women entrepreneurship barriers in context to Nepal in the food industry. Hence, semi-structured interviews were vital to getting more descriptive and precise information about further additional barriers, which and literature reviews did not cover the topic. Therefore, it was essential for the researchers to reveal the thoughts, attitudes, and experiences of the obstacles these successful women entrepreneurs in the food industry of Nepal. The questions constructed was according to the understanding level of the women entrepreneurs of Nepal. Many of the participants did understand English, but few of them needed translation into the Nepali language. Therefore, the questions were for the interview were few, open-ended and semi-structured to allow the interviewee to consider and give them time to respond, designed for the participants to answer qualitatively. The main aim of the questions was to get as much information as possible and let the participants express their thoughts on barriers to women entrepreneurship in the food industry of Nepal. All the interviews were from Nepal, Kathmandu, an epicentre of women-oriented businesses.

4.14.6.3 Secondary data

Documents are secondary data sources. This study's secondary data comprises journals, books, customer or investor surveys, newspaper articles, websites, corporate videos, published teaching case studies, practitioner reports, leaflets, brochures, in-house newsletters, and annual financial reports. The tertiary data sources are mainly online databases, indexes and bibliographies designed to help access primary and secondary data (Saunders et al., 2009). The documents primarily collected for this study were official documents, including company newsletters, email communications, a few official documents, and training materials.

4.14.7 Stage 5: Data collection process

Since this is a mixed-method study, the hypothesis and the literature conclusion cover all aspects of Nepal and further develop robust questions from the literature review. The researcher conducted the pilot study before doing a broad survey and interview.

This pilot study aims not to answer questions but to see the questions coverage, reliability, validity of the questions, or whether the questions cover all the issues. The researcher designed a draft questionnaire based on the conceptual framework and the objectives of this study. And then conducted a pilot study and distributed the draft survey questionnaire to senior colleagues. Thus, the pilot study enabled the researcher to shape the extensive survey questions further, remove the unclear, irrelevant, and unnecessary words, and avoid duplication. The researcher used responses to examine and scrutinise the questionnaire. The respondents suggested adding additional questions. One of the entrepreneurs even pointed that the researcher is immature and unprofessionally. Hence, the researcher shaped how to approach these target samples to conduct this study. The researcher prepared all the documents required before conducting this survey and interviews. However, three women entrepreneurs said that the questionnaire was short and too general. Hence, the researcher had to shape all the questionnaires and make them more fun and long so that the participants do not feel bored and at the same time provide some rich data. All the respondents' feedback was applied to conduct a more extensive survey and interview.

On completion of the pilot study, the researcher incorporated beneficial suggestions from the respondents; therefore, the researcher undertook an extensive survey after this step. Then open-ended semi-structured interview questions were designed after survey questions. The researcher designed interview questions so that all aspects were covered where the survey questionnaire was lacking. An interview schedule is a simple guide/listing of general areas to cover with each informant (Taylor and Bogdan, 1984). It guides the researcher on phrasing the questions and when to ask them during the interview situation. This schedule was also piloted and amended during the pilot study. The interview schedule contained open-ended questions that pertained to the research questions (see Appendix E). The open-ended questions approach enables individuals to express their personal experiences (Creswell, 2003). The researcher designed two interview schedules for two different stakeholder groups—the interview schedule for women entrepreneurs comprised five sections. A copy of the 8-interview schedule (women entrepreneurs) used in the data collection are in Appendix E. The first part of the schedule (Section A and B) consisted of demographic questions, both personal and business. The second section consisted of questions examining the barriers women entrepreneurs face in Nepal. The interview guide (Appendix F) for participants of business support organisations consisted of sections about their background (position and firm). In the final phase of the interview (both groups), the researcher asked the participants whether there was anything else they wanted to

add. It should reveal any aspect of their experiences on barriers that had not been covered in the survey questionnaire/or discuss any further clarification they would like to discuss. Finally, the researcher asked the participants to recommend how to contribute and boost women entrepreneurship in the context of Nepal.

4.14.8 Stage 6: Data Analysis

The data analysis where an extensive questionnaire through sample population is collected and analysed using statistical tools. Despite the concerns mentioned above about using electronic survey techniques, this analysis used the Google form website to distribute the questionnaire electronically. Following the return and storage of the data, the researcher then transferred to the SPSS package for statistical tests and analysis techniques (Phellas, Bloch & Seale, 2011). Then researcher calculated mean and standard deviation values used to determine whether respondents agree on all the barriers Nepalese women entrepreneurs face in the food industry. After this, the researcher used Cronbach's Alpha to evaluate the data collection techniques' reliability and internal consistency; basically, an internal consistency coefficient was used to measure an analysis test's reliability for a study sample and achieved 0.83. Then Pearson correlation was carried out to determine the degree of correlation between independent variables and eliminate multicollinearity. Also, the researcher performed regression analysis to determine the degree to which independent variables influence dependent variables. The data collected was primary, which came directly from a source. Furthermore, the questionnaire was designed correctly, based on the criteria, and tested in the pilot study and distributed electronically. Similarly, the researcher always maintained all recordings and notes when conducting the interviews. After completing the questionnaire, the researcher approached all participants for an interview to further explore their contribution. They also chose to include their e-mail addresses and phone numbers so that the researcher could contact them after data review, if appropriate and gave them three weeks to complete the questionnaire.

The data from questionnaires provided a good response and answers needed for the study. Then hypothesis testing was performed with the help of SPSS and got descriptive statistics. The researcher used a one-tailed T-test because the purpose was to test the mean for each hypothesis than to compare. Based on this, the researcher rejected the null hypothesis because the pi value was less than 0.5 and achieved an overall mean of more than 3.5. Hence, statistically, this helped the researcher go with the alternate hypothesis.

After the survey, the researcher decided to conduct an in-depth interview with minimal selected questions and selected interviewees. Interviews lasted about 30-45 minutes with eleven questions and were audio-recorded. Since the researchers did not have enough time to write notes during the interview; hence, the audio recording served as a note. Also, this will help researchers to make transcripts which will help in final analyses. The researcher has not used video recording due to confidentiality issues. The most crucial stage is editing the audio into the transcript, observation reports, or interpretation of documents (Dowling, 2005). During this process, researchers required more time to analyse the transcripts than during the interview process because the researcher was more focused on formulating the questions according to the responses received from the participants to ensure efficiency. Interviews were analysed using thematic analysis. It involved assigning themes and sub-themes and the responses narrated to the interview responses (Cameron, 2010), and the transcripts denoted the discussion on the repeating barriers, either form's themes or repeated content. For example, detailed barriers are financial resources for this study, which prompted the researcher to rate the main themes or sub-themes. The researcher ordered these themes with the hypothesis formulated. Hence, all the keywords from the interviewees form themes and themes analysed are to find out whether there is a correlation in the article so that researcher can accept or reject the hypothesis. For validity, the researcher analysed the transcripts multiple times using thematic analysis. All the data changed to the transcript, ordered, coded, and categorised to meet the research objectives. The motivation for using semi-structured interviews was to allow the researchers flexibility. The aim of this part of the data collection process was to give rich data on the experiences of women entrepreneurs so that the findings from the questionnaire could be triangulated (Fryer, 2006).

4.14.9 Stage 7: Integration of data

This research phase aimed to compare the emergent concepts, themes and relationships with extant literature, past studies, responses from survey questionnaires and interviews. The integration started first collecting and analysing quantitative data for addressing the research questions. Then secondly, the researcher conducted qualitative phase to validate the results from quantitative data. The researcher has chosen the quantitative method first because it allowed the researcher to formulate hypotheses and then validate them across a larger sample. Thus, the researcher used the qualitative method to identify and uncover topics and areas not

covered by the survey and talk about them more deeply. Then the research identified similar and contradicting ideas integrating the literature, survey responses, emergent concepts and themes from interviews helped researcher to interpret on how qualitative results helped to explain the initial quantitative result and identify barriers with more substantial validity, wider generalisability, and higher conceptual levels (Teddie & Tashakkori, 2009). From quantitative data, five barriers were identified, and this was supported by qualitative data during interview. The themes developed from qualitative data Furthermore, further new barriers, which interviewees repetitively expressed, formed a new theme of barriers. When the ideas and concepts were determined with no further contribution, iterating between quantitative and qualitative data was completed Then by evaluating, comparing, and analysing, the researcher concluded the findings for this study.

4.15 Ensuring validity and reliability

This study adopted a mixed approach that allows researchers to expand an understanding from quantitative to qualitative to converge or confirm findings and follow-up quantitative research qualitatively to obtain more detailed information (Sage, 2019). However, data accuracy remains a challenge for such 'self-reported (that is, the involved actors') interpretations. Therefore, all business research should consider validity, realisability, and generalisability to conduct and produce excellent and quality research (Zikmund, 2010).

Reliability is a valuable tool to investigate the internal reliability of the data (Noble & Smith, 2015, p.34). One of the most reliable tools to determine data reliability is Cronbach's alpha coefficient. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient range is 0 to 1, with the minimum degree of acceptance being 0.6. Therefore, research that demonstrates a Cronbach's alpha value above 0.7 is considered representative of a sheer level of internal reliability. Cronbach's alpha is used in this study to assess the internal consistency of the questionnaires, in which it functions as a correlation coefficient between mediate variables (Huck, 2011).

The researcher used Cronbach alpha to determine the questionnaire's internal consistency and reliability. A Cronbach alpha value above 0.60 is considered acceptable for reliability (Sekaran 2004; Saunders et al. 2009), and as reported in the results section, this study achieved the value 0.83, which denoted the data obtained was reliable, and the responses are consistent and remain the same over some time and within different contrasting situations.

Like wisely, according to Noe et al. (2014, p.153), validity is the concept of determining whether the research methods used in a particular study can generate accurate results. Validity is mainly divided into three main types and is measured based on a scale. One validity technique is face validity, sometimes referred to as content validity, where the researcher tests the literature about the experts in the field. Another validity test is criterion validity, determining whether the scale would predict results accurately and reliably concerning the dependent variables. The third type of validity test is constructed validity, reflecting on the data analysis based on the structured quantitative design and involves hypothesis testing and research questions analysis (Drost, 2011). This thesis uses two measures of validity. The questionnaire was distributed to a group of academics and experts for face validity assessment, and the researcher evaluated concurrent validity via a pilot study, the internal validity sub-type, triangulation. The data gathered in this study were from different sources, including closed- and open-ended questionnaires. Then the researcher started interviews which were quite diverse. Also, the member checking technique was used for qualitative data to build the trustworthiness of data where data, interpretations, and shared conclusions with the participants. It allowed participants to clarify their intentions, correct errors, and provide additional information if necessary. This technique ensures credibility that the findings were correct. Following this, the researcher reshaped the questionnaire to improve it based on feedback and reviews from these assessments.

Hence for this research, methodological coherence is conducted to ensure congruence between the research question and the components of the method and efforts were made in every step of this research to ensure that the research question and method and data were coherent to meet the analytic objectives, with each component verifying the previous and the methodological assumptions. Secondly, the researcher chose the appropriate sample 150, consisting of participants who best represent or know the research topic. "This ensures efficient and effective saturation of categories, with optimal quality data and minimum dross" (Morse, 2016, p. 18). To ensure that the sample was appropriate, the author reviewed the women entrepreneurship literature and reached out to specific business development organisations to know the model required for this study. Subsequently, the researcher decided that multiple actors and sites would be surveyed and interviewed. An iterative approach was adopted for this study to do data collection and analysis concurrently. For instance, the researcher moved back and forth between different research processes. Data analysis was done simultaneously with the data collection.

After this step, ideas emerging from data are reconfirming in existing data; this gives validation to the existing hypotheses/assumptions which, in turn, must be verified in data already collected" (Morse, 2016, p.18). It was done by reconfirming the ideas emerging from data analysis of one method followed by the following method. Eventually, the researcher used statistical data from a survey and the themes emerging from interviews to triangulate data. Moreover, finally, the aspect of testing existing hypotheses/assumptions is to move with deliberation between a micro perspective of the data and a macro conceptual/theoretical understanding" (Morse, 2016 p. 18). The author used the conceptual framework developed in section 4.16 as a template for analysis in the present study. The themes identified from the framework enabled the reduction of voluminous data and helped identify common data patterns. Thus, this strategy ensured to test existing theory was an outcome of the research process and provided hypotheses to be tested (Gidron, 2013).

4.16 Summary of the chapter

This chapter began by outlining the approaches used in this analysis and providing a thorough rationale for their use. The chapter then details the data collection techniques used, including design, content, and distribution methods. Following that, a review of how data would be collected, interpreted, and analysed and an overview of the significant ethical concerns this report would address in the research process.

In summary, after briefly reviewing the several problems that could apply to the research, this chapter provided a rationale for the chosen model and variables for this study. This chapter the analysis findings will be discussed in depth in the following sections, and they will be compared to the results of previous research to draw appropriate conclusions.

CHAPTER FIVE: DATA ANALYSIS

5.1 Introduction

The data analysis chapter presents the findings gathered from the research questionnaire and interview phase. The chapter includes the quantitative and qualitative results and analysis from the questionnaire and interviews. The survey response and data section include a demographic study to analyse the essential characteristics of respondents. After interpreting and analysing the demographic data, the researcher presented the closed-ended statement analysis, including dependent and independent variables. Then, it administered the study to achieve the aim of the study, which was to identify career barriers to women's entrepreneurship in the food industry of Nepal and provide recommendations regarding how to overcome them. Developing the framework led to identifying career barriers. There were about 140 respondents in the quantitative survey, and these were women entrepreneurs in the food industry.

Hence the quantitative statistical analysis is also presented. The statistical analysis includes the reliability analysis and correlation analysis. As mentioned by Reading (2013), the researcher performed a reliability test to check the consistency of the data so that the researcher could easily justify the validity and reliability of the research. Therefore, reliability analysis and Cronbach's Alpha value aided further in calculating the data consistency.

In the interview data section, the researcher presented the qualitative analysis from the interview phase of the research. Furthermore, the researcher interviewed eight women entrepreneurs of Kathmandu Valley and two men and two women from a business development organisation. These participants were aware of Nepalese women's barriers in doing their business. In the discussions, ten semi-structured questions were for women entrepreneurs. In addition, seven semi-structured questions were for business development organisations, use of thematic analysis assisted the researcher to analyse the answers. Then the researcher generated and narrated numerous themes based on the thematic analysis. However, to make the study more transparent, the primary data gathered through this research's qualitative and quantitative phases are further aligned with the secondary data discussed in the literature review in Chapter 2. Finally, it is presented in chapter five to prove the study by showing extensive discussion. In

this way, the study's overall findings are confirmed and justified by creating alignment between previous studies and the current results.

5.2 Survey Data and Responses

5.2.1 Exploratory Overview of Demographics Analysis:

Table 8: Exploratory Overview of Demographic Population

Age	Percentage
18-25	17.9%
26-35	35.7%
36-45	20%
46-55	9.3%
56+	17.1%
Relationship status	
Single	15.7%
Engaged	21.4%
Married	45%
Separated	7.1%
Widow	10.7%
No. of children	
1-2	53.56%
3-5	27.9%
Not applicable	18.6%
How long has the respondent been involved in this business?	
1-2 years	14.3%
3-5 years	20.7%
6-8 years	35%
Eight and more years	20%
What is the respondent's highest education level?	
High school or less	17.9%
Diploma	33.6%
Bachelor	35.7%

Postgraduate	12.9%
Any last pieces of training to develop the business?	
Yes	78.6%
No	21.4%

The sample population were about their demographic information before moving on to closed-ended statements. Hence, the data presented in Table 7 illustrates that most participants belong to the 26-35 (35.7%) age group, whereas the lowest number of participants belong to the 46-55 age group (9.3%). Nonetheless, the data depicts that all aged women entrepreneurs participated in the survey with 20% belonging to the 36-45 age group, 17.9% participants belonging to the 18-25 age group, and with just some percentage less are from age group 56+ (17.1%). Likewise, the second data reveals their relationship status question. This question was to know the commitment of all the participants with their families. Hence, most participants were under the married category with 45%, and the least number of participants belonged under the separated category from their partners with 7.1%. Sequentially, 21.4% of participants are engaged, and 15.7% are single. Moreover, only 10.7% are a widow. Hence, most of the data provide rich data for hypothesis five.

The third question reveals, “How *many children do you have?*”. The data shows that 53.56% of participants have children between 1-2, 27.9% have children between 3-5, and 18.6% do not have any children. The fourth question on demographics is “How *long have you been involved in this business?*”. This data depicts that 35% of respondents have been doing business in Nepal for 6-8 years, whereas only 14.3% of respondents do business for 1-2 years. 20.7% of respondents have been doing business for 3-5 years, and 20% have been doing it for more than eight years. The next question was to explore the educational level of the participants. The data reveals that 35.7% had bachelor’s degrees, 12.9% of the respondents had a post-graduate degree, 33.6% had a diploma, and 17.9% had a high school or less educational background. Therefore, this data reveals majority of the participants had a solid academic experience. The final question was to explore whether the participants had previous training before doing their business or not. Most respondents with 78.6%, revealed that they had prior training, whereas 21.4% had no previous training. Hence, this data is critical to test hypothesis one.

5.2.2 Descriptive Analysis of close-ended statements

The following section outlines a descriptive analysis derived from a sample population and their agreement on the barriers that women entrepreneurs face in Nepal's food industry. Here, the participants must tick on their understanding of the statements about the career barriers faced by women entrepreneurs. These barriers are training & development programme and education, legal barriers, access to financial resources, cultural and social constraints, and the work-family interface.

The researcher calculated the mean and standard deviation for each statement. The results illustrate the participants' degree of acceptance and satisfaction with the barriers identified in the comments. The four primary levels of measuring scales used to gather data in surveys and questionnaires, each being a multiple-choice question, are described as Nominal, Ordinal, Interval, and Ratio. All survey question scales, such as Likert, Semantic Differential, Dichotomous, and others, are derived from these four fundamental levels of variable assessment. Hence, the researcher used an ordinal scale for variable measurement, which showed the order of variables rather than the differences between them. The participants had to respond to their agreement based on strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, and agree to agree for each statement strongly. The comments were about the identified barriers that Nepalese women entrepreneurs face on a five-point Likert scale in this report.

The interviews presented an interesting contrast to these findings, and later sections 5.5 provided illustrative facts from the interviews, in keeping with the mixed approaches. The two systems were to eliminate the possibility of imbuing methods with empirical respectability (Shorten & Smith, 2017). Instead, it is essential to describe the study process so that potential researchers will learn from or expand on it (Eden, Jones & Sims, 1979).

This study utilises interviews as part of a mixed approach to offer additional insights and triangulate the results. However, the consistency of the interview process is the most crucial consideration for the researcher due to the complexities of interviews (Olsen, 2004). The thematic analysis was used to clarify the level of agreement and satisfaction with the interviews' barriers, as described in methodology chapter 4. Moreover, it provides context to the questionnaire results and allows for a more profound interpretation. Although the interviewees share a similar background, they are from separate populations, so these quotes allow

triangulation of the study results (Saunders et al., 2009). Quotes from the interviewees are included in Sections 5.6 and 5.7. The interviews are discussed in greater depth later in this chapter. This section discusses how the interview findings helped identify the career barriers that Nepalese women entrepreneurs face in the food industry.

5.2.2.1 Lack of adequate training & development programmes and access to basic education

It is the first barrier representing adequate training & development programmes and access to basic education where the participants showed their response if they agree on the series of closed statements provided.

Table 9: Mean and standard deviation of lack of adequate training & development programmes and access to basic education

Closed Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation
1. Lack of career guidance hinders business participation by women entrepreneurs to access various public and private offered support services, including business development services and information on business growth	4.32	1.08
2. The fact that women have fewer connections than men with experts in specific fields hinders the women entrepreneurs in business.	3.85	1.27
3. Many women entrepreneurs lack the skills and education needed to set up and run their businesses	3.86	1.16
4. Even the educated women are provided either less or inadequate education than their male counterparts partly due to marriage	4.06	1.28
5. The sex segregation policies in educational facilities limit the learning experience of women entrepreneurs.	3.96	1.24
6. Illiteracy among women often restricts their approach and scope for knowledge advancement, making them shy and suffer from low self-esteem and self-confidence in entrepreneurial activities	3.93	1.28
7. Most women lack entrepreneurial skills in terms of administrations, marketing, accounts, and public relations.	4.06	1.17
Total	4.01	0.44

From table 9, the mean of all statements on lack of adequate training & development programmes and access to basic education is (4.01), indicating substantial agreement. In addition, the standard deviation is 0.44, which is normal and shows that the responses from the participants from the survey questionnaire are converging. The highest mean (4.32) is for statement 1: “Lack of career guidance hinders business participation by women entrepreneurs to access various public and private offered support services, including business development services and information on business growth”, The lowest mean (3.85) is for statement 2, indicating significant agreement: “The fact that women have fewer connections than men with experts in specific fields hinders the women entrepreneurs in business”. Therefore, it is clear from the responses that adequate training and development and access to basic education is significant barrier to women entrepreneurship in Nepal.

Figure 10: Mean and standard deviation chart of lack of adequate training & development and access to basic education

The radar chart from figure 10 represents the responses from the participants. Moreover, the statement regarding " Even the educated women are provided either less or inadequate education than their male counterparts partly due to marriage " and " Many women entrepreneurs lack the skills and education needed to set up and run their businesses " has a high level of agreement, with a mean value of (4.06); and " Illiteracy among women often restricts their approach and scope for knowledge advancement, making them shy and suffer from low self-esteem and self-confidence in entrepreneurial activities " also show a high level of agreement with a mean (3.93). With a mean (3.96), the statement " The sex segregation

policies in educational facilities limit the learning experience of women entrepreneurs " indicates considerable agreement from the participants.

The findings' interpretation is that educational and training decisions in Kathmandu are generally the result of women's logical choices, but they are still culturally and socially built. Decisions taken by either parents or employers determine education and management training, which influences Nepalese cultural traditions, customs, and norms. Results from Rao & Venkatachalam (2012) affirm the findings of this study, stating that educational institutions assist women entrepreneurs in developing a business plan and are responsible for their success. Educational institutions must address these barriers women entrepreneurs face, especially business strategy and management skills instillation.

Such findings align with those of Joshi (2000), who agrees that there are gaps in education quality and prospects provided to women in Nepal, putting women who want to be entrepreneurs at a disadvantage due to low education quality. In addition, Tlaiss & Kauser (2011) and Mordi et al. (2011) found that women often lack the required training needed to do the business and succeed.

5.2.2.2 Legal constraints

It is the second barrier found from the literature review, supported by the sample population, and showed agreement on the closed statements presented in the following table:

Table 10: Mean and standard deviation of legal constraints

Closed Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation
1. Business licensing is an of women entrepreneurs as the process is lengthy and complex, excessive bureaucracy, and in some cases demands for bribes by officials	3.87	1.13
2. Weak judicial systems, inconsistency in implementing laws, bureaucracy, hooliganism, abuse of political power limits women participation in business	3.87	1.28
3. Laws and practices discriminate between women and men.	3.82	1.22
4. High rates of insurance, taxes, and duties limit women's involvement in the business	3.97	1.21
5. Legal constraints are barriers to women entrepreneurs in Nepal.	3.90	1.34
6. There is a lack of government support for women entrepreneurs regarding laws and regulations.	3.89	1.22
7. There is a lack of coordination between government departments regarding business procedures that help women entrepreneurs.	3.88	1.21
8. Laws and regulations restricting women from getting a license without their husbands' permission limit their business involvement.	3.87	1.38
Total	3.89	0.41

Table 10 shows that the mean of all legal constraints statements is (3.89), showing high agreement. The standard deviation is also (0.41), which is typical and indicates sample response convergence. The highest mean (3.97) indicates strong agreement with statement 4: "High rates of insurance, taxes, and duties limit women's involvement in the business," while the lowest mean (3.82) indicates strong agreement with statement 3: "Laws and practices discriminate between women and men." The participant's responses to the statements indicate apparent agreement with the legal restrictions.

Figure 11: Mean and standard deviation chart of legal constraints

More specifically than Table 10, Figure 11 shows that participants identify legal constraints as barriers to successful women entrepreneurs getting involved in business activities. As a result, all of the statements have high mean values, indicating that they are all in agreement: “Legal constraints are barriers to women entrepreneurs in Nepal.” as (3.90); “There is a lack of government support for women entrepreneurs regarding laws and regulations” (3.89); “There is a lack of coordination between government departments regarding business procedures that help women entrepreneurs” scored 3.88; “Business licensing of women entrepreneurs as the process is lengthy and complex, excessive bureaucracy, and in some cases demands for bribes by officials”, “Weak judicial systems, inconsistency in implementing laws, bureaucracy, hooliganism, abuse of political power limits women participation in business”, and “Laws and regulations restricting women from getting a license without their husbands' permission limit their business involvement” both scored 3.87.

It is clear from the findings that though there are laws supporting women entrepreneurs, women entrepreneurs in Nepal face this barrier despite these existing laws. The study conducted by Shrestha (2013) also agreed that women entrepreneurs are not aware of these supporting laws, but the tax legislation changes over time. Like wisely, the direction in Nepal where the permission from male guardian or husband needed to decide on behalf of women are also encountered by women entrepreneurs while doing business in Nepal (Sila, 2014).

5.2.2.3 Lack of socio-cultural support

It is the most significant barrier found in Nepal for women entrepreneurs. This study found that women entrepreneurs in Nepal encounter this barrier as the main barrier rooting other identified obstacles from the literature review (Chapter 2 and 3) and agreed by the sample population for the following closed-ended statements formulated below:

Table 11: Mean and standard deviation of lack of socio-cultural support

Closed Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation
1. Social norms prevent women entrepreneurs from managing their businesses independently, impairing their mobility and affecting their interaction with others.	3.90	1.09
2. Women entrepreneurs face additional handicaps due to the prevailing social and cultural gender-based inequalities and biases.	3.04	1.56
3. Most companies or people, in general, prefer to deal or work with men than women.	3.94	1.31
4. A lack of support and help from other women limit women's involvement in the business.	4.00	1.22
5. Negative opinions voiced about the role of women in business limit their involvement.	3.86	1.24
6. Castes and religions dominate with one another hinder women entrepreneurs.	3.90	1.34
7. There is a lack of suitable models to represent successful women entrepreneurs.	3.93	1.19
8. Although women entrepreneurs operate in the same environment as men entrepreneurs, there are gender biases embedded in society, limiting women from active economic participation and access to business and development services.	3.93	1.36
Total	3.81	0.83

Table 11 shows that the overall mean of all statements linked to a lack of socio-cultural support (3.81), indicating that most of the participants' views on this topic are accepted. Furthermore, the standard deviation is (0.83), indicating that the response is accurate. The highest mean (4.00) is for statement 4, i.e., "lack of support and help from other women limit women's involvement in the business", indicating significant agreement whilst the lowest mean (3.04) was for statement 2, "Women entrepreneurs face additional handicaps due to the prevailing social and cultural gender-based inequalities and biases." Therefore, it indicates a high level of agreement.

In general, the responses from participants to the statements revealed strong agreement on the barriers related to the socio-cultural aspect.

Figure 12: Mean and standard deviation chart of lack of socio-cultural support

Figure 12 reveals the stability of the respondent's responses to the given statements. For example, " Most companies or people, in general, prefer to deal or work with men than women." scored (3.94). However, " There is a lack of suitable models to represent successful women entrepreneurs ", and "Although women entrepreneurs operate in the same environment as men entrepreneurs, there are gender biases embedded in society, limiting women from active economic participation and access to business and development services" both scored 3.93. For the remaining statements, the agreement is also vital: " Social norms prevent women entrepreneurs from managing their businesses independently, impairing their mobility and affecting their interaction with others " and " Castes and religions dominate with one another hinder women entrepreneurs " both statements scored 3.90 and finally " Negative opinions voiced about the role of women in business limit their involvement " is (3.86).

Nepal is a patriarchal country where women entrepreneurs face many barriers related to socio-cultural embedded obstacles to succeed in their respective fields (Singh & Chauhan, 2016). According to the study conducted by Reeves (2010), women are seen in Nepal as secondary to men due to their conservative attitude towards women entrepreneurs.

5.2.2.4 Lack of easy access to financial resources

It is one of the most common barriers that all entrepreneurs face while doing business. Hence, the agreement to the closed statements is in the following table:

Table 12: Mean and standard deviation of lack of easy access to financial resources

Closed Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation
1. Women entrepreneurs suffer from inadequate financial resources and working capital, and they do not acquire external financial assistance due to the absence of tangible security and credit in the market.	3.95	1.36
2. Banks tend to exaggerate the likelihood of women entrepreneurs' default, hence imposing unrealistically high collateral requirements, which results in credit-rationing	3.86	.22
3. Lack of access to capital and credit schemes and the constraints of financial systems are barriers to potential entrepreneurs as main hindrances to business innovation and success in developing economies	3.99	1.33
4. In Nepal, a male is socially dominant in every aspect; hence, banks lack trust in a woman's ability and commitment to paying back their loan.	3.93	1.37
5. There has been a decline in the opportunities available in the capital and other large cities, resulting in an insubstantial entrepreneurial environment.	3.90	1.29
Total	3.93	1.03

Table 12 reveals that the mean of all statements on a lack of easy access to financial resources is (3.93), suggesting a high degree of agreement. Furthermore, the standard deviation is (1.03), which is normal and indicates that the participants' responses for all these statements are converging. Statement number 3 has the highest mean (3.99), "Lack of access to capital and credit schemes and the constraints of financial systems are barriers to potential entrepreneurs as main hindrances to business innovation and success in developing economies", indicating solid agreement and the lowest mean (3.86) was for statement number 2, "Banks tend to exaggerate the likelihood of women entrepreneurs' default, hence imposing unrealistically high collateral requirements, which results in credit-rationing". Overall, the responses from participants to the statements revealed that easy access to financial resources is a barrier to women entrepreneurs in Nepal.

Figure 13: Mean and standard deviation chart of lack of easy access to financial resources

Figure 13 reveals a high degree of consistency in the scores for the various statements. Apart from the highest and lowest scores listed above, the responses show that the participants strongly agreed with the statement that "Women entrepreneurs suffer from inadequate financial resources and working capital, and they do not acquire external financial assistance due to the absence of tangible security and credit in the market" with (3.95). Furthermore, " In Nepal, a male is socially dominant in every aspect; hence, banks lack trust in a woman's ability and commitment to paying back their loan " with (3.93); " There has been a decline in the opportunities available in the capital and other large cities, resulting in an insubstantial entrepreneurial environment " with (3.90).

Though lack of financial resources is a common barrier to all types of entrepreneurs, women entrepreneurs, specifically in Nepal, face this barrier because Nepal is a culturally embedded country and women's decisions ultimately depend on societal formation. Hence, the financial industry is male-oriented, and women entrepreneurs face this barrier in gaining finance from banks and other financial institutions, supported by Marlow's study (1997). Therefore, the fund to start a business or expand a company depends on family or friends due to a lack of confidence in women entrepreneurs from the financial institutions (Das, 2000). As a result, they had to manage their funds (Sinha, 2003), and the investment climate is gendered differentiated, which women entrepreneurs in Nepal encounter (Chamlou, 2008).

5.2.2.5 The Work-family interface

It is also one of the significant barriers found from the literature review to women entrepreneurship in Nepal, and the support from the participants to the closed-ended statements are as follows:

Table 13: Mean and standard deviation of the work-family interface

Closed Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation
1. A women entrepreneur must play the role of a daughter, wife, and daughter in law, this limits women's participation in her business, hence hindering her success	3.91	1.27
2. The prevailing attitude that a woman's place is at home with her family further constrain many married women from venturing into entrepreneurship	3.82	1.29
3. The increasing demands of husbands and children hinder the business activities of women's ability to succeed in business.	3.89	1.34
4. A lack of moral support from the family and husband is one social barrier to commencing a business to women entrepreneurs.	3.86	1.33
5. The stereotypical gender roles for work/family responsibilities hinder the female entrepreneurs from participating in business activities.	3.94	1.36
Total	3.88	0.71

The mean of all statements related to the work-family interface (3.88) is shown in Table 13, indicating a high level of agreement. Furthermore, the standard deviation is (0.71), which is typical and shows the sample's response convergence. The highest means (3.94) is for statement 5, " The stereotypical gender roles for work/family responsibilities hinder the female entrepreneurs from participating in business activities." and statement 2 ", The prevailing attitude that a woman's place is at home with her family further constrain many married women from venturing into entrepreneurship " has the lowest mean of (3.82), which also reflects strong agreement. As seen in Figure 14, the responses from participants toward the statements revealed that the work-family interface is also one of the significant barriers to women entrepreneurship in Nepal.

Figure 14: Mean and standard deviation of the work-family interface

From Table 13 and Figure 14, the participants showed strong agreement with the remaining statements like " A women entrepreneur must play the role of a daughter, wife, and daughter in law, this limits women's participation in her business, hence hindering her success " scored (3.91); " The increasing demands of husbands and children hinder the business activities of women's ability to succeed in business " scored 3.89 and finally, " A lack of moral support from the family and husband is one social barrier to commencing a business to women entrepreneurs " (3.86) which also reflects the substantial agreement of the sample.

It is not shocking that women in Nepal are confined to domestic roles and expected to play in society (Goffee & Scasse, 1985). Nepalese women are expected to look after children and do other household chores. Hence, these statements agree with the ideas presented in the table where women entrepreneurs in Nepal cannot succeed without support from husbands and family. Therefore, they had to balance personal and professional lives, which hinders their success and influences the growth of women entrepreneurship in Nepal (Hada & Shrestha, 1992).

5.3 Hypothesis Testing

For hypothesis testing, independent variables for this study are lack of adequate training and development programmes and access to basic education, legal constraints, lack of easy access to financial resources, lack of socio-cultural support, and the work-family interface. In contrast, the dependant variable is business involvement by women entrepreneurs in Nepal.

The following sections provide a clear picture of how researchers perform hypothesis testing. A one-tailed T-test aided researcher rejects the null hypothesis and accepts the alternate hypothesis statically to test each statement.

Hypothesis statement A: Adequate training & development and access to basic education strengthen business involvement by women entrepreneurs in Nepal.

The findings of the first hypothesis analysis in Figure 15 shows that the average Standard Deviation (SD) value (0.44) shows convergence on the participants’ responses, whereas the mean value is (4.01).

One-Sample Statistics				
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Adequate training & development and access to basic education strengthen business involvement by women entrepreneurs in Nepal.	140	4.0112	.43657	.03690

Figure 15: Hypothesis testing of statement A

One-Sample Statistics				
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Adequate training & development and access to basic education strengthen business involvement by women entrepreneurs in Nepal.	140	4.0112	.43657	.03690

Figure 16: T-test of hypothesis statement A

The researcher rejects the null hypothesis and accepts an alternative hypothesis based on figure 16, where P-value is .000, which is less than .05 meaning, adequate training & development and access to basic education strengthen business involvement in women entrepreneurship in Nepal.

The agreement for this statement is shown in the chart below.

Figure 17: Graph of the mean and standard deviation of Hypothesis statement A

To sum up, the research revealed that a lack of adequate training and development programmes and access to basic education hinder the career progression of women entrepreneurs in the food industry, especially in Nepal. These decisions are not the product of women making rational decisions but are traditionally and socially built.

Hypothesis statement B: : Legal constraints is the main barrier for Nepalese women entrepreneurs to involve in business.

The findings of the second hypothesis analysis in Figure 18 shows that SD value (.407) is average and indicates the responses from the participant's convergence, whereas the mean value is (3.89)

One-Sample Statistics				
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Legal constraints is the main barrier for Nepalese women entrepreneurs to involve in business.	140	3.8986	.40783	.03447

Figure 18: Hypothesis testing of statement B.

One-Sample Test						
Test Value = 0						
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Legal constraints is the main barrier for Nepalese women entrepreneurs to involve in business.	113.106	139	.000	3.89857	3.8304	3.9667

Figure 19: T-Test of hypothesis statement B

The researcher rejects the null hypothesis and accepts an alternative hypothesis based on figure 19, where P-value is .000, which is less than .05, implying that legal constraints are the main barrier for Nepalese women entrepreneurship to involve in businesses.

The agreement for this statement is shown in the chart below.

Figure 20: Graph of the mean and standard deviation of Hypothesis statement B

Hence, according to the study, legal constraints have an impact on the careers of women entrepreneurs in Nepal's food industry. In addition, these restrictions, according to the study, contribute to women impacted by corruption and bad governance.

Hypothesis statement C: Lack of socio-cultural support does affect women entrepreneurs in business activities in Nepal

The findings of the third hypothesis analysis in Figure 21 display that the SD value (1.22) is average and indicates the responses from participants convergence with the mean value (3.97).

One-Sample Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Lack of socio-cultural support does affect women entrepreneurs in business activities in Nepal	140	3.8134	.82664	.06986

Figure 21: Hypothesis testing of statement C.

One-Sample Test

Test Value = 0

	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Lack of socio-cultural support does affect women entrepreneurs in business activities in Nepal	54.583	139	.000	3.81339	3.6753	3.9515

Figure 22: T-test of Hypothesis statement C

With a P-value of .000 from figure 22, which is smaller than .05, the researcher rejects the null hypothesis and accepts the alternative hypothesis, i.e., lack of socio-cultural support affects women entrepreneurship in Nepal's business activities.

Figure 23: Graph of the mean and standard deviation of hypothesis statement C

The sample agreement on cultural constraints in Figure 23 depicts that cultural restriction and a lack of social support limits women's participation in business operations in Nepal. Cultural barriers and a lack of social encouragement, according to the researcher, hinder the career progression of women entrepreneurs in Nepal and due to negative outlooks against women who have their jobs and run their own companies. Due to the cultural and traditional background, which includes the husband's perceived weakness in helping and caring for the family while his wife works. Furthermore, as the literature review revealed, attitudes and beliefs towards women working outside the home are adversely correlated with entrepreneurship practices globally.

Hypothesis statement D: Easy access to financial resources boosts business activities amongst women entrepreneurship in Nepal.

The findings of the fourth hypothesis analysis in figure 24 shows that the SD value (1.23) is average and represents the sample's response convergence and the mean value is (3.93),

One-Sample Statistics				
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Easy access to financial resources boost business activities amongst women entrepreneurship in Nepal.	140	3.9300	1.02989	.08704

Figure 24: Hypothesis testing of statement D.

One-Sample Test						
Test Value = 0						
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Easy access to financial resources boost business activities amongst women entrepreneurship in Nepal.	45.151	139	.000	3.93000	3.7579	4.1021

Figure 25: T-test of hypothesis statement D

From figure 25, with a P value of .000, which is smaller than .05, research rejects the null hypothesis and accepts an alternative hypothesis, i.e., easy access to financial resources boosts business activities amongst women entrepreneurship in Nepal. The chart below shows the agreement from participants on easy access to financial resources.

Figure 26: Graph of the mean and standard deviation of hypothesis statement D

In Nepal, women entrepreneurs cannot become entrepreneurs due to a lack of financial resources. Understanding why a lack of financial resources hinders women entrepreneurs in Nepal is evident from the literature review and results from section 3.6.1. Because of their

limited access to funds, women are more likely to have personal loans and carry less bank debt and individual savings.

Hypothesis Statement E: The work-family interface does affect business activities to women entrepreneurship in Nepal.

The findings of the fifth hypothesis analysis in Figure 27 illustrates the SD value (1.05) is average and represents the participants’ response convergence, and the mean value is (4.08)

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
The work-family interface affects women entrepreneurs' business activities in Nepal.	140	3.8843	.70683	.05974

Figure 27: Hypothesis testing of statement E.

	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
The work-family interface affects women entrepreneurs' business activities in Nepal.	65.022	139	.000	3.88429	3.7662	4.0024

Figure 28: T-test of hypothesis statement E

With a P-value of.000, which is less than.05 in figure 28, the researcher rejects the null hypothesis and adopts an alternative hypothesis that the work-family interface does affect business activities to women entrepreneurship in Nepal.

The following graph as represented in figure 29, depicts an example agreement on the impact of the Work-Family Interface:

Figure 29: Graph of the mean and standard deviation of hypothesis statement E

Gender roles and the absence of alternatives to balance work and family lives to women entrepreneurs in Nepal reveals why the work-family interface is a barrier to women entrepreneurs' career progression in Nepal. Since Nepal is a patriarchal country, it has become challenging for women entrepreneurs to balance their professional and personal lives and progress in their careers.

5.4 Statistical Analysis

5.4.1 Reliability Analysis

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	140	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	140	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.834	35

Figure 30: Reliability Analysis

As Read (2013) mentioned, reliability analysis explains how the scale measurement shows consistency in the construct. Pedersen et al. (2016) state that reliability analysis explores the value of Cronbach's alpha and evaluates whether the data is consistent. Noble & Smith (2015) explain that Cronbach's alpha range needs to be between 0.75 to 0.95, and any data below 0.75 shows inconsistency, resulting in false data or unreliable data.

In this research, after sampling the data into SPSS, a reliability test was performed. The 41 close-ended statements devised in the questionnaire underwent reliability analysis. As shown in the table in figure 30, the number of items is 41, and the Cronbach's alpha value is 0.83. Hence, this proves the data is reliable, and there is consistency.

5.4.2 Correlation Matrix

The correlation matrix test was used to ensure that each element was independent of the others (lack of adequate training and development programs, access to basic education, legal constraints, lack of easy access to financial resources, and work-family interface) (Schmidt & Hunter, 2014). The correlation matrix between the independent variables is in figure 31.

Posterior Distribution Characterization for Pairwise Correlations^a

			Adequate training & development and access to basic education strengthen business involvement to women entrepreneurship in Nepal.	Legal constraints is the main barrier for Nepalese women entrepreneurship to involve in business.	Lack of socio-cultural support does affect women entrepreneurship in business activities in Nepal.	Easy access to financial resources boost business activities amongst women entrepreneurship in Nepal.	The work-family interface does affect business activities to women entrepreneurship in Nepal.
Adequate training & development and access to basic education strengthen business involvement to women entrepreneurship in Nepal.	Posterior	Mode		.093	.508	.460	.343
		Mean		.091	.500	.452	.336
		Variance		.007	.004	.004	.006
	95% Credible Interval	Lower Bound		-.071	.375	.319	.190
		Upper Bound		.253	.621	.580	.480
	N			140	140	140	140
Legal constraints is the main barrier for Nepalese women entrepreneurship to involve in business.	Posterior	Mode	.093		.370	.290	.228
		Mean	.091		.364	.284	.224
		Variance	.007		.005	.006	.006
	95% Credible Interval	Lower Bound	-.071		.220	.132	.068
		Upper Bound	.253		.503	.433	.378
	N			140	140	140	140
Lack of socio-cultural support does affect women entrepreneurship in business activities in Nepal.	Posterior	Mode	.508	.370		.838	.627
		Mean	.500	.364		.833	.619
		Variance	.004	.005		.001	.003
	95% Credible Interval	Lower Bound	.375	.220		.781	.516
		Upper Bound	.621	.503		.882	.718
	N			140	140	140	140
Easy access to financial resources boost business activities amongst women entrepreneurship in Nepal.	Posterior	Mode	.460	.290	.838		.682
		Mean	.452	.284	.833		.674
		Variance	.004	.006	.001		.002
	95% Credible Interval	Lower Bound	.319	.132	.781		.582
		Upper Bound	.580	.433	.882		.761
	N			140	140	140	140
The work-family interface does affect business activities to women entrepreneurship in Nepal.	Posterior	Mode	.343	.228	.627	.682	
		Mean	.336	.224	.619	.674	
		Variance	.006	.006	.003	.002	
	95% Credible Interval	Lower Bound	.190	.068	.516	.582	
		Upper Bound	.480	.378	.718	.761	
	N			140	140	140	140

a. The analyses assume reference priors ($c = 0$).

Figure 31: Correlation Matrix

The figure 31 shows that the highest correlation was between lack of socio-cultural support and easy access to financial resources (.838). In contrast, the lowest correlation was between lack of adequate training & development and access to basic education programmes with legal constraints (.091). Additionally, all correlations between independent variables are below one, indicating no multicollinearity.

5.4.3 Regression analysis

According to Alchemer (2021), Regression analysis is a reliable method of identifying which variables impact a topic of interest. Performing a regression allows confidently determining which factors matter most and how these factors influence each other.

To understand regression analysis fully, it is essential to comprehend the following terms:

Dependent Variable: This is the main factor to understanding or predicting. The dependent variable is the involvement of Nepalese women in the food industry.

Independent Variables: These are the factors that hypothesize the impact of the dependent variable. All the barriers like lack of adequate training and development program and basic education, lack of socio-cultural support, lack of easy access to financial resources, work-family interface and legal constraints are independent variables. The following is the graphical representation of regression analysis.

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Business involvement to successful women entrepreneurship in Nepal	27.4071	6.16779	140
Barriers	47.6714	5.06709	140

Correlations

		Business involvement to successful women entrepreneurship in Nepal	Barriers
Pearson Correlation	Business involvement to successful women entrepreneurship in Nepal	1.000	.447
	Barriers	.447	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	Business involvement to successful women entrepreneurship in Nepal	.	.000
	Barriers	.000	.
N	Business involvement to successful women entrepreneurship in Nepal	140	140
	Barriers	140	140

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Barriers ^b	.	Enter

a. Dependent Variable: Business involvement to successful women entrepreneurship in Nepal

b. All requested variables entered.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Change Statistics			Sig. F Change
						F Change	df1	df2	
1	.447 ^a	.200	.194	5.53590	.200	34.543	1	138	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Barriers

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1058.616	1	1058.616	34.543	.000 ^b
	Residual	4229.177	138	30.646		
	Total	5287.793	139			

a. Dependent Variable: Business involvement to successful women entrepreneurship in Nepal

b. Dependent Variable: (Constant), Barriers

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	1.444	4.442		.325	.746	-7.340	10.227
	Barriers	.545	.093	.447	5.877	.000	.361	.728

a. Dependent Variable: Business involvement to successful women entrepreneurship in Nepal

Figure 32: Regression Analysis

From figure 32, the researcher performed regression analysis to examine the relationship between business involvement by Nepalese women entrepreneurs and various potential barriers. Each barrier identified is positively and significantly correlated with the criterion, indicating that those barriers tend to limit the participation of Nepalese women entrepreneurs in the food industry of Nepal. The adjusted R square should be positive and less than R squared. The difference between R² and the adjusted R² is that R² assumes that every variable explains the dependent variable's variation. On the other hand, the adjusted R² shows that the percentage of variation is by only the independent variables that affect the dependent variable (Everitt & Skrondal, 2010).

Hence, the result from figure 32 denoted that multiple regressions model with all the barriers and business involvement by Nepalese women entrepreneurs produced a positive adjusted R²=0.194 which is < R². Therefore, this model is validating for the data and significant. Also, the p-value for a variable is less than the significance level, i.e., p<0.05. The sample data provide enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis for the entire population. This variable is statistically significant and a useful addition to the regression model.

(See residual plot in Appendix 16)

5.5 Interview Data

This section presents the analysis of the data collected from 12 semi-structured interviews composing 8 participants who are women entrepreneurs of Nepal and 4 participants from business development organisations who deal with women entrepreneurship and women empowerment programmes to elicit in-depth information of direct relevance relating to research Objectives b and c (Section 1.7). The qualitative data was analysed using thematic analysis. The author adopted a human-based theme system (Creswell, 2003; Gibbs, 2007; Bailey, 2008) in conjunction with supporting quotes from women entrepreneurs to provide an in-depth picture of female entrepreneurs' experiences. This chapter will primarily examine participants' barriers whilst doing business.

The analysis structure provided the themes introduced in the semi-structured interview schedule (see Appendix 4 & 5). The researcher used these themes as main headings (1) barriers faced by Nepalese women entrepreneurs (2) subthemes from each central theme. The researcher noted the number of respondents who referred to specific themes, and each theme produces its sub-themes. Percentages indicate the proportion of participants in the study who referred to a particular theme. The researcher used each quote as the theme, so the participants answered the questions asked. This chapter presents a detailed description of findings based on the results of this study.

5.5.1 Summary of personal and business demographics of female entrepreneurs

The researcher conducted an online interview with eight female entrepreneurs from different stages of their businesses to obtain data. The main criteria are for women who are doing business in Nepal.

Table 14: Summary of Personal and Business Demographics of Women Entrepreneurs

Participants N=8		
Age	18-25	2
	26-35	1
	36-45	2
	46-55	2
	56+	1
Educational Level	High school or less	1

	Diploma	2
	Bachelor	3
	Postgraduate	2
Marital status	Single	1
	Engaged	0
	Married	4
	Separated	1
	Widow	2
No. of children	1-2	4
	3-5	2
	Not Applicable	2
Business experience in years	1-2 years	1
	3-5 years	1
	6-8 years	3
	8 +	3
Previous Training	Yes	6
	No	2
No. of employees	None	0
	1 -5	3
	6-15	2
	16+	3

5.5.2 Significant of these findings

The design of the interview schedule provided an introduction of general themes as they related to the research questions. The study questions enabled female entrepreneurs to present more information about their personal experiences and perceptions relevant to the study. Female entrepreneurs commenced their interviews by providing information on their background, demographic, academic and business experience.

There were six general themes in the questionnaire. The first theme was concerning training & development programmes and education barriers for women entrepreneurs. The second theme was the legal constraints these women entrepreneurs experienced whilst doing their business

in Nepal. The third theme was on the financial barriers, and the fourth theme was socio-cultural constraints. The fifth theme was on the work-family interface. Finally, the sixth theme was other barriers other than the mentioned ones. The following sections include a detailed analysis of these themes and themes that further emerged from each general piece supported by selective narratives of research participants.

1.5.3 Thematic analysis

Table 15: Themes developed from interviews.

No.	Themes	• Sub-themes
1	Training & development and educational barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of training and development programme • Prior access to training and development programme • Education attainment is crucial for career progression. • Impact of education recognition on the business
2	Legal barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender discrimination in law • Government supporting women business. • Foreign relation • Impact of tax policies
3	Financial barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial support from a financial institution • Financial support from the government • Financial help from family/ friends
4	Socio-cultural barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender discrimination • Stereotype • Women viewed as homemakers, not breadwinners
5	Work-family interface barrier	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Childcare issues • Balancing family and work-life • Family support on business
6	Other barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networking • Technological • Marketing and strategies planning • Mentoring

Do you consider that lack of adequate training and development programmes and access to basic education limits women entrepreneurs to do their business in Nepal?

5.5.3.1 Theme A: Training & development programmes and educational barriers

Figure 33: Themes developed from training & development and educational barriers.

Sub-themes 1: Availability of training and development programme

6 out of 8 women entrepreneurs agreed that there are many training and development programmes related to entrepreneurship in Nepal, both for men and women. Nevertheless, they asserted that since women entrepreneurs are low compared to men, they need more advanced training and development programmes.

WE01 shared her experience as

“...When I started my entrepreneurship journey.... there were many training and development programmes to choose from. Especially, if you contact any women development organization,

they make you aware of many pieces of training available in Nepal according to your skills and time.”-WE01.

Sub-themes 2: Prior access to training and development programme

6 out of 8 women entrepreneurs said they had prior training and development programmes before doing business. Only two said they do not have any training or involvement in these programmes.

WE03 got involved in some events which provide training and development programme to women entrepreneurs for a good three years. Later, after receiving the certificate, she started her pickle business.

She added:

“During the time we started....it was very difficult, even to get training. There are many training programmes for women, so it is difficult to learn skills and get basic entrepreneurial training. But the country's situation is getting worse, which is creating difficulties not only for women but also for men. Some several co-operatives and organizations provide proper guidance not only to women but also to men. I have shared with my cases, as in the case of VAT, but besides that, nowadays, I don't think there are any extra problems in doing business for women.”-WE03.

Whereas WE07 cleared that she was not aware of any training programmes and tried to ask for help to support her business, she could not find anything that matched her business structure. Likewise, WE05 also supported but asserted that she did not have enough time to get involved now or before starting her business in these programmes.

Hence, prior training and development programmes help women entrepreneurs showcase their talents and guide them on the correct path for career progressions and increase the involvement of women in business activities.

Sub-themes 3: Education attainment is crucial for career progression.

Education is vital, especially today when the world is getting very competitive. Hence, the education system in Nepal has developed but unfortunately not in all parts of the country. Many women entrepreneurs during the interview are almost giving 100 % strong agreement on education and how it is crucial for career progressions.

According to (WE06), *“Education is very crucial these days whether be it for a job or business. Having a strong educational background transforms yourself first, then other things like your career. So, without educational background, women can start a business, but I doubt for career progressions”*.

Also, WE05 mentioned that she does not come from an educational background that affects their business. However, general problem solving, running the business, strategies, marketing, and sometimes dealing education helps to deal with customers.

Sub-themes 4: Impact of education recognition on the business

Almost 6 out of 8 women entrepreneurs agreed on the importance of education and its impact on the business. They stated that academic degree does affect their day-to-day operation. Education helps develop real-world skills and helps have a thriving life in a rapidly changing world.

WE06 comes from an educational background. Her education level has built up her confidence and widens her understanding of the world via education from her academic life.

She says, *“I believe... education is essential not just for women, it's equally crucial for all citizens. I think it's the right to go to school. I have many friends who dropped out early in school due to personal problems. Now they are earning but feels like they could grow if they proceeded their education and completed at least Bachelor's degree.”*

WE05 *“.... Today I feel that education is the most important thing to do anything. I have not completed my school, so I feel embarrassed when I show my clients or customers when I cannot write and speak in English; I don't know how to do maths properly. I need the help of my 11 years old son. I could have grown more successful, but my education is the big barrier to this. So, I am taking vocational training where I can learn.”*

WE02 states, *“It is not those businesses cannot run without management education, but it empowers you with the knowledge, skills and learning agility required to stay of times and competitors. The fast-paced industrial world demands the need for management abilities to handle the complex, multidimensional business spheres. In such a scenario, management education with proper guidance and training becomes indispensable. It has to be admitted that*

a collective knowledge from education and experience is what forms the right foundation for future managers, leaders, and entrepreneurs”.

It is clear from the result that education positively impacts the business. Concerning everyday business, problem-solving is learnt from experience and academics.

Therefore, the participants from the interview agreed that women entrepreneurs in Nepal face barriers related to lack of training & development and education programmes. Hada & Shrestha (1992) also supports which states that training and educational programmes are significant factors for development, and the absence of these will handicap them in business. The success of women entrepreneurs depends on this factor, which can change the women in terms of attitude, relevant skills needed for entrepreneurship, and increase the confidence to grow (Gautam et al., 1994). However, even though many governmental and non-governmental institutions are now launching these programmes, there is a lack of awareness, laws supporting women entrepreneurship, or maybe available in specific areas of Nepal where all women entrepreneurs find it challenging to access it (Shrestha, 2007).

Explain if there are any legal barriers whilst doing business.

5.5.3.2 Theme B: Legal Barriers

Legal restrictions and legal complication processes are significant barriers agreed upon by most participants. Most of the participants have expressed their opinions on the lengthy process to start or even expand the business, a heavy tax on international trade, no legal protection on the products or ideas innovated by an individual entrepreneur, and some legal barriers found from interviewees.

Figure 34: Themes developed from legal barriers.

Sub-themes 1: Gender discrimination in law

Regarding working with women entrepreneurs as average entrepreneurs, 5 out of 8 women entrepreneurs stated they had experienced legal discrimination. Furthermore, while business rules tend to be gender-neutral, laws outside the business world discriminate against women in subtle ways.

WE08 expressed her feelings as-

“Recently, a law passed stating that women cannot travel overseas without her husband’s or family’s permission. These laws discourage women and stifle their ambitions to strive for careers and business ownership.”

Also, to support this, WE03 and WE01 shared their opinions on the government about discrimination between men and women. However, if a woman wants to do anything, women have several legal obligations than men.

WE03” *As a woman, though laws are supporting and empowering women entrepreneurs, it's only in the book, but most of the worker themselves haven’t read that law. I faced so many obligations to start my business, but when my husband tried to sort the issue, it solved within a sec.”*

Hence, from the feedback, discrimination in law hinders women entrepreneurs from progressing in their careers.

Sub-themes 2: Government supporting women business

Most women entrepreneurs claim that there are no regulations that encourage local goods and that business practices are more efficient if women entrepreneurs have personal relations with government officials. Furthermore, according to the WE07, legal regulations and the numerous conditions required to obtain government assistance and a lack of legislation to protect the entrepreneur's ideas and interests contribute to a complex legal climate for business.

Furthermore, WE04 argued that.

“These legal obstacles constitute a set of complicated requirements for establishing a business. There is a lack of legal support for women entrepreneurs, discrimination between female and male entrepreneurs in the regulations high cost of protecting intellectual property such as the business idea. trademark and copyright in some procedures with some government agencies a man’s approval is needed.”

During the lockdown, WE02 had expected some government help for small and medium enterprises. No such service has materialized. *“The government seems confused. The only ray of hope..... is that consumers learned the value of the online business during the lockdown”*.

These responses showed that the government demonstrates no support-to-support women business. Hence legal barriers do limit the involvement of women and hinder career progressions.

Sub-themes 3: Foreign relation

All eight women entrepreneurs agreed that Nepal’s relationship with foreign countries and its rules and regulations regarding business is one of the career barriers to becoming successful women entrepreneurs.

WE01 claims that

“The Nepalese Constitution of 2015 provides for expropriation of the property only in compliance with the legislation and public interest. Only after adequate compensation has been charged, it makes it illegal to nationalize a foreign-invested industry. Expropriation, whether

direct or indirect, should only be done for the benefit of the public. These laws prohibit any licensed industry from being privatized and are only permitted for public purposes.” WE01 -

WE07 opposed the thought that

“.....Except for explosives and some radio equipment, there are no restrictions on importing project equipment under the Nepalese rule. Various projects, such as solar, hydropower, wind energy, biogas, and hotels, are eligible for customs duty and value-added tax exemptions. Imports to businesses located in special economic zones and star hotels and resorts are excluded from such restrictions. To qualify for those exemptions, you must get a recommendation from a government official....” WE07 -

Even if women entrepreneurs run their business successfully within the country, foreign relations make it difficult to expand their business globally. There is no recognition of Nepal as a business country across the world. Hence, it becomes difficult for women entrepreneurs to globalise their business, affecting their career progressions.

Sub-themes 4: Impact of tax policies

There has been a significant impact on all types of entrepreneurs in Nepal due to high taxes. There is an absence of flexibility in export and import procedure.

WE09 replied:

“The business I am running can add so much to Nepal’s economy, but due to high tax in this industry, I am unable to give the maximum output that my company is capable of. There are so many Chinese food products on the market. If the tax imposed on them were high and given the home-based product priority with less tax, I believe we could have sold our product at least across Nepal. But unfortunately, due to high tax, we must price accordingly, making our product a bit expensive than the Chinese. This automatically directs the target customers to buy Chinese products.”-WE09.

Hence, this feedback clearly shows that tax policies hinder women entrepreneurs from growing or strategically planning their business structure.

To sum up, women entrepreneurs in Nepal encounter these participants' interviews to support the legal barriers. Furthermore, the questionnaire and literature participants agree that Nepalese women entrepreneurs encountered this barrier while doing business in Nepal. Firstly, the laws are gender-neutral—secondly, the rules on socio-cultural aspects of Nepal, which already discriminate against women and men. Finally, even if there is support from women entrepreneurs, the procedure is lengthy, complicated, and unnecessary, hindering successful women entrepreneurs in Nepal (UNIDO, 2011).

Do you consider easy access to financial resources is the barriers to successful Nepalese women entrepreneurs to get involved in business activities?

5.5.3.3 Theme C: Financial Barriers

The fund is the most common challenge to any entrepreneur, but the barrier to women entrepreneurs in Nepal is the lack of trust from banks to these women who want to do business. Most of the interviewees highlighted high interest from banks, no available quotas for women entrepreneurs, limited funds, the financial paperwork required to get a loan as the barriers encountered by these women entrepreneurs in Nepal.

Figure 35: Themes developed from financial barriers.

Sub-themes 1: Financial support from a financial institution

All the women interviewed concluded that financial barriers for women entrepreneurs include the difficulties of securing bank guarantees, the problem of obtaining funding due to a lack of trust in women entrepreneurs and stress on complicated, lengthy, and time-consuming processes to receive financial assistance from banks or other government agencies. Many women entrepreneurs encountered several economic challenges when developing their own companies, including bank restrictions such as having a male guarantor.

Other financial barriers that women entrepreneurs face, according to another respondent, include a lack of financial support and banks limiting loans and services offered to women entrepreneurs without a man as a supporter.

Sub-themes 2: Financial support from government

Finance is the most crucial factor in starting any business. Hence, if there is financial support from the government primarily to women entrepreneurs, then the status of women entrepreneurs can be uplifted and boost the economy of Nepal. Hence, 5 out of 8 women entrepreneurs agreed that the government has financial help.

According to WE08 mentioned that –

“Umm.... there is much financial help from the government like micro-financing, less interest, etc. The government is trying their best to empower women in Nepal”.

Sub-themes 3: Financial support from family/friends

All the women entrepreneurs have agreed that they get easy access to finance from family or friends. They have received financial support from their family and friends to initiate a business, whether big or small help. The reason is that they are the most accessible means to get funds without any hassle and restriction, unlike financial institutions and government support.

As a result of the interviews, it became apparent that Nepalese women entrepreneurs lack financial resources, corroborating the results of the literature reviews and questionnaire. However, the study discovered that financial institutions do not discriminate against women; instead, they could not meet their credit requirements due to their businesses' low-income yielding tendency and their failure to have appropriate collateral securities (Akingunola & Onayemi, 2010).

Do you think lack of socio-cultural support could form a barrier to conduct business activities for women entrepreneurs in Nepal?

5.5.3.4 Theme D: Socio-cultural barriers

Most of the women entrepreneurs did agree that socio-cultural barriers hinder their career for progressions. Though the context is changing these days, this change can be seen only in a few cities, but overall Nepalese women entrepreneurs face this as a barrier.

Figure 36: Themes developed from socio-cultural barriers.

Sub-themes 1: Gender discrimination

There is gender discrimination still in Nepal amongst male and female entrepreneurs. Though there is much awareness made to empower women, men are taken seriously than men when it comes to business, which acts as a career barrier to progress.

This was clearly said by WE03, as

“The time has changed a lot likewise, the perception of people. But it doesn’t matter how big the women entrepreneur is; when dealing with specific clients, they prefer a male member. I still don’t know why this is, so I have been in this industry for long almost 12 years, but still,

its 21st century, when I deal with foreign clients, even they show different attitude towards me being a woman.”-WE03.

Similarly, WE01 also expressed her feeling as

“People says its equality era... everybody is same. But I feel it’s still the same. Yes, people have accepted women as an entrepreneur but not taken seriously. They think we are becoming entrepreneurs to kill time and do not have anything else to do.”-WE01.

It generally hints that gender discrimination is seen but not apparent. Nevertheless, every women entrepreneur in Nepal does face this barrier that affects their business operation.

Sub-themes 2: Stereotype

Stereotyping is the most common social problem most women entrepreneurs expressed in the interview. 5 out of 8 entrepreneurs expressed their disappointment on how women are perceived in Nepalese society and have become culture.

WE04 old expressed as

“We women are perceived in a certain way in our society. Women should never do this has stopped and created a huge barrier to women, not just entrepreneurs. And for us entrepreneurs, we can hear people saying ahh! she is a woman, she doesn’t know, or she is a woman she won’t be able to do this is a most common thing that I hear in daily basis.”-WE04.

Supporting this statement, WE02 explained that:

“Women themselves perceive we women are bound to certain things. I got questions from my female friend when I started this business. One of my female friends said, how can you do this type of business when you could have a nice job paying a good salary. This entrepreneurs’ thing doesn’t suit me. I was like. Are you even serious”-WE02

It means stereotyping is a barrier to women entrepreneurs of Nepal. This culture affects the career progressions of women entrepreneurs in Nepal.

Sub-themes 3: Women viewed as homemakers, not breadwinners.

Due to the cultural and conventional background, negative attitudes toward women who have their jobs and enterprises remain, including the husband's failure in helping and caring for the family. It is an age-old convention that women are less capable and inefficient in working than men. Traditionally women are seen as housekeepers and child-bearers. WE01 years old added:

"Culture in Nepal supports women as entrepreneurs and accepts the woman to be entrepreneur.... but still she faced culture issue as a mother and wife". -WE01

Hence, from the interviewee's response, the researcher is confident that this is one of Nepal's most significant barriers to women entrepreneurship. The embedded culture and societal attitude constraints women entrepreneurs and make them difficult to realise their capacities (IEDI, 2013). However, the setting is changing in urban areas of Nepal, but low value to women's work is still in practice in rural areas. It is the main barrier that branches other relevant obstacles hinder women's entrepreneurship in Nepal. In addition, various ethnicities, cultures, traditions, and traditional societal behaviours towards women and their duties add many hidden barriers to women entrepreneurs in Nepal (Thapa, 2009).

Do you consider balancing family and business responsibilities could form the barriers to women entrepreneurs in Nepal whilst doing business?

5.5.3.5 Theme E: Work-family interface barriers

Figure 37: Themes developed from work-family interface barriers.

Sub-themes 1: Childcare issues

Most of the problems mentioned by woman entrepreneurs from the interview revolve around raising small children, which can be a significant career progression barrier for a mother and a husband's lack of support.

Furthermore, according to WE03, because families do not want woman entrepreneurs to fly alone and meet and speak to men, children and motherhood take time away from her company.

WE08: *"If you have a husband and kids... they will expect from you to be available to them 24hrs, and you should satisfy their expectations no matters if you are an entrepreneur... the husband, kids and family expect you to do all the family responsibilities and not care if you are busy as an entrepreneur".*

According to WE07,

"It is the prime duty of most of the working women to prepare breakfast, lunch as well as dinner for the family members as well as self. In a joint family, the other family members provide help in different domestic work and take care of children during meal preparation or food materials but if the working women belonging to a nuclear family or residing alone were uncomfortable

even if we take the help of maidservant because meal preparation takes more time, it is daily routine work and cannot ignore our child.”-WE07.

WE05 said that:

“I am from joint family...during our working period, the family members take responsibility for preparing meals and caring for the children...so that I can continue the employment. The working women residing with children also furnish the task of folding and dressing the children”-WE05.

Sub-themes 2: Balancing family and work-life

The data indicates that more than 75% of working women suffer in participating in the ceremony of relatives or closed person either regularly or sometimes. It is a crucial problem before the working women in the city of Kathmandu. Most of the active women residing in rural areas occasionally visited the native place to participate in such a ceremony. Working women were also considering their children's education and disturbance in daily routine work if they participate in the tradition of relatives or closed persons.

A woman could still bear up with these problems if she controls over money that she earns, but their father, husband, or in-laws, in most cases, control their earnings. Therefore, the primary purpose for seeking employment to get independence is null in many cases.

Sub-themes 3: Family support on business

In conclusion, the participants encountered numerous challenges when establishing their enterprises, such as family expectations for women to be available 24 hours a day. Women entrepreneurs must meet their expectations and perform all their tasks. We heard some time ago that in developed countries like America, couples do household works together, but it is not the case in Nepal. Here, women must do the household works alone while the husbands sit in front of the TV or read the newspaper reclining on a couch. After about six to eleven hours of work, a typical working woman must return home and make food for the family.

WE08 says that:

"If the husband is not supporting and understand that you are an entrepreneur and you are busy, you can't continue your business because you will get a lot of family issues". -WE08

Similarly with the case of WE01,

"Family commitment and the issue we have with our culture. sometimes you leave your business in a busy time because of family commitments, which will affect me, and I believed most of the women entrepreneurs' business". -WE01

Thus, the hypothesis formulated work-family interface is a barrier to women entrepreneurship in Nepal has been validated not only by the questionnaire and work from previous studies but also from the interview conducted in this thesis. Specifically, in Nepal, women are confined to the four walls responsible for caring for children, family, or function family rituals (Kote et al., 2012). Therefore, the term "DEVI" given to Nepalese women defines that though the women are working, entrepreneurs or part of something other than domestic household chores still have to manage their personal and professional lives (Hada & Shrestha, 1992), which then affect their growth and expansion of business.

Are there any other barriers that hinders business activities for women entrepreneurs in Nepal that should be addressed?

5.5.3.6 Theme F: Other Unexplored barriers

Figure 38: Additional unexplored barriers

Sub-themes 1: Networking

According to the literature review, networking support is also essential for female entrepreneurs. Networking helps female entrepreneurs develop their social capital. All respondents stated that they needed support with networking and building a network. In addition, they felt that they could develop personally and professionally through networking with other female entrepreneurs. Most of the respondents (n=5) in this study received networking support through their business development providers. While few respondents were networking proactively on their own in addition to networking support from their providers, few respondents (n=3) had never heard about networking events and never attended any event. The following quotes highlight the importance of networking,

“Networking is the most vital thing any entrepreneurs should have. Networking has helped me a lot to grow my business. Without this, your brand is nothing the work you do your talent everything gets showcased on your networking skills.”-WE02.

“That just has been fantastic. I get a lot of networking support you know from people, and I support them. There was a new lady. I helped her basically to the network, so we sat down and helped each other, and at the least, in return, she will give me some work or referrals. And to be honest, you will start seeing the result after you have as much as networking positively”-WE03.

Though most respondents were aware of networking events and their potential benefits for their businesses, they did not access networks for various reasons, including time, distance, and childcare.

Sub-themes 2: Technological know-how

Technological know-how is a critical aspect in running a business to survive and compete in the market. Computer, fax machine, telephone, internet, generator, sewing machine, and other machinery equipment are examples of modern technology mentioned in this study, depending on the industry in which the business operates. However, several women entrepreneurs believed that they could not use the machine to its full potential.

WE08 said-

“Every day I wake up and go through newspaper to see if there are any new updates on technology in Nepal or internationally and then if necessary I take a course if available in Nepal you never know this is competitive age and world of globalisation without these skills... your business is incompetent in the contemporary market.”- WE08

Sub-themes 3: Marketing and strategies planning

In addition to financial support, several respondents stated that they wanted strategic planning and marketing support. Most business development organizations help their participants with business plans and marketing strategies. However, 3 out of 8 women entrepreneurs received marketing support, and five stated that they did not receive strategic planning for their businesses. Although the respondents received help with marketing and strategic planning, they were not satisfied as the support was very generic. The unsatisfactory general support might result from a lack of expert advisers.

WE01 mention that-

“Before doing business, I receive marketing and strategic planning support from the business development organizationit helped me a lot how to channel my brand and how to reach my target customers. I plan my business model with all the strategy I received from the organization and its benefits. A lot.”-WE01

However, WE08 says, *“I have no idea on marketing and strategic planning. Neither did I receive any support on these. This has left me on a blank journey, a journey of experience where I failed. I learned then I applied the necessary planning. Hence, if I were aware of these skills, it would have saved lots of my time and energy, and my business would never have to face a massive downfall.”*-WE08.

The range of quotes illustrates a need for dedicated specialist advisers to support businesses.

Sub-themes 4: Mentoring

Almost 5 participants who had accessed a business development organization stated that they receive mentoring, which has been beneficial to their growth. In addition, WE01, WE02 and WE06 agree that they had good mentoring support.

“I am thankful for my mentor who has been guiding me for four years, and still I am connected with her.”- WE01.

“My mentor channel my inner abilities and skills.... She is always there for me 24/7 whenever I need her, and she is updated with all existing trends of the business.” - WE02

“Yes, I did have a mentor who was an expert of marketing and has good networking across the nation. I take his advice if I am about to introduce something new in my company”-WE06.

However, WE04 states that-

“Finding a mentor is very difficult...there is lack of trust...you never know if they are working with your competitors and... in Nepal.... everything is possible... if you have money, these mentors get a bribe, and I had a bad experience with one of my mentors as she was helping my competitor. She was always helping me. But her decision on my business was foolish. And didn't work out well so, yes a good mentor plays a role on your business.”-WE04.

Respondents need a mentor or adviser at every step of their businesses to support them and tell them when they are not doing well or discuss and share their problems.

Therefore, this study has discovered new barriers by the interview. This exploration of barriers to women entrepreneurship in Nepal is an innovation of this research with an action research strategy implemented in the food industry. Mentoring is one of the most vital to all women entrepreneurs in Nepal, which can boost the women entrepreneurs, provide necessary advice to guide them and introduce another professional network that helps them succeed (Cohoon, Wadhwa & Mitchell, 2010). However, networking, technological know-how, marketing, and strategic planning are significant barriers for successful women entrepreneurs in Nepal's food industry. Balhara & Singh (2015) report argues that these barriers must be resolved for women entrepreneurs in Nepal to contribute adequately to the economy and gain economic empowerment.

5.6 Additional Interviews with Business development organizations of Nepal

5.6.1 Introduction

This section presents qualitative findings to address research Objectives a, b, and c (See Section 1.4). Firstly, this section will show the data collected from the semi-structured interviews of 4 business coaches/advisers that support entrepreneurs and observation at various workshops, seminars, and events. The word allowed the author to study the participants in their context. Qualitative data were in the form of semi-structured interviews and observation. The interviews elicited in-depth information of direct relevance relating to research objectives a, b, and c (Section 1.4). The same analysis was carried out with these interviews using thematic analysis. The interview's six main themes were to see the barriers encountered from the questionnaire, and interviews with women entrepreneurs in Nepal validates to conclude. All the discussion on the findings is in later chapter 5.

The quotes illustrate themes to protect the respondent's anonymity. Thus, the confidentiality of the names of individuals from quotes is maintained. The population selected for semi-structured interviews included two males and two females from a Nepal business development organisation. Many organisations provide business support, some exclusively to female entrepreneurs in Nepal. The participants were from four of these organisations. All participants are culturally diverse, had a range of experience, business and coaching, and education that facilitated valuable information for the study. The research population was composed of participants who had their businesses or entrepreneurial backgrounds. Two of the female participants are founders of their organisations, providing support exclusively to female

entrepreneurs. The participants were from the diverse city of Kathmandu, Pokhara and Chitwan of Nepal..

5.6.2 Personal and business demographic of these participants from the business development organizations

Table 16: Personal and demographic information of participants from business development organizations

Participant No	Age	Gender	Education Level	Marital status	Business experience in years	Branches under the supervisions	Position
Participant1 (P01)	35	Male	Postgraduate	Married	15 years	8	Vice-Chairman, FNCCI
Participant2 (P02)	45	Female	Postgraduate	Married	10 years +	5	General Secretary, FWEAN
Participant3 (P03)	60	Female	Bachelor	Widow	25 years+	10	President, MEDEP
Participant4 (P04)	31	Male	Bachelor	Single	5 years	2	Treasurer, WCS

5.6.3 Study Findings

The findings from quantitative data from 140 survey questionnaires and qualitative from 8 interviews provide a clear picture of career barriers to women entrepreneurship in Nepal in the food industry. However, this section will enable the participants to present more information about their personal experiences and perceptions about the study. This action research strategy determines whether these identified barriers validate the hypothesis or discover other obstacles. From the viewpoint of these participants, they provided a practical recommendation to overcome these barriers. The participants commenced their interviews by providing information on their profession and the background of their organisations.

From the interview with these 4 participants, the following themes emerged, which are presented in the table below:

Table 17: Themes developed from Business Development Organization

Themes
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Entrepreneurial mindset • Funding • Education • Childcare • Skills Training • Advisor/mentoring

5.6.3 1 Themes A: *entrepreneurial mindset*

According to three participants, the greatest challenge to establishing and maintaining a sustainable entrepreneurial ecosystem is the people’s entrepreneurial mindset. Nepalese are resilient, which is both a good and a bad thing, and they, for the most part, have a challenge-overcoming entrepreneurial mindset. On the other hand, Nepalese people have a fast-cash, rent-seeking, risk-averse, and security-oriented entrepreneurial mindset. Furthermore, it is evident that the difficulty of many women entrepreneurs who have persuaded their risk-averse parents to support - or at the very least not actively impede - their entrepreneurial ambitions. A solid entrepreneurial mindset is a set of abilities that help people recognise and seize opportunities, overcome, learn from setbacks, and achieve success in various situations that, unfortunately, Nepalese women entrepreneurs lack.

According to P01-

“Yes, the entrepreneurial mindset should be strong whether its men, women or young entrepreneurs...in my 15 years of service towards entrepreneurship development in Nepal... I

have seen that only those strong-minded entrepreneurs survive in this competitive business environment....and entrepreneurial mindset is critical if we are talking about women entrepreneurs ...it's because women go through lots of barriers especially socio-cultural.... they have lots of commitment apart from their business hence, she should have a solid entrepreneurial mindset to accomplish if she wants to be successful women entrepreneurs in Nepal. .”-P01

Similarly, P04 added-

“I believe the main reason why women entrepreneurs are lagging is because of entrepreneurial mindset. They feel that they should stop at a certain point or after a certain point of accomplishment, and then their progressions become stagnant. Most of the women entrepreneurs put a full stop after realising a certain profit. They don't go beyond those thinking hence she never should put a full stop on anything if she wants to progress.”- P04

“ the collective entrepreneurial mindset of people should shift from the perception that only business students do business, or engineering students do only engineering.”- P03

5.6.3 2 Theme B: Funding

Most female entrepreneurs began their businesses with funds provided by family and friends and the entrepreneur's funds. However, most banks are reluctant to provide loans to new businesses without collateral and a two-year company track record agreed by four participants. As a result, a lack of easy access to finance was vital for Nepalese women entrepreneurs (Ratha, 2012). It creates a new barrier for women entrepreneurs who are just starting, rather than those with a track record. The most significant barrier is the lack of easy access to finance and debt. As a result, women entrepreneurs cannot sustainably utilise the economic prospects in their local area.

According to P02, *“Fund, investment, capital, etc. all these terms come first on entrepreneurs mind when it comes to doing business...especially in Nepal. Nepal is a developing country. Hence when it comes to accessing money, it's tough. The banking and other financial institute has not flourished yet when it comes to funding entrepreneurs. There are lots of paperwork. Also, since Nepal has a culture of patriarchal property, women barely have something they own*

on their names. This makes the biggest barriers of a women entrepreneurs to invest even for Rs. 1 lakh -Rs 150 lakh business.”-P02

5.6.3 3 Themes C: Skills Training

Most training programmes are unidimensional, giving only one of the many necessary skills to develop sustainable firms mentioned and agreed upon by all four participants. Skilled persons should provide skill training components linked to other skill training institutions or activities (Davis, 2012). All four participants claim that while there are numerous skill related programmes for women entrepreneurs, those skills are very common, not specialised. Entrepreneurs need specialised skills first that are suitable for all types of industries.

According to P03,

“Tech entrepreneurship is rising, and they face their unique issues. Social issues aren’t yet fully embedded with technological solutions. People are tech-savvy but not in ways beneficial to their entrepreneurial drive. The use of technology has been limited in a communication way only and not in a way that helps others. But capacitating skilled people is not enough. Retaining skilled people is another challenge, and perhaps the hardest one.”-P03.

Agreeing with P03, P04 also added –

“Most skilled people seem to migrate to developed nations, and although part of the recent interest in entrepreneurship among women can be explained due to relatively high women unemployment levels, it is not the first choice for women to work in. While women entrepreneurship fosters employment, economy, and development, most women are reluctant to become entrepreneurs.”

“One of the main issues of Nepali business entrepreneurs is sharing knowledge, collaboration, supervising this between different actors in the ecosystem of business does not often happen, especially regarding skill training and sharing learnings. It also stems from a lack of information and data tracking the type and effectiveness of training programmes provided....and any subsequent analysis of its outcomes. Especially women entrepreneurs are not innovative in providing training, although that has started to change in the past two to three

years. Innovation in technical and interpersonal skills is significant for progressing and boosting our economy. However, we lack the policy capacity, the technical and cultural capability to share learnings across training.....and a focus on evidence-based policy”. - P01

5.6.3 4 Theme D: Education

All participants identified the education system as a significant barrier and a hindrance for women entrepreneurs in Nepal. They believed that education needs reformation regarding technique and attitude to learning, particularly in rural and local communities. While there are a few universities that include entrepreneurship in their curriculum and practical instruction, modern technology, and information, this scarcity is more noticeable in rural areas of Nepal.

Supporting this, P02 said-

“Education must be reformed especially so in rural areas, and local areas Education, specifically in business undergraduate colleges have become more relevant to entrepreneurial development, but there's a long way to go.”-P02.

“There is a massive gap in mentoring your student. There are some exceptions with teachers and some students who are not enthusiastic and go through the motion. But as a rule, a mentorship culture believed to be essential with the vital distinction being the match of personalities and the extension of said culture to outside the valley” stated by P01

Also, P03 put up her opinion on education as

“Colleges and universities need facilities like business incubators ideas like ‘thesis to the businesses and global learnings and methodologies like the ‘lean business model’ An environment of collaboration and a multidisciplinary approach is missing. The current way business and management education in Kathmandu, generally in Nepal, is designed to make us job-seekers rather than job-creators.”-P03.

“....a free mind, lack of pressure, a practical approach to entrepreneurship through creating a dummy company.... project work start-up internship among others should be done to transition

from a system based more on rote-learning and grade-based system to one that focuses on the practicality of the pedagogy if we want to empower women and boost the women entrepreneurship status in Nepal.”-P01

5.6.3 5 Theme E: Childcare

Childcare continues to be an issue for female entrepreneurs. All 4 participants agreed that childcare is an issue. Therefore, the clients cannot work around it and are often not allowed to bring their children.

P02 stated that childcare was one of the issues that hinder or limits their participation in businesswomen entrepreneurs in Nepal.

“Most of the businesses that women are setting up are in terms of the sector are hobby businesses or lifestyle businesses, so they tend to be things that can be run from home and very rarely tend to be from shops. So, they don’t tend to have large investment projects. They tend to things that they can start quite small, fit around their children or their husbands or their partners or family life. I probably have got a handful of small female entrepreneurs that have taken forward their businesses. Still, they tend to be single and don’t have any children. So, I think that part of the reasons it is but outside of the programme, many examples of women who have got children who have got families are running successful programmes. Still, I am not saying that is a 174 factor to why they are successful but certainly from the women I have supported that are successful have a certain profile.”

“It is you know we have had before if they can bring children with them, to be perfectly honest, we would never say no, but we don’t encourage that because this is about businesses, and you wouldn’t take a to a business meeting with you so you shouldn’t be doing this. However, we are considerate to people with different needs at different times. So, I would say we have a flexible approach to it.” -P04

5.6.3 6 Theme F: Advisor/mentoring

All participants stated a need for advisers/ mentors to show the way for different types of women entrepreneurs in Nepal.

“Women who might lack the confidence to make that first initial step makes it so much easier to come into a community centre or space that they are fully confident about. It is just around the corner from where they live, and it makes it a lot easier for them to talk to other women. they can connect with other women. They can access support groups, I think that’s very important for women entrepreneurs because of that confidence and also part of my job is not meeting them in a business setting, but I go into people’s homes, and for female entrepreneurs, it is difficult getting out of their homes because of child care and to be able to do that, and if I was a male and if I were to go to an Asian woman’s house, they probably might have issues around that, but because I am a female, women feel more comfortable sharing that part of life with me and you have a very open discussion you know whereas men wouldn’t have done that from a women’s perspective, but I think we have a very open discussion and both in terms of religious barriers, cultural barriers, gender barriers and I think that makes a massive difference to getting over that first initial hurdle which is talking about your ideas with.” -P02

In contrast to this P01 added,

“I don’t know why women prefer women advisers. I am a male. I have coach almost 50-55 women entrepreneurs. I feel they all are comfortable with me. This is a business, not a job, so they need someone to guide, so whether the mentor or adviser is male or female, I don’t think it’s an issue. The issue here is mentorship. I try to reach out to many entrepreneurs, especially women, so that I can help them. Still, women entrepreneurship lacks the idea of a need for mentoring. Hence, I feel that women entrepreneurs need a mentor or advisor to progress or even run their business properly. ”- P01

Hence, lack of mentoring/ advisor is the career barrier to successful women entrepreneurship in Nepal. The interview conducted with 4 participants (i.e., two males and two females) from a business development organisation in Nepal provided more insight on the status of women entrepreneurship in Nepal and the barriers women entrepreneurs face. Two new barriers, i.e., entrepreneurial mindset and childcare, are identified from these interviews. The literature review, questionnaire survey, and interviews with eight women entrepreneurs in Nepal did not identify these barriers. It is another innovation of this study because these participants are specialised in dealing with many women entrepreneurs' issues, programmes, funding from different industries of Nepal and are aligned with the country's government and laws. Hence, their viewpoint on the topic is representative of all sectors and rational irrespective of gender

based. The researcher outlined the other barriers in section 4.5.3.6. However, entrepreneurial mindset and childcare issues are significant barriers to successful women entrepreneurs in Nepal, confirmed by these participants, which is in line with Bharadwaj et al., 2011. His study also stated that the entrepreneurs' entrepreneurial mindset and childcare issues are still critical barriers to women entrepreneurship development. Therefore, in the next section, hypothesis testing is carried out, and once these hypotheses are validated, the researcher will discuss the barriers identified in chapter 6.

5.7 Summary of the chapter

The data obtained through the questionnaire and analysed using the SPSS statistical method and the results from the interviews uncovered the barriers to women's participation in entrepreneurship in Nepal, as well as offering further insights into the survey findings, especially about the training opportunities available to women entrepreneurs in Nepal were presented in this chapter. Furthermore, the results revealed that the findings confirmed all the hypothesised factors.

Women entrepreneurs in Nepal face severe barriers due to a lack of socio-cultural support. Culture refers to a group's or society's ideals, opinions, norms, and behavioural trends. Therefore, this factor heavily influences women entrepreneurs who contribute to significant barriers in Nepal. Apart from this barrier, financial and legal restrictions and family factors also affect the development of women entrepreneurs in Nepal. However, many of these restrictions apply to both female and male entrepreneurs, but still, women entrepreneurs face these barriers due to severe biased socio-cultural norms and practices ingrained in legislation, legal frameworks, and social support systems. For instance, the need to obtain male consent for some legal documentation or travel limits women's ability to operate their business freely. Adequate training and basic education have also been barriers to Nepalese women entrepreneurs' careers and limit their business activities. Some women may face the issue due to a lack of expertise to build and develop a business. Put another way, they can lack real-world business knowledge in the industry they are launching their project due to a lack of required skills and knowledge, which affects their ability to excel in this competitive business environment.

Furthermore, one of the most severe barriers women faces is balancing work and family obligations. As a result, women turn to self-employment to gain greater autonomy and

independence over their job and personal lives as they strive to achieve a better work-life balance. As a result, controlling and balancing work and family commitments becomes more challenging for women entrepreneurs. In Nepal, women manage all aspects of family care, and work and family roles are formalized according to traditional gender roles. As a result of the social construction of gender, men are traditionally assumed to be breadwinners and women to be homemakers, implying that motherhood is less versatile than fatherhood.

To summarise, these barriers will significantly impact the country's economy. If these barriers are not solved or addressed, the position of Nepalese women entrepreneurs will deteriorate in the future. Hence, the research findings are discussed in the following chapter to validate the data obtained.

CHAPTER SIX: DISCUSSIONS

6.1 Introduction

This chapter aims to discuss the findings from chapter 4. Since the data types used for this research are mixed data, i.e., the quantitative and qualitative data using primary data collection methodology and questionnaire and interview as tools. These helped the researcher gain insight into the topic researched and answer the research question. Here, the researcher discussed those findings to meet the research objectives and aim of the case.

The research was to explore the career barriers to successful women entrepreneurs in the food industry of Nepal and how to overcome these barriers. In this mixed-method study, the main obstacles were lack of adequate training & development programmes and access to basic education, legal constraints, lack of easy access to financial resources, lack of socio-cultural support and work-family interface. In addition, some other barriers like entrepreneurial mindset, networking, skilling, mentoring/advisor, unnecessary government laws that affect the business activities of women entrepreneurship in Nepal have also been found, which will go in-depth in a later section.

6.2 Interpretation of Findings

There were three parts to the analysis of the data. The first part of the study dealt with the results of the quantitative data analysis, which involved 140 survey questionnaires of 150 collected from the sample population. Statistical analysis included mean and standard deviation values. Likewise, for qualitative data, there were two parts, i.e., part B was the data from 8 women entrepreneurs of Nepal and 4 participants from business development organisations of Nepal via interview analysed via thematic analysis. Now, the researcher will discuss these findings based on research questions.

6.2.1 Research Objectives:

From section 1.8, there are three research questions to meet the aims and objectives of this thesis from chapter 1. The following is an interpretation of the findings by research objectives. Each research objectives explored the barriers that Nepalese women face in the food industry that limit their business activities participation. There is a need to research determining the

barriers of women entrepreneurs, which affects their business activities. This study will contribute to overcoming these barriers via action research design. From chapter 5, five main barriers have been identified, which was empirically tested and found to be significant when related to career barriers to successful women entrepreneurs in the food industry of Nepal.

Here the researchers explain briefly on how this study met its research objectives which are mentioned as follows:

a) To discuss the current situation of women entrepreneurship in the food industry of Nepal.

The researcher has reviewed all relevant literature in chapters 2 and 3 to achieve this objective. Despite the growth of women entrepreneurs in the Neplases food industry, they still face significant barriers that prevent them from participating in their businesses. Nevertheless, the food industry is a significant source of revenue for the country. Raising awareness is crucial to boosting the status of women entrepreneurs in this industry. Further, Nepal's food industry does not require any skills or education, so women are attracted to this field quickly.

b) To identify the main barriers limiting women entrepreneurs' business involvement in Nepal.

The study identified some significant barriers to answering the research question that limits business activities for women entrepreneurs in the food industry in Nepal.

a) Lack of adequate training and development programs and basic education affects business activities to women entrepreneurs

The critical finding is valid after testing the hypothesis: women entrepreneurs in Nepal had a reasonable consensus on the role of adequate training and basic education on their career progressions, with a general mean of all statements of (4.01) relating to women entrepreneurship. It suggests that Nepalese women entrepreneurs lack adequate training & development and access to essential educational programmes that limit their business involvement. In contrast to the case for men, the interview answers reflect the lack of access to primary education and adequate training support faced by women while doing business, which represents it as a barrier. Appropriate training and basic education are essential for successful

entrepreneurial start-ups, establishments, and development which are not available in all locations for women.

Although from the findings, there is an optimal amount of training, development, and educational support for women entrepreneurs, some specialist provisions are needed to suggest market failure. This study backs up the findings of several previous studies. This study also discovered that a lack of adequate training and basic education courses, which leads to expertise and experience gaps, will make it difficult for a woman entrepreneur to succeed. Furthermore, women suffered from a lack of access to basic training, which affected their success.

b) Legal constraints affect business activities to women entrepreneurs in Nepal

The critical finding is valid after testing the hypothesis testing results: the woman entrepreneurs strongly agreed on the influence of legal constraints on women entrepreneurs in the food industry of Nepal with a general mean of all statements relating to legal restrictions (3.89). It suggests that legal restrictions hinder the development of Nepalese woman entrepreneurs. Similarly, the interviewees' responses represent the many legal restrictions encountered by women entrepreneurs whilst doing business in Nepal.

These results confirm the findings of many previous studies. According to Republica Nepal (2020), a new law that has been passed in Nepal stating that women are not allowed to travel without consent from the husband, family member, or government proves that these legal barriers do affect the women to progress in any field. Hence, this is a significant barrier to women entrepreneurs in Nepal for career progressions.

c) Lack of easy access to financial resources limits business activities to women entrepreneurs in Nepal

The finding is valid after analysing the hypothesis testing results: the women entrepreneurs strongly agreed on the role of easy access to finance as the career barriers to successful women entrepreneurs in the food industry of Nepal, with a general mean of all statements relating to lack of easy access to financial resources of (3.93). It suggests that women entrepreneurs are limited in their potential to start new companies due to a shortage of access to financial resources. The interviewees also agreed that insufficient financial resources affected the progression or expansion of the business. Women entrepreneurs were restricted from accessing

loans and other facilities without male guarantees, faced difficulties raising capital due to a lack of bank trust, and were presented with complicated, complex, and lengthy procedures to get financial assistance.

These findings corroborate the findings of several previous research. For example, one of the most significant barriers women encountered was concerns over insufficient initial financing for their planned companies due to the prominent tension between family and work problems. Also, from this doctoral study, women had a more significant restriction in private funding due to interrupted and punctuated work history and low wages.

d) Lack of socio-cultural support hinders women entrepreneurs to get involve in business activities in Nepal

The critical finding is valid after testing the hypothesis testing results. Women entrepreneurs had a reasonable consensus on the impact of cultural and social constraints on women entrepreneurs of Nepal, with a general mean of all statements relating to lack of socio-cultural support on women entrepreneurs (3.81). It suggests that women entrepreneurs' desire to advance in their enterprises is the barrier to cultural construction in Nepal. Also, most interviewees agreed that Nepalese society limits women's opportunities as entrepreneurs and hinders their ability to advance in their careers. Furthermore, as woman entrepreneurs, women receive little social support, but this is starting to change as views shift and people continue to embrace women in any business position.

Many previous studies agree that women must deal with smaller salaries, discrimination, difficulty to advance. It is mainly due to the patriarchal societies and conservative attitudes towards women, the lack of legal mechanisms and institutions to monitor and penalize discrimination.

e) The work-family interface affects women entrepreneurship whilst doing business in Nepal

The critical finding is valid after analysing the hypothesis testing results. Women entrepreneurs firmly agree that the work-family interface is one of the main barriers to successful women entrepreneurs in Nepal, with a general mean of all statements relating to the work-family interface (3.88). As a result, the work-family interface's influence hinders women entrepreneurs' careers for advancement. Also, regardless of how active they are as entrepreneurs, the

interviewees agreed that balancing work and family lives is also the main career barrier for women entrepreneurs, such as family demands that women be available 24 hours a day and meet those standards, as well as fulfil all household roles.

These results corroborate the findings of several previous studies. Women balance their work and personal lives to gain greater independence and autonomy, which leads to self-employment. As a result, it is easy to see why Nepalese women are hesitant to pursue higher education or start their own company. They are female creates societal barriers that prevent them from openly seeking higher education, employment, and career objectives.

Additional barriers

Similarly, the interview sample reviews revealed additional problems and barriers. These findings are close to many previous studies. Another stumbling block is women's lack of knowledge and experience. From identifying opportunities to running a company, all stages of entrepreneurship growth depend on relevant practice. These barriers are defined as follows:

1. Entrepreneurial mindset

Entrepreneurial mindset plays a vital role in entrepreneurship, specifically to women. from the interviews, the most critical barrier women entrepreneurs face is their entrepreneurial mindset. Negative talks about themselves, low confidence, fear of failure are the factors that sum up the whole stand. Most women entrepreneurs have an entrepreneurial mindset that restricts them from doing business or progress in Nepal due to the five identified barriers (see section 2.8). In Nepal, men were supposed to lead and dictate, while women chose feminine careers. According to evolutionary theory, women have a long way to go change social perceptions regarding leadership positions and entrepreneurship. Women had to imitate male behaviours to compete in a male-dominated field, being competitive, aggressive, and harsh. The same behaviour from a man and a woman was assessed differently, with confidence as bossy, commitment as aggression, and desire as greed. Hence, it tapped into a conflict between expected behaviour and gender norms; leadership roles requiring confidence, risk-taking, and self-awareness became a source of frustration for women. Women's skill set and experience were on par with men. Still, to compete in an unequal playing field, women started using their feminine leadership characteristics to complement men's to be taken seriously.

Jamali (2009) supported these findings that women entrepreneurs need to overcome this barrier by combining personal attitudes such as their passion, determination, hard work, perseverance, ambition, strong personality, self-confidence, autonomy, and devotion to work during their business development. Also, entrepreneurs' poor entrepreneurial mindset may hinder growth and business development.

2. Networking

One of the career barriers identified in the report was a lack of networking. Women had small social networks and only networked with other women who shared almost identical business knowledge characteristics in their immediate region. Low education was one explanation for inadequate networking, which hindered their success. In addition, they could not make social contacts outside of their work environments, and their exposure to other corporate realms and growth opportunities was minimal as a result. As a result, women's businesses face a barrier to growth regarding networking, which prevents them from growing and seeking deals that could help them advance their businesses.

This study revealed that social networks are needed for a venture to advance further. For example, a person might detect an entrepreneurship opportunity but lack the social connections necessary to turn the opportunity into a business start-up. Access to a broader social network is one way to solve this issue. Furthermore, where there are more excellent social connections to resource contributors, acquiring resources increases growth opportunities. Unfortunately, unlike men, women network only with family members, which hinders their success, resulting in lower revenues and development.

3. Skills constraints

The ability to operate a business was identified as a barrier to women entrepreneurs' success, as most women lacked skills such as marketing, developing strategies, and operational skills, among other things, which was the study's central challenge, preventing them from planning, becoming innovative, and expanding their companies. It restricted their opportunity to enter and develop markets, forcing them to operate small, low-growth firms with little chance of

focusing on possibilities. This study showed that women lack soft skills and confidence in running their businesses, resulting in low entrepreneurship creation and high failure rates among new companies. The findings claim that women are concentrated in those occupations because they lack marketable skills beyond what they have already learned at home and find it relatively straightforward to pursue specific jobs.

4. Advisor/mentoring

The participants in this study commented on the need to share experiences with other female entrepreneurs and believed that female advisers or coaches could be beneficial as business support. In addition, women are more likely than men to operate businesses from home.

The rural/semi-urban area females were unaware of the contact persons who could help them expand their work. The females often felt reluctant to approach people for further direction and guidance. At times, they were also unaware about whom to come to seek the proper advice. Government institutions in urban and semi-urban/ rural regions are ready to provide entrepreneurial guidance. These females were not aware and, at times, were not confident of approaching them.

The findings highlight two main issues in the discussions about mainstream or specialist provision for women entrepreneurs. First, concern about the number of women who would engage with specialist institutions as many established female entrepreneurs regards women-only business support mechanisms with great reservation. Second is a concern that mainstream business support provision is generally targeted at high-growth businesses, excluding women-owned businesses, as relatively few can meet the thresholds for inclusion in many of these selective programmes and initiatives that are true about the female entrepreneurs in this study. Therefore, gender-blindness may be disadvantageous to female-owned businesses, typically smaller in scale.

c) To recommend grassroots solutions on overcoming the identified barriers and uplift the status of women entrepreneurship in the Nepalese food industry.

The researcher attempts to meet this objective in the following chapter. Finally, the researcher provides recommendations to the policymaker and recommendations on the identified barriers

from this study. This attempts to overcome the barriers and uplift the status of women entrepreneurs in the Nepalese food industry.

6.3 Summary of the chapter

The previous chapter's data analysis addressed findings and answered the research questions. However, other significant barriers emerge from the responses to the interview questions. While the factors identified, such as a lack of adequate training and access to basic education, legal constraints, socio-cultural constraints, lack of easy access to financial resources and a work-family interface, have continued to constrain women entrepreneurs in Nepal's food industry, new barriers have emerged that further hinder them. After determining that the hypothesis made in this study is valid, the researcher uncovered further barriers that restrict the business involvement by women entrepreneurs in Nepal's food business. The next chapter continues to present the conclusions drawn from the topic.

Additionally, survey questionnaires and interviews validate the identified barriers built from the literature review on barriers faced by women entrepreneurs. Because this study used mixed methods, it has a strong positive impact on the validity of the studies due to triangulation, which helped to structure the results and provides each procedure with solid support from the others, meaning that the findings accurately represent the actual condition in the research sample and the environment in which they live (Kumar, 2005). As a result, hypotheses confirm a lack of adequate training and development programmes and lack of access to basic education, financial constraints, legal constraints, family commitments, and a lack of socio-cultural support. On the other hand, the literature review could not validate some new barriers discovered through interviews. These barriers uncovered from this study are entrepreneurial mindset, mentoring and skills constraints, and networking, as significant barriers to successful women entrepreneurship in Nepal's food industry hindering their participation.

CHAPTER SEVEN: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

7.1 Introduction

Chapter seven presents the conclusions resulting from the mixed-method study. This research aimed to look at the barriers that women entrepreneurs face while running a business in Nepal and resolve them. This chapter commences with a relationship between hypotheses and theoretical contribution. Further sections include the research issues, draws insights from the results of this study, highlights the research's contributions to knowledge, theory and practice and recommendations made accordingly.

7.2 Purpose of the study

This exploratory research design explores the significant barriers that limit women entrepreneurs in Nepal to conduct business activities. This study utilises positivism and interpretivism philosophies with a mixed approach, i.e., employing both deductive and inductive approaches whereby the researcher used both quantitative and qualitative analysis to collect primary data and analyse the data collected. Also, since this is in the food industry, this study becomes a case study analysis. Furthermore, the researcher combined this strategy with action research to develop novel innovations and provide recommendations to overcome the barriers identified. Finally, the researcher chose this approach to test the theories already existing in the topic, answer some questions, and conclude.

Hence, to carry out this research, three questions formulated for this thesis were: 1. What is the current situation of women entrepreneurship in the food industry of Nepal? 2. What are the main barriers that women entrepreneurs face that limit their business activities in the Nepalese food industry? And 3. What measures are needed to eliminate the identified barriers to strengthen women entrepreneurship and increase business activities in the Nepalese food industry?

More specifically, through this mixed approach, further objectives were developed by the researcher to pursue this thesis:

- a) To discuss the current situation of women entrepreneurship in the food industry of Nepal.
- b) To identify the main barriers limiting women entrepreneurs' business involvement in Nepal.
- c) To recommend grassroots solutions on overcoming the identified barriers and uplift the status of women entrepreneurship in the Nepalese food industry.

Chapters 2 and 3 addresses the first research objective i.e., To discuss the current situation of women entrepreneurship in the food industry of Nepal. This leads to the development of a conceptual framework for the study. The research findings and their critical discussion regarding existing research and objectives two are in chapters 4, 5 and 6. The study produced an array of findings. The questionnaire survey and semi-structured interviews examined Nepalese woman entrepreneurs face whilst doing business in the food industry. Therefore, academics and policymakers must explore how business support can be provided for female entrepreneurs to help them develop and sustain their businesses. Furthermore, this study contributes to innovation to further barriers not discussed in-depth in previous academic studies, especially in the Nepalese food industry context.

7.3 Methodology

This study adopted mixed methods to gather data and analyse the identified barriers to women entrepreneurship in Nepal. The reason to employ both quantitative and qualitative data types is that the researcher aimed to uncover further the unidentified significant barriers that limit business activities for women entrepreneurs that need awareness in today's business environment.

The researcher pursued primary data collection with tools like survey questionnaires and online interviews to collect the data. It has benefited the researcher to validate the data and provide the recommendation to minimise or solve these barriers existing in the context of Nepal.

7.4 Scope and Limitation of the Study

As noted in chapter one, the critical limitation of this study is the lack of time and budget; data collection was on women entrepreneurs registered in Kathmandu Valley, Nepal. However, the most prominent limitation was the limitation of data and the data gathering. It prevents the application of the quantitative results in other sectors than the food industry. Moreover, the quantitative data was solely on the food industry analysis, mainly in the niche market. Therefore, this limitation provides less room for amendments to the multi-operative industries of the country. Another rule was that the respondents were in a formal interview condition and had limited time to answer. Therefore, some respondents gave replies to questions in summarised form. However, some respondents' answers were very detailed and required much time to make the themes out of the solution. Nepal's food industry is vast; the data collection could be gathered from different sectors and vast populations to study the research topic deeply. However, there was minimal data available online regarding the food industry of Nepal and the companies operating within the industry. Due to the lack of time and budget, data collection was only on women entrepreneurship in Kathmandu Valley. This new concept of women entrepreneurship in Kathmandu Valley can serve as a springboard for further research into the field. The study also suggests that additional research be undertaken in other cities similar to the Kathmandu Valley in Nepal to understand their unique needs better. Customised plans, policies, strategies, and intervention mechanisms developed by the country's government regarding the unique characteristics of each city or town. Similarly, future research might investigate the various attributes of women-owned businesses.

1.5 Key findings and interpretations

This study aimed to identify the significant career barriers that Nepalese women entrepreneurs encounter and how they may overcome them to advance in their careers. The study's objectives were to figure out what barriers women entrepreneurs face while starting a business in Nepal. These barriers included those found in the literature study and validated in the research conducting survey questionnaires, and the interviewees raised new barriers.

- Lack of adequate training & development programmes and access to basic education
- Legal constraints
- Lack of Socio-Cultural support

- Lack of easy access to financial resources
- The Work-family interface
- Entrepreneurial mindset
- Networking
- Skills constraints
- Advisor/mentoring

Additionally, by incorporating mixed methods and introducing essential data, this study contributes to existing research knowledge by exploring the types of coping mechanisms employed by Nepalese women to overcome the barriers that prevent them from advancing in their careers. This study can improve the status of women entrepreneurs in Nepal by allowing them to have decision-making positions and grow their businesses. Women who lead businesses effectively can identify and remove the social, individual, and organisational barriers they face.

It addressed most of the barriers that have been mentioned in previous studies and used this understanding to analyse how barriers affect women entrepreneurs in Nepal. In addition, this study also explores culture as a significant barrier to Nepalese women's achievement. As a result, this study contributes significantly by identifying the main barriers that entrepreneurial women in Nepal face. Following are some conclusions regarding each of the barriers identified:

1.5.1 Lack of socio-cultural support

According to literatures and findings from this study section 5.2.2.3 reveals that lack of socio-cultural support is one of the significant barriers to women entrepreneurs' limiting them in business activities in Nepal. Culture refers to a group's or society's values, beliefs, customs, and behavioural patterns. As a result, consideration of external influences is a must alongside female entrepreneurship (Mordi et al., 2010).

As a result of a lack of positive family support, many women worldwide have a hard time sustaining their entrepreneurial ventures (Lakshmi & Vidya, 2014). It appeared to be entirely accurate for the current study on entrepreneurial women. Furthermore, women in Nepalese culture are considered "humble and modest" (Karki, 2013), with their primary priorities being their roles as spouses and mothers, not as female entrepreneurs. Additionally, girls and women

suffered extreme hardship due to their exclusion during their menstrual cycles. These findings covered various topics, including child marriages, widow discrimination, and participants who were traumatized by in-laws. The participants also discussed their husbands' lack of affection and support in their lives. Socio-cultural factors negatively impacted women's daily lives and entrepreneurial ambitions (Gajurel, 2015). For example, women in Nepal are subject to a strict male guardianship system (Basnet, 2016).

1.5.2 Lack of easy access to financial resource

This barrier is essential in the study, supporting the literature's initial findings (see Section 5.2.24). According to the literature review, while easy access to financial resources is a significant barrier to women's entrepreneurship globally (Coleman, 2004), it is a vital barrier for entrepreneurs in Nepal (Dhakal, 2006). However, adequate funding may be a significant stumbling block for any entrepreneur, especially women. For female entrepreneurs, accessing finance is a barrier (Hampel, 2010). Both men and women face these barriers, but due to the significant conflict between family and job issues, women are more likely to receive inadequate initial funds for their proposed companies (Taiwo, Alege and Olokoyo, 2016).

Furthermore, because of the difficulties in obtaining funds, women are more likely than men to struggle with personal finance and less bank debt and personal savings (Rakhal, 2015). This study confirms that easy access to financial resources is the barrier for Nepalese women entrepreneurs, especially in short-term bank financing, crucial to their success. Most financial institutions could not accept loans for business expansion, requiring at least a five-year track record before even considering it. As a result, most of their companies begin with funds supported primarily by their friends, family members, and personal savings. Similarly, a lack of expansion capital was the most significant barrier to developing these women entrepreneurs' enterprises. Many women entrepreneurs in Kathmandu have been unable to grow their companies due to a shortage of funding. As a result, expansion capital is critical for any company seeking to unwind and seize opportunities (Luitel, 2001).

1.5.3 Legal Constraints

In Nepal, both men and women are discouraged from starting companies due to legal constraints (Hawkes et al., 2013). This argument confirmed the results of this study (see Section 5.2.2.2). Many of these restrictions apply to both female and male entrepreneurs. Still, women entrepreneurs face unique challenges resulting from deeply rooted discriminatory sociocultural norms and practices embedded in legislation, legal frameworks, and social support systems. By focusing on skills and equality, communities with greater inclusion and access to law and order may be more accessible to working women, leading to a more significant number of career opportunities for women (Tavosoli et al., 2022).

According to this report, legal restrictions are a barrier to women entrepreneurs in Nepal. Certain specific issues in the area restrict women's right to operate freely, such as the need to obtain male consent for some legal papers or even travel in some instances. In Kathmandu, registering a company for aspiring entrepreneurs was slow and inefficient. Furthermore, the registration process is too complicated and expensive due to corruption. Again, several participants thought the cost of registering a company was high. These findings mean that steps to speed up the registration process and minimize the cost of doing business are necessary. These problems prevent young women entrepreneurs from pursuing careers in Kathmandu and other parts of Nepal.

1.5.4 Lack of adequate training & development programmes and access to basic education

A lack of adequate training and development programmes and access to basic education is another critical barrier to women entrepreneurs' career progression in Nepal's food industry (see Section 5.2.2.1). In addition, sons have more preference to pursue their education over daughters in typical Nepalese families. Therefore, it will be challenging for a woman to succeed as an entrepreneur due to inadequate skills and education (Samuels & Ghimire, 2013).

Even though women are permitted to undertake higher education and graduate studies in Nepal, the social empowerment needed to increase their learning experiences is lacking. In schools and colleges, there is sex separation, meaning gender division (Ikupolati et al., 2017). As a result, women's facilities are typically smaller, and class sizes are more significant than men. However, this research reveals that entrepreneurs may succeed without formal education, while traditional education could benefit entrepreneurship. Since the easiest way to learn

entrepreneurship is through experience, including informal learning experiences from family members also assist in the growth of entrepreneurial prospects (Botha, 2014).

Furthermore, according to this study, while women in Nepal have access to training and development programmes, perhaps even more so than males, barriers do remain. As the interviews revealed, some areas get neglected, and women entrepreneurs' specialised training to succeed in business is typically unavailable.

7.5.5 Work-family Interface

The ability to balance work and family commitments remains one of the most significant career barriers women faces (see section 5.2.2.5). As a result, women turn to self-employment to gain greater autonomy and independence over their job and personal lives as they strive to achieve a better work-life balance.

In Nepal, women entrepreneurs face more significant challenges managing business and family commitments because they are responsible for family care and work, and family roles are formalized based on traditional gender roles (Guttek et al.,1991). According to these stereotypical gender roles, men are breadwinners and women are housewives, implying that motherhood is less versatile than fatherhood because of the social construction of gender (Noor, 2010).

As a result, women in Nepal undertake traditional roles in society, with their main contribution being caring for the family and raising children (Shinnar, Giacomini & Janssen, 2012). Women entrepreneurship in Nepal, on the other hand, has been steadily gaining traction and recognition since the turn of the century, when more and more women are moving out of their conventional positions and expressing desires to contribute to society in ways other than raising a family (Tlaiss & Kauser, 2011).

7.5.6 Additional Barriers

Apart from the five barriers found to be significant in this research (see section 5.5.3.6), the researcher found four other challenges from the triangulation results carried out in Chapter six

that affect the business involvement by women entrepreneurs in Nepal's food industry: *lack of entrepreneurial* mindset, Networking, Skills constraints, and Advisor/mentoring.

The entrepreneurial mindset of women entrepreneurs in Nepal is a significant barrier found in this study. Since Nepal is a culturally embedded country, society teaches women to divide their roles based on gender. Hence, it is evident that women from a child lack confidence in doing something different from men. Especially in entrepreneurship, women need to have lots of courage, support from family, curiosity, perseverance, and strong-mindedness to enter the entrepreneurship world, which most women lack. Despite the changing world and exposure to media, women entrepreneurs still face their entrepreneurial mindset to compete and expand their business as a crucial barrier. This study found that this barrier hinders their progression or even runs the business in Nepal's context (Vosseberg, 2013).

Likewise, networking is another barrier found in the study that hinders women entrepreneurs' career progression in Nepal. Networks provide information, a platform to find valuable business contacts, and support and advice. However, existing literature suggests that women entrepreneurs are not generally included in traditional networks or unaware of such networks, leading them to lose networking opportunities. Women entrepreneurs' reduced network activities also mean less information or access to potential business opportunities. From the findings, networking events were considered beneficial to women entrepreneurs; whilst most women entrepreneurs were very aware of the benefits of attending networking events, a small minority were not even aware of networking or how it could benefit their businesses or their lives. Nevertheless, they found them very useful in building their confidence and networks (Doss, 2010).

Another barrier is skilled constraints. Women often dismiss their entrepreneurial aspirations as they do not believe they have the required skills. The findings suggest that women lack skills when it comes to setting up a business. The level of skills seems to result from their previous work experience and education. The results also suggest that single women with no dependents are more skilled than dependent children. Children's needs and familial responsibilities are essential for several sample participants, and childcare facilities are always in high demand regardless of the location. The findings suggest a great need for organisational skills training and bookkeeping, accounting, and taxes. Female entrepreneurs lack information regarding the legal side of the business, such as intellectual property, trademarks, hiring employees, taxes,

government benefits. The findings indicate that entrepreneurship helped in empowering and adding skills in women. Women become skilful once they start their businesses successfully (Joshi, 2000).

Another primary conclusion of this research is that there is a requirement, and evidence of demand, for the further advisor/ mentoring to support female entrepreneurship in Nepal. Although remarkable progress has been made in recent years by the government and private enterprises in providing business support for women, there are still gaps in the pattern of female business support provision. There is evidence of the need for a government centre that delivers services directly to women entrepreneurs. Women entrepreneurs require advisors and mentor to advise based on their individual needs. Some participants in the study suggested having trained and experienced female advisers to provide support because they felt female advisers could empathise with their situations better than a male adviser. In the case of a few female entrepreneurs, cultural and religious barriers prevented them from using the services of male advisers (Subba et al., 2013).

7.6 Contributions of the Research

The contributions of this study are presented in under two sections which are mentioned below:

7.6.1 Theoretical Contribution

Numerous studies have investigated the significant barriers women entrepreneurs face, regardless of their nation of origin or industry. The findings of the current study support different approaches to barriers that women entrepreneurs face discussed in the literature, namely financial barriers, cultural barriers, gender barriers, family role barriers and laws constraints. This mixed-method study investigated the Nepalese food industry and collected data via surveys and interviews from diverse women entrepreneurs in Nepal for identifying the barriers that limit the involvement of women entrepreneurs in Nepal. This research identified five significant barriers: lack of adequate training and development programmes and basic education, legal constraints, lack of socio-cultural support, lack of easy access to financial resources, and the work-family interface. Although these barriers have been validated within Western cultures and other developing nations, exploring those established concepts in-depth in another context adds to the growing body of knowledge, specifically Nepal being a typical

patriarchal society and the business world being predominately dominated by male further contributes to knowledge. This research makes a theoretical contribution to the literature by empirically identifying barriers to successful women entrepreneurs that limits women entrepreneurs' involvement in business activities in the Nepalese food industry. The discussions of the findings are presented in chapter 6, indicate that these contributions may be generalised to the food industry and other industries in Nepal in general. If addressed, these challenges may offer better opportunities for women entrepreneurs in Nepal to engage in entrepreneurship and grow their businesses.

7.6.2 Practical Contributions

Based on the women entrepreneur's perspective explored in this study, this study provides insights into Nepal's policymakers, government, and business development officers. The findings are original since they are based on the analysis of primary data gathered specifically for this study. The aim of exploring the link between these five career barriers and women entrepreneurs is to see if the results will give any ideas about overcoming those barriers and increasing women's entrepreneurial activities in Nepal.

Some of the vital practical contributions of this doctoral research are presented below:

7.6.2.1 Relationship between adequate training & development programmes and access to basic education and involvement in business activities by women entrepreneurs in Nepal

It is clear from section 5.3.21 that adequate training and basic education play a significant role in the success of entrepreneurs in general and women entrepreneurs. The degree to which training and education impact business activities to successful women entrepreneurship in Nepal are still unclear. However, evidence in the literature states that required training and a basic level of education influence the career progression of women entrepreneurs in Nepal. As a result, the research hypothesis is as follows:

A: A lack of adequate training & development programmes and access to basic education affects business activities to women entrepreneurship in Nepal.

7.6.2.2 Relationship between legal constraints and involvement in business activities by women entrepreneurs in Nepal

As seen in section 5.3.2.2, legal constraints impact entrepreneurs, especially women having a more significant impact than men. Since Nepalese laws vary from those in other countries, it is essential to understand how legal restrictions impact women entrepreneurs in Nepal. This study aims to explore this issue, and the following hypothesis are proposed:

B: Legal constraints limits business activities to women entrepreneurship in Nepal.

7.6.2.3 Relationship between lack of socio-cultural support and involvement in business activities by women entrepreneurs in Nepal

It is evident from section 5.3.2.3 that this barrier has significant consequences. Many aspects of Nepalese society, including religion, impose restraints on men and women. These limitations are more severe for women than for men. Similarly, the social system has consequences for the assistance received by women entrepreneurs in Nepal. Since it is a significant hindrance for women entrepreneurs, it plays an essential role in caring for their families, and their success links to the success of their families rather than their businesses. As a result, cultural constraints and a lack of social support become significant roadblocks in the path to successful women entrepreneurship in Nepal. The following is a possible hypothesis:

C: Lack of socio-cultural support hinders business activities by women entrepreneurship s in Nepal.

7.6.2.4 Relationship between lack of easy access to financial resources and involvement in business activities by women entrepreneurs in Nepal

As shown in chapter 2 and section 5.3.2.4, the literature review clearly states that financial constraints are significant career barriers that women entrepreneurs face. In addition, Carter & Kolvereid (1997) found that women had more significant limitations in accessing personal savings, given more punctuated and interrupted work histories and lower remuneration patterns. their entrepreneurial dreams.

Similarly, Nepal must change its antagonistic attitude toward female entrepreneurs and avoid written and unwritten social norms that limit women's entrepreneurial endeavours. Instead, the necessary support must enable female entrepreneurs to start and run their businesses successfully. Finally, Nepalese societies must recognise the excellent contributions to society and their communities (Madichie & Gallant, 2012).

Hence, as a result, the following hypothesis for the research is as follows:

D: Lack of access to financial resources affects business activities by women entrepreneurship in Nepal.

7.6.2.5 Relationship between work-family and involvement in business activities by women entrepreneurs in Nepal

It is evident from the literature review and section 5.3.2.5 that work-family balance is a significant career barrier to entrepreneurs in general. However, due to the social structure and Nepalese culture, this barrier adds more to women entrepreneurs in Nepal who had always faced this barrier. Patriarchy acts through hierarchical control structures in the family context, whereby age and gender significantly influence the freedom to make entrepreneurial choices and access household labour and resources (Viswanathan, Gajendiran & Venkatesan, 2008).

There have been no thorough studies of how such barriers affect women entrepreneurs in Nepal. Therefore, the following hypothesis needs testing:

E: The work-family interface affects women entrepreneurship to conduct business in Nepal.

In addition to the above, the conceptual framework built for this study (see Figure 9) has been statistically validated and supports the arguments presented above. On the other hand, this study identified new barriers that women entrepreneurs in Nepal face. The study uncovered four barriers that have not been commonly discussed in the extant literature about the context of developed countries, namely *Mindset, Networking, Skills constraints, and Advisor/mentoring* through interviews with women entrepreneurs in Nepal. These should be added to the list of barriers that women entrepreneurs in Nepal face. This research offers a better understanding of the career barriers faced by women entrepreneurs and how they impact involvement in business activities. As a result, the findings of this study have made practical contributions by demonstrating an understanding of the different barriers faced by women entrepreneurs engaged in business activities in Nepal.

7.7 Recommendations

The final objective (c) of this study was to recommend grassroots solutions on overcoming the identified barriers and uplift the status of women entrepreneurship in the Nepalese food industry. To meet this objective the researcher has presented this section and divided in two sections which is presented as follows:

7.7.1 Recommendations for the identified barriers from this study

7.7.1.1 Enhancing women entrepreneurship education and skills development

According to Singh (2021), one of the significant barriers to women entrepreneurship is a lack of training, education, mentoring, networking, marketing skills, mindset, and professional skills. This study also reveals that most women face these barriers limiting their business involvement. Ganesan et al. (2021) and Vazirani & Bhattacharjee (2021) also emphasize the importance of the skills and training needed to become women entrepreneurs. However, the findings in this study reveal that not all participants had prior training, received support and access to education prior to starting their business. Therefore, there is a need for programs solely focused on women entrepreneurs' development that offers all the necessary skills, education, and training related to start-ups to developing a business. By offering these programs, women entrepreneurs can learn about the appropriate technologies and how to cope with competitive markets that can help them succeed in any business setting. Also, women entrepreneurs should be aware of their weaknesses and development needs and improve their competencies. A proactive woman entrepreneur can only manage to organize and improve rather than inactive ones.

To summarise, there is a need for general entrepreneurship skills training at a mixture of levels and in a range of subjects that would cater to business start-up and growth needs. Besides, this study's findings support delivering courses and agencies with partnership building and awareness-raising in women's minds. The agencies can help by enhancing networks, offering access to events and training, and providing a source of inspirational, positive role models. The courses would reinforce positive role models, highlight best practices and establish strong networks and routes to business support.

7.7.1.2 Improve credit facilities.

Access to finance and credit is one of women entrepreneurs' significant barriers. This study reveals that most samples used their saving to start a business. Hence, women entrepreneurs face most significant barriers to gaining finance from formal financial channels. According to Chu, Kara & Benzing, (2018), lack of finance stands as a significant constraint due to social structure and customs, women's limited inheritance, illiteracy, lack of awareness and even suspicion of new institutions. Also, this research revealed that most women entrepreneurs started businesses from their savings. Therefore, if a women entrepreneur uses her saving for her business activities, then there is a high chance of less involvement in further business activities. Hence, this study recommends that easy access to finance programs should be promoted, and workshops for banks and other financial institutions should be conducted regularly to learn about women entrepreneurs' needs and boost their confidence in financial institutions.

Furthermore, providing financial incentives to women entrepreneurs to cover their expenses can enable them to fully concentrate on their idea and actively engage rather than holding a part-time job to sustain themselves during the research phase. Implementing a credit program is also beneficial to check the business cycle and then offer a loan or credit to women entrepreneurs. It can increase trust between financial institutions and women entrepreneurs.

7.7.1.3 Ensuring Mentorship

According to the study by Yadav, Sarangdevot & Sharma (2019), positive mentoring like peer support, business enterprise champions and business mentors (male or female) can also build confidence in women to fight social stigma. Women should have the opportunity to select their mentors. It will ensure that mentors are suited to the mentee's expectations of experience, credibility, and relevance.

The findings from this study reveal that a lack of mentoring is one of the significant barriers to women entrepreneurs. Hence, this study recommends that professional mentors support women in advising, providing professional experience, feedback, and mental support. In addition, a concise set of rules detailing the mentorship process may be helpful as well expectations for

both mentors and mentees at the beginning of the contract could be useful for both mentors and the tenant entrepreneurs.

7.7.2 Recommendations on implications including theoretical / conceptual, managerial, government implications

7.7.2.1 Create online platform

The business registration process is very complex in Nepal. There is no place where women entrepreneurs can get all the information needed to register their business (Brixiova & Kangoye, 2021). This study also found that the legal requirements to start or get involved in business, especially for women, are very complex.

Based on this finding, the researcher recommends that an online platform with all the rules, regulations, policies, and procedures of business registration in one place where women entrepreneurs are provided with required training must be provided to enhance and boost women entrepreneurship. This can be achieved if the country's government change the legal processes by lowering business registration costs for entrepreneurs and speeding up the process. Knowledge and procedures should be coordinated effectively and transparently by such authorities. This might inspire more female aspirant entrepreneurs to step out and start their businesses, thus contributing significantly to the country's economy.

Regarding business legislation, registration conditions and licenses should be precisely specified, and tax exemption for less than a year old should be considered, as the revenue raised from tax amnesty may be used to help them grow their businesses.

7.7.2.2 Improving Access to Finance

Many researchers such as Malla & Chhetri (2021), K.C. et al. (2011) and Tripathi (2012) has stressed the importance of finance in building women entrepreneurship. The country's government should adopt various entrepreneurship plans coordinated with multiple stakeholders and correctly applied providing an easy access to finance. However, banks and

other microfinance institutions cannot take advantage of the situation by introducing high capital costs in their offerings.

Therefore, this research suggests that the development of financial literacy training programs to empower women and inclusion of financial literacy in school curriculums should be implemented. It can contribute to women entrepreneurs learning and understanding of finance, which can be helpful in their ventures. There is a need for lobbying to ensure strict subsidized and collateral-free loans for women with solid monitoring and feedback mechanisms. The country's government should partner with Venture capitalists to allocate funds to venture capitals and business incubators to incubate Women-centric companies that aim to provide green solutions to the people.

7.7.2.3 Optimizing the Regulatory Environment

The socio-cultural barriers are the significant barriers for women entrepreneurs which is proved from the findings of this research. Therefore, it is recommended to adopt an explicit 'zero tolerance policy toward all forms of violence. Safe, clean, respectful working environments where women can freely commit their time and energy to business activities. Women should also be valued and appreciated because it motivates them to perform even better. The value of women's unpaid work to families and communities needs to be acknowledged by offering tax deductions and providing subsidies for care infrastructure development (Lakshmi & Vidya, 2019). Therefore, this study suggests the government to fully factor familial care into the social policies such as maternity leaves and childcare expenses.

Furthermore, the policymakers, government, business incubators should promote sole ownership registration for women entrepreneurs with a holistic and simplified approach. An alternative would be to assist joint ownership registration for microenterprises; wife-husband (or other types of female-male family members) with simplification and cost reduction of registration processes in areas where limited asset ownership by women is a significant bottleneck. Based on the feedback from the participants of this study, it is recommended that the government update the curriculum and teachers educate a student in entrepreneurial skills. Universities can also have business incubators and advisors in their learning environments to help budding and other entrepreneurs and include entrepreneurship courses in their curricula.

7.7.2.4 Promoting Awareness and Networking

There is a need to promote women in entrepreneurship to recover the trade deficit of Nepal. Domestic, regional, and national and international networking opportunities for women entrepreneurs also help facilitate access to domestic and international trade fairs, arts, and crafts bazaars (Mahat, 2018). Hence, this study proposes the government should consider allocating funds to subsidize participation in trade fairs, the provision of export intelligence, and other export promotion activities that specifically target women SMEs.

Furthermore, this study also proposes promoting clustering and networking for women producer groups to access services collectively, which they might not purchase as individual entrepreneurs due to societal norms. There is a need to pool resources for a central buying office for different types of women entrepreneurial products/services. Women's entrepreneurship growth should be a priority for the Nepalese government. Such programs should have customised business planning services to help entrepreneurs grow their businesses. Business coaching, counselling, training, financing, mentoring, and incubators are only a few examples. Support from NGOs, international NGOs, technical colleges, and the Nepalese government should be partnered for these business development programs. To promote sustainable business development and growth in women-owned enterprises, the government should establish an effective and productive support system to foster business growth.

7.8 Future Research

The researcher can conclude that more study is required to fill some of the gaps in this field of research based on the study's conclusions and findings. The findings of this small-scale study show some of the biggest challenges and questions that women food entrepreneurs in the Kathmandu valley encounter on a daily basis (Kathmandu, Bhaktapur & Lalitpur). A more in-depth study conducted in various areas of Nepal, with people of various ethnicities, castes, and languages from various parts of the nation, could yield more information about Nepalese women entrepreneurs.

More research is needed to examine the factors influencing women's entrepreneurship in other communities, so future studies may give a broader perspective of South Asian countries with characteristics that differ from Nepal. This aligns with the calls of a variety of authors for further

research into the importance of culture in contemporary entrepreneurship, as well as the various modes of entrepreneurship that might emerge in the future when Western cultural norms are less dominant (Huggins & Thompson, 2014). The current research is limited to the Nepalese food industries. So, future studies should also focus on the entrepreneur of other sectors like Aviation and Information Technology.

The current research does not examine the financial success of women-owned businesses. Future research should look at whether training, age or qualifications impact a company's financial results. Research needs to be conducted using performance-based data like sales, profit, growth, etc. Successful and unsuccessful businesses owned by woman entrepreneurs can be analysed. A comparison of working styles, education levels, training, support, and other factors can be made based on the research, providing insight into the success and failure factors. A study that examines how entrepreneurship has influenced women entrepreneurs. What has improved in their social and economic situation? It is possible to report on the social implications of women's entrepreneurship. This research would not address how policy changes impact women-owned businesses, so a study that contrasts performance-based data with policy changes should be conducted.

7.9 Closing remarks and Self-reflection

This research aimed to explore career barriers to successful women entrepreneurship in Nepal's food industry and provide recommendations on overcoming these barriers. To start this thesis, the journey I had planned initially wholly changed at a later stage. I intended to adopt a realist approach to identify those barriers to all the women entrepreneurs in Nepal. However, my ideas and experience changed from what I founded in business research.

I have become more aware of Nepalese women entrepreneurs and their situation. I realise that there are different ways to interpret reality. With this fruitful research, I aim to provide recommendations to the government of Nepal to develop and promote women entrepreneurship in Nepal. I connected with many successful women entrepreneurs and business organisations in Nepal. Implementing the mixed method, I explored many new barriers that were not studied before.

Finally, I have learnt that research involves much effort, and a more disciplined approach is needed to complete the task at hand. I learned from this research journey that entrepreneurship is a vehicle for female economic empowerment and autonomy, especially for women from deprived backgrounds affected by social, gender, familial, ethnic, and racial inequality in society. Although studies describing and evaluating policies and initiatives to encourage women into the enterprise are gaining popularity, it is still a minor theme in the female entrepreneurship literature. Given the contribution of entrepreneurship to female empowerment, I plan on continuing research and writing about female entrepreneurship while simultaneously helping women launch and grow their businesses.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Participation information and consent form

“Exploring career barriers to successful women entrepreneurship in the food industry of Nepal and how to overcome these barriers”.

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

You are invited to consider taking part in the study mentioned above. Please read this information sheet and, if you wish, discuss it with others before deciding whether to participate. Please email the researcher using the information at the bottom of this sheet if you have any questions or would like more information.

PURPOSE OF THE RESEARCH

The research aims are to explore the barriers of women entrepreneurship in the food industry of Nepal which hinders their career progression as being a woman and how to overcome these identified barriers. This builds on previous studies made on women entrepreneurs and the challenges or hurdles they face in the specific business environment.

You have been approached because you are a women entrepreneurs of Nepal involved in food industry, which is where the research is being conducted. All women entrepreneurs of Nepal in food industry are eligible to participate. It's entirely up to you. If you decide to participate but then change your mind, you can withdraw at any time during the research for up to 15 days after it ends.

METHODS OF PARTICIPATION

There are two-parts part A to complete survey questionnaire or part B to have 20-45 mins long interview. But you will be asked to participate only in one part which will be decided by the researcher.

Part A: If you were requested to submit a response to the questionnaire survey, then it will take 10 mins long questions. You will be asked to provide few basic demographic questions like age, marital status whilst the other questions are totally based on the barriers identified, you will only have to tick on the statements you agree or disagree.

Part B: If you are requested to provide 20-45 mins long interview, then the researcher will fix an appointment with you based on your availability. Then the researcher will provide you with the link to join video call with or without video on. Due to covid-19, there will be no face-to-face interviews due to safety precautions.

FINDINGS AND BENEFITS OF THE RESEARCH

It is not assured that participating in the study would result in any direct benefits. However, the study would be able to identify the barriers to women entrepreneurs to complete this thesis and conduct successful research.

POSSIBLE RISKS

It is unlikely that you will feel any disadvantages or discomfort because of participating in the study. If it's an interview, you'll be asked to share your thoughts on the barriers that women entrepreneurs face in Nepal, or you'll be asked to share your journey and the hurdles you've encountered. Please let me know if any of the questions make you feel uncomfortable. We can pause the interview for a few seconds, you can skip a topic, and you can opt out at any point while still participating in any part of the study.

PRIVACY PROTECTION

Any of the information gathered during this study will be kept exclusively confidential. Following data collection, all data would be de-identified to ensure privacy by using codes instead of names to identify participants. Throughout the research process, paper documents and electronic files which has been collected will also be stored **on a password protected and encrypted in UWS One Drive platform**. Any documents and videos used to collect evidence will be destroyed after the study is completed.

It is entirely up to you to decide whether to take part in this research. If you do decide to take part, a consent form will be provided for you to sign. Should you require any further information, please do not hesitate to contact me provided at the end of Participant Consent Form.

Thank you for reading this information sheet and I hope you will help me complete my study with your valuable participation.

PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM

University of the West of Scotland Ethics reference no.: 13970- 13631

Participant name or Study ID Number:

Title of Project: Exploring career barriers to successful women entrepreneurship in the food industry of Nepal and how to overcome these barriers.

Researcher: Lasta Dangol

Please answer the following questions by ticking the response that applies:

	YES	NO
1. I have read the Information Sheet for this study and have had details of the study explained to me.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. My questions about the study have been answered to my satisfaction and I understand that I may ask further questions at any point.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. I understand that I am free to withdraw from the study within the time limits outlined in the Information Sheet, without giving a reason for my withdrawal or to decline to answer any questions in the study without any consequences to my future treatment by the researcher.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. I agree to provide information to the researchers under the conditions of confidentiality set out in the Information Sheet.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. I wish to participate in the study under the conditions set out in the Information Sheet.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

"नेपालको खाद्य उद्योगमा सफल महिला उद्यमशीलताका लागि क्यारियर अवरोधहरू अन्वेषण र यी अवरोधहरूलाई कसरी हटाउने"।

साझी जानकारी पत्रक

तपाईंलाई माथि उल्लेखित अध्ययनमा भाग लिन विचार गर्न आमन्त्रित गरिएको छ। कृपया यो सूचना पाना पढ्नुहोस् र, यदि तपाईं चाहनुहुन्छ भने, भाग लिने वा नगर्ने निर्णय गर्नु अघि अरूसँग छलफल गर्नुहोस्। कृपया यस पानाको तल रहेको जानकारी प्रयोग गरेर अनुसन्धानकर्तालाई ईमेल गर्नुहोस् यदि तपाईंसँग केही प्रश्नहरू छन् वा बढि जानकारी चाहनुहुन्छ भने।

अनुसन्धानको उद्देश्य

अनुसन्धानको उद्देश्य भनेको नेपालको खाद्य उद्योगमा महिला उद्यमशीलताका अवरोधहरूको अन्वेषण गर्नु हो जसले महिलाको रूपमा उनीहरूको क्यारियरको प्रगतिमा बाधा पुऱ्याउँछ र ती पहिचान गरिएका अवरोधहरूलाई कसरी पार गर्ने। यो महिला उद्यमीहरू मा बनाइएको अधिल्लो अध्ययन मा बनाउछ र चुनौतिहरू वा अवरोधहरू को विशिष्ट व्यापार वातावरण मा उनीहरूले सामना गर्छन्।

तपाईंसँग सम्पर्क गरिएको छ किनभने तपाईं खाद्यान्न उद्योगमा संलग्न नेपालका महिला उद्यमी हुनुहुन्छ, जहाँ यो अनुसन्धान भइरहेको छ। खाद्य उद्योगमा नेपालका सबै महिला उद्यमीहरू यसमा भाग लिन योग्य छन्। यो पूर्ण रूपमा तपाईंमा निर्भर छ। यदि तपाईं भाग लिने निर्णय गर्नुहुन्छ तर आफ्नो विचार परिवर्तन गर्नुभयो भने, तपाईं अनुसन्धानको बखत कुनै पनि फिर्ता लिन सक्नुहुन्छ १ 15 दिन सम्म यसको अन्त्य भएपछि।

पार्टीलिस्टेशनका विधिहरू

सर्वेक्षण प्रश्नपत्र पूरा गर्न दुई भाग A वा भाग बीमा २०-4545 मिनेट लामो अन्तर्वार्ता हुन्छ। तर तपाईंलाई केवल एउटा भागमा भाग लिनको लागि सोधिनेछ जुन अनुसन्धानकर्ताले निर्णय लिने छ।

भाग A: यदि तपाईंलाई प्रश्नावली सर्वेक्षणमा प्रतिक्रिया बुझाउन अनुरोध गरिएको थियो भने, यसले १० मिनेट लामो प्रश्नहरू लिनेछ। तपाईंलाई उमेर, वैवाहिक स्थिति जस्ता केही आधारभूत जनसांख्यिकीय प्रश्नहरू प्रदान गर्न सोधिनेछ जहाँ अन्य प्रश्नहरू पूर्ण रूपमा पहिचान गरिएका बाधाहरूमा आधारित हुन्छन्, तपाईंले केवल तपाईंले सहमत गर्नुहुने वा असहमति व्यक्त गरेको बयानहरूमा जाँच गर्नुपर्नेछ।

भाग बी: यदि तपाईंलाई २०-4545 मिनेट लामो अन्तर्वार्ता प्रदान गर्न अनुरोध गरिएको छ भने अनुसन्धानकर्ताले तपाईंको उपलब्धताको आधारमा तपाईंलाई भेट्ने समय मिलाउनेछ। त्यसोभए अन्वेषकले तपाईंलाई लिंक कल प्रदान गर्दछ भिडियो कलमा वा बिना भिडियो कलमा सामेल हुना कोविड १ to को कारणले, सुरक्षा सावधानीका कारण अन्तर्वार्ताको अनुहार हुने छैन।

खोज र खोजीको फाइदाहरू

यो आश्वासन छैन कि अध्ययनमा भाग लिएर कुनै प्रत्यक्ष लाभ हुनेछ। यद्यपि उक्त अध्ययनले महिला अनुसन्धान सम्पन्न गर्न र सफल अनुसन्धान गर्न महिला उद्यमीहरूका लागि अवरोधहरू पहिचान गर्न सक्दछ।

सम्भावित जोखिमहरू

यो अध्ययनमा भाग लिने परिणाम स्वरूप तपाईंलाई कुनै पनि बेफाइदा वा असुविधा महसुस हुने सम्भावना छैन। यदि यो एक अन्तर्वार्ता हो भने, तपाईंलाई महिला उद्यमीहरूले नेपालमा सामना गर्ने अवरोधहरूको बारेमा आफ्ना विचारहरू साझा गर्न सोधिनेछ, वा तपाईंलाई आफ्नो यात्रा र तपाईंले सामना गरेका अवरोधहरू

साझा गर्न आग्रह गरिनेछ। कृपया मलाई मलाई थाहा दिनुहोस् यदि कुनै प्रश्नले तपाईंलाई असहज महसुस गराउँदछ। हामी केही सेकेन्डको लागि अन्तर्वार्ता रोक्न सक्छौं, तपाईं एक विषय छोड्न सक्नुहुन्छ, र तपाईं अध्ययनको कुनै पनि भागमा भाग लिइरहेको बेला कुनै पनि बिन्दुमा अप्ट आउट गर्न सक्नुहुन्छ।

गोपनीयता संरक्षण

यस अध्ययनको दौरान भेला भएका कुनै पनि जानकारीलाई गोप्य रूपमा राखिनेछ। डेटा स्कलनको अनुसरण गर्दै, सबै डेटा सहभागीहरूको पहिचान गर्नका लागि नामको सट्टा कोड प्रयोग गरेर गोपनीयता सुनिश्चित गर्न डि-पहिचान हुनेछ। अनुसन्धान प्रक्रियाको क्रममा, कागज कागजातहरू र इलेक्ट्रोनिक फाइलहरू जुन स्कलन गरिएको छ त्यो पनि पासवर्डमा भण्डार हुनेछ र पासवर्ड सुरक्षित र यूडब्ल्यूएस ड्राइभ प्लेटफर्ममा ईन्क्रिप्टेड हुनेछ। प्रमाणहरू स्कलन गर्न प्रयोग गरिएका कुनै पनि कागजातहरू र भिडियोहरू अध्ययन समाप्त भए पछि नष्ट हुनेछन्।

यो अनुसन्धानमा भाग लिने कि नगर्ने भन्ने निर्णय लिनु तपाईंको पूरै निर्भरता हो। यदि तपाईंले भाग लिने निर्णय गर्नुभयो भने, तपाईंलाई हस्ताक्षर गर्न एक स्वीकृति फारम प्रदान गरिनेछ। यदि तपाईंलाई कुनै थप जानकारीको आवश्यक छ भने, कृपया मलाई सहमति फारमको अन्त्यमा प्रदान गरिएको मसँग सम्पर्क गर्न नहिचकिचाउनुहोस्।

यस जानकारी पाना पढ्नको लागि धन्यवाद र मलाई आशा छ कि तपाईंले मलाई आफ्नो बहुमूल्य सहभागितामा मेरो अध्ययन पूर्ण गर्न मद्दत गर्नुहुनेछ।

पार्टिसिपन्ट कन्सेन्ट फारम

स्कटल्याण्ड नैतिकता को पश्चिम को विश्वविद्यालय सन्दर्भ संख्या: 13970- 13631

सहभागीको नाम वा अध्ययन आईडी नम्बर:

परियोजनाको शीर्षक: नेपालको खाद्य उद्योगमा सफल महिला उद्यमशीलताका लागि क्यारियर अवरोधहरू अन्वेषण र यी अवरोधहरूलाई कसरी पार गर्ने।

अन्वेषक: लस्ता डंगोल

कृपया तलका प्रश्नहरूको उत्तर दिनुहोस् जुन लागू हुन्छ भनेर टिकट गरेर:

	हो	होईन
यस अध्ययनका लागि मैले सूचना पाना पढेको छु र अध्ययनको विवरण मलाई बुझाइएको छ।	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
अध्ययनका बारेमा मेरा प्रश्नहरू मेरो सन्तुष्टिलाई जवाफ दिइयो र म बुझ्छु कि म कुनै पनि बिन्दुमा थप प्रश्नहरू सोध्न सक्छु।	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
म बुझ्छु कि सूचना पानामा उल्लिखित समयावधिभित्र अध्ययनबाट फिर्ता लिन म स्वतन्त्र छु, मलाई फिर्ता लिने कारण नदिई वा अध्ययनले कुनै खास प्रश्नको उत्तर दिन अस्वीकार गरेको भएमा मेरो भविष्यको उपचारको कुनै परिणाम नपरोसा।	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
अन्वेषक		
म सूचना पानामा उल्लेख गरिएका गोपनीयता शर्तहरूमा अनुसन्धानकर्ताहरूलाई सूचना प्रदान गर्न सहमत छु।	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
म सूचना पानामा तोकिएका सर्तहरूको अन्तर्गत अध्ययनमा भाग लिन चाहन्छु।	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Subject: Exploring career barriers to successful women entrepreneurship in food industry of Nepal and how to over these barriers.

I very much hope that you will agree to take part in some research into this important area. The information that you provide will help us to better understand the career barriers to successful women entrepreneurship of food industry in Nepal. If you agree, I shall interview you. The interview will last approximately one hour. It will be audio-taped. Your name will not be recorded/used.

I can confirm that the information collected will be accessed ONLY by me and will be used ONLY for research purposes. The results are anonymous and will be kept confidential. If you have any desire to view the results of this study, it will be my pleasure to provide you with a copy of the executive summary at the end of the research.

Please inform me if you would like to participate in this research. If so, an email will be sent to you along with the briefing on the purpose of this research. If you have any questions you wish to ask, please do not hesitate to contact me through email [REDACTED] or my direct contact number [REDACTED]

Thank you, and I very much hope that you will agree to assist in this important research into something which, I am sure, is close to your heart, that is, helping to understand the challenges of women like yourself.

Personal details withheld.

Lasta Dangol

DBA Researcher

अन्तर्वार्ता प्रोटोकल र प्रश्नहरू

प्रिय अन्तर्वार्ता,

विषय: नेपालको खाद्य उद्योगमा सफल महिला उद्यमशीलता र यी अवरोधहरू कसरी हटाउने भन्नेमा क्यारियर अवरोधहरू अन्वेषण गर्दै।

म धेरै आशा गर्दछु कि तपाईं यस महत्वपूर्ण क्षेत्रमा केही अनुसन्धानमा भाग लिन सहमत हुनुहुनेछ। तपाईंले दिनु भएको सूचनाले हामीलाई नेपालमा खाद्य उद्योगको सफल महिला उद्यमशीलतामा क्यारियर अवरोधहरू राम्रोसँग बुझ्न मद्दत गर्दछ। यदि तपाईं सहमत हुनुहुन्छ भने, म तपाईंलाई अन्तर्वार्ता दिनेछु। अन्तर्वार्ता करीव एक घण्टा लामो हुनेछ। यो अडियो-ट्याप हुनेछ। तपाईंको नाम रेकर्ड / प्रयोग गरिने छैन।

म पुष्टि गर्न सक्दछु कि एकत्रित गरिएको जानकारी म द्वारा मात्र पहुँच गरिन्छ र अनुसन्धानका लागि मात्र प्रयोग गरिनेछ। परिणाम अज्ञात छन् र गोप्य राखिनेछ। यदि तपाईंसँग यस अध्ययनको परिणामहरू हेर्नको लागि केही इच्छा छ भने, यो अनुसन्धानको अन्त्यमा तपाईंलाई कार्यकारी सारांशको एक प्रति उपलब्ध गराउन खुशी हुनेछ।

कृपया मलाई सूचित गर्नुहोस् यदि तपाईं यस अनुसन्धानमा भाग लिन चाहानुहुन्छ। यदि त्यसो हो भने, यस शोधको उद्देश्यको बारेमा ब्रीफिंगको साथ तपाईंलाई एक ईमेल पठाइनेछ। यदि तपाईंलाई केहि प्रश्न सोध्नु छ भने कृपया मलाई ईमेल [REDACTED] वा मेरो सिधा सम्पर्क नम्बर [REDACTED] मा फर्त सम्पर्क गर्न नहिचकिचाउनुहोस्।

धन्यवाद, र मलाई धेरै आशा छ कि तपाईं यस महत्वपूर्ण अनुसन्धानमा सहयोग गर्न सहमत हुनुहुनेछ जुन मलाई पक्का छ, तपाईंको मुटुको नजिक छ, त्यो हो, तपाईं जस्तो महिलाको चुनौतीहरूलाई बुझ्न मद्दत गर्ने।

Personal details withheld.

Lasta Dangol

DBA Researcher

Appendix 3: Survey questionnaire

“Exploring career barriers of women entrepreneurs in the food industry of Nepal and how to overcome these barriers.”

Please tick from the option.

Part One: This is about you

1. Age

- 18-25
- 26-35
- 36-45
- 46-55
- 56+

2. Relationship Status

- Single
- Engaged
- Married
- Separated
- Widow

3. How many children do you have?

- 1-2 children
- 3-5 children
- Not applicable

4. Educational Attainment level

- High school
- Diploma
- Bachelor
- Postgraduate

6. How long have you been in this business?

- 1-2 years
- 3-5 years
- 5-8 years
- 8 years +

7. Did you have any prior training to develop this business?

- Yes
- No

Part Two: About the topic

Identified Barriers (Independent variable)	SD	D	N	A	SA
1. Lack of career guidance hinders business participation by women entrepreneurs to access various public and private offered support services, including business development services and information on business growth.					
1. Many women entrepreneurs lack the skills and education needed to set up and run their businesses.					
2. Even the educated women are provided either less or inadequate education than their male counterparts partly due to marriage					
3. The sex segregation policies in educational facilities limit the learning experience of women entrepreneurs.					

4. Business licensing is an of women entrepreneurs as the process is lengthy and complex, excessive bureaucracy, and in some cases demands for bribes by officials.					
5. Laws and practices discriminate between women and men.					
6. Legal constraints are barriers to women entrepreneurs in Nepal.					
7. Most women lack entrepreneurial skills in terms of administrations, marketing, accounts, and public relations.					
8. There is a lack of coordination between government departments regarding business procedures that help women entrepreneurs.					
9. Laws and regulations restricting women from getting a license without their husbands' permission limit their business involvement.					
10. Complications with import and export laws limit women's involvement in the business.					
11. Foreign relations with other countries that result in bureaucratic hurdles limit women's involvement in the business.					
12. There is a lack of government support for women entrepreneurs regarding laws and regulations.					
13. High rates of insurance, taxes, and duties limit women's involvement in the business.					
14. There is a lack of suitable models to represent successful women entrepreneurs.					
15. Illiteracy among women often restricts their approach and scope for knowledge advancement, making them shy and suffer from low self-esteem and self-confidence in entrepreneurial activities					
16. Social norms prevent women entrepreneurs from managing their businesses independently, impairing their mobility and affecting their interaction with others.					

17. Women entrepreneurs face additional handicaps due to the prevailing social and cultural gender-based inequalities and biases.					
18. Most companies or people, in general, prefer to deal or work with men than women.					
19. Although women entrepreneurs operate in the same environment as men entrepreneurs, there are gender biases embedded in society, limiting women from active economic participation and access to business and development services.					
20. Women entrepreneurs suffer from inadequate financial resources and working capital, and they do not acquire external financial assistance due to the absence of tangible security and credit in the market.					
21. In Nepal, a male is socially dominant in every aspect; hence, banks lack trust in a woman's ability and commitment to paying back their loan.					
22. There has been a decline in the opportunities available in the capital and other large cities, resulting in an insubstantial entrepreneurial environment.					
23. The prevailing attitude that a woman's place is at home with her family further constrain many married women from venturing into entrepreneurship					
24. The increasing demands of husbands and children hinder the business activities of women's ability to succeed in business.					
25. A lack of moral support from the family and husband is one social barrier to commencing a business to women entrepreneurs.					
26. The stereotypical gender roles for work/family responsibilities hinder the female entrepreneurs from participating in business activities.					

27. Weak judicial systems, inconsistency in implementing laws, bureaucracy, hooliganism, abuse of political power limits women participation in business					
Business involvement to women entrepreneurship in Nepal (Dependent variables)					
28. Banks tend to exaggerate the likelihood of women entrepreneurs' default, hence imposing unrealistically high collateral requirements, which results in credit-rationing.					
29. The fact that women have fewer connections than men with experts in specific fields hinders the women entrepreneurs in business.					
30. Castes and religions dominate with one another hinder women entrepreneurs.					
31. A women entrepreneur must play the role of a daughter, wife, and daughter in law, this limits women's participation in her business, hence hindering her success.					
32. Negative opinions voiced about the role of women in business limit their involvement.					
33. A lack of support and help from other women limit women's involvement in the business.					
34. Lack of access to capital and credit schemes and the constraints of financial systems are barriers to potential entrepreneurs as main hindrances to business innovation and success in developing economies.					

In Nepali Script

सर्वेक्षण प्रश्नावली

"नेपालको खाद्य उद्योगमा सफल महिला उद्यमशीलताका लागि क्यारियर अवरोधहरू अन्वेषण र यी अवरोधहरूलाई कसरी हटाउने।"

विकल्पबाट टिक गर्नुहोस्।

भाग १: यो तपाईंको बारेमा हो

१. उमेर

- १८-२५
- २६-३५
- ३६-४५
- ४६-५५
- ५६+
-

२. सम्बन्ध स्थिति

- एकल
- संलग्न
- विवाहित
- विभाजित
- विधवा

३. तपाईंका कति बच्चाहरू छन्?

- १-२ बच्चाहरू
- ३-५ बच्चाहरू
- लागू हुँदैन

४. एदुचतिओनल अत्तैन्मेंट लेवेल

- हाई स्कूल
- डिप्लोमा
- स्नातक
- पोस्ट ग्रेजुएट

६. तपाईं यस व्यवसायमा कति समयदेखि हुनुहुन्छ?

- 1-2 years
- 3-5 years
- 5-8 years
- 8 years +

7. के तपाईंसँग यस व्यवसायलाई विकास गर्न कुनै पहिलेको प्रशिक्षण थियो?

- हो
- होईन
-

भाग दुई: शीर्षकको बारेमा

पर्याप्त प्रशिक्षणको अभाव	SD	D	N	A	SA
क्यारियर मार्गनिर्देशनको अभावले महिला उद्यमीहरूको क्यारियर प्रगतिमा बाधा पुऱ्याउँछ विभिन्न सार्वजनिक र निजी प्रस्ताव गरिएको समर्थन सेवाहरू जसमा व्यवसाय विकास सेवाहरू र व्यापार बृद्धिमा जानकारी समावेश छन्।					
केहि तथ्यहरूमा महिलाहरूसँग पुरुषहरू भन्दा कम सम्पर्क छ भन्ने तथ्यले व्यवसायमा महिला उद्यमीको क्यारियरको प्रगतिमा बाधा उत्पन्न गर्दछ।					
धेरै महिला उद्यमीहरू सेटअप र आफ्नो व्यवसाय चलाउन आवश्यक सीप र शिक्षा को कमी छ।					
शिक्षित महिलालाई समेत पुरुषको तुलनामा कम वा अपर्याप्त शिक्षा प्रदान गरिएको छ आंशिक रूपमा विवाहको कारण					
शैक्षिक सुविधाहरूमा लैङ्गिक छुट्टै नीतिले महिला उद्यमीहरूको सीमित अनुभव सीमित गर्दछ					
महिला बीच निरक्षरता प्रायः उनीहरूको ज्ञान र प्रगतिको दायरा प्रतिबन्ध गर्दछ जसले उनीहरूलाई शर्मिलो बनाउँदछ र कम आत्मसम्मान र आत्मविश्वासबाट ग्रस्त हुन्छ उद्यमशीलता गतिविधिका अवधिमा।					
धेरै जसो महिलाहरूको प्रशासनिक, मार्केटिङ, खाताहरू र सार्वजनिक सम्बन्धका क्षेत्रमा उद्यमशीलताको कमी छ।					
कानूनी अवरोधहरू					
व्यवसाय इजाजतपत्र महिला उद्यमीहरूको एक हो किनकि प्रक्रिया लामो र जटिल, अत्यधिक नौकरशाही हो र केही अवस्थामा अधिकारीहरूले घूस लिन माग गर्दछ। कमजोर न्यायिक प्रणाली, कानूनहरू कार्यान्वयनमा असंगति, अफसरशाही, गुंडागर्दी, राजनीतिक शक्तिको दुरुपयोग र भ्रष्टाचारको नियन्त्रणको अभावले महिलाहरूलाई आफ्नो काम सुरु गर्न निरुत्साहित गर्दछ।					
कानून र अभ्यास महिला र पुरुष बीच भेदभाव					
बिमा, करहरू, र कर्तव्यहरूको उच्च दरहरूले व्यवसायमा महिलाको संलग्नतालाई सीमित गर्दछ					
कानूनी अवरोधहरू नेपालमा महिला उद्यमीहरूको अवरोध हुन्					
कानून र विनियमको अवधिमा महिला उद्यमीहरूका लागि सरकारी समर्थनको अभाव छ					
त्यहाँ महिला उद्यमीलाई सहयोग पुऱ्याउने व्यापार प्रक्रिया सम्बन्धी विभिन्न सरकारी विभागहरू बीच समन्वयको अभाव छ					
तथ्य यो छ कि कानून र नियमले महिलालाई आफ्नो पतिको अनुमति बिना लाइसेन्स प्राप्त गर्न प्रतिबन्ध लगाउँदछ					

आयात र निर्यात कानूनको जटिलताले व्यवसायमा महिलाको संलग्नतालाई सीमित गर्दछ					
अफसरशाही अवरोधहरूको परिणामस्वरूप अन्य देशहरूसँग वैदेशिक सम्बन्धले महिलाको व्यवसायमा संलग्नता सीमित गर्दछ					
सामाजिक सांस्कृतिक समर्थनको अभाव					
सामाजिक मान्यताले महिला उद्यमीहरूलाई स्वतन्त्र रूपमा उनीहरूको व्यवसाय प्रबन्ध गर्नबाट रोक्छ, जसले तिनीहरूको गतिशीलतालाई बिगार्दछ र अरूसँगको उनीहरूको अन्तरक्रियामा असर गर्दछ। महिला सामाजिक उद्यमीले विद्यमान सामाजिक र सांस्कृतिक लिंगमा आधारित असमानता र पूर्वाग्रहका कारण थप बाधा भोग्नुपन्थो।					
धेरै कम्पनिहरू वा व्यक्ति, सामान्यतया, महिला भन्दा पुरुषसँग काम गर्न वा काम गर्न रुचाउँछन्					
एक समर्थन र अन्य महिलाको मद्दत को अभावले व्यवसायमा महिलाको संलग्नता सीमित गर्दछ					
नकारात्मक विचारहरूले व्यवसायमा महिलाको भूमिकालाई उनीहरूको संलग्नतामा सीमित बनायो					
जाति र धार्मिक प्रभुत्वले एक अर्कासँग महिला उद्यमीलाई बाधा पुऱ्याउँछ					
सफल महिला उद्यमीहरूको प्रतिनिधित्व गर्न उपयुक्त मोडेलको अभाव छ					
जसरी महिला उद्यमीले पुरुष उद्यमीले उस्तै वातावरणमा काम गरिरहेका छन्, त्यहाँ समाजमा लैंगिक पक्षपात रहेको छ, जसले महिलालाई सक्रिय आर्थिक सहभागिता र व्यापार र विकास सेवामा पहुँच गर्न सीमित गर्दछ।					
वित्तीय स्रोतहरूमा सहज पहुँचको अभाव					
महिला उद्यमीहरू अपर्याप्त वित्तीय स्रोत र कार्यशील पूँजीबाट ग्रस्त छन् र उनीहरूले बजारमा स्थिर सुरक्षा र creditणको अभावका कारण बाह्य वित्तीय सहायता प्राप्त गर्न सक्षम छैनन्।					
बैंकहरूले महिला उद्यमीहरूको पूर्वनिर्धारितको सम्भावनालाई बढाइचढाइ गर्ने गर्छन्, त्यसैले अवास्तविक रूपमा उच्च जमानतको आवश्यकताहरू लगाउँदछ, जसले creditण-राशनमा परिणाम दिन्छ।					
पूँजी र योजनामा पहुँचको कमी र वित्तीय प्रणालीको अवरोध सम्भावित उद्यमीहरूले व्यापार आविष्कार र विकासशील अर्थव्यवस्थामा सफलताको मुख्य अवरोध हो।					
नेपालमा पुरुष सामाजिक रूपले सबै पक्षमा प्रभावशाली छन् यसैले यसले महिलाको क्षमता र कर्जा फिर्ता गर्ने प्रतिबद्धतामा बैंकले विश्वासको कमी देखाउँदछ।					
राजधानी र अन्य ठूला शहरहरूमा उपलब्ध अवसरहरूमा गिरावट आएको छ, परिणामस्वरूप एक अपूरणीय उद्यमशीलताको वातावरण					
कार्य-परिवार ईन्टरफेस					
एक महिला उद्यमीले छोरी, पत्नी र बुहारीको भूमिका खेल्नु पर्दछ, यसले उनको व्यवसायमा महिलाको सहभागिता सीमित गर्दछ त्यसैले उनको सफलतामा बाधा पुऱ्याउँछ।					
एक महिलाको घर मा उनको परिवार संग छ कि प्रचलित दृष्टिकोण धेरै विवाहित महिला उद्यमशीलता मा उद्यम गर्न रोक्छ					
पति र बच्चाहरूको बढ्दो मागले व्यवसायमा सफल हुने महिलाको क्यारियरलाई बाधा पुऱ्याउँछ					
महिला उद्यमीको क्यारियरको प्रगतिमा परिवार र पतिबाट नैतिक समर्थनको अभाव एउटा सामाजिक अवरोध हो					

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Appendix 4: Interview schedule questions - Women entrepreneurs

1. Can you please talk about yourself, your family, your education like.?

Age:

Education

Marital status

No. of children

2. Can you give a brief overview of your enterprise and your entrepreneurial journey like.?

Business experience in years

Previous trainings

Business:

No. of employees

3. What were the barriers as a woman you faced whilst doing this business? Are these still a barrier to you?

4. Can you give me some details on financial barriers in your work as a women entrepreneur?

5. Do you consider that lack of adequate training and development programmes and education is the barrier to you? (If yes, please explain how)

6. Explain if there are any legal barriers whilst doing your business?

7. Do you think that culture and social support could form barriers to you being a women entrepreneur? If yes, please explain.

8. Did you ever face problems balancing your family and business responsibilities as a women entrepreneur?

9. Do you have anything to add besides financial, legal, social, cultural, educational, and family responsibilities barriers while doing a business as a woman? If yes, if you were male entrepreneurs, would this still be a barrier to you?

10. Can you share your opinion on how to overcome these barriers?

In Nepali Script

साक्षात्कार कार्यक्रम प्रश्न - महिला उद्यमी

१. के तपाईं कृपया तपाईंको बारेमा, तपाईंको परिवार, तपाईंको शिक्षा जस्ता बताउन सक्नुहुन्छ ..Age:

Education

Marital status

No. of children

१. के तपाईं तपाईंको उद्यम र तपाईंको उद्यमशीलता यात्रा को एक संक्षिप्त सिंहावलोकन दिन सक्नुहुन्छ .. वर्ष मा व्यापार को अनुभव

अघिल्लो प्रशिक्षण

व्यवसाय:

कर्मचारीहरूको संख्या

महिलाको रूपमा के अवरोधहरू थिए, तपाईंले यो व्यवसाय गर्दासम्म सामना गर्नुभयो? के यो अझै तपाईंलाई बाधा छन्?

तपाईं मलाई एक महिला उद्यमीको रूपमा आफ्नो काममा वित्तीय अवरोधहरूको बारेमा केहि विवरण दिन सक्नुहुन्छ?

के तपाईं पर्याप्त प्रशिक्षण र विकास कार्यक्रम र शिक्षा को अभाव तपाईं को बाधक हो भनेर विचार गर्नुहुन्छ? (यदि हो भने, कृपया कसरी वर्णन गर्नुहोस्) बुझाउनुहोस् यदि त्यहाँ कुनै कानूनी बाधा छन् जबकि तपाईंको गर्दै?

के तपाईं सोच्नुहुन्छ कि संस्कृति र सामाजिक समर्थन तपाईंलाई महिला उद्यमी बन्न बाधा उत्पन्न गर्न सक्छ। यदि हो भने, कृपया वर्णन गर्नुहोस्।

के तपाईंले कहिल्यै महिला उद्यमीको रूपमा परिवार र व्यापारिक जिम्मेवारी सन्तुलनमा समस्याहरूको सामना गर्नु भएको छ?

तपाईंसँग आर्थिक, कानूनी, सामाजिक, सांस्कृतिक, शैक्षिक, र पारिवारिक उत्तरदायित्व बाधा बाहेक केहि थप केहि छ जब एक महिलाको रूपमा एक व्यवसाय गर्दै? यदि हो भने, के तपाईं पुरुष उद्यमी हुनुभएको जस्तो लाग्छ भने, के यो अझै पनि तपाईंलाई रोक्ने थियो?

यी अवरोधहरूलाई कसरी पार गर्ने भनेर तपाईं आफ्नो राय साझा गर्न सक्नुहुन्छ?

Appendix 5: Interview schedule questions- Business Development Organizations

Personal and business demographics

1. Could you please introduce yourself like.?

Age:

Gender:

Educational Level:

Marital status:

Business experience in years:

No. of branches you supervise:

Position:

2. Can you briefly tell me about your firm and services offered by your organization to entrepreneurs? Is it for specific entrepreneurs? If yes, please mention it.
3. What difference do you find in services, business environment setting, programmes offered to women entrepreneurs and male entrepreneurs?
4. Do you consider women entrepreneurs face more barriers while doing business than males? If yes, please explain.
5. In your opinion, are women entrepreneurs' significant barriers to the lack of financial resources, legal restrictions, socio-cultural support, balancing family and work life, and lack of access to training and educational programmes? If yes, please explain how?
6. Do you have any other barriers in your mind that you consider the main barriers to women entrepreneurs other than the one mentioned above? If yes, please explain.
7. What do you think should be done to overcome the barriers women entrepreneurs face and promote women entrepreneurship in Nepal?

Appendix 6: Interview Transcript

Interview Transcript- Women Entrepreneur

Transcript #1: WE01

1. Can you please talk about yourself, your family, your education like.?

Age: 23

Education: Bachelor

Marital status: Single

No. of children: Not applicable

2. Can you give a brief overview of your enterprise and your entrepreneurial journey like.?

Business experience in years: 3 years

Previous trainings: Yes

Business: Beverages

No. of employees: 2

3. What were the barriers as a woman you faced whilst doing this business? Are these still a barrier to you?

“Well, there are many barriers when I started my company. I didn’t have the exact starting point where to start the business, what to do, what to expect, etc. Firstly, since I am young, my networking is very poor, plus the trust issues is something I always must prove even to my parents. I come from the specific ethnic group, that alcohols are almost a sin to even look. So, they were my biggest barriers that I had to conquer I believe. They are not barrier now, but I have some other barriers.”

4. Can you give me some details on financial barriers in your work as a women entrepreneur?

“Hmmm.. apart from this, financial barrier is almost all entrepreneurs face no matter you are a man. But thank God, once I convinced my parents, they supported me like they funded my business which I have returned them within year. So, I didn’t have to go through loan procedure and all credits from the finance companies. I heard that these process takes a lot of time.”

5. Do you consider that lack of adequate training and development programmes and education is the barrier to you? (If yes, please explain how)

“When I started my entrepreneurship journey....there were many training and development programmes to choose from. Especially, if you contact any women development organization, they make you aware of many pieces of training available in Nepal according to your skills and time. So, I believe these days there are many programmes, vocational education, events happening to promote women entrepreneurs. I cannot say the same with other cities or areas, but I reside in Kathmandu, so there are always something happening only for women entrepreneurs.”

6. Explain if there are any legal barriers whilst doing your business?

“ I always wanted to expand my business and do export to other foreign countries. But the foreign relation is very poor in context with Nepal. So, yes there are several legal obligations. The Nepalese Constitution of 2015 provides for expropriation of the property only in compliance with the legislation and public interest. Only after adequate compensation has been charged, it makes it illegal to nationalize a foreign-invested industry. Expropriation, whether direct or indirect, should only be done for the benefit of the public. These laws prohibit any licensed industry from being privatized and are only permitted for public purposes.”

7. Do you think that culture and social support could form barriers to you being a women entrepreneur? If yes, please explain.

“Ha-ha! You know is funny that people say its equality era... everybody is same. But I feel it's still the same. Yes, people have accepted women as an entrepreneur but not taken seriously. They think we are becoming entrepreneurs to kill time and do not have anything else to do. They think... we are becoming entrepreneurs to kill time and do not have anything else to do. Culture in Nepal supports women as entrepreneurs and accepts the woman to be entrepreneur.... but still she faced culture issue as a mother and wife. Though I am single with no kids, and also I am the only kid of my parents.. so, imagine... I had to hear... I don't know from where I start... about my beverage business.. my parents were like.. you are a girl... how can you do this business.. society will think bad about you.. who will marry you... blah!!! blah!!!blah!!! So, a big YES, that women do face this barrier not only in doing business but also anything I believe...hee-hee ”

8. Did you ever face problems balancing your family and business responsibilities as a women entrepreneur?

“ You know I just realised that while giving this interview that... everything is revolving around this culture affect especially for women. Off course family commitment and the issue, we have with our culture. sometimes you leave your business in a busy time because of family commitments, which will affect me. and I believed most of the women entrepreneurs' business.”

Do you have anything to add besides financial, legal, social, cultural, educational, and family responsibilities barriers while doing a business as a woman? If yes, if you were male entrepreneurs, would this still be a barrier to you?

“Wow! Yeah, before doing business before doing business, I receive marketing and strategic planning support from the business development organization ...it helped me a lot how to channel my brand and how to reach my target customers. I plan my business model with all the strategy I received from the organization and its benefits a lot and I am thankful for my mentor who has been guiding me for four years, and still, I relate to her. I have come across so many women entrepreneurs now... so they all complain about networking, and training programmes they require for specific trend .. or to even modify their current business plan, we women need the most than men. Because men entrepreneurs do not have family commitments, culture boundaries, skills they are allowed to go anywhere at any time, for us women, we need permission... What I found is men do have barriers but insignificant barriers, but we women entrepreneurs have barriers, challenge, hurdle all time in our entrepreneurial journey.”

9. Can you share your opinion on how to overcome these barriers?

“If you take my opinion to public then all I can suggest is that government should amend the Financial Sector Charter to afford women easier access to external finance. Learning institutions need to develop affordable and specific training programmes to assist women entrepreneurs to acquire education and training to combat barriers. Business rules and policy should be stable for every industry then Nepal can develop a lot. Also, NRN investment in Nepal should be legal to create jobs and entrepreneurs in Nepal.”

Transcript #2: WE02

1. Can you please talk about yourself, your family, your education like.?

Age: 32

Education: Bachelor

Marital status: Married

No. of children: Not Applicable

2. Can you give a brief overview of your enterprise and your entrepreneurial journey like.?

Business experience in years: 1 year and 7 months

Previous trainings: Yes

Business: Cashmere shawl production

No. of employees: 5

3. What were the barriers as a woman, you faced whilst doing this business? Are these still a barrier to you?

“Oh Yeh!!!! Since I went back home from UK after 4 years. So, after 4 years many things had changed in Nepal in terms of starting business. I had knowledge about UK market but zero knowledge on Nepalese market. I took quite a lot of time to study the market of Nepal. Then I got introduced to NYEF, where I even learnt about the current market situation of Nepal. So, yes my barrier was my knowledge, say no basic information not how to operate business.”

4. Can you give me some details on financial barriers in your work as an women entrepreneur?

“ To be honest... it is a barrier to me so partially yes. I took help from my parents as well as I had to borrow loan from bank. This loan procedure was difficult. I had to prove some many things, so many documents required even to start SME. Imagine, if I was planning to build 5 starts (giggling). It took nearly 6 months to get approval from bank. I nearly gave up and thought of getting a job but my family and me in laws too supported a lot. Without them I don't think so I will be here.”

5. Do you consider that lack of adequate training and development programmes and education is the barriers to you? (If yes, please explain how)

“You know what! It is not those businesses cannot run without management education, but it empowers you with the knowledge, skills and learning agility required to stay of times and competitors. The fast-paced industrial world demands the need for management abilities to handle the complex, multidimensional business spheres. In such a scenario, management education with proper guidance and training becomes indispensable. It has to be admitted that a collective knowledge from education and experience is what forms the right foundation for future managers, leaders, and entrepreneurs.”

6. Explain if there are any legal barriers whilst doing your business?

“ Oh my gosh! There are so many legal barriers to women entrepreneurship. There is no provision from government side... no helped specifically I this pandemic. we women entrepreneurs get frustrated... going through depression and government seems to sit quietly... I am not saying men entrepreneurs are getting indirect help... government wants to boost women entrepreneurs in Nepal, but the government seems confused. The only ray of hope..... is that consumers learned the value of the online business during the lockdown.”

7. Do you think that culture and social support could form barriers to you being a women entrepreneur? If yes, please explain.

“Well, this is obvious from all aspect that we women entrepreneurs have some social boundaries that we are not allowed to cross or even rebel.. otherwise, we become the “*kaalo dhabba*” (black rotten roots) of the society... firstly... Women themselves perceive we women are bound to certain things. I got questions from my female friend when I started this business. One of my female friends said, how can you do this type of business when you could have a nice job paying a good salary. This entrepreneurs’ thing doesn’t suit me. I was like. Are you even serious?”

8. Did you ever face problems balancing your family and business responsibilities as a women entrepreneur?

“Luckily, my in-laws, parents and my husband are very supportive... they assume that I have capabilities and skills .. after all I came back from UK. So, they did not want my talent to go on waste. So, any I do not have to compromise and able to balance both professional and personal life so far.”

9. Do you have anything to add besides financial, legal, social, cultural, educational, and family responsibilities barriers while doing a business as a woman? If yes, if you were male entrepreneurs, would this still be a barrier to you?

“ Like I mentioned that I came back from UK, so I didn’t have any idea how to do business. So, I had to hire a mentor. mentoring for me is the barriers I believe to all women who wants to do something for her own. My mentor channel my inner abilities and skills.... She is always there for me 24/7 whenever I need her, and she is updated with all existing trends of the business.

Networking is the most vital thing any entrepreneurs should have. Networking has helped me a lot to grow my business. Without this, your brand is nothing the work you do your talent everything gets showcased on your networking skills.”

10. Can you share your opinion on how to overcome these barriers?

“Finance is a barrier for any enterprise to expand or succeed. But the banking system in Nepal is not sufficiently responsive to social banking needs and has not been able to deal with barriers that hinder women from using or gaining access to credit. So, there should be adequate arrangements for the supply of credit facility at concession rate for the women entrepreneurs in view of their growing needs... also creating provision of micro credit system and enterprise credit system to the women entrepreneurs at local level with low rate of interest must be looked at. Provision should be made to provide land / sheds to deserving women entrepreneurs on priority basis. Women Entrepreneurship programmes must be promoted in rural sector by reinigorating activitiesskills on traditional crafts or practices with which they are acquainted.”

Transcript #3: WE03

1. Can you please talk about yourself, your family, your education like.?

Age: 42

Education: Postgraduate

Marital status: Married

No. of children: 3 children

2. Can you give a brief overview of your enterprise and your entrepreneurial journey like.?

Business experience in years: 12 years

Previous trainings: Yes

Business: 5-star hotel

No. of employees: 50

3. What were the barriers as a woman, you faced whilst doing this business? Are these still a barrier to you?

“ Oh, my lovely daughter, where do I start from? There we are still lots of barriers doing business in Nepal that also as a women entrepreneur. I started my own company from black and white era.”

4. Can you give me some details on financial barriers in your work as an women entrepreneur?

“ So, obviously I was struggling from financial resources. Well, yes. Our first obstacle was that we needed to be financed. I approached IFC (International Finance Corporation) and ADB (Asian Development Bank), and they all turned me down because they said my hotel was too small a project. Then I approached the local banks, and do you know what they told me? They asked me, “What is your collateral? These rotten pieces of wood?” Eventually, we managed to get a consortium – about four or five banks – and they agreed to give us a loan. Yes, it was difficult: Who did I think was – a woman doing all this?”

5. Do you consider that lack of adequate training and development programmes and education is the barriers to you? (If yes, please explain how)

“During the time we started...it was very difficult, even to get training. There are many training programmes for women, so it is difficult to learn skills and get basic entrepreneurial training. But the country's situation is getting worse, which is creating difficulties not only for women but also for men. Some several co-operatives and organizations provide proper guidance not only to women but also to men. I have shared with my cases, as in the case of VAT, but besides that, nowadays, I don't think there are any extra problems in doing business for women.”

6. Explain if there are any legal barriers whilst doing your business?

“ I feel...as a woman, though laws are supporting and empowering women entrepreneurs, it's only in the book, but most of the worker themselves haven't read that law. I faced so many obligations to start my business, but when my husband tried to sort the issue, it solved within a sec.”

7. Do you think that culture and social support could form barriers to you being a women entrepreneur? If yes, please explain.

“ Like I said, I started my business a decade ago. The time has changed a lot likewise, the perception of people. But it doesn't matter how big the women entrepreneur is; when dealing with specific clients, they prefer a male member. I still don't know why this is, so I have been in this industry for long almost 12 years, but still, its 21st century, when I deal with foreign clients, even they show different attitude towards me being a woman.”

8. Did you ever face problems balancing your family and business responsibilities as a women entrepreneur?

“ Absolutely... I did face this barrier. Since, I and my husband moved out from his house, to involve in business I had to sacrifice my family life. I used to travel abroad, and my children was looked by their nanny it was a great obstacle for me because families do not want me to fly alone and meet and speak to men, children and motherhood nearly took time away from my company.”

9. Do you have anything to add besides financial, legal, social, cultural, educational, and family responsibilities barriers while doing a business as a woman? If yes, if you were male entrepreneurs, would this still be a barrier to you?

“ For me to reach out the customers and now to keep up with the change is emerging as barriers. For example, this covid has changed everything. We must shift working from home approach. Then upgrade of everything makes bit difficult to cope. Having said that I am involved in women entrepreneurship programmes and one of the vice presidents of FWEAN... That just has been fantastic. I get a lot of networking support you know from people, and I support them. There was a new lady. I helped her basically to the network, so we sat down and helped each other, and at the least, in return, she will give me some work or referrals. And to be honest, you will start seeing the result after you have as much as networking positively”.

10. Can you share your opinion on how to overcome these barriers?

“Time waits for no one, so we should all ensure we utilize our time well. Rural women should be encouraged to take advantage of the opportunities. Women should work hard to attain success and not just talk about it; action is needed by all women. It is important to work from the grassroots level if you want to be successful and have an impact with what you do. It is

important to work for the betterment of the country and serve the neediest people in society. In this way you can achieve great things and maybe even make a name for yourself. Hence, the entrepreneurial mindset of women should be strong and prepare for doing something for themselves and not waste their individual talent.”

Transcript #4: WE04

1. Can you please talk about yourself, your family, your education like.?

Age: 25

Education: Bachelor

Marital status: Married

No. of children: 1 child

2. Can you give a brief overview of your enterprise and your entrepreneurial journey like.?

Business experience in years: 7 years

Previous trainings: No

Business: Online jewellerys and food delivery

No. of employees: 14

3. What were the barriers as a woman, you faced whilst doing this business? Are these still a barrier to you?

“Yes, I did face some barriers in starting my own business. Financial and not awareness how to start the business and how to implement my skills. I had no idea no how to register so basically I didn’t have any help. “

4. Can you give me some details on financial barriers in your work as an women entrepreneur?

“ Pheww!!! This was my major financial barriers. I had to do job first and then save the money to start my business. Then I had to apply for loan which took so many documents to get

approved. Since, all the property was in the name of my husband, the bank processes a lot of time to prove whether I am eligible for the funding or not...”

5. Do you consider that lack of adequate training and development programmes and education is the barriers to you? (If yes, please explain how)

“Yes I do.... Because I didn’t have any formal training or involved in any sort of programmes I didn’t know how to start my business. I actually didn’t know my talents, my capabilities... so, this acted as major barriers to doing business in Nepal.”

6. Explain if there are any legal barriers whilst doing your business ?

“ You know.. the rule of this country is that.. husband should give consent as well for wife to undertake any business... hence these legal obstacles constitute a set of complicated requirements for establishing a business. There is a lack of legal support for women entrepreneurs, discrimination between female and male entrepreneurs in the regulations high cost of protecting intellectual property such as the business idea. trademark and copyright in some procedures with some government agencies a man’s approval is needed.”

7. Do you think that culture and social support could form barriers to you being a women entrepreneur? If yes, please explain.

“ There is no doubt on this...we women are perceived in a certain way in our society. Women should never do this has stopped and created a huge barrier to women, not just entrepreneurs. And for us entrepreneurs, we can hear people saying ahh! she is a woman, she doesn’t know, or she is a woman she won’t be able to do this is a most common thing that I hear in daily basis.”

8. Did you ever face problems balancing your family and business responsibilities as a women entrepreneur?

“No, honestly, I didn’t face any barriers as such. Since everybody at house was supportive, I could manage my time to maintain this balance.”

9. Do you have anything to add besides financial, legal, social, cultural, educational, and family responsibilities barriers while doing a business as a woman? If yes, if you were male entrepreneurs, would this still be a barrier to you?

“ As I have mentioned earlier, I do not have prior training or being involved... like I didn't do my homework properly before doing business.. so, finding a mentor is very difficult...there is lack of trust...you never know if they are working with your competitors and... in Nepal...everything is possible... if you have money, these mentors get a bribe, and I had a bad experience with one of my mentors as she was helping my competitor. She was always helping me. But her decision on my business was foolish. And didn't work out well so, yes a good mentor plays a role on your business. Maybe if I was a man, then I wouldn't have to face this as men usually have lots of friends... anyway they do get guidance form their friends as well. So, a proper professional mentor is needed to boost the women entrepreneurs in Nepal”

10. Can you share your opinion on how to overcome these barriers?

“To extend confessional rates facilities and schemes for women entrepreneurs to prosper in the field of enterprise acquainted. Women entrepreneurs should be provided marketing facilities and subsidy for raw materials. · There should be an incessant attempt to motivate, give confidence, inspire, and assist women entrepreneurs. Government should provide better educational facilities and schemes to women folk. There should be continuous monitoring, improvement of training programmers, practical experience and personality development programmes to improvise their over-all personality standards.”

Transcript #5: WE05

1. Can you please talk about yourself, your family, your education like.?

Age: 57

Education: High School or less

Marital status: Widow

No. of children: 2 children

2. Can you give a brief overview of your enterprise and your entrepreneurial journey like.?

Business experience in years: 15 years

Previous trainings: Yes

Business: Handicraft business

No. of employees: 20

3. What were the barriers as a woman, you faced whilst doing this business? Are these still a barrier to you?

“When I started this business, I really didn’t know whether it will work or not. My business is related to products which are made of wool which are necessary to keep us away from the cold and my grandma used to make many woollen products. So, whenever she gets ill or cannot work, my small business used see some loss. So, I would say the health of my employees is barriers in my career.”

4. Can you give me some details on financial barriers in your work as an women entrepreneur?

“Since, I started with small investment, I started saving from the profits I received from this business plus touchwood, my family is well off. So, it didn’t have such barriers. “

5. Do you consider that lack of adequate training and development programmes and education is the barriers to you? (If yes, please explain how)

“ I do not come from educational background which is affecting my business. Today I feel that education is the most important thing to do anything. I have not completed my school, so I feel embarrassed when I show my clients or customers when I cannot write and speak in English; I don’t know how to do maths properly. I need the help of my 11 years old son. I could have grown more successful, but my education is the big barrier to this. So, I am taking vocational training where I can learn she asserted that she didn’t have that much time to get involved now or before starting her business in these kinds of programmes. Definitely, this sums up that this is a barrier specifically to women entrepreneurs in Nepal.”

6. Explain if there are any legal barriers whilst doing your business ?

“ I wouldn’t say this as a barrier to me. My business is handicraft which is small so.. the legal restriction is not that high in this type of business.”

7. Do you think that culture and social support could form barriers to you being a women entrepreneur? If yes, please explain.

“Yes, it can because most of the women are treated as housewives. So, the culture and social boundaries limit women to showcase their talent. They listen to the society and spend their whole life looking after her family due to criticism. “

8. Did you ever face problems balancing your family and business responsibilities as a women entrepreneur?

“ I am a widow, and I am from joint family...during our working period, the family members take responsibility for preparing meals and caring for the children...so that I can continue the employment. The working women residing with children also furnish the task of folding and dressing the children.”

9. Do you have anything to add besides financial, legal, social, cultural, educational, and family responsibilities barriers while doing a business as a woman? If yes, if you were male entrepreneurs, would this still be a barrier to you?

“To start something new in the first place one needs a lot of courage. The fearing inner voice is always there who just wants to go through the simple way. For example: I want to start a business, there is always a fear voice calling out loud how you are going to fail, and you are going to lose money. Well, we need to hear a courageous inner voice. This might be one of the barriers which I would like to call a self-barrier which is other than the above-mentioned barriers. So, if I was men then this should be a barrier because they don’t have restriction in terms of anything... “

10. Can you share your opinion on how to overcome these barriers?

“In my opinion.....government should support the women entrepreneurs for starting and growing a business; it is the requirement of the hour to implement the related policies and programmes honestly for development of the women entrepreneurs. The ratio of high educational status (postgraduate and graduate) is very low in women entrepreneurs. Lack of

awareness about girls' education is the reason of low educational status in rural area of Nepal. So, families should help girls to educate themselves for a better decision making, awareness, self-esteem, self-independence, and bright future. Women entrepreneurs should try to start their businesses with adequate funds, exploring the product and services, search the new markets, network and consult with professionals for solve these difficult.”

Transcript #6: WE06

1. Can you please talk about yourself, your family, your education like.?

Age: 45

Education: Diploma

Marital status: Separated

No. of children: 4 children

2. Can you give a brief overview of your enterprise and your entrepreneurial journey like.?

Business experience in years: 6 years and 11 months

Previous trainings: Yes

Business: Beauty Salon

No. of employees: 5

3. What were the barriers as a woman, you faced whilst doing this business? Are these still a barrier to you?

“Yes I did face many barriers. Since I come from low level income family. There was no one to support financial, emotionally, I do not have any educational background. And Women in my family were only confined to do household chores. So, I had to fight with that stigma first.”

4. Can you give me some details on financial barriers in your work as an women entrepreneur?

“As I mentioned Yes I did face financial barrier. I started my business with what I have at my home. I used all the resources available and made a beauty salon. Then for packaging and other things to make my own brand product I needed money. So, I borrow small amount from my neighbours which I agreed to pay interest too. So, I was not making any money which was huge loss. Still, I realised that hard work pays off. So, I continued even when I was in loss.”

5. Do you consider that lack of adequate training and development programmes and education is the barriers to you? (If yes, please explain how)

“ Yes.....education is very crucial these days whether be it for a job or business. Having a strong educational background transforms yourself first, then other things like your career. So, without educational background, women can start a business, but I doubt for career progressions. I believe... education is essential not just for women, it's equally crucial for all citizens. I think it's the right to go to school. I have many friends who dropped out early in school due to personal problems. Now they are earning but feels like they could grow if they proceeded their education and completed at least Bachelor's degree.”

6. Explain if there are any legal barriers whilst doing your business ?

“Ummm.. this is not a barrier I would term.. my registration was simple....I had to register and get certificate from the local ward which took a week. Without this I was not allowed to advertise. But other than that,... everything is well.”

7. D
o you think that culture and social support could form barriers to you being a women entrepreneur? If yes, please explain.

“Yes. I highly believe that this is the most barriers that all women face. We live in a country where women are looked as doing only certain things. Everybody objected and even my husband was not supporting me. But I had to do this as I felt I need to do something. I was getting crazy. But still, I pursue this profession didn't listen to them. My society even criticize me today. But I cannot stop them.”

8. Di
d you ever face problems balancing your family and business responsibilities as a women entrepreneur?

“ Touchwood, I am a single mum.. and I did start my business when my elder one was 16... so my elder daughter looked after my younger kids... and we live alone... so I do not have faced yet.. any balancing barriers.”

9. Do you have anything to add besides financial, legal, social, cultural, educational, and family responsibilities barriers while doing a business as a woman? If yes, if you were male entrepreneurs, would this still be a barrier to you?

“I believe all the women entrepreneurs needs or lacks mentor to start business.... Yes, I did have a mentor who was an expert of marketing and has good networking across the nation. I take his advice if I am about to introduce something new in my company.”

10. Can you share your opinion on how to overcome these barriers?

“All it takes is an entrepreneurial mindset change and this mind-set change also needs to come in from the ecosystem. There have been several instances of gender-bias towards women-led start-ups based on their personal goals or the investor’s assumption of their personal goals. We also need policies that positively discriminate women entrepreneurs and employees along with the infrastructure that assures a safe and healthy environment for them.”

Transcript #7: WE07

1. Can you please talk about yourself, your family, your education like.?

Age: 50

Education: Postgraduate

Marital status: Widow

No. of children: 2 children

2. Can you give a brief overview of your enterprise and your entrepreneurial journey like.?

Business experience in years: 8 years

Previous trainings: No

Business: Financial institution

No. of employees: 22

3. What were the barriers as a woman, you faced whilst doing this business? Are these still a barrier to you?

“I faced lot of barriers in transforming my dream into reality. Being a girl and moving to city all alone was something which was unimaginable in my family or for that matter even in my village. Everyone would ask what the need is of moving to city when you can get everything here in Pokhara. However, my mother supported me, and that support helped me move to Kathmandu. Real struggle began when I came to Kathmandu. One takes time to get used to the busy city life, travel in bus to reach office on time, etc. All this demanded lot of rigorous work and this made the base of my career strong. Initially, I faced resistance from the industry as I did not have any prior work experience. People had complained about my working style. I knew I couldn't continue like this for long and hence decided to work on my weak areas. My senior colleagues guided me, and I learnt the tricks of the trade from them. Though stressful at times but it was fun as well.”

4. Can you give me some details on financial barriers in your work as an women entrepreneur?

“ Since my business is about finance.. so, I needed huge money. The government has announced that banks will provide loans up to Rs 1.5 million to women without collateral. But when I visited around half a dozen banks, I was told that the policy is yet to be implemented. Due to such announcements which are limited to paper only, I was in a dilemma whether to start or not...”

5. Do you consider that lack of adequate training and development programmes and education is the barriers to you? (If yes, please explain how)

“ 100% it's a barrier...I was not aware of any of these programmes. I tried to ask for help to support my business, but I couldn't find any that could match my business structure.. also, now I didn't have that much time to get involved now or before starting my business in these kinds of programmes. But I wish to get involved in future.”

6. Explain if there are any legal barriers whilst doing your business ?

“ Um.. these regulatory challenges, as well as the many conditions required to obtain government assistance, along with a lack of legislation to protect the entrepreneur's ideas and interests, contribute to a complex legal climate concerning the requirements for starting a new

company. Except for explosives and some radio equipment, there are no restrictions on importing project equipment under the Nepalese rule. Various projects, such as solar, hydropower, wind energy, biogas, and hotels, are eligible for customs duty and value-added tax exemptions. Imports to businesses located in special economic zones and star hotels and resorts are excluded from such restrictions. To qualify for those exemptions, you must get a recommendation from a government official.”

7. Do you think that culture and social support could form barriers to you being a women entrepreneur? If yes, please explain.

“ Yes, Nepal is very cultural country.. Female founders of start-up companies are still facing cultural and social challenges compared to their male counterparts. Society must be very sensitive towards this issue.”

8. Did you ever face problems balancing your family and business responsibilities as a women entrepreneur?

“ Yes.. It is the prime duty of most of the working women to prepare breakfast, lunch as well as dinner for the family members as well as self. In a joint family, the other family members provide help in different domestic work and take care of children during meal preparation or food materials but if the working women belonging to a nuclear family or residing alone were uncomfortable even if we take the help of maidservant because meal preparation takes more time, it is daily routine work and cannot ignore our child.”

9. Do you have anything to add besides financial, legal, social, cultural, educational, and family responsibilities barriers while doing a business as a woman? If yes, if you were male entrepreneurs, would this still be a barrier to you?

“Marketing and networking are one of the barriers I faced to keep up with changing dynamic. And I do still think this will be a barrier to women than men.”

10. Can you share your opinion on how to overcome these barriers?

“ It’s all joint effort, a single being cannot change.. so, if government, individual, we all as society.... So, if these all entities put an effort to promote women entrepreneurship.. then these barriers can be overcome.”

Transcript #8: WE08

1. Can you please talk about yourself, your family, your education like.?

Age: 42

Education: Diploma

Marital status: Married

No. of children: 2 children

2. Can you give a brief overview of your enterprise and your entrepreneurial journey like.?

Business experience in years: 10 years

Previous trainings: Yes

Business: Supermarket Retail shop

No. of employees: 8

3. What were the barriers as a woman, you faced whilst doing this business? Are these still a barrier to you?

“Yes, I did. When I took over the retail business, the male family members were not happy. They thought I am woman that cannot handle and since being a woman at that age, they said, I won’t be able to make decisions . My family is bit traditional, so I was explaining all the modern plans how we can run business. So, we had huge clash.”

4. Can you give me some details on financial barriers in your work as an women entrepreneur?

“Umm.... Umm.... there is much financial help from the government like micro-financing, less interest, etc. The government is trying their best to empower women in Nepal. So, there are nowadays financial help available to women.”

5. Do you consider that lack of adequate training and development programmes and education is the barriers to you? (If yes, please explain how)

“Yes. Since most of the men have access to outside since their childhood, they have much knowledge on these programmes. So, they are kind of use to of these events which results in any kind of business activities. Whereas we women, are taught to do household chores since childhood. This lacks our knowledge to outer world. So, to start a business for a woman is like breaking a big rock without any knowledge.”

6. Explain if there are any legal barriers whilst doing your business ?

“No. One good thing about being in food business is that for licensing and other legal procedure, women can get it done in free cost. Last time I went to register my shop, where I wasn’t charge whereas my uncle got charged. I was happy but recently, a law passed stating that women cannot travel overseas without her husband’s or family’s permission. These laws discourage women and stifle their ambitions to strive for careers and business ownership.”

7. Do you think that culture and social support could form barriers to you being a women entrepreneur? If yes, please explain.

“ Yes. Because we women get married someday. So, once we are married we don’t have any right on our paternal family business. These perceptions are mostly based on the association of entrepreneurship with traditional male stereotypes. Like, when its festivals time, I cannot focus on my business because I am a woman and need to do household chore and shop work. I sometimes have to close the shop but most of the time I handover to the reliable employee of mine.”

8. Did you ever face problems balancing your family and business responsibilities as a women entrepreneur?

“Yes I did face this barrier because if husband is not supporting and understand that you are entrepreneur and you are busy, you can’t continue your business because you will get a lot of family issues. If you have a husband and kids... they will expect from you to be available to them 24hrs, and you should satisfy their expectations no matters if you are an entrepreneur.”

9. Do you have anything to add besides financial, legal, social, cultural, educational, and family responsibilities barriers while doing a business as a woman? If yes, if you were male entrepreneurs, would this still be a barrier to you?

“Um....Every day I wake up and go through newspaper to see if there are any new updates on technology in Nepal or internationally and then if necessary I take a course if available in Nepal you never know this is competitive age and world of globalisation without these skills... your business is incompetent in the contemporary market. I have no idea on marketing and strategic planning. Neither did I receive any support on these. This has left me on a blank journey, a journey of experience where I failed. I learned then I applied the necessary planning. Hence, if I were aware of these skills, it would have saved lots of my time and energy, and my business would never have to face a massive downfall..”

10. Can you share your opinion on how to overcome these barriers?

“Education is most important factor for any development. So, to achieve that economy and develop women entrepreneurship.. then everybody should be educated. awareness programmes should be available and textbook regarding entrepreneurship should be included from primary level.”

Appendix 7: Interview Transcript- Business Development Organizations

Transcript #1: P01

1. Could you please introduce yourself like.?

Age: 35

Gender: Male

Educational Level: Postgraduate

Marital status: Married

Business experience in years: 15 years

No. of branches you supervise: 8

Position: *Vice Chairman*, FNCCI

2. Can you briefly tell me about your firm and services offered by your organization to entrepreneurs? Is it for specific entrepreneurs? If yes, please mention.

“FNCCI, established in 1965 is the nationally and internationally recognized umbrella organisation of business in Nepal with the aim of promoting business and Industry..... It provides inter alia, information, advisory, consultative promotional and representative services to business and government and organizes training/workshop/seminar on a regular basis. We provide services like establishment of women entrepreneurship development committee within district and municipality chambers of Commerce and Industry, Regional workshop on women problems and prospects, Buyer sellers meeting for market promotion, Interaction program on relevant topics for WED such as marketing, networking, Training program on entrepreneurship development, skill development training, etc we aim to encourage women entrepreneurs in the field of business and industries, and it's for everybody not only for women.”

3. What difference do you find in services, business environment setting, programmes offered to women entrepreneurs and male entrepreneurs?

“ Well to be very honest, the services, the provision, programmes for women and men are more or like same, in fact we focus more to women than men.... But this is also sad part that despite of focusing and encouraging so much on women entrepreneurship, the status is still low in compared to men.”

4. Do you consider women entrepreneurs face more barriers while doing business than males? If yes, please explain.

“Ahhhhmmmm!!!! Well, it's very difficult to answer as the situation might vary from gender to gender... overall yes I would say women had to face ...tackle...handle... some circumstances like the cultural aspect of women in Nepal... then their families, etc makes up a barrier to them to enter entrepreneurship field whereas.... Men just can enter if they have fund to invest with them.... “

5. In your opinion, is lack of financial resources, legal restrictions, socio-cultural support, balancing family and work life and lack of access to training and educational programmes is major barriers for women entrepreneurs? If yes, please explain how?

“ It’s obvious that financial constraints are faced by all types of entrepreneurs, no matter you are from developed or developing countries... then... if we talk about Nepalese aspect.. then yes... socio- culture plays a vital role to form other barriers like you have mentioned balancing work and personal life...trainings and education and some laws are gendered based in this country... “

6. Do you have any other barriers in your mind that you consider the main barriers to women entrepreneurs other than the one mentioned above? If yes, please explain.

“There is a massive gap in mentoring your student. There are some exceptions with teachers and some students who are not enthusiastic and go through the motion. But as a general rule, a mentorship culture believed to be essential with the vital distinction being the match of personalities and the extension of said culture to outside the valley... a free mind, lack of pressure, a practical approach to entrepreneurship through creating a dummy company....project work start-up internship among others should be done to transition from a system based more on rote-learning and grade-based system to one that focuses on the practicality of the pedagogy if we want to empower women and boost the women entrepreneurship status in Nepal and also yes, the entrepreneurial mindset should be strong whether its men, women or young entrepreneurs...in my 15 years of service towards entrepreneurship development in Nepal... I have seen that only those strong-minded entrepreneurs survive in this competitive business environment...and entrepreneurial mindset is critical if we are talking about women entrepreneurs ...it’s because women go through lots of barriers especially socio-cultural....they have lots of commitment apart from their business hence, she should have a solid entrepreneurial mindset to accomplish if she wants to be successful women entrepreneurs in Nepal. One of the main issues of Nepali business entrepreneurs is sharing knowledge, collaboration, supervising this between different actors in the ecosystem of business does not often happen, especially regarding skill training and sharing learnings. It also stems from a lack of information and data tracking the type and effectiveness of training programmes provided....and any subsequent analysis of its outcomes. Especially women entrepreneurs are not innovative in providing training, although that has started to change in the past two to three years. Innovation in technical and interpersonal skills is significant for progressing and boosting our economy. However, we lack the policy capacity, the technical and cultural capability to share learnings across training .and a focus on evidence-based policy. I don’t know why women prefer women advisers. I am a male. I have coach

almost 50-55 women entrepreneurs. I feel they all are comfortable with me. This is a business, not a job, so they need someone to guide, so whether the mentor or adviser is male or female, I don't think it's an issue. The issue here is mentorship. I try to reach out to many entrepreneurs, especially women, so that I can help them. Still, women entrepreneurship lacks the idea of a need for mentoring. Hence, I feel that women entrepreneurs need a mentor or advisor to progress or even run their business properly.”

7. What do you think should be done to overcome the barriers faced by women entrepreneurs and promote women entrepreneurship in Nepal?

“We have been promoting about the programmes and events to develop the status of women from all possible ways.. we really want women to come out of those four walls and use their talents as this country needs such talents and working population.... So, all the women if they are interested then they should break the ceiling and reach out to the organization like us... then we can really guide and channel their abilities... likewise government also should continuously work to promote the women entrepreneurship in Nepal. Everybody should be educated especially women, because we cannot change their motherly behaviour just like that... but if all women are educated with formal education.. then at least they can pass down to the generation.. one woman should encourage another woman.”

Transcript #2: P02

1. Could you please introduce yourself like.?

Age: 45

Gender: Female

Educational Level: Postgraduate

Marital status: Married

Business experience in years: 10 years +

No. of branches you supervise: 5

Position: General Secretary, FWEAN

2. Can you briefly tell me about your firm and services offered by your organization to entrepreneurs? Is it for specific entrepreneurs? If yes, please mention.

“Well... FWEAN is a non-government, non-political and non-profitable organisation aiming at representing the collective efforts of women entrepreneurs in the economic progress of the nation and decision making at national and international levels. FWEAN is the apex body of WEAN which was established in 1989. FWEAN is a focal point for interaction not only with the government, but also with various national and international women's organisations. The Federation ultimately seeks to redefine the perspective of women entrepreneurship through contribution to economic growth and poverty alleviation towards participation of women at all levels in the socio-economic sectors. FWEAN is the focal point for networking and strengthening WEAN chapters at the district levels of Nepal. FWEAN networks effectively as a co-coordinating organisation that supports the interest of women entrepreneurs in Nepal, through effective lobbying for relevant policies and programmes on women's issues with government and non- government organisations for national, socio-economic development. Build linkages and affiliations at the regional and international level for joint promotional entrepreneurial activities, annual exchange of visits for trade and inter exchange of services, setting up of intra country cooperative, focusing on promotion and marketing of products of women entrepreneurs. This is specifically for women entrepreneurs of Nepal to develop the status and empower women. “

3. What difference do you find in terms of services, business environment setting, programmes offered to women entrepreneurs and male entrepreneurs?

“ Ummmmhhh....well being biased.. women are very humble and polite in our country... generally... so most of the women prefer female advisor... mentor... because they feel comfortable to talk to women about anything.... Plus... government lacks funds to provide provision to poor women.. whereas there are so many options to men..... but since there are many programmes and trainings provided these days to women specially.”

4. Do you consider women entrepreneurs face more barriers while doing business than male? If yes, please explain.

“ Yes they do... the main thing is the divided gender roles... stigma.... A women should do this... she should be at home looking after kids... these are main barriers they need to break... then comes other barriers like you have mentioned.... Finance.. family life... legal, etc.”

5. In your opinion, is lack of financial resources, legal restrictions, socio-cultural support, balancing family and work life and lack of access to training and educational programmes is major barriers for women entrepreneurs? If yes, please explain how?

“ Yes definitely, these are the barriers like fund, investment, capital, etc. all these terms come first on entrepreneurs mind when it comes to doing business...especially in Nepal. Nepal is a developing country. Hence when it comes to accessing money, it's tough. The banking and other financial institute has not flourished yet when it comes to funding entrepreneurs. There are lots of paperwork. Also, since Nepal has a culture of patriarchal property, women barely have something they own on their names. This makes the biggest barriers of a women entrepreneurs to invest even for Rs. 1 lakh -Rs 150 lakh business. Education must be reformed especially so in rural areas, and local areas Education, specifically in business undergraduate colleges have become more relevant to entrepreneurial development, but there's a long way to go.”

6. Do you have any other barriers in your mind that you consider the main barriers to women entrepreneurs other than the one mentioned above? If yes, please explain.

“ Most of the businesses that women are setting up are in terms of the sector are hobby businesses or lifestyle businesses, so they tend to be things that can be run from home and very rarely tend to be from shops. So, they don't tend to have large investment projects. They tend to things that they can start quite small, fit around their children or their husbands or their partners or family life. I probably have got a handful of small female entrepreneurs that have taken forward their businesses. Still, they tend to be single and don't have any children. So, I think that part of the reasons it is but outside of the programme, many examples of women who have got children who have got families are running successful programmes. Still, I am not saying that is a 174 factor to why they are successful but certainly from the women I have supported that are successful have a certain profile.”

7. What do you think should be done to overcome the barriers faced by women entrepreneurs and promote women entrepreneurship in Nepal?

“Umm... yeah the government interventions like consulting, implementing more legislation like tax relief...they need to encourage the financial institutions, credit facilitators and lending

institutions as well.....as Nepal has high rate of unemployment... women entrepreneurship definitely contribute reducing unemployment... the government need to raise awareness about these.... The crimes happening to women should be minimised and women should be protected.. they should feel safe first to do anything... there should be change even with the existing women entrepreneurs.... Change related with the attitudes...ways of thinking, etc. One successful women entrepreneur should act as role model to other women. This awareness can be achieved via social networking sites.. TV, news, etc”

Transcript #3: P03

1. Could you please introduce yourself like.?

Age: 60

Gender: Female

Educational Level: Bachelor

Marital status: Widow

Business experience in years: 25 years +

No. of branches you supervise: 10

Position: President, MEDEP

2. Can you briefly tell me about your firm and services offered by your organization to entrepreneurs? Is it for specific entrepreneurs? If yes, please mention.

“In order to meet the economic necessities of the rural people and to help those who are living below the poverty line the Government of Nepal and UNDP entered into a technical collaboration to promote off farm employment and income generating opportunities. The partnership between the Nepal Government and the UNDP established MEDEP in July 1998 in 10 districts of Nepal covering two districts each from the five development regions. The development aim of the program is to contribute to the government's efforts to reduce poverty in the country. MEDEP goals are two folds one to reduce poverty among low-income families in rural areas and the other is to ensure the institutional development and capacity building of local service delivery organisations to work as catalysts in the development of rural micro-enterprise sector. The aim of the programme is to help low-income families become entrepreneurs, promote the development of their enterprises and to help and support the promotion of micro-enterprises on sustainable footing.”

3. What difference do you find in terms of services, business environment setting, programmes offered to women entrepreneurs and male entrepreneurs?

“ I do not think there are any difference for men and women... the programmes.... Trainings.. events are carried out for both men and women...”

4. Do you consider women entrepreneurs face more barriers while doing business than male? If yes, please explain.

“ Well! Well!! Yes there are many barriers that women entrepreneurs had to face and tackle in compared to men. For example, they had to go through their family’s permission to take any decision whether its small or big.. but son in the house can do anything without any consents... plus if the women is married and have kids... then other responsibilities they must bear along with professional life.... so... I won’t lie... but women do face more than men.”

5. In your opinion, is lack of financial resources, legal restrictions, socio-cultural support, balancing family and work life and lack of access to training and educational programmes is major barriers for women entrepreneurs? If yes, please explain how?

“Yes....Colleges and universities need facilities like business incubators ideas like ‘thesis to the businesses and global learnings and methodologies like the ‘lean business model’ An environment of collaboration and a multidisciplinary approach is missing. The current way business and management education in Kathmandu, generally in Nepal, is designed to make us job-seekers rather than job-creators.”

6. Do you have any other barriers in your mind that you consider the main barriers to women entrepreneurs other than the one mentioned above? If yes, please explain.

“In the history of my service.. I can say that or believe proper entrepreneurial mindset is lacking in women.... the collective entrepreneurial mindset of people should shift from the perception that only business students do business, or engineering students do only engineering. Tech entrepreneurship is rising, and they face their unique issues. Social issues aren’t yet fully embedded with technological solutions. People are tech-savvy but not in ways beneficial to their entrepreneurial drive. The use of technology has been limited in a communication way

only and not in a way that helps others. But capacitating skilled people is not enough. Retaining skilled people is another challenge, and perhaps the hardest one”

7. What do you think should be done to overcome the barriers faced by women entrepreneurs and promote women entrepreneurship in Nepal?

“ I will speak on behalf of the organizations.... In my opinions.. we must develop some kinds of educational packages.. modules... or course that can teach female entrepreneurs’ skills that they lack or at least provide some information which are not easy to get...which are time convenient. There should be more of one- to -one support for women entrepreneurs.. and for women entrepreneurs out there they should do the proper homework first if they want to succeed rather than just trying and failing.”

Transcript #4: P04

1. Could you please introduce yourself like.?

Age: 31

Gender: Male

Educational Level: Bachelor

Marital status: Single

Business experience in years: 5 years

No. of branches you supervise: 2

Position: Treasurer, WCS

2. Can you briefly tell me about your firm and services offered by your organization to entrepreneurs? Is it for specific entrepreneurs? If yes, please mention.

“ Okay...WCS is a co-operative financing organisation promoted by 28 women promoters.... established in January. 1995 under the Co-operative Act, 1922, to uplift the socio-economic condition of rural as well as urban women through access to financial services and other development.. The main mission or objective of WCS is to develop itself as a special financial institution to provide easy access to financial services for women in urban and rural areas and assist in alleviating poverty through women empowerment by raising their economic and social status. WCS provides two types of services to women entrepreneurs: one is financial service and second is non-financial services. Under financial service it provides various credit facilities

and micro credit scheme provided through groups on the village level. Under non-Financial Service it provides pre-group training, leadership training, health and hygiene, social awareness, and development training, EDP training and counselling, computer training, vegetable farming, goat raising, candle making, soap making, enterprise development training, beauty parlour training and business management training. All of WCS's programmes are focused on the Kathmandu Valley.”

3. What difference do you find in terms of services, business environment setting, programmes offered to women entrepreneurs and male entrepreneurs?

“ I’m sorry, I don’t find any differences yet.”

4. Do you consider women entrepreneurs face more barriers while doing business than male? If yes, please explain.

“ There is clear evidence that shows that yes women entrepreneurs do face unconditional number of barriers than men entrepreneurs. I believe.. it is because.. this is how we are brought up in the society... men have full liberty... even I am a man... so yes I do have responsibilities to feed my family.... But I don’t have to do the household chores... look after the kids... or scared of the society... whereas women have thousands of issues to tackle for their daily operation... imagine... if that woman wants to start business... she has to go through lots.”

5. In your opinion, is lack of financial resources, legal restrictions, socio-cultural support, balancing family and work life and lack of access to training and educational programmes is major barriers for women entrepreneurs? If yes, please explain how?

“ Yes these are major barriers along with other barriers. I mean these are the basic barriers where I can say.. professionally that all women must go through.... I can say that these are evident barriers... the new women entrepreneurs must be very aware of these barriers...”

6. Do you have any other barriers in your mind that you consider the main barriers to women entrepreneurs other than the one mentioned above? If yes, please explain.

“ Ummm... well.....It is you know we have had beforeif they can bring children with them, to be perfectly honest, we would never say no, but we don't encourage that because... this is about businesses, and you wouldn't take a to a business meeting..... with you so you shouldn't be really doing this. However,..... we are considerate to people with different needs in different times. So, I would say we have a flexible approach to it. I believe the main reason why women entrepreneurs are lagging is because of entrepreneurial mindset. They themselves feel that at certain point... or after certain point of accomplishment.. they should stop and then their progressions become stagnant..... most of the women entrepreneurs put full stop after realising certain profit. They don't go beyond those thinking..... hence she never should put full stop on anything if she wants to progress. Most skilled people seem to migrate to developed nations, and although part of the recent interest in entrepreneurship among women can be explained due to relatively high women unemployment levels, it is not the first choice for women to work in. While women entrepreneurship fosters employment, economy, and development, most women are reluctant to become entrepreneurs.”

7. What do you think should be done to overcome the barriers faced by women entrepreneurs and promote women entrepreneurship in Nepal?

“ Our Nepal government plays a very crucial role in uplifting the economy by promoting entrepreneurship... and if it's for women .. then the government should take extra measure and initiatives... women themselves should work on themselves first... then organization like us should be more visible to all types of women from school till they graduate their masters. I know there are so many childcare issues with women entrepreneurs, government should talk responsibilities by building childcare facilities with proper care.. education must be provided to all even in very undeveloped areas of Nepal. There should be support from family and friends.”

Appendix 8: Previous studies on women entrepreneurship

From the previous section, the concept of women entrepreneurship has mentioned many characteristics that women entrepreneurs possess. Hence, according to Rao & Joshi (2013), "A study on Entrepreneurial characteristics and success of women entrepreneurs operating fashion

and apparel business" focused on analysing the entrepreneurial characteristics with the success of women entrepreneurs operating micro, small and medium scale fashion, and apparel enterprises. A self-administered questionnaire was employed to collect the data from the sample in the study area. For this purpose, the women entrepreneurs classify into four levels of success based on the employment generation and the sales turnover. Cross tabulation to show the significance of the different entrepreneurial characteristics and the success of women entrepreneurs. Analysing entrepreneurial characteristics in terms of human capital reveals that education, training in the specific sector and prior experience help operate the enterprise successfully. The study on entrepreneurial intensity suggests that successful entrepreneurs run a considerable risk in operating and expanding enterprises. According to the study's findings on entrepreneurial motivation, regardless of their level of success, most woman entrepreneurs are motivated to start a business by their dreams and desires. It is a crucial thing when establishing and running a company. According to the literature, entrepreneurship is a complex phenomenon with no cause credited to success. His research aimed to compile a list of entrepreneurial characteristics that could aid in the success of a business.

The study of Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development [OECD (2013)] addresses two related issues: distinguishing entrepreneurs from other economic agents and distinguishing women and men enterprises. Rai (1981) have also argued that female entrepreneurial activity is closely related to social and economic issues, mainly because women focus on their families. Armane et al. (2021) studied driving factors for women in Denmark to start their companies, their backgrounds, financing patterns, balancing work life and family and challenges in doing so. She reported that personal motivations, business ideas, perceptions and characteristics play a critical role in acting entrepreneurially. Women in their natural environment and have their well-established network are more often pulled to become entrepreneurs, while international women expose to conditions that push them to start their businesses. Women often have intrinsic motives behind their business activities. Women have a preference to start small without making significant investments. Business growth is not a priority for women who emphasise work-life balance.

A study conducted by Budlender and Moussie (2013) " Empower Women - Making Care Visible Women's Unpaid Care Work in Nepal, Nigeria, Uganda and Kenya", among 200 trained women entrepreneurs who have participated in entrepreneurship training at Central Bank of Nigeria (CNB) Entrepreneurship Development Centre. The findings from the 200 trainee's sampled shows that the need for independence is the primary reason women start a business.

The broad objective of this study was to investigate the effect of entrepreneurship training on women business activities. In addition, the study had the following specific objectives:

1. To investigate the factor(s) that motivates women to be entrepreneurial.
2. To investigate the characteristics of women business owners in Nigeria.

They used structured questionnaires to gather quantitative data using a stratified random sampling procedure and analysed the data using descriptive statistics. The study showed that most respondents used their funds to start their business and operate home-based and unregistered businesses that could hardly pay a levy for their business operation. Contrary to the traditional buying and selling businesses women did in the past, businesses in the service sector are gradually taking over.

From the empirical study by Akingunola & Onayemi (2010) on "The Role of Informal Finance in the Development of Women Micro-Businesses in Nigeria. A Case Study of Ogun and the Ohio States" by analysing statistically, both primary and secondary data set collected for the purpose. The objective of this paper was to establish the extent of women accessibility to finance and discover the relevance of microcredits in financing businesses owned by women in the informal sector of the economy. Their study conducted questionnaires among 500 women from the target audience in five Ogun and Oyo States towns. Their study focused on household type targets that focused on the source of credit, assessment of eligibility to access a loan, the rate of interest on a loan, utilisation pattern of credit. The research concluded that insignificant proportions (respondents) of women entrepreneurs patronised traditional commercial banks for loans, implying the need to provide alternatives to formal institutions and the increasing need to encourage informal micro-finance groups. The research further found that formal financial institutions may not discriminate against women; instead, they were unable to satisfy their credit needs because of the low-income yielding propensity of their businesses and the inability of these women micro-entrepreneurs to provide acceptable collateral securities.

Furthermore, Wube (2010) studied the "Factors affecting the performance of women entrepreneurs in Micro and Small Enterprises". It also addressed the characteristics of women entrepreneurs in MSEs and their enterprises. A descriptive survey research design was employed to assess the key factors that affect the performance of women entrepreneurs in MSEs in Dessie town. The study has used stratified and simple random sampling to sample 203 women entrepreneurs engaged in 5 sectors. The study results indicate the personal characteristics of women entrepreneurs in MSEs, and their enterprise affects their performance. It also shows that lack of own premises (land), financial access, competition, inadequate access

to training, access to technology and access to raw materials were the key economic factors that affect the performance of women entrepreneurs in MSEs. The study also found that the significant social factors that affect these entrepreneurs were conflicting gender roles, social acceptability, and network with outsiders.

Similarly, Chotkan (2009) studied a comparison between Surinamese female entrepreneurs in Suriname and Surinamese female entrepreneurs in the Netherlands. The factors considered are family support, business growth, motivation, gender effect. In her study, she found a positive influence on their career choice and that the family is supportive towards their choice and size of the firm does not matter, but their high level of motivation creates growth automatically. On the other hand, the female entrepreneurs in the Netherlands lack self-confidence when it concerns the growth of their business, and women in developed countries like the Netherlands are more often 'pulled' into entrepreneurship. In contrast, women in developing countries as Suriname are more often pushed' into entrepreneurship due to economic circumstances.

Unlike Wube (2010) and Choktan (2009), who focused on the barriers to women entrepreneurs, Hackler, Harpel & Mayer (2008) investigated the relationship between human capital elements and self-employment among women. The study found that most human capital variables differ from self-employed women from salaried and wage-earning women. The research also found that self-employed women had a higher college attainment rate than working women. By comparing self-employed women to other working women, the number of women in managerial positions is higher. This research has revealed the similarities and differences in the circumstances of self-employed men and women. In terms of schooling, experience, and training, self-employed men and women are almost identical. The most significant distinction, though, is in occupational and industry experience. Self-employed women have a lower percentage of the workforce in management occupations than self-employed men. In sectors such as communication, transportation, wholesale trade, manufacturing, and construction, self-employed women have lower participation rates than self-employed men.

However, the study "Managerial Competencies and Venture Survival: The Case of Women Entrepreneurs Owner – Managers of Micro-Small Enterprises (MSEs) in Khartoum State – Sudan " by Rahman (2020) investigated the management competencies of female entrepreneurs' owner-managers of micro-small enterprises (MSEs) within urban settings in Khartoum State, Sudan. It addresses a knowledge gap in the literature regarding the

competencies of female entrepreneurs in Sudan. It is an exploratory study that follows an interpretive approach and applies Grounded Theory techniques. According to the study findings, the competency levels possessed by owner-managers (MSEs) vary by competency area, line of activity, venture type, and entrepreneur attributes. Female entrepreneurs typically adhere to a relational management style and follow a pragmatic approach, with a high capacity to adapt innovatively to complex operational conditions, supported by their networks. Further enhancing some competency areas through education and skill development programs is recommended to ensure venture survival and success.

To sum up, the study is beneficial in understanding the methodologies in conducting research. The study was analysed and discussed using various metrics like age, marital status, education, social status, family members support, types of activities, location of the business, constraints. The study also provided guidance on analysing the characteristics of women entrepreneurs and on explaining the style of business operations by women entrepreneurs. Further, the study also discussed the constraints factors those women of Sudan faced while conducting their business. A few constraints were sexual harassment, difficulties in getting funds, illiteracy and lack of knowledge and skills, time constraints, negative stereotyping of women's market, gender-power relations, and lack of regulatory laws. These constraints are no different from what women entrepreneurs in Nepal face. Hence, this study serves as guidance in discussing those in Nepal.

From a different perspective, Ranasinghe (2008) identified the factors contributing to women's entrepreneurial success. Findings were from six successful women entrepreneurs from six different businesses. The findings are captured through the qualitative research method according to the conceptual framework developed. The key findings support the factors identified in the framework: early childhood experiences, psychological characteristics, entrepreneurial competencies, formal and informal learning, and external support; and an additional factor identified was culture to contribute to women's entrepreneurial success.

Agreeing with Ranasinghe (2008), the research on "Job Satisfaction of Women in Construction Trades" conducted by Dabke et al. (2008a) was to assess the perceived importance and satisfaction level associated with work elements for tradeswomen. The objectives of this study were (a) to summarise existing research and literature on women in construction trades and evaluate studies performed on job satisfaction of construction workers in the United States, (b) to determine the level of satisfaction or dissatisfaction related to work factors, i.e. "work",

"pay", "supervision", "opportunities for promotion", "people on the job", and "job in general," and to analyse the relationships that exist between these satisfaction measures and demographic variables. These variables include age, education, number of dependents, number of trade years, duration of work, and frequency of work outside the local area. The researchers accomplished the first objective by conducting a comprehensive online literature review of 12 databases and a bibliographical search. To meet the second objective, the researchers developed a questionnaire to collect information about demographics importance and corresponding satisfaction related to work elements from women working in construction trades in and around the metropolitan areas of Cincinnati, Ohio. Survey with thirty-nine tradeswomen from the Cincinnati area to assess their satisfaction or dissatisfaction with construction work. The study concluded that research on women in the construction trades is limited. No study has provided empirical evidence regarding perceptions of tradeswomen about the different elements of construction work. Although survey among a few female workers in the past surveys of construction workers, no study has compared their perceptions with men. Studies on motivation and job satisfaction of construction workers neither identify nor compare perceptions of tradeswomen about their work. This exploratory study showed that pay, benefits, and job security are most important to women in their occupations. Although tradeswomen appear to be satisfied with the nature of work in construction trades, this is not the case regarding pay, benefits, and job security. Demographic variables did not affect job satisfaction for women in the construction trades. To develop appropriate programmes and guidelines, manage a diverse workforce, there is a need to study the perceptions of tradeswomen about their work.

Unruh et al. (2014) studied "The characteristics of successful Nigerian Women Entrepreneurs", where he focused on describing the characteristics of Nigerian Women entrepreneurs who have been successful in their business venture. This paper attempts to understand who these successful women are and their trademarks for success. A questionnaire survey results from 75 respondents identified themselves as female Nigerian Entrepreneurs and have achieved recognised success in their businesses. It provides insight into these women's personal and business experiences to give a broad picture of successful women. The study addresses personal profile, business profile, motivations, problems encountered on their way to success, and the success formulae. A questionnaire survey for this study over six months in 1992/2000, consisting of eight sections: 1. Personal Background; 2. family Background; 3. Previous Work Experience; 4. Background on existing Business; 5. Business Experience; 6. Motivation for

Starting Business; 7. Problems Encountered; 8. Attitudes toward Success. The questionnaire comprised a total of 37 questions. Some significant findings were that successful women entrepreneurs have no education than unsuccessful ones. Among the successful entrepreneurs, 70% had a university degree, whereas only 23% of the less successful were university graduates—almost two out of five (38% women entrepreneurs owned one business. The rest owned more than one business. 25% owned two businesses, 27% owned three businesses, while 10% owned more than three businesses. It worked out to an average of two businesses per entrepreneur. Overall, 39% of women-owned businesses were in service, 29% retail, 21% wholesale, and 11% manufacturing. About two-thirds (64%) of the businesses were private limited companies; the rest were partnerships (21%), sole proprietorships (14%) and public companies (1%). About two out of five (43%) women entrepreneurs employed family members. The family members included siblings (28%), spouse or fiancé (20%), parents (10%) and children (10%). When asked where their source of financing for starting the business came from, 83% of women entrepreneurs indicated that they used their savings. Other sources of finance came from family, relatives, or friends (50%), banks (28%). The successful women entrepreneurs seemed to be the ones likely to have initiated the idea of starting the business than the less successful ones. Among the successful women entrepreneurs, the need to support the family also seemed to be greater than that of the less successful ones. The successful entrepreneurs seemed to have faced more social problems than the less successful ones (significant at $P = 0.05$). 67% of the successful women faced this problem compared to 29% of the less successful ones. It meant that at the start-up stage of the business, the successful women felt discriminated against in the male-dominated business community, probably due to gender prejudice.

In contrast, Carter et al. (2003) conducted a literature review and study of over four hundred academic articles directly focused on women entrepreneurship. Their studies indicated that most studies include descriptive accounts of the characteristics and motivations of women in business and their experiences. Within more recent studies, specialist themes have emerged in finance, business networks and performance.

Brush (1992) observed that men and women entrepreneurs differ very little concerning demographic and psychological variables, while more pronounced differences exist in business goals and management styles. Similarly, Minniti, Arenius & Langowitz (2005) found that the factors influencing female and male entrepreneurship tend to be the same. However, despite

these similarities, women participation rates in entrepreneurship are systematically below men. Greene, Han & Marlow (2013) provides a possible answer to this puzzle by suggesting the existence of differences in average human and social capital.

Certain studies like Singh & Sengupta (1986) on women entrepreneurs have attended entrepreneurship development programmes. The conclusion was that a woman entrepreneur gets dominated by either education or lack of it. Educated women perceived entrepreneurship as a challenge, ambition fulfilment, and doing something fruitful, whereas less educated entrepreneurs had clarity about their projects but needed moral support from males and other family members to set up their enterprises.

Conversely, Cooper & Javier (1990) proposed that three factors influence entrepreneurship "antecedent influences" (i.e., background factors such as family influences and genetic factors that affect motivation, skills and knowledge), the "incubator organisation" (i.e., the nature of the organisation that the entrepreneur employs in just prior to starting a business, the skills learned there), and "environmental factors" (e.g., economic conditions access to venture capital and support services; role models). Hence, research from western nations indicates that women and men differ on some of the above factors. For example, women have more significant difficulties in acquiring venture capital, lack financial resources and skills (Heemskerck, 2003), have fewer informal support systems and networks (Drine & Grach, 2012), and have less direct, relevant experience than men (e.g., Stevenson, 1986). Other obstacles women entrepreneurs face acceptance as a woman in business, lack of a role model, lack of professional interaction, difficulties in gaining the confidence of their clients and suppliers, lack of adequate training, and lack of related experience (Berglund, 2007).

While these are important issues, many researchers feel that tension between personal lives and career pursuits is the most significant problem women entrepreneurs face (Berglund, 2007). For example, Goffee & Scase (1982) found that tension between personal life and career was a significant problem for these women in a study on female entrepreneurs in Florida. Spouses are generally not very involved in their wives' businesses, are not supportive of them, and expect them to continue their household duties despite their business demands. Therefore, it is not surprising that confining women to private, domestic roles until recently. The role of the entrepreneur did not conform to the traditional roles expected that women play in society. These factors and others may result in female owners facing more work-family conflicts than their male counterparts. While the primary reasons for starting a business are similar for men

and women, the researchers found some differences. For example, according to Mariotti (2007), the potential for financial gain was not the primary motivating factor for women; women were more likely to start a business for the challenge and opportunity for self-fulfilment. Other researchers have suggested that women are more likely to start a business for control over the quantity and quality of work and as an option to limitations in career advancement (Chinomona & Maziriri, 2015).

Appendix 9: Motivation and Management factor for women entrepreneur

Individuals' desire to engage in entrepreneurial activity differs (Verheul et al., 2010). Being an entrepreneur has different motivations for different social categories, such as being a member of an ethnic or religious minority community, an immigrant (Smith-Hunter, 2003). Entrepreneurs start and run companies for various purposes, and they follow through with their plans if they feel they will be able to build long-term value and profit (Mariotti & Glackin, 2013). On the other hand, motivation is crucial (Verheul et al., 2010). Some people want to be self-sufficient; as a result, they want to become entrepreneurs due to opportunities, whilst others become entrepreneurs due to need (Botha, 2014; Frederick et al., 2012; Westhead & Wright, 2013).

Entrepreneurial motivations are "pull forces," under which entrepreneurs start a company because of a perceived opportunity presented by business concepts (Eijdenberg & Masurel, 2013; Ikupolati et al., 2017). These elements are known as "attraction" variables (Bruni, Gherardi, & Poggio, 2004). For example, independence, drive, self-interest, self-fulfilment, status, power, and a desire for riches are all "pull" factors that can entice someone to start a business (Botha, 2014; Orhan & Scott, 2001). Therefore, this entrepreneur is an "opportunity entrepreneur" (Botha, 2014; Frederick et al., 2012).

Any entrepreneurship motivations are "push factors," in which entrepreneurs start a company due to a pressing need (Eijdenberg & Masurel, 2013; Ikupolati et al., 2017). These are "compulsion" factors (Bruni et al., 2004b), and the entrepreneurs are "necessity entrepreneurs" (Botha, 2014; Frederick et al., 2012). "Opportunity entrepreneurship refers to attempts to launch a business "to take advantage of a business opportunity," while need entrepreneurship occurs because "there are very few choices for work" (Verheul et al., 2010, p. 4). Several studies have found that some individuals start a business due to opportunity and necessity motivations, rather than just one of them (Verheul et al., 2010).

Li, Bao, & Jiang (2013) conducted a study in "Leadership styles of Entrepreneurial Women in Eastern China: Characteristics and Differences". This study explored the Leadership Style (LS) among entrepreneurial women in eastern Zhejiang Province and Shanghai in China by surveying 225 entrepreneurial women selected randomly from economically developed. The participants were launching or operating their business ventures under the influence of a robust entrepreneurial atmosphere that currently prevails in the developed areas in eastern China and to realise their value better. The women were primarily opportunity-based entrepreneurs.

The objective of the survey is to interpret the characteristics and differences among the LS of a group of entrepreneurial women in eastern China. The authors researched several studies on women's entrepreneurship ranging from the 1970s to the 2000s. To conduct this study, the authors distributed questionnaires through three channels:

1. They surveyed women studying the Executive Master of Business Administration program in a Chinese university distributed to their class teachers.
2. The researchers themselves and their friends and relatives directly distributed questionnaires to their women acquaintances or friends who were entrepreneurs.
3. The researchers sent questionnaires to the class advisors of two primary schools in a city in Zhejiang Province, and women who were entrepreneurs were from among the parents of children attending these primary schools.

The study from the Leader Behavior Description Questionnaire (LBDQ) interprets the characteristics of the LS of entrepreneurial women. The questionnaire studies two dimensions of leadership, i.e. (i) the extent to which a leader applies management functions to define the roles of leaders and group members, initiates action, organises group activities, and establishes well-defined working patterns and (ii) the extent to which a leader exhibits concern and respect for the members of the group. According to how each participant performed in the questionnaire, each entrepreneur was in four leadership styles, i.e., directive, participative, supportive, and achievement oriented. The result concluded that most of the women adopted an achievement-oriented leadership style. In addition, there were differences in both initiating structure and consideration leadership styles of the women entrepreneurs. According to the length of time, the women's enterprise was working had been established. Li, Bao, and Jiang used Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) 16.0 to do all their statistical analysis.

In summary, the research work of Li, Bao, and Jiang was instrumental in understanding the leadership style adopted by the women entrepreneurs. Further, it also confirmed that women could possess masculine and feminine traits while running their businesses. The percentage of women having both masculine and feminine traits was highest among senior female managers.

An article called "Entrepreneurial Women and the Business of Self Development in Global Russia" by Mazzarino (2013). She focused on women in small and medium-sized businesses. The article is on ethnographic fieldwork with women who occupied management positions in St. Petersburg and Moscow firms. To understand how women forged a social niche for themselves, she conducted nineteen months of fieldwork between 2005 and 2010 with highly educated managerial women and their families, spouses, romantic partners, colleagues, and friends. Research methods included participant observation in professional, domestic, and recreational settings in addition to a series of semi-structured interviews with each of the twenty-six women who served as key informants.

In conclusion, the author points out that women's personalised approaches to change worked against the epistemic violence of their inability to see themselves in Russian politics, the media or popular culture. It took effort and social collaboration to say that they wanted something for themselves rather than to subscribe to a collective good, not of their choosing. Furthermore, with their definitions of women's identities and interests, women did not want their interests circumscribed by someone else, whether contemporary political institutions or foreign feminist groups.

Research conducted by Bhardwaj et al. (2011) on "Women Entrepreneurship in India." is intended to find out various motivating and demotivating internal and external factors of women entrepreneurship. It is an attempt to quantify some for non-parametric factors to give the sense of ranking. These factors also suggest eliminating and reducing hurdles of women entrepreneurship development in the Indian context. The main objective of this study was to identify the reason for women for involving themselves in entrepreneurial activities, identify the factors of a hindrance for women entrepreneurship, determine the possible success factors for women in such entrepreneurial activities, and evaluate people's opinions about women entrepreneurship. This study was on primary and secondary data. The secondary data is from a review of past researchers and other reports. The factors are categorised as factors responsible for hindrance, starting the business, and success in women entrepreneurship. Eliminating barriers to women's entrepreneurship involves a significant shift in people's traditional attitudes

and mindsets, rather than focusing only on creating opportunities for women. The most fundamental prerequisite for developing women's entrepreneurship is to be conscious of their own life, unique identity, and contribution to its economic growth and development. Therefore, entrepreneurs should be in women's minds from an early age. Women's entrepreneurship may be aided by including a skill training package, and the government can prioritise women's entrepreneurship. The research attempted to determine the differences in critical factors affecting women's entrepreneurship opportunities in general among different groups of people. So, it should be with actual entrepreneurs. Women's entrepreneurship is essential for developing every economy, big or small, regardless of the factors that influence it.

According to Botha et al. (2015), African American women have the highest percentage of businesses owned by women in the US. However, social barriers and economic challenges unique to African American women make their success persisting beyond the 5-year start-up average astounding. The purpose of the study was to identify the motivational factors that influenced African American women to pursue entrepreneurship. It also explored how Black women business owners use those motivators to lead their organisations. The methodologies used were four open-ended interview questions. The researcher interviewed 6 African American women entrepreneurs who resided locally in her place of business with their permission. The concluding remark of their research was that driving motivators for entrepreneurship are the pursuit of happiness and passion for the work, ability to achieve work-life balance contributes to success as an entrepreneur, community involvement is a responsibility, reluctance to talk about barriers, and education is essential to sustaining business. C.S. & Mishra (2019) support Botha et.al (2011) that women most often found businesses to meet personal goals, such as gaining feelings of achievement and accomplishment. Sinha (2007) studied the issues, initiatives, and experiences in developing women entrepreneurs in South Asia. They focused on women entrepreneurs in the formal sector rather than micro-enterprises and stated that women's family obligations often hinder them from being successful entrepreneurs in both developed and developing nations.

Similarly, Orsolya (2010) also studied female entrepreneurs' motivation for starting up and managing small and medium-sized businesses but in two Romanian counties, the two administratively identifiable territories of Harghita and Covasna counties. They found that women entrepreneurs from Szeklerland have average education, are more willing to study, participate in vocational training, have better communicative competence in the Romanian language, and many of them speak English as well. For most women, the entrepreneurial

activity must be compatible with family life, and almost everything is in the second place: individual self-fulfilment, professional success, and career development. Older women are less risk-taking entrepreneurs, rather organisational ones. Younger women are those who are willing to take on considerable financial risks; they are more flexible, more courageous, and are open to other kinds of "territories." In terms of entrepreneurship, they are much more dynamic. Only a small number of women can be called intentional entrepreneurs: they are the ones whose old dream and desire were to create an individually imagined job and an exceptional working environment. Independence occurs as a significant motivating effect: in those cases, for the non-forced entrepreneurs, the most important motivating effects were independence, income, and flexible working hours.

Cphoon, Wadhwa & Mitchell (2010) study presented a detailed exploration of entrepreneurs' motivations, backgrounds, and experiences for men and women entrepreneurs. The study is on the data collected from successful women entrepreneurs. Out of the 59% had founded two or more companies. The study identifies the top five financial and psychological factors motivating women to become entrepreneurs. These are desire to build wealth, and they wish to capitalise on business ideas they had; the appeal of start-up culture, a long-standing desire to own their own company and working with someone else did not appeal to them. The challenges are more related to entrepreneurship rather than gender. However, the study concluded with further investigation, such as why women are more concerned about protecting intellectual capital than their counterparts. Mentoring is critical to women, which provides encouragement and financial support of business partners, experiences, and a well-developed professional network.

Similarly, Gadar & Kamal (2009) conducted a study, "The Influence of Personality and Socio-Economic Factors on Female Entrepreneurship Motivations in Malaysia", among 685 Malaysian women to examine the entrepreneurs' background motivation factors personal characteristics, and perception of entrepreneurial behaviours. The authors collected data by using both interviews and questionnaires. Questionnaires included 76 closed-ended questions. The sample of 685 women covered all 13 countries in Malaysia, which were from five zones. The 685 registered entrepreneurs within the Malay Chamber of Commerce, Trade Association of Bumiputra Women and Women Entrepreneur Association in Malaysia. Analysing the data showed that most of the respondents were Malays, 618 (90%), and more than half of them aged

above 40 had three children or more. In addition, 70% of respondents had secondary qualifications, 10% were university graduates, and the remaining 20% had primary education.

Almost 50% of the respondents did not come from an entrepreneur's family background. The majority of respondents were engaged in various business types such as manufacturing, restaurant and café, transportation and business services. The result of the analysis further showed three main findings. First, the correlation analysis shows that an entrepreneur's income correlated very weak with education and experience levels. On the other hand, there is no correlation between entrepreneurial income and age. Third, except for the age factor, an entrepreneur's income differs significantly according to experience and education. Second, the study found that job dissatisfaction, retrenchment, and social networking were essential factors influencing female entrepreneurship. Finally, this study showed that the economic environment, such as technology and information, was the driving force for starting a business which contradicts earlier studies that found economic independence was the most crucial factor for women to start a business.

However, Balhara & Singh (2015) investigated women entrepreneurship in Lesotho and made practical recommendations to enhance women entrepreneurship. A survey that included 54 women-owned businesses were motivated by pull factors, such as the need for independence, self-fulfilment, work flexibility and a need for a challenge to self-employment. In addition, factors such as dissatisfaction with salaried jobs and insufficient family income pushed them into self-employment. However, they currently face obstacles, such as obtaining finances, work-home conflict, lack of education, and business and management skills training. They, furthermore, indicated financial support, business training and advice, the need to network with other business owners and marketing support as their primary support needs. Therefore, practical recommendations are suggested to Government and women entrepreneurs to overcome these obstacles and ensure that they can sufficiently contribute to the economy and empower themselves economically.

The analysis of women entrepreneurs by Goffee & Scase (2008) shows how business start-up enables many women, but not all, to achieve forms of economic and social independence that they would not otherwise enjoy. Further, they illustrate how business proprietorship has a wide variety of effects upon individuals and their relationships and lifestyles. Finally, they refute the notion of a single entrepreneurial experience and argue that the causes and consequences are

highly conditioned by how women are committed to traditionally prescribed roles and profitability.

In contrast, Singh (2008) presents "An Insight into the Emergence of Women-owned Businesses as an Economic Force in India" at a conference held on December 14, 2008. The paper identifies the reasons and influencing factors behind the entry of women into entrepreneurship. He explained the characteristics of their businesses in the Indian context and obstacles and challenges. He mentioned the obstacles in the growth of women entrepreneurship are mainly lack of interaction with successful entrepreneurs, social un-acceptance as women entrepreneurs, family responsibility, gender discrimination, missing network, low priority given by bankers to provide loans to women entrepreneurs. He suggested remedial measures like promoting micro-enterprises, unlocking institutional framework, projecting, pulling to grow and supporting the winners. The study advocates ensuring synergy among women related ministry, economic ministry, and social and welfare development ministry of the Government of India.

Nevertheless, Bushell (2008) highlighted that entrepreneurship for women is a journey out of poverty and a march towards equality. Studies have proven that entrepreneurship, in the form of small and medium-sized enterprises, can indeed empower women and, through time, fundamentally transform power relations within a society, making it a place where women can lead. However, in the past, women's entrepreneurship in much of the developing world has gone little beyond informal business ventures, ensuring daily survival for women and their families. Bullough et al. (2015) argued that women entrepreneurs are a significant force in the economy generating in the US economy over a trillion dollars in revenue annually and employing millions of workers, and Women entrepreneurs make significant contributions to their economies.

In Nepal, embedded structural and socio-cultural constraints challenge women entrepreneurs and make it hard for them to realise their potential as leaders in business. It suggests policy measures, business and management training, and the promotion of entrepreneurial networking systems are potential ways to empower women entrepreneurs and create leadership opportunities to bring women into the mainstream business sector in Nepal (Atteraya et al., 2015).

Likewise, Orser, Riding & Stanley (2012) studied the factors influencing women to start up the business in a traditional female industry sector or a more male-oriented high technology industry sector. He found that differences exist between women who own and operate a business in transitional industry sectors compared to those in the high technology sector. The education and educational system are also vital in developing technology-based entrepreneurs. In addition, parental influences the choice of non-traditional careers. It further talks about females in traditional industry sectors who are likely to associate themselves with feminine traits like flexibility, quality-oriented, customer-focused, sympathetic, but high technology counterparts associate more with masculine traits.

The study by Mark (2007) describes the experiences, initiatives and obstacles faced at five Nordic countries like Finland, Denmark, Iceland, Norway, and Sweden towards women entrepreneurship in "Women Entrepreneurship – A Nordic Perspective". This study aims to promote female entrepreneurship, identify obstacles that prevent women businesses from growing, and learn from other countries' initiatives and best practices. It broadly identifies a few obstacles like financing, lack of knowledge and skills in business life, markets and entrepreneurial activity, the work-life balance including lack of growth and wishes to grow, and most importantly, women as other groups are heterogeneous. The paper concludes that the Nordic countries are somewhat different regarding policies and strategies towards women entrepreneurs. The study compares early-stage entrepreneurial male & female activity among Nordic countries with the USA. It also compares various programs and schemes developed by Nordic countries and agencies that support them. OECD and European Commission are focusing on methodologies in analysing quantitative and qualitative women entrepreneurship. Therefore, the Nordic countries need a framework for policy learning to develop a proper policy mix towards promoting women entrepreneurship.

Literature around female entrepreneurs focuses on female entrepreneurship in the developing world and Finland, respectively. The study has discussed the various pull and push motivational factors to become an entrepreneur: independence, self-fulfilment, income, dissatisfaction towards work, age, difficulty in receiving the job. The study consists of theoretical research as well as empirical research. They have found that a difference exists between male and female entrepreneurs. Females mainly strive to achieve self-fulfilment and accomplishment through self-employment. For example, during a study in Ghana by Anwar & Rasid, female

respondents ranked self-fulfilment higher than other results (Jhlhankangas (2007); Anwar & Rasid (2006).

Similarly, Heilman & Chen (2003) and Botha, Nieman & Van-Vuuren (2006) argued that various push-and-pull factors could motivate women to start their businesses. Maas and Herrington (2006) defined push factors as the more negative factors, such as unemployment and retrenchment, which force people to become entrepreneurial to survive. They regard "pull" factors as more positive factors, such as government support and role models, which might influence people to choose entrepreneurship as a career option. Ghosh and Cheruvalath (2007) found that only one-fifth of women are drawn into entrepreneurship by pull factors. The rest are forced into entrepreneurship by push factors Mohinuddin (2006) women became entrepreneurs due to the following reasons: (a) Economic needs, (b) As a challenge to satisfy some of their personality needs (power, achievement, novel experience (c) Educated women to like to utilise their knowledge gained. (d) Family occupation and (e) leisure time activity women face the same difficulties as men. Orhan & Scott (2001) examined "Why women enter into entrepreneurship: an explanatory model", using in-depth interviews with 25 successful French women entrepreneurs. The study further investigates why women set up their firms. It sets out the principal activity of their businesses, the professional sector they operate in, the number of their employees and the geographic area in which they operate and identifies several themes within the discussions of why they set up their businesses. The information was gained from interviews, analysed, and combined with previous research to develop a consolidated model of female entrepreneurial motivation. This research has identified there is a range of reasons why females become entrepreneurs, namely "dynastic compliance", "no other choice", "entrepreneurship by chance", "natural succession", "forced entrepreneurship", "informed entrepreneur" and "pure entrepreneur". The findings do not reinforce the assumption that most women become entrepreneurs for reasons of necessity and identified antecedents to the generalised "push", "pull", and environmental motives. This analysis develops a typology of women entrepreneurs - dynastic compliance, no other choice, entrepreneur by chance, natural succession, forced entrepreneur, informed entrepreneur and pure entrepreneur, illustrating this with quotes from the interviews.

However, Kanugo (1998) explained that the country's development is possible only through the emergence of small-scale and rural enterprises. He believed that this requires building up a broader population capable of entrepreneurial behaviour. He took an example of India in the

context of development that industrial development took place in urban centres in the initial stage, which trickled down to rural communities over time. However, development strategy today seeks a more proactive and immediate change in India. Some people believe that enterprise creation is a function of appropriate economic conditions, and others have stressed training and attitudinal change as vital elements.

Nevertheless, these interventions are not on systematic observation and research through which entrepreneurship emerges and sustains itself. So, there is a need to develop comprehensive research-based models of entrepreneurship in the context of development. Various authors have contributed articles on different topics like conceptual models, focus on the entrepreneur as a person, role of entrepreneurial intentions and motivations in enterprise creation and growth, management skills needed for starting and sustaining a small business.

The authors like Cromie & Hayes (2000) and Hisrich & Brush (1985) found that dissatisfaction, frustration, and boredom in previous jobs were the most frequently cited reasons for pursuing entrepreneurship. In the Hisrich & Brush (1985) study, job dissatisfaction issues were among female entrepreneurs. Buttne & Moore (1997) examined the primary entrepreneurial motivations within a group of women executives and professionals who had left large organisations to start their businesses. The potential satisfaction from entrepreneurial opportunities to pursue independent interests and factors related to previous job dissatisfaction. This study found satisfaction with the autonomy and independence of ownership to be the most critical determinant of this group of female entrepreneurs. Most of the studies examining the demographic characteristics of female entrepreneurs have done so in comparison to male business owners (see, for example, Brownell & Goldsmith, 2006; Bertaux & Bilginsoy, 2002). While such studies have identified some differences, many of the demographic predictors of entrepreneurship were identical to those of males: age, work experience, and years of self-employment were also the dominant predictors of success for female entrepreneurs. In addition, having a parent who was a business owner has increased the likelihood of female entrepreneurship (Adams et al., 1996).

The study by Shah (1987) was on three categories of a sample (i) women entrepreneurs of middle and high middle-income groups, including working women and homemakers. (ii) Women entrepreneurs with science and technology backgrounds come from middle and lower-middle-income groups, and (iii) women entrepreneurs of low-income groups come from the lower strata of society. The data analysed revealed that the distinctive features of women

entrepreneurs in all three categories were self-sufficiency in terms of internal and external resource awareness, initiative-taking, problem-solving and risk-taking. Among the motives to become an entrepreneur were economic needs which was an essential motive in the low-income group, utilisation of experience, and education by women with science and technology education. In addition, women in all groups expressed the husband's family support and interest, availability of full time and finance, desire to be independent, and personal ego satisfaction of doing something on one's own. Therefore, a survey and administered to a sample of 62 practising Nigerian female entrepreneurs. The survey was into sections that recorded personal demographics, the entrepreneur's perceptions of the business environment and their venture and the motivations and drives that led to the birth of their business. With no or few significant differences shown to exist between male and female business owners or managers once they have already started an enterprise, there is a strong indication that Africa has sizeable hidden growth potential in its women. The results presented show that micro-financing and family dynamics drive female entrepreneurship that works to shape and influence the birth of a business in Nigeria.

Indeed, although women are still the minority in the business world, they have exhibited entrepreneurial potential and are an essential resource in economic growth. In the light of this statement, women entrepreneurs can influence positive economic growth because of employment creation. Moreover, the standard of living improves as income increases. Therefore, female entrepreneurship is considered an essential tool in enabling female empowerment and emancipation (Anwar & Rashid, 2006). Bowen and Hisrich (1986) contrasted and evaluated various entrepreneurship research studies, particularly women's entrepreneurship. It summarises various studies to show that female entrepreneurs are relatively well educated in general but not necessarily in management skills, have a high internal locus of control, are more masculine or instrumental in their values than other women, are more likely to have had entrepreneurial fathers, are more likely to have first born or only children, and are less likely to start a business in traditionally male-dominated industries. C.S. & Mishra (2019) also support Bowen & Hisrich (1986) that woman entrepreneurs tend to be highly motivated and self-directed. They also exhibit a high internal locus of control and achievement. As a result, like Nepalese woman entrepreneurs, some women are likely to open businesses due to push factors such as a shortage of employment opportunities and meeting basic needs (Frederick et al., 2012). On the other hand, some rural Nepalese women may start a company due to "pull factors" such as self-recognition, self-accomplishment, and family

motivators " (Valencia, 2007). In developing Asian countries, however, most women become entrepreneurs because of "push" factors such as poverty and unemployment rather than "pull" factors such as education (Ikupolati et al., 2017).

To summarise, many factors were contextual and personal motivational factors for women entrepreneurs of Nepal. The personal factors can be family structures, whereas contextual factors are education, training and development programmes, gender equity and technological advancement (Tripathi, 2012).

Appendix 10: Statistics of rural and urban Nepal

The national population and housing census data compiled by Nepal's CBS in 2019 as follows:

Indicators	Nepal	Rural Nepal	Urban Nepal	Variances (Rural – Urban)
Population	26.49 million	21.97 million	4.52 million	+ 17.45 million
		82.93%	17.07%	+ 65.86%
Population (female)	51.7%	11.43 million	2.22 million	+ 3.36%
		52.03%	48.67%	
Population (male)	49.1%	10.54 million	2.31 million	- 3.14%
		47.97%	51.11%	
Literacy rate (total population)	65.94%	62.48%	82.22%	- 19.74%
Literacy rate (male)	75.14%	71.99%	89.02%	- 17.03%
Literacy rate (female)	57.39%	53.83%	75.20%	- 21.37%
Religion (Hindu)	81.34%	80.95%	83.27%	- 2.32%
Religion (Buddhist)	9.04%	9.10%	8.75%	+ 0.35%
Average household size	4.88 persons	5.02 persons	4.32 persons	+ 0.7 person
Total households	5.4 million	4.3 million	1.05 million	+ 3.25 million

Households where females did not own anything	79.42%	81.15%	72.21%	+ 8.94%
Households where females owned fixed assets	19.70%	18.02%	26.73%	- 8.71%
Households that used tap or pipelines as primary source of drinking water	47.78%	45.06%	59.19%	- 14.13%
Households that used tube well or hand pump as primary source of drinking water	35.13%	37.67%	24.48%	+ 13.19%
Households that owned a toilet	61.19%	54.28%	90.14%	- 35.86%
Households that cooked with firewood	63.99%	73.13%	25.69%	+ 47.44%
Households that cooked with LP gas	21.03%	9.89%	67.68%	- 57.79%
Households that cooked with cow dung	10.38%	12.50%	1.51%	+ 10.99%
Households that used electricity for lighting	67.26%	60.85%	94.11%	- 33.26%
Households that used kerosene for lighting	18.28%	21.68%	4.05%	+ 17.63%

Households that used solar power for lighting	7.44%	9.17%	0.20%	+ 8.97%
Households that owned a mobile phone	64.58%	59.95%	83.93%	- 23.98%
Households that owned a radio	50.79%	50.14%	53.47%	- 3.33%
Households that owned a television	36.42%	30.65%	60.57%	- 29.92%
Households that did not own any amenities	13.68%	15.96%	4.13%	+ 11.83%

Table 18: Comparative Census Data from Rural and Urban Nepal (2019)

Source: Adapted from CBS, 2019

The above table is the presentation of Nepal's overall status in rural and urban areas. From this table, we can grasp an idea of the progress Nepal is making, what the contemporary context of Nepal so that it can be helpful for the researcher to conduct this thesis. It is apparent in the mind of the researcher where the women stand and the living standard of the people of Nepal.

Appendix 11: Castes, ethnic groups, and religion of Nepal

Nepal's population comprises people of various ethnic groups who belong to 103 castes and follow various religions such as Hinduism, Buddhism, Animism, Christianity, Islam, and sometimes a mix of faiths (Pradhan & Shrestha, 2005). Nepal's official language is Nepali, but the country also has 22 other distinct languages (Dana, 2014) and 92 spoken languages (Rai, 2015). In 2019, 126 castes or ethnic groups were in Nepal, with Chhettris accounting for 16.6% of the population and Brahmin's accounting for 12.2%. (CBS, 2012). The caste system identifies Nepalese people after the National Code or Muluki Ain in 1854. Their social status and the privileges available were by the code (Atteraya, Kimm & Song, 2015; Abay et al., 2018, Dahal, & Govindasamy, 2008). Higher castes like Brahmins and Chhettris and lower castes like Dalits have more gender-based patriarchal behaviour for women and girls than indigenous communities like Gurung, Rai, and Limbu (Samuels & Ghimire, 2013). This hierarchy and ranking influence entrepreneurship in Nepal by a person's social and ethnic status. Brahmins and Chhettris were less interested in entrepreneurial practices than ethnic groups belonging to the Newar caste (Zivetz, 1992). The caste system has stifled the growth of

women's entrepreneurship, as lower caste women are refused entrance into upper caste homes. Due to increased knowledge and understanding, racist behaviour dependent on the caste system is steadily diminishing in modern times (Acharya, 2000).

Appendix 12: Economy, poverty, and rural development of Nepal

According to the United Nations Development Programme's (UNDP) Human Development Report for 2020, Nepal is ranked 142nd out of 180 countries surveyed, with an HDI of 0.602. (UNDP, 2019). With a Human Development Index of 0.548, Nepal remained one of the poorest countries in 2019, ranking 145th out of 186 countries (UNDP, 2015). In Nepal, 21.6 per cent of the population lived in poverty in 2016. (Ministry of Finance [MOF], 2016a). Nepal's actual GDP in basic prices was Rs. 695.2 billion (NZD 9.93 billion) in 2015/16, and its annual GDP per capita was USD 752 (NZD 1094). (MOF, 2016). In the fiscal year 2014/15, the economic growth rate was 2.32 per cent, but in 2015/16, it was 0.77 per cent. The earthquake's impact, border obstructions with India that hampered transportation, and protracted strikes contributed to the low economic growth rate (MOF, 2016a). Nepal's economy is dependent on agriculture (Dudwick, Hull & Katayama, 2011; Waring, 1988; Youngblood-Coleman, 2015c; Zivetz, 1992). In Nepal, 68 per cent of people work in and rely on the agricultural sector (ILO, 2016); however, agriculture concentrates on reliance in rural areas, where it is still "subsistence and least modernized" (Lamichhane & Shrestha, 2009, p. 25). Women also traditionally played an essential role in agriculture, making most work-related decisions (Acharya, 2000). One-third of Nepal's population lives in poverty (Khatriwada, 2001), with poverty largely concentrated in rural areas (Bhatta, 2001; Lamichhane & Shrestha, 2009). Entrepreneurship is crucial and necessary for rural development, but cultural influences, a lack of role models, limited networks, and insufficient funding as significant barriers to rural entrepreneurship growth (Gautam, 2014; Vaillant & Lafuente, 2007). Rural poverty in Nepal is due to a lack of access to resources, poor productivity, and infrastructure for receiving and selling agricultural products (Acharya, 2008). Improvements in the agricultural sector could boost productivity, reduce poverty, and help people in Nepal's rural areas live better lives (Lamichhane & Shrestha, 2009).

Appendix 13: Foreign employment of Nepal

Young men and women forcefully leave Nepal in search of work due to the country's weak financial situation and hunger. As a result, the number of Nepalese men and women departing

for work in foreign countries has increased dramatically. Gurung (2012) found that 84 per cent of the total sample population that migrated for foreign employment in Nepal's Babiyabirta VDC was male, 90 per cent were literate, and three-quarters of them were between the ages of 20 and 40. As a result, 25.2 per cent of rural Nepalese women and 28.1 per cent of urban Nepalese women are the heads of their households, making decisions on household spending, nutritious food, health care, and schooling (UN Women, 2014). These drive factors lead to Nepalese women's increased participation in entrepreneurship activities because it allows them to manage household chores while earning and contributing to their families (Gurung & Thapa, 2016). However, due to a shortage of education, most Nepalese women move to other countries such as the Middle East and Malaysia to work in low-paying occupations (Acharya & Halpenny, 2013). As a result, these rural areas have a higher percentage of senior citizens and women with dependent children. As a result, historically physically challenging "male" occupations such as digging fields are now performed by women; however, traditionally "female" jobs such as cooking and cleaning are now avoided by men because they are "undervalued" (Samuels & Ghimire, 2013, p. 5).

Appendix 14: Status of women in Nepal.

The status of women entrepreneurship can be viewed by the following terms:

14.1 Gender disparity

Women in Nepal are less motivated than men and lag well behind them in the educational, political, commercial, and social sectors (UN Women, 2014). They also face discrimination (Bhatt et al., 2009). Women's psychological and spiritual oppression is due to misconceptions and patriarchal perceptions (OHCHR, 2011). Cultural traditions such as child marriage, dowry, early marriage, polygamy, low schooling, widowhood, and preference for sons over daughters make Nepalese women vulnerable to discrimination (Government of Nepal [GON], 2010). In contrast to the birth of a daughter, the birth of a son is a happy occasion in a household (Luitel, 2001; Pradhan et al., 2011). In the distribution of food in a family, there is a discriminatory pattern in which girls get a smaller share than boys (Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights [OHCHR], 2011). Nepalese women are also victims of harmful cultural practices such as "Deuki," "Chaupadi," "Jhuma," and "Dhan-Khanne," in which widows get accused of being witches, young girls are offered to a temple and must remain unmarried for the rest of their lives, and menstruating women have to live away from

their homes (OHCHR, 2011; Gurung & Thapa, 2016). There is also a tradition known as "Satipratha," in which living Nepalese women were forced to burn themselves on their husband's funeral pyre and denied the right to live after their husband died (Luitel, 2001; Ajit Pradhan et al., 2011). Widows in Nepal face discrimination and are socially and economically marginalized (Thapa et al., 2015). They are also vulnerable to gender-based violence (Gurung & Thapa, 2016). Widows are referred to as "Bidwa" in Nepali, a term that conjures up images of shame and pain for single women (Gurung & Thapa, 2016; Poudel, 2015). Divorced women get looked down on, and remarriage is impossible due to social, cultural, and religious constraints (Acharya, 2005). Nepalese people often revere "Kumari" as a living goddess, trusting in her healing abilities (Guo, 2008). However, the girl's personal experience of "Kumari" could be very different.

A Kumari's life in Nepal raises an essential question to the researcher's mind about multiple realities for females of Nepal; is it a case of gender disparity for young girls as they are robbed of their childhood or is it a case of glorification for young girls as a living goddess?- Acharya, 2005.

Debate on discrimination and disparities toward women in Nepal over the past two decades, yet nothing has improved (Pradhan & Shrestha, 2005). However, revising several genders-biased legislations affecting women's rights to inheritance, marriage and divorce provisions, and acknowledging women's sexuality to speed up equality between men and women (GON, 2010).

14.2 Child marriage

Women's wellbeing, education, and decision-making are also affected by early marriage (Human Rights Watch [HRW], 2016). Marriage before the age of 18 is a fundamental violation of human rights, according to the United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund [UNICEF], 2016b. In 2014, a study showed that 10% of girls in Nepal get to marry at the age of fifteen, and 37% at eighteen (UNICEF, 2016a). Since 1963, there has been a prohibition on child marriage in Nepal (HRW, 2016; Pradhan et al., 2011). For Nepalese men and women, the minimum age of marriage is 20, and child marriage is punishable by a fine of up to Rs. 10,000 (NZD 143) and a sentence of up to three years in jail (HRW, 2016). Adults engaged in every aspect of child marriage, including those who marry a child, those who plan the marriage, and

religious figures who conduct the marriage, are all responsible for the offence and are liable to punishment, according to the statute (HRW, 2016). However, due to poor implementation of the rules, Nepal has Asia's third-highest rate of child marriage (HRW, 2016). According to the United Nations Children's Fund, Nepal has the tenth highest incidence of child marriage in the country.

14.3 Violence against women

Woman's violence is a sign of "unequal power ties between men and women" (Joshi & Kharel, 2008, p. 3). Many women and girls worldwide are victimized by different types of abuse, which are also common in Nepalese society (Hawkes et al., 2013). Domestic violence is the most common type of violence against women, defined as "a pattern of abuse and abusive behaviour by an individual against his or her intimate partner, including physical, sexual, and psychological assaults" (Agnihotri et al., 2006, p. 30). According to a study conducted in six Nepalese districts, 48 per cent of women have faced some level of violence in their lives (GON, 2012). Many women and girls get trafficked in Nepal to physical, emotional, and sexual harassment, and many have committed suicide as a result (Pradhan et al., 2011). Most violent crimes in Nepal go unreported and unaddressed, and there are no statistics on domestic and sexual harassment against women (OHCHR, 2011). Women and girls do not report abuse for various reasons, including maintaining family prestige and anonymity, fear of retaliation by their husbands and other family members, sexual harassment, a lack of resources, a lack of legal defence, socio-cultural norms (Joshi & Kharel, 2008). Torture of women in Nepal during menstruation is another type of abuse (GON, 2012). Due to the prevalent culture of shame, menstruation, which is the most common event in any woman's life, is found to be "dealt with secrecy in many parts of Nepal" (WaterAid in Nepal, 2009, p. 1). For Nepalese women, the social stigma and prohibitions around menstruating women are also examples of gender discrimination (Robinson, 2015). They are separated from their relatives and must take their food independently. They get banned from visiting the kitchen, making direct contact with people, touching a tap or any other supply of water, and sleeping with little or no bedding (Robinson, 2015; Samuels & Ghimire, 2013). Based on her own family's customs, confident girls and women face severe challenges such as staying in a cowshed, being excluded from their house, or being barred from attending school (HRW, 2016). If a menstruating woman violates existing societal standards, her family will suffer misfortune, death, illnesses, and water scarcity (Robinson, 2015). Many girls and women have died because of this ritual,

including snakebites, wild animal attacks, mental illness, abuse, influenza, hypothermia, and pneumonia, as well as shame and a system of terror and exclusion (Sauve, 2014).

14.4 Women's unpaid work

Women make up more than 60% of the population in Nepal's rural areas, and they are also actively engaged in unpaid domestic duties and family roles (Bhatt et al., 2009). In Nepal, women account for 78.3 per cent of the total population, with 55.2 per cent working in agriculture and 44.8 per cent working in non-agricultural activities (UN Women, 2020). According to Waring (1988), "anthropological literature on Nepal explains Nepalese women doing the majority of farm jobs" (p. 91). However, Nepalese women are often required to perform daily house chores, and their contributions get overlooked (Mishra & Sam, 2016). As a result, women in Nepal spend less time dreaming and more time doing unpaid housework than men (Budlender & Moussié, 2013). There is also a difference in the number of hours served by male and female Nepalese children aged ten to fourteen. According to a World Bank report conducted in Nepal, male children worked 4.8 hours a day, while female children worked 7.3 hours a day (Waring, 1988).

Every day, Nepalese women are engaged in household practices such as childcare, elder care, and informal market activities with goats, hens, chickens, pigs, and oxen. Nevertheless, even though Nepalese women work longer hours than men, most women in Nepal live in "extreme poverty" (International Fund for Agriculture Development [IFAD], n.d.) and earn less than half of what men do (UN Women, 2014).

14.5 Organisations and programmes for women

In Nepal, government and non-governmental organizations collaborate to help women. The Government of Nepal and the United Nations Development Program (UNDP) launched the Micro-Enterprise Development Program (MEDEP) to alleviate poverty, control women's decision-making capacity, and improve the economic conditions of low-income families, especially women (Bhattarai & Paudel, 2011). The Microcredit Project for Women (MCPW) and the Production Credit for Rural Women (PCRW) help women boost their socioeconomic status by providing them with services to help them generate income (Bhatta, 2001). Grameen Bikas Bank (GBB), also known as the Regional Rural Development Bank, UNDP, and the Agriculture Development Bank (ADP), offer financial services to the vulnerable, with a particular emphasis on women; however, men have been able to take full advantage of these

services by obtaining large loans when compared to women (Bhatta, 2001). As a result, numerous initiatives and projects have been launched in Nepal to encourage women to raise income and motivate them to make decisions; however, women's status in Nepal has not improved significantly (GON, 2010; Luitel, 2001).

14.6 Socialization Pattern

In Nepalese society, women are a subordinate position at all levels. Through the various phases of her life cycle, a woman's life becomes apparent how this societal structure and the concomitant value system have affected women's attitudes. Most of the women face the problem of the wrong attitude of society. In a male-dominated society, women encountered many socio-personal problems. The entire socialization pattern in Nepalese society is such that the young boys are prepared for the world of productive works and decision-making, while girls need to be practical housewives, mothers, and service providers. From a very early age, it is instilled into girls' minds that their duty lies in providing services to their family and assisting the mother in household responsibilities. In this way, society prepares her for the world of caretaking the future generations (Surkan et al., 2015). Therefore, self-effacement, gentleness, sacrifice, soft-spoken and other feminine qualities are encouraged in her upbringing. On the other hand, decision-making, strength of expression and articulateness, opinion formation, thinking of one's own needs and interests, future career planning are given low priority during her socialization process (Tuladhar, 1996).

14.7 Social Attitudes towards Women's Outside Work

Most of the women face the problem of the wrong attitude of the society in which they must live and work. There is discrimination against women in Nepal despite constitutional equality. Women do not get equal treatment in male-dominated Nepalese society, and the male ego puts barriers to their progress. Entrepreneurship is a male preserve, and the idea of women taking up entrepreneurial activities is a distant dream. Women must face role conflict as soon as they initiate any entrepreneurial activities. It is an uphill task for women to face such conflict and cope with the twin roles. A woman working outside the house is considered a disgrace to the family in some parts (Upadhyay, 2015). Working women must bear a double work burden which does not attribute any higher status to them. Society seems to be very harsh to women at the middle level. Most women do not have their own choice, even in education. A large proportion of rural girls drop out of schooling early (Uprety & Adhikary, 2009). In the case of

getting employment, men do not have much problem in taking up employment of their choice. However, women in Nepal and other Asian countries also face many problems in getting suitable employment.

Nevertheless, in many cases, social or community attitudes towards women are still the same. Women are weak, passive, and obedient. In some cases, society considers weakness in a man if his wife is working outside. Except for a few fortunate urban elite women cases, it must be considered a success for women in rural areas to come out from their traditional cocoons. It takes time to realize that women are also a valuable human resource. Therefore, government and society must undertake more substantial efforts to change women's societal values and traditions (Vinding & Kampbel, 2012).

Appendix 15: Graph representation of the outcome from survey

		Age			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18-25	25	17.9	17.9	17.9
	26-35	50	35.7	35.7	53.6
	36-45	28	20.0	20.0	73.6
	46-55	13	9.3	9.3	82.9
	56+	24	17.1	17.1	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Figure 39: Measurement and Graphical Presentation based on age

Figure 40 reveals the age of respondents. This question explores that most respondents belong from which age bracket to most minor women entrepreneurs. Data shows that 17.9% of respondents belong to the 18-25 age group, 35.7% belong to the 26-35 age group, 20% belong to the 36–45-year age bracket, and 9.3% belong to the 46-55-year age bracket and 17.1% belong to 56+ age group. Therefore, most respondents were from the 26-35 age brackets. By gathering the data different aged women entrepreneurs, it was easier to maintain the reliability of the data. In addition, these respondents shared their views more openly, as they were keen to share their views regarding the barriers they faced whilst doing business in the Nepalese food industry.

Relationship Status

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Single	22	15.7	15.7	15.7
	Engaged	30	21.4	21.4	37.1
	Married	63	45.0	45.0	82.1
	Separated	10	7.1	7.1	89.3
	Widow	15	10.7	10.7	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Figure 40: Measurement and Graphical Presentation based on relationship status

The data in figure 41 is about the relationship status of the women entrepreneurs participating in this survey. The data revealed that 15.7% are single, 21.4% women entrepreneurs were engaged, 45% were married, 7.1% were separated, and widow shares 10.7%. This question is essential to know the family commitment and barriers they face with their professional life. Hence most of the women entrepreneurs were married, which aided the researcher to identify and validate the barriers they face in the food industry.

How many children do you have?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1-2 children	75	53.6	53.6	53.6
	3-5 children	39	27.9	27.9	81.4
	Not Applicable	26	18.6	18.6	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Figure 41: Measurement and Graphical Presentation based on children

Figure 42 is the third question asked participants about their responsibilities towards their children. Therefore, 53.6% have 1-2 children, 27.9% have 3-5 children, and for 18.6%, the question is not relevant. Hence, from this data, maximum women entrepreneurs have other family responsibilities, which aided the researcher to get an idea of the barriers they face whilst doing business in Nepal.

Education Attainment level

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	High school or less	25	17.9	17.9	17.9
	Diploma	47	33.6	33.6	51.4
	Bachelor	50	35.7	35.7	87.1
	Post Graduate	18	12.9	12.9	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Figure 42: Measurement and Graphical Presentation based on education level

The above figure 43 reveals the data related to respondents' level of education. Therefore, this question explored the educational background of respondents who contributed to the study. Based on the above graph, about 17.9% of respondents had a high school or less, 33.6% of respondents had a diploma, 35.7% had bachelor's degrees, and the remaining 12.9% had a post-graduate degree. Therefore, most respondents had a bachelor's degree, which shows that they had a solid educational background and were more aware of entrepreneurship as a business student.

How long have you been in this business?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1-2 years	20	14.3	14.3	14.3
	3-5 years	29	20.7	20.7	35.0
	6-8 years	49	35.0	35.0	70.0
	8 years and more	42	30.0	30.0	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Figure 43: Measurement and Graphical Presentation based on business length

The above figure 44 reveals the data gathered from ‘*How long you have been in this business?*’ This question was to know the length of service of the respondents. Based on the information about 14.3% of respondents had their business for 1-2 years, 20.7% of respondents had had their business for 3-5 years, 35% are running their business for 6-8 years and the remaining 30% respondents had had their business more than 8 years. Hence, from the data, most respondents had had their business for 6-8 years, and they have good experience in this field.

Did you have any prior training to develop this business?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	110	78.6	78.6	78.6
	No	30	21.4	21.4	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Figure 44: Measurement and Graphical Presentation based on prior training

The above figure reveals the data gathered from ‘*Did you have any prior training to develop this business?*’ This question was to know the prior training received by the respondents. Based on the information in Figure 45, about 78.6% had training before starting their entrepreneurial journey, whilst only 21.4% did not receive any training prior to starting their business. This statement aided researcher to validate the barriers identified for training and development programmes.

Lack of career guidance hinders business participation by women entrepreneurs to access various public and private offered support services, including business development services and information on business growth.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	8	5.7	5.7	5.7
	Disagree	5	3.6	3.6	9.3
	Neutral	3	2.1	2.1	11.4
	Agree	41	29.3	29.3	40.7
	Strongly Agree	83	59.3	59.3	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Lack of career guidance hinders business participation by women entrepreneurs to access various public and private offered support services, including business development services and information on business growth.

Figure 45: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 1

Figure 46 reveals the data gathered from the statement related to the lack of career guidance that hinders business participation by women entrepreneurs to access various public and private offered support services, including business development services and information on business growth. Based on this, the data shows that approximately 9.3% of respondents disagreed, 11.4% were neutral, and the remaining 40.7% agreed. Hence, the results reveal that most respondents agreed with the statement and believed career guidance is essential for all women entrepreneurs to increase participation in entrepreneurship.

The fact that women have fewer connections than men with experts in specific fields hinders the women entrepreneurs in business.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	10	7.1	7.1	7.1
	Disagree	18	12.9	12.9	20.0
	Neutral	11	7.9	7.9	27.9
	Agree	44	31.4	31.4	59.3
	Strongly Agree	57	40.7	40.7	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Figure 46: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 2

The data is about the connection women entrepreneurs have with an expert. It means that lack of expert guidance hinders their business activities as they cannot build that connection with them than men. However, 20% disagreed with this statement, 27.9% remained neutral, and almost 59.3% agreed.

Many women entrepreneurs lack the skills and education needed to set up and run their businesses

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	8	5.7	5.7	5.7
	Disagree	15	10.7	10.7	16.4
	Neutral	12	8.6	8.6	25.0
	Agree	58	41.4	41.4	66.4
	Strongly Agree	47	33.6	33.6	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Figure 47: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 3

Figure 48 reveals the data gathered from the statement related to the lack of skills and education needed for a women entrepreneur to set up and run a business. Based on this, the data shows that approximately 16.4% of respondents disagreed, 25% were neutral, and the remaining 66.4% agreed. Hence, the results reveal that most respondents agreed with the statement and believed that they lack the entrepreneurial skills and education needed to start and run their business in Nepal.

Even the educated women are provided either less or inadequate education than their male counterparts partly due to marriage

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	12	8.6	8.6	8.6
	Disagree	11	7.9	7.9	16.4
	Neutral	6	4.3	4.3	20.7
	Agree	38	27.1	27.1	47.9
	Strongly Agree	73	52.1	52.1	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Figure 48: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 4

Figure 49 reveals the data gathered from the statement related to the notion that educated women are provided either less or inadequate education than their male counterparts, partly due to marriage. Based on this, the data from the above graph shows that 16.4% of respondents disagreed, 20.7% of respondents were neutral, and the remaining 47.9% of respondents agreed. Hence, most respondents agreed with the statement, and they believed even women or girls who had basic primary education are only educated up to a certain level because they need to get married. It limits their business participation because their goals and aims get diverted, and they cannot cope with the changing business environment.

The sex segregation policies in educational facilities limit the learning experience of women entrepreneurs

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	9	6.4	6.4	6.4
	Disagree	17	12.1	12.1	18.6
	Neutral	6	4.3	4.3	22.9
	Agree	46	32.9	32.9	55.7
	Strongly Agree	62	44.3	44.3	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Figure 49: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 5

The graph in Figure 50 reveals the data gathered from the statement related to the fact that sex segregation policies in the educational system limit women entrepreneurs learning experience. The data shows that 18.6% of respondents disagreed, 22.9% were neutral, and the remaining 55.7% of respondents marked on agree. Hence, this corroborates Vossenberg (2013) study, and it proves that due to sex segregation in primary school and other educational institutions, girls/ women get limited learning facilities and ideas than men.

Illiteracy among women often restricts their approach and scope for knowledge advancement, making them shy and suffer from low self-esteem and self-confidence in entrepreneurial activities

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	13	9.3	9.3	9.3
	Disagree	10	7.1	7.1	16.4
	Neutral	12	8.6	8.6	25.0
	Agree	43	30.7	30.7	55.7
	Strongly Agree	62	44.3	44.3	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Illiteracy among women often restricts their approach and scope for knowledge advancement, making them shy and suffer from low self-esteem and self-confidence in entrepreneurial activities

Figure 50: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 6

The graph in Figure 51 reveals the data gathered from the statement related to the fact that illiteracy among women often restricts their approaches and scope for knowledge advancement, making them shy and suffer from low self-esteem and self-confidence in entrepreneurial activities. The data shows that 16.4% of respondents disagreed, 25% were neutral, and the remaining 55.7% of respondents marked on agree. Hence, when a woman has no primary education, it limits her activities in business, approach, and knowledge, which tends to make them with low esteem self-confidence to do business.

Most women lack entrepreneurial skills in terms of administrations, marketing, accounts, and public relations

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	8	5.7	5.7	5.7
	Disagree	6	4.3	4.3	10.0
	Neutral	18	12.9	12.9	22.9
	Agree	43	30.7	30.7	53.6
	Strongly Agree	65	46.4	46.4	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Figure 51: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 7

The graph in Figure 52 reveals the data gathered from the statement related to the idea that most women entrepreneurs lack administration, marketing, accounts, and public relations skills. Based on this, the data shows that 10% of respondents disagreed, 22.9% of respondents were neutral, and the remaining 53.6% of respondents agreed. The results gathered from the questionnaire survey demonstrated that most respondents agreed with the statement and believed that women entrepreneurs lack these skills, which further limits their involvement in any business in Nepal.

Business licensing is a barrier of women entrepreneurs as the process is lengthy and complex, excessive bureaucracy, and in some cases demands for bribes by officials

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	4	2.9	2.9	2.9
	Disagree	24	17.1	17.1	20.0
	Neutral	3	2.1	2.1	22.1
	Agree	63	45.0	45.0	67.1
	Strongly Agree	46	32.9	32.9	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Business licensing is a barrier of women entrepreneurs as the process is lengthy and complex, excessive bureaucracy, and in some cases demands for bribes by officials

Figure 52: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 8

The graph in Figure 53 reveals the data gathered from the statement related to the concept of business licensing as a barrier for women entrepreneurs as the process is lengthy and complex, excessive bureaucracy, and demand for bribes by officials. The data shows that 20% of respondents disagreed, 22.1% were neutral, and the remaining 67.1% of respondents agreed with the statement. Hence, this shows that most respondents agreed with the statement, and they believed that due to complex and lengthy procedures to register a business, many women entrepreneurs get demotivated or sometimes give up their business idea.

Weak judicial systems, inconsistency in implementing laws, bureaucracy, hooliganism, abuse of political power limits women participation in business

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	11	7.9	7.9	7.9
	Disagree	17	12.1	12.1	20.0
	Neutral	8	5.7	5.7	25.7
	Agree	47	33.6	33.6	59.3
	Strongly Agree	57	40.7	40.7	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Figure 53: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 9

The graph in Figure 54 reveals the data gathered from the statement related to the weak judicial system, abuse of power, hooliganism limiting women to participate in the business. The data shows that 20% of respondents disagreed, 25.7% were neutral, and the remaining 59.3% of respondents agreed with the statement. Hence, this shows that most respondents agreed with the statement and agreed from the literature review. The whole weak judicial system discourages women entrepreneurs because they feel that they are not secure.

Laws and practices discriminate between women and men.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	12	8.6	8.6	8.6
	Disagree	12	8.6	8.6	17.1
	Neutral	10	7.1	7.1	24.3
	Agree	61	43.6	43.6	67.9
	Strongly Agree	45	32.1	32.1	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Figure 54: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 10

The graph in Figure 55 shows the data gathered from the statement related to laws and practices that discriminate between women and men. In addition, Cardella (2020) mentions that there is discrimination between women and men, and even laws and practices ignore. Women entrepreneurs get support from the government, and if laws are bent to boost and favour women entrepreneurs, then the participation will increase in any country. Hence, the data gathered from the above graph illustrate that 17.1% of respondents disagreed, 24.3% were neutral, and the remaining 67.9% agreed with the statement.

High rates of insurance, taxes, and duties limit women's involvement in the business

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	8	5.7	5.7	5.7
	Disagree	17	12.1	12.1	17.9
	Neutral	5	3.6	3.6	21.4
	Agree	51	36.4	36.4	57.9
	Strongly Agree	59	42.1	42.1	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Figure 55: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 11

The graph in Figure 56 reveals the data gathered from the statement related to the concept of high insurance rates, taxes, and duties limiting women's involvement in the business. The data shows that 17.9% of respondents disagreed, 21.4% were neutral, and the remaining 57.9% of respondents agreed with the statement. Hence, this shows that most respondents agreed with the statement, and they believed that high tax rates and insurance limit women's business participation. Thus, the government should consider the tax rate where there is a need for women entrepreneurs.

Legal constraints are barriers to women entrepreneurs in Nepal

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	10	7.1	7.1	7.1
	Disagree	23	16.4	16.4	23.6
	Neutral	3	2.1	2.1	25.7
	Agree	38	27.1	27.1	52.9
	Strongly Agree	66	47.1	47.1	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Figure 56: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 12

The graph in Figure 57 shows the data gathered from the statement related to legal constraints being barriers to Nepalese women entrepreneurs. In addition, Cardella (2020) mentions that legal barriers are significant barriers limiting women entrepreneurs to progress, succeed, and get involved in any business activities. Hence, the data gathered from the above graph illustrate that 23.6% of respondents disagreed, 25.7% were neutral, and the remaining 52.9% agreed with the statement.

There is a lack of government support for women entrepreneurs regarding laws and regulations

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	6	4.3	4.3	4.3
	Disagree	21	15.0	15.0	19.3
	Neutral	13	9.3	9.3	28.6
	Agree	43	30.7	30.7	59.3
	Strongly Agree	57	40.7	40.7	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Figure 57: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 13

The graph in Figure 58 reveals the data gathered from the statement related to the idea that women entrepreneurs lack government support in terms of laws and regulations towards them. Based on this, the data shows that 19.3% of respondents disagreed, 28.6% of respondents were neutral, and the remaining 59.3% of respondents agreed. The results gathered from the questionnaire survey demonstrated that most respondents agreed with the statement and believed that there is no support from the government of Nepal to support women entrepreneurship, and there are no laws and regulation which increases the participation of women in business.

There is a lack of coordination between government departments regarding business procedures that help women entrepreneurs

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	7	5.0	5.0	5.0
	Disagree	20	14.3	14.3	19.3
	Neutral	14	10.0	10.0	29.3
	Agree	28	20.0	20.0	49.3
	Strongly Agree	71	50.7	50.7	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Figure 58: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 14

The graph in Figure 59 illustrates the data gathered from the statement related to the idea that women entrepreneurs lack government coordination regarding enhancing business procedures. Based on this, the data shows that 19.3% of respondents disagreed, 29.3% of respondents were neutral, and the remaining 49.3% of respondents agreed. Hence, the data gathered from the quantitative survey show that most respondents agreed with the statement, and they believed there is a lack of coordination from Nepal's government regarding business conducted and owned by women entrepreneurs. Therefore, this further limits them from doing any business activities in Nepal.

Laws and regulations restricting women from getting a license without their husbands' permission limit their business involvement

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	14	10.0	10.0	10.0
	Disagree	16	11.4	11.4	21.4
	Neutral	10	7.1	7.1	28.6
	Agree	33	23.6	23.6	52.1
	Strongly Agree	67	47.9	47.9	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Figure 59: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 15

This data in figure 60 is about the statement with laws and regulations that restrict women entrepreneurs from getting a license without their husbands' permission and limit them from doing business. Hence, the data revealed that 21.4% disagreed, 28.6% were neutral, and 52.1% supported this statement. In Nepal, women are not allowed to do business or even travel without their husbands or guardians' permission (Republica, 2020).

Complications with import and export laws limit women's involvement in the business

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	15	10.7	10.7	10.7
	Disagree	16	11.4	11.4	22.1
	Neutral	6	4.3	4.3	26.4
	Agree	41	29.3	29.3	55.7
	Strongly Agree	62	44.3	44.3	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Figure 60: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 16

The graph in Figure 61 reveals the data gathered from the statement related to the complications with import and export laws limiting women's involvement in the business. The literature claimed that women start limiting their business whenever there are complications with import and export laws. Therefore, it demotivated them to grow and succeed. The data shown in the above graph illustrate that 22.1% of respondents disagreed, 26.4% were neutral and the remaining 55.7% marked agreed. Hence, the results reveal that most respondents agreed with the statement.

Foreign relations with other countries that result in bureaucratic hurdles limit women's involvement in the business

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	9	6.4	6.4	6.4
	Disagree	22	15.7	15.7	22.1
	Neutral	7	5.0	5.0	27.1
	Agree	31	22.1	22.1	49.3
	Strongly Agree	71	50.7	50.7	100.0
Total		140	100.0	100.0	

Foreign relations with other countries that result in bureaucratic hurdles limit women's involvement in the business

Figure 61: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 17

The graph in Figure 62 illustrates the data gathered from the statement related to the idea that the relationship with foreign countries resulting in bureaucratic conflicts limits women entrepreneurs in business activities. Based on this, the data shows that 22.1% of respondents disagreed, 27.1% of respondents were neutral, and the remaining 49.3% of respondents agreed. Hence, the data gathered from the quantitative survey show that most respondents agreed with the statement, and they believed that whenever there is a conflict with foreign countries, it demotivates and limits participation from women in an entrepreneurial journey.

Social norms prevent women entrepreneurs from managing their businesses independently, impairing their mobility and affecting their interaction with others.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	4	2.9	2.9	2.9
	Disagree	18	12.9	12.9	15.7
	Neutral	12	8.6	8.6	24.3
	Agree	60	42.9	42.9	67.1
	Strongly Agree	46	32.9	32.9	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Social norms prevent women entrepreneurs from managing their businesses independently, impairing their mobility and affecting their interaction with others.

Figure 62: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 18

The graph in Figure 63 reveals the data gathered from the statement related to the social norms preventing women entrepreneurs from managing their business independently, impairing their mobility and affecting their interaction with others. The data shown in the above graph illustrate that 15.7% of respondents disagreed, 24.3% were neutral and the remaining 67.1% marked agreed. Hence, the results reveal that most respondents agreed with the statement.

Women entrepreneurs face additional handicaps due to the prevailing social and cultural gender-based inequalities and biases.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	28	20.0	20.0	20.0
	Disagree	40	28.6	28.6	48.6
	Neutral	14	10.0	10.0	58.6
	Agree	15	10.7	10.7	69.3
	Strongly Agree	43	30.7	30.7	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Figure 63: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 19

The graph in Figure 64 shows the data gathered from the statement that women entrepreneurs face additional handicaps due to the prevailing social and cultural gender-based inequalities and biases. Hence, the data gathered from the above graph illustrate that 48.6% of respondents disagreed, 58.6% were neutral, and the remaining 69.3% agreed with the statement.

Most companies or people, in general, prefer to deal or work with men than women

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	10	7.1	7.1	7.1
	Disagree	18	12.9	12.9	20.0
	Neutral	10	7.1	7.1	27.1
	Agree	34	24.3	24.3	51.4
	Strongly Agree	68	48.6	48.6	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Figure 64: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 20

The graph in Figure 65 reveals the data gathered from the statement related that most companies or people prefer to deal with men than women. According to Shrestha (2020), there is a social business in the business environment amongst men and women. People or companies trust men's abilities more than women. Therefore, it demotivates women entrepreneurs in Nepal and restricts them from doing business. The data shown in the above graph illustrate that 20% of respondents disagreed, 27.1% were neutral and the remaining 51.4% marked agreed. Hence, the results reveal that most respondents agreed with the statement.

A lack of support and help from other women limit women's involvement in the business

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	8	5.7	5.7	5.7
	Disagree	14	10.0	10.0	15.7
	Neutral	14	10.0	10.0	25.7
	Agree	38	27.1	27.1	52.9
	Strongly Agree	66	47.1	47.1	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Figure 65: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 21

The graph in Figure 66 illustrates that a woman entrepreneurs' encouragement can motivate women entrepreneurs, and when this is lacking amongst women entrepreneurs, it limits the participation of women to take any business. The data shows that 15.7% of respondents disagreed, 25.7% were neutral, and the remaining 52.9 % agreed with the statement. Hence, the majority of respondents agreed with the statement.

Negative opinions voiced about the role of women in business limit their involvement

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	6	4.3	4.3	4.3
	Disagree	23	16.4	16.4	20.7
	Neutral	13	9.3	9.3	30.0
	Agree	40	28.6	28.6	58.6
	Strongly Agree	58	41.4	41.4	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Figure 66: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 22

The graph in Figure 67 reveals the data gathered from the statement related to negative voices for women entrepreneurs limiting them from participating in business activities. Based on this, the data shows that 20.7% of respondents marked disagreed, 30% were neutral, and the remaining 58.6% of respondents agreed. It means that women entrepreneurs often hear their negative thoughts and prioritise them. As a result, they are built with low confidence and low esteem, limiting them from taking or starting any business in Nepal (Cardella et al., 2020).

Castes and religions dominate with one another hinder women entrepreneurs

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	11	7.9	7.9	7.9
	Disagree	20	14.3	14.3	22.1
	Neutral	7	5.0	5.0	27.1
	Agree	36	25.7	25.7	52.9
	Strongly Agree	66	47.1	47.1	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Figure 67: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 23

The graph in Figure 68 shows the data gathered from the statement related to castes and religions dominating with one another hinder women entrepreneurs. Fernandes et al. (2021) mention that castes and religion limit women entrepreneurs to start any business in the literature. Due to the numerous acts system, women get restricted to specific domestic work rather than partaking in any entrepreneurial venture in Nepal. Hence, the data gathered from the above graph illustrate that 22.1% of respondents disagreed, 27.1% were neutral, and the remaining 52.9% agreed with the statement.

There is a lack of suitable models to represent successful women entrepreneurs.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	7	5.0	5.0	5.0
	Disagree	16	11.4	11.4	16.4
	Neutral	14	10.0	10.0	26.4
	Agree	45	32.1	32.1	58.6
	Strongly Agree	58	41.4	41.4	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Figure 68: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 24

According to Bushell (2008), there is a lack of role models restricting other women from partaking in business. The graph in figure 69 represents the statement that there is a lack of suitable models to represent successful women entrepreneurs. Hence, the data gathered from the above graph illustrate that 16.4% of respondents disagreed, 26.4% were neutral, and the remaining 59.6% agreed with the statement. One woman entrepreneur can motivate other women to get involved in the business. Therefore, it will increase the participation of women in business.

Although women entrepreneurs operate in the same environment as men entrepreneurs, there are gender biases embedded in society, limiting women from active economic participation and access to business and development services

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	8	5.7	5.7	5.7
	Disagree	26	18.6	18.6	24.3
	Neutral	8	5.7	5.7	30.0
	Agree	24	17.1	17.1	47.1
	Strongly Agree	74	52.9	52.9	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

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Figure 69: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 25

The graph in Figure 70 reveals the data gathered from the statement related to women entrepreneurs' biases when operating in the business. Based on this, the data shows that 24.3% of respondents marked disagreed, 30% were neutral, and the remaining 47.1% of respondents agreed. Men dominate the business environment in Nepal. Consequently, their bias towards women entrepreneurs limits their involvement in business and any development services (Yaqoob,2021).

Women entrepreneurs suffer from inadequate financial resources and working capital, and they do not acquire external financial assistance due to the absence of tangible security and credit in the market

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	15	10.7	10.7	10.7
	Disagree	11	7.9	7.9	18.6
	Neutral	9	6.4	6.4	25.0
	Agree	36	25.7	25.7	50.7
	Strongly Agree	69	49.3	49.3	100.0
Total		140	100.0	100.0	

Women entrepreneurs suffer from inadequate financial resources and working capital, and they do not acquire external financial assistance due to the absence of tangible security and credit in the market

Women entrepreneurs suffer from inadequate financial resources and working capital, and they do not acquire external financial assistance due to the absence of tangible security and credit in the market

Figure 70: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 26

Cardella et al. (2020) claimed that women entrepreneurs suffer from inadequate financial resources and working capital and do not acquire external financial assistance due to the absence of tangible security and credit in the market. Therefore, it tends to limit the women to do or start a business. Based on this, the data in figure 71 shows that 18.6% of respondents marked disagreed, 25% were neutral, and the remaining 50.7% of respondents agreed.

Banks tend to exaggerate the likelihood of women entrepreneurs' default, hence imposing unrealistically high collateral requirements, which results in credit-rationing

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	6	4.3	4.3	4.3
	Disagree	21	15.0	15.0	19.3
	Neutral	14	10.0	10.0	29.3
	Agree	41	29.3	29.3	58.6
	Strongly Agree	58	41.4	41.4	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Banks tend to exaggerate the likelihood of women entrepreneurs' default, hence imposing unrealistically high collateral requirements, which results in credit-rationing

Figure 71: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 27

The graph in Figure 72 illustrates that the responses to the statement banks tend to exaggerate the likelihood of women entrepreneurs' default, hence imposing unrealistically high collateral requirements, which result in credit rationing. Bushell (2008) claimed that banks in Nepal question women's living in the literature. Hence, they charge high collateral and interest, limiting them from taking any business. The data shows that 19.3% of respondents disagreed, 29.3% were neutral, and the remaining 58.6 % agreed with the statement. Hence, the majority of respondents agreed with the statement

Lack of access to capital and credit schemes and the constraints of financial systems are barriers to potential entrepreneurs as main hindrances to business innovation and success in developing economies

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	9	6.4	6.4	6.4
	Disagree	21	15.0	15.0	21.4
	Neutral	7	5.0	5.0	26.4
	Agree	29	20.7	20.7	47.1
	Strongly Agree	74	52.9	52.9	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Lack of access to capital and credit schemes and the constraints of financial systems are barriers to potential entrepreneurs as main hindrances to business innovation and success in developing economies

Figure 72: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 28

The graph in Figure 73 illustrates the data gathered from the statement related to the idea that lack of access to capital and credit schemes and the constraints of financial systems are barriers to potential entrepreneurs as man hindrances to business innovation and success in developing economies. Furthermore, Syed et al. (2012) mentioned that women restrict themselves from doing business because of capital and credit schemes. Therefore, the credit system limits innovation and success to women entrepreneurs. Hence, the data reveals that 21.4% of respondents disagreed, 26.4% neutral, and 47.1% agreed. Hence, the results reveal that most respondents agreed with the statement.

In Nepal, a male is socially dominant in every aspect; hence, banks lack trust in a woman's ability and commitment to paying back their loan.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	16	11.4	11.4	11.4
	Disagree	11	7.9	7.9	19.3
	Neutral	7	5.0	5.0	24.3
	Agree	39	27.9	27.9	52.1
	Strongly Agree	67	47.9	47.9	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Figure 73: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 29

The graph in Figure 74 illustrates that Nepal is male dominated in every aspect, which acts negatively to women entrepreneurs. Banks lack trust in women's ability and payback (Manandhar, 2019). The data shows that 19.3% of respondents disagreed, 24.3% were neutral, and the remaining 52.1 % agreed with the statement. Hence, most respondents agreed with the statement

There has been a decline in the opportunities available in the capital and other large cities, resulting in an insubstantial entrepreneurial environment.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	9	6.4	6.4	6.4
	Disagree	21	15.0	15.0	21.4
	Neutral	8	5.7	5.7	27.1
	Agree	39	27.9	27.9	55.0
	Strongly Agree	63	45.0	45.0	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Figure 74: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 30

The graph in Figure 75 illustrates the data gathered from the statement related to the idea that there has been a decline in the opportunities available in the capital and other large cities, resulting in an insubstantial entrepreneurial environment. Hence, the data reveals that 21.4% of respondents disagreed, 27.1% neutral, and 55% agreed. Hence, the results reveal that most respondents agreed with the statement. The decline in business opportunities limits women in business in cities areas. Hence, there should be a favourable business environment for women entrepreneurs to conduct or start businesses.

A women entrepreneur must play the role of a daughter, wife, and daughter in law, this limits women's participation in her business, hence hindering her success

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	5	3.6	3.6	3.6
	Disagree	29	20.7	20.7	24.3
	Neutral	2	1.4	1.4	25.7
	Agree	41	29.3	29.3	55.0
	Strongly Agree	63	45.0	45.0	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Figure 75: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 31

The graph in Figure 76 illustrates the data gathered from the statement related to the idea that a women entrepreneur must play the role of a daughter, wife, and daughter law. It limits women's participation in business, hence hindering her success. Hence, the data reveals that 24.3% of respondents disagreed, 25.7% neutral, and 55% agreed. Hence, the results reveal that most respondents agreed with the statement. According to Bushell (2008), a woman must play many roles. Hence this might conflict with professional life a well. Therefore, it restricts further involvement by women entrepreneurs to start businesses and succeed.

The increasing demands of husbands and children hinder the business activities of women's ability to succeed in business.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	10	7.1	7.1	7.1
	Disagree	22	15.7	15.7	22.9
	Neutral	8	5.7	5.7	28.6
	Agree	33	23.6	23.6	52.1
	Strongly Agree	67	47.9	47.9	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

The increasing demands of husbands and children hinder the business activities of women's ability to succeed in business.

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Figure 76: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 32

The graph in Figure 77 illustrates the data gathered from the statement related to the idea that increasing demands of husbands and children hinder the business activities of women's ability to succeed in business. Syed et al. (2012) mentioned that when women's commitment to their husbands and children increases, their business involvement gets limited due to high demand from their families. Therefore, a woman tries to fulfil her family's interest first rather than her interest. Hence, the data reveals that 22.9% of respondents disagreed, 28.6% were neutral, and the remaining 52.1% agreed. Hence, the results reveal that most respondents agreed with the statement.

A lack of moral support from the family and husband is one social barrier to commencing a business to women entrepreneurs

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	9	6.4	6.4	6.4
	Disagree	22	15.7	15.7	22.1
	Neutral	15	10.7	10.7	32.9
	Agree	28	20.0	20.0	52.9
	Strongly Agree	66	47.1	47.1	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

A lack of moral support from the family and husband is one social barrier to commencing a business to women entrepreneurs

Figure 77: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 33

The graph in Figure 78 reveals the data gathered from the statement related to the lack of support that women entrepreneurs receive from family and husbands tends to be a barrier in starting a business. On the contrary, there should be full support both from family members and husband to start a business by their wife or daughter. Hence discouragement should be avoided to increase women’s participation in the entrepreneurial journey. Based on this, the data shows that 22.1% of respondents marked disagreed, 32.9% were neutral, and the remaining 52.9% of respondents agreed.

The stereotypical gender roles for work/family responsibilities hinder the female entrepreneurs from participating in business activities

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	11	7.9	7.9	7.9
	Disagree	19	13.6	13.6	21.4
	Neutral	10	7.1	7.1	28.6
	Agree	28	20.0	20.0	48.6
	Strongly Agree	72	51.4	51.4	100.0
Total		140	100.0	100.0	

Figure 78: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 34

The graph in Figure 79 reveals the data gathered from the statement related to the fact that stereotyping on gender roles hinder women's participation in business. The data shows that 21.4% of respondents disagreed, 28.6% were neutral, and the remaining 48.6% of respondents marked on agree. Therefore, gender roles on what a woman should do and don'ts limit their business involvement because this limits their idea. For example, a plumbing business is for men in Nepal. Hence, if a woman wants to start this business, these roles restrict them from partaking in it.

The prevailing attitude that a woman's place is at home with her family further constrain many married women from venturing into entrepreneurship

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	11	7.9	7.9	7.9
	Disagree	19	13.6	13.6	21.4
	Neutral	8	5.7	5.7	27.1
	Agree	48	34.3	34.3	61.4
	Strongly Agree	54	38.6	38.6	100.0
Total		140	100.0	100.0	

Figure 79: Measurement and Graphical Presentation statement 35

The graph in Figure 80 reveals the data gathered from the statement related to the fact that women's prevailing attitude from their own home constrain them into getting involved in the business when they get married. The data shows that 21.4% of respondents disagreed, 27.1% were neutral, and the remaining 61.4% of respondents marked on agree. Hence, it is imperative to treat their daughter and encourage them from the start if they want to start their business to stand up for themselves even when they get married.

Appendix 16: Residual plot for regressions analysis

Figure 80: Regression Residual Plot

Figure 81 demonstrates that the residual plot is above the regression line. It means the result is significant and positive. Therefore, the result is valid and can trust regression coefficients and another numeric result. The residual displayed are consistent, and the regression model's predictions are correct on average.